

THREADS OF CONTACT

TRACING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EGYPT AND
THE SOUTHERN LEVANT THROUGH TEXTILE TOOLS

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CATALOGUE

This catalogue is the result of an extensive effort to gather all available evidence of textile tools from the sites selected as case studies: Megiddo, Hazor, Beth Shean, Tell el-Far‘ah North, Lahun, Gurob, and Deir el-Medina. It includes data derived from both published literature and first-hand observations. Not all tools mentioned in the literature were accessible for direct study, and not all the tools examined during this research had been previously published.

To distinguish between sources, items studied directly are marked in **blue**, while those known only from the literature appear in **black**. A dedicated column provides the bibliographic references used in compiling the catalogue.

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MEGIDDO

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
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SPINDLES

1	b 137		Bone						E 2032	Loud 1948: pl. 197.1		Bone stick, broken at both ends and with ring incisions near one of the broken ends.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	M3530		Bone						Locus 1140	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.38		Bone spindle composed of three joining elements and tapering towards one of the ends. Both ends are flat. Between one of the joining points two dome spindle whorls are inserted, with the flat part attached to that of the other.	LB I	
1	b433 a		Bone						T.3018 F	Loud 1948: pl. 197.2	from the same context also spindle whorl b433b, like pl. 171.17 (dome with four dotted rings).	Spindle composed by a series of decorated bone rings. Core disintegrated. Discoid spindle whorl with lateral decorative incisions.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	M2374		Bone						Tomb 856	Guy/Engberg 1938: 172, pl. 142		Small fragment of a polished shaft.	LB I	
1	M3568		Bone						Tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:6, pl. 84		Shaft composed of two joining parts. One end is flat, and the other is missing but probably was pointed. Richly decorated by lattice and incised strips. Two spindle whorls were mounted on the shaft based on M3530.	LB II	
1	M3569a		Bone						Tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Fragment of a shaft with a lattice decoration.	LB II	
1	M3569b		Bone						Tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Fragment of a shaft with parallel incised strips.	LB II	
1	M3569c		Bone						Tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Shaft, probably complete, with parallel incised strips at both ends	LB II	
1	M2435		Bone	3,8	0,6			1,8	Tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 33-36, 170, pl. 95		Fragment of a bone shaft with bands decorated by parallel incised	LB II	1934-1620 ?

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												strips and oblique incisions. Both ends missing.		
1	M2433		Bone						Tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 33-36, 170, pl. 95		Bone shaft, complete. One end is flat and the other pointed. It is decorated by thread bands of an incised lattice pattern.	LB II	
1	M2852		Bone	2,4	1,2			1,4	Tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100:26.		Element carved in the form of a pomegranate to insert on top of a bone shaft.	LB II	1934-2113 ?
1	M2853		Bone	21,6	0,6			10,2	Tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100.30		Complete bone shaft with both ends flattened. Decorated by several groups of incised parallel strips.	LB II	1934-2116 ?
1	M2856		Ivory						Tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100.29		Broken bone shaft, which tends to taper towards the preserved end, which is flat. Decorated by several groups of incised parallel strips.	LB II	
1	x748		Bone						Tomb 40	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig. 175, pl. 156.13		Complete bone shaft, with a flat end and the other which ends with a tenon. Decorated by bands of incised lattice pattern. Composed by two pieces.	LB II	
1	x632		Bone						Tomb 40	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig. 175, pl. 156.12		Fragment of a bone shaft, with one flat end and the broken.	LB II	
1	x1977		Bone						Tomb 59A	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig. 175, pl. 157		Shaft broken at one end, the other is flat with a deep rounded groove.	LB II	
1	3826		Bone						Tomb 63 E	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig. 175, pl. 158.7		Bone fragment of shaft, broken at both ends and decorated by incised parallel strips.	LB II	
1	a944		Bone						N 15	Loud 1948: pl. 197.3		Broken bone shaft, both ends missing. Decorated with a lattice band and some parallel and circular incised lines.	LB II	
1	M6054		Bone						E 1831	Loud 1948: pl. 197.4		Broken bone shaft, one preserved end is decorated by a lattice pattern.	LB II	
1	M6028		Bone						1831	Loud 1948: pl. 197.5		Completed bone shaft with mortise at both ends. Decorated by diagonal	LB II	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												incision closed by parallel incised strips.		
1	M6130		Bone						N 1835	Loud 1948: pl. 197.6		Completed bone shaft with mortise at both ends. Decorated by parallel incised strips.	LB II	
1	M6083		Bone						1814	Loud 1948: pl. 197.7		Large shaft with one end flat and the other is hollow. Decorated by an incised lattice pattern and several parallel incised strips resembling rings.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M5963		Bone						1814	Loud 1948: pl. 197.8		Bone shaft with one end flat and the other is hollow. Decorated by an incised pattern of diagonal lines and several parallel incised strips resembling rings.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M5985		Bone						S 1825	Loud 1948: pl. 197.9		Bone shaft with one end flat and the other is hollow. Decorated by an incised pattern of diagonal lines and several parallel incised strips resembling rings.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M5673 a		Bone						N 1771	Loud 1948: pl. 197.10		Shaft broken in two pieces but complete. Surface decorated by lattice pattern and groups of parallel incised lines.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M5673 b		Bone						N 1771	Loud 1948: pl. 197.11		Shaft broken at one end while the other is flat. Partially decorated by parallel and diagonal incised lines.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M 5776		Bone						1769	Loud 1948: pl. 197.13. Paice 2004: pl. 125.	Found with two bone whorls and spindle M 5777	Bone shaft, complete. Both ends are flat. Partially decorated with a lattice pattern and two carved strips parallel to the ends.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	00/K/100/A R7		Bone	7,3	0,9	0,7		5,21	K-5(?)	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.30.		Bone shaft, one end flat but hollow and the other broken but full. Almost complete covered by an incised lattice pattern.	IA I	
1	M 1274		Ivory						Locus 404	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96:12	Stratum IV	Bone shaft, one end is flat, and the other is broken. Decorated by incised lattice patterns.	IA II (Str. IV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5176								Locus 1482	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96:21	Stratum IV filling	Bone shaft with one end broken end the other carved in a pomegranate shape.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 4519		Bone						Locus 1478	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 100:10	Stratum IV	Pomegranate element vertically pierced	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 4835		Ivory						Locus 1486	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96:10	Stratum III	Bone shaft, one end missing and the other is flat decorated with two simple circular lines.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4505		Ivory						Locus 4505	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96:11	Stratum III	Ivory shaft broken at one end while the other is flat and decorated by two deep grooves.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4484		Ivory						Locus 1414	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96:20	Stratum III	Ivory shaft broken at one end and the other is carved in pomegranate shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	06/M/19/A R9		Bone							Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.8.		Hollow shaft with both ends flat and decorated by a lattice pattern. Probably not a spindle.		
1	08/H/18/A R1		Bone	2,6	1,1			3,7				Fragment of a bone/ivory shaft, cylindrical, with one flat end preserved, the other missing. Incised decoration is made of a chevron pattern closed by three horizontal incisions on both sides.		
1	08/Q/87/A R7		Bone	1,5	1		0,3					Small fragment of a bone shaft, cylindrical with one flat end preserved, the other missing. Decorated bay incised parallel lines.		
1	10/H/16/A R11		Bone	2	0,8							Small fragment of a bone/ivory rod, darkened.		
1	10/Q/107/A R10		Bone	2,2	0,7							Small fragment of a bone/ivory rod, darkened.		
1	10/J/151/A R1		Bone	12,5	1x0,8		0,45	14,1				Bone shaft broken at one end but probably almost complete. Decorated by three parallel lines near the preserved end, and traces of the same decoration at the other end. Slightly tapering toward the preserved end. Hole but not pierced through.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	10/K/44/A R5		Bone	12,7	0,8			5,7				Bone shaft with large, incised decoration, complete. One end is pointed, the other flat with a cross-shaped incision. Decoration made of chevron pattern alternated to parallel lines.		
1	12/H/53/A R2		Bone	4,8	1			5,8				Fragment of a bone/ivory shaft, cylindrical, with one flat end preserved, the other missing. Incised decoration is made of a lattice pattern closed by horizontal incisions on both sides. Small through perforation on the shaft.		
1	14/H/83/A R2		Bone	3	1	0,3			Topsoil			Small fragment of bone shaft, broken at both ends. Decorated by two deep parallel lines.		
1	14/Q/117/A R1		Bone	5,2	0,7			3,3				Bone shaft with one preserved end crudely decorated by two parallel grooves and the other end missing. Shaft is smooth but not perfectly rounded.		

SPINDLE WHORLS

Early Bronze Age

1	00/J/75/AR1	Lenticular	Pottery	2	3,7			10,55 +x	Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 35 g.	Fragment of a pottery spindle whorl lenticular shape. Well crafted.	EB Ib	
1	98/J/21/AR1	Discoid	Pottery	1				3,8+x	Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.		Discoid pottery spindle whorl, only a small part preserved. Hole not preserved.	EB Ib	
1	98/J/89/AR1	Discoid	Pottery	1,3				11,05 +x	Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 27 g.	Discoid pottery whorl partially preserved. Quite irregular, with flat base degrading toward the hole.	EB Ib	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/J/152/AR1		Pottery						Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Preserved about 35%	Specially made	EB Ib	
1	00/J/008/AR2	Biconical	Pottery	2,5	3,6			16,64+x	Level J-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 33,5 g.	Biconical pottery spindle whorl, broken with just a small part of hole preserved. Smoothed surface.	EB III	670006
1	06/J/114/AR1	Cylindrical	Pottery						J-5, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4.	Original weight 50,2 g.	Cylindrical pottery spindle whorl, fragmentary.	EB III	
1	98/J/50/AR1	Discoid	stone	1,7	4,3			35,8+x	J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.		Pebble broken during perforation.	EB III	
1	96/J/88/AR1	Discoid	Pottery					24+x	Level J-6 (F?);	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:5.	Original weight 48 g.	Discoid pottery spindle whorl, half preserved. Specially made.	EB III	
1	04/J/89/AR3	Dome	Pottery					28,89	J-6b, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.3.		Dome pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	EB III	
1	06/J/64/AR2	Dome	Pottery					39,15+x	J-5, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.3.		Small pottery spindle whorl, complete.	EB III	

Middle Bronze Age

1	2796		stone	0,6	6,9x5,7		1,6x2,1	24,8+x				Flat ovoid object with quite large hole in central position.	MB I	(I-3301)
1	08/J/201/AR1	Biconical	Pottery					12,05+x	J-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881.	Original weight 24,1 g.	Biconical pottery spindle whorl, fragmentary.	MB I	
1	242	Discoid	stone	1	4,3		0,6	30,2				Stone discoid spindle whorl, complete. Quite well shaped, with regular, cylindrical hole.	MB I	I-2850
1	d 298	Dome	Grey stone			2			5093	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Peculiar whorl made of stone, complete. Flat base, sides sloping and slightly convex top. Very large hole.	MB I (Str. XIIIb)	
1	d 480	Dome	Bone			2,2			5155	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 368	Dome	Bone			2,4			5126	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Dome bone spindle whorl, chipped on the side. Well shaped.	MB I (Str. XIV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	288	Spherical	Pottery	3	3,4		0,5	34,92				Spherical pottery whorl, complete. Hole not perfectly central. Wear traces near both sides of hole.	MB I	I-1565
1	x 960	Biconical	Pottery						tomb 43	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:2, pl. 110.15		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Shape quite irregular.	MB II	
1	x 891	Biconical	Pottery						tomb 44	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:3, pl. 110		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	MB II	
1	00/F/95/AR1 pt 001	Biconical	Pottery	1,7	2,8		0,3	8,95+ x	Level F-11	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 12 g.	Pottery biconical spindle whorl partially preserved. One third missing. Highly worn near a side of the hole, less near the other side.	MB II	
1	00/M/17/AR 2	Biconical	Pottery					27,75 +x	M-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, half preserved. Not perfectly specular.	MB II	
1	14/K/100/A R1	Biconical	Clay					12+x	K-11			Completely broken spindle whorl, made of unbaked or slightly baked clay. Apparent shape was biconical.	MB II	
1	x 892	Cylindrical	Pottery						tomb 44	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:1, pl. 110		Cylindrical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Shape quite irregular.	MB II	
1	96/F/026/AR 4 PT0I2	Discoid	Limestone	0,9	5,2	0,6		30+x	Level F-12(A)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:10.	Original weight 43 g.	Limestone discoid spindle whorl, chipped on two sides. Quite well shaped.	MB II (mixed with EB materials)	
1	d 79	Dome	Bone			1,2			5031	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped. Decorated by a series of concentric incision.	MB II (Str. XI)	
1	x1969	Spherical	Pottery						tomb 49	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:4, pl. 112		Spherical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	MB II	
1	10/K/33/AR 1	Spherical	basalt	2,6		12,8, s 1,5		12,7+ x	K-11			Spherical basalt spindle whorl, broken. Well polished surface.	MB II	
1	08/K/126/A R1	Conical	Bone	0,7	2,8		0,3	4,6	K-10			Conical bone spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly larger at the base. (0,35 cm). On the base, long	MB III/LB I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												and superficial crossing incisions, signs of manufacture.		
1	08/K/126/AR4	Conical	Pottery	0,6	1,9		0,3	1,4	K-10			Conical pottery spindle whorl, complete but highly worn. Hole slightly larger at the base.	MB III/LB I	
1	12/K/5/AR5	Conical	Bone	0,7	2		0,25	2,4	K-10			Bone conical spindle whorl, complete. Well smoothed dome, less well finished on the flat base.	MB III/LB I	
1	98/M/28/AR26	Cylindrical	stone					15,3+ x	M-7, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.	Original weight 46 g.	Cylindrical stone spindle whorl, small part preserved. Hourglass hole.	MBIII/LB I	
1	10/K/73/AR3	Discoid	stone	1,4	4,5		0,7	22	K-10			Stone discoid whorl, chalky surface. Shape not perfectly rounded and hole slightly oblique.	MB III/LB I	
1	08/K/125/AR1	dome	Bone	0,8	2,8		0,3	4,8	K-10			Dome bone spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved. Hole slightly conical, larger at the base (0,35 cm). Surface of the base was probably polished, now is worn and cancellous bone is exposed.	MB III/LB I	
1	10/K/25/AR10	Dome	Bone	0,5	1,5		0,2	1	K-10			Bone dome spindle whorl (?), complete. Extremely small. Hole slightly larger towards the base (0,2). Round concentric lines due to manufacture are visible on the bone, crossing parallel lines on the base. Upper part of the hole slightly chipped.	MB III/LB I	
1	10/K/73/AR6	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,2		0,3	2,6	K-10			Bone dome spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly larger toward the flat base (0,4 cm). Well smoothed dome, while the base is rough with evident signs of manufacture. Hole well shaped with very small and thin wear traces.	MB III/LB I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	14/K/33/AR 1	Dome	Ivory	0,8	2,8		0,3	5,5	K-10			Ivory dome spindle whorl, complete. Well polished on the dome, lesser on the base where traces of manufacture are visible. Lower part of the hole more irregular than the other and with small traces of wear.	MB III/LB I	
1	14/K/51/AR 2	Dome	Ivory	0,7	2,5		0,3	4,3	K-10			Dome, ivory spindle whorl, complete. Well polished on the surface. Hole slightly larger on the base (0,4). Well polished on the dome, lesser on the base, where traces of manufacture, with crossing lines, are evident. Wear traces near both sides of the hole.	MB III/LB I	
1	d 668	Dome	Bone			0,5			5225	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by groups of incised radial lines.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	c 110	Dome	Bone			1			4021	Loud 1948: pl. 171		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by four incised circles with a dot in the middle.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	06/M/48/AR 3	Dome	Bone					1,72	M-7, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2.		Extremely light spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped and made of bone.	MBIII/L B I	
1	06/M/56/AR 1	Dome	Bone					5,77	M-7, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2.		Bone dome spindle whorl, complete.	MBIII/L B I	
1	08/K/119/A R4	Spherical	Limestone	3,4	4,6		1	130	K-10			Spherical limestone whorl (?), complete. Perforation not finished. Well dressed surface and regular hole.	MB III/LB I	

Late Bronze Age

1	94/F/88/AR 1 PT 002	Discoid	Limestone		5,8		0,8	35 +x	Level F-11/F-10	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:11.	Original weight 64 g.	Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, broken in half. Irregular on the edges, with evident marks of chipping. Possibly not finished.	MB-LB mixed context	
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Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/F/72/AR6	Discoid	Ivory	0,3	3,4		0,4	3,84	F-10	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 412, fig. 18.42		Discoid, ivory spindle whorl, complete. Very thin, decorated with a petal pattern on one surface. Scratches on both surfaces.	LB I	
1	d 199	Discoid	Bone			0,2			5056	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Discoid, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very thin.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	00/F/36/AR4	Dome	Bone	1,5	4,2		0,5	15,05 +x	Level F-10b	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.	Original weight 16,5 g.	Dome, bone spindle whorl, chipped on one side and near the hole. Quite large.	LB I	
1	98/F/70/AR1	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,4		0,3	4,3	Level F-10a	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.	Bone or ivory	Dome, bone spindle whorl, almost complete. On the dome an incised decoration of four circles with a dot in the middle. Wheel's signs on the dome and of polishing on the base, but very light.	LB I	
1	98/F/94/AR1	Dome	serpentine	0,5	1,6		0,2	1,7	F-10b	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.		Dome, serpentine spindle whorl, complete. Apparently too small for using as a spindle whorl. On the bases, traces of polishing are visible.	LB I	
1	d 31	Dome	Bone			0,8			T.5013 A	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. One incised circular line near the external diameter.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	b 723	Dome	Bone			0,6			T.3018 F	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated with radial incisions which branches near the edge.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	b 174	Dome	Bone			0,9			T.3018 C	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	b 75	Dome	Bone			1			T.3013	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. On the dome an incised decoration of four circles with a dot in the middle.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	a 113	Dome	Bone			0,6			T.2015	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	M 6030		Bone						Locus E 1831, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167			LB II (Str. VII)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/K/105/AR1		Bone	0,7	4x2		0,5	6	Level K-9			Peculiar object with an oval shape, with central hole.	LB IIA	
1	M2437	Biconical	Ivory	1,5	2,1		0,4	2,78	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95		Small biconical ivory spindle whorl, broken in three pieces.	LB II	1934-1622
1	M2838	Biconical	Bone	1	2,6		0,4	3,39+ x	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Biconical bone/ivory spindle whorl, fragmentary. Surface highly worn.	LB II	1934-2103
1	10/K/61/AR18	Biconical	Pottery	2,2	3,8		0,6	29,4	K-9			Biconical spindle whorl, complete. Made of pottery, specially made, with hourglass hole.	LB IIA	
1	12/H/81/AR4	Biconical	Bone		2,2	1,1	0,3	4	Sq. E8, H-14, A			Biconical bone spindle whorl, complete but with tiny chips. Extremely polished.	LB IIB	
1	M2436	Button	Bone	0,7	2		0,3	1,22	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95, 175.		Small bone button, with highly worn surface.	LB II	1934-1621
1	M2881	Button	Bone	0,5	3,1		0,3	2,68	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Small bone button, small crack on the side. Well polished dome, while base very worn. Circular incision near the edge on the dome.	LB II	1934-2125
1	M2807	Button	Bone	0,5	1,9		0,25	1,17	tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:15, pl. 119		Small bone button, complete. Surface well polished, decorated by a circular incision near the outer rim. Polishing traces on the base.	LB II	1934-1812
1	M2806	Button	Bone	0,6	2,2		0,3	1,53	tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:17, pl. 119		Small bone button, broken in two pieces. Well polished surface, decorated by a double circular incision near the outer rim.	LB II	1934-1811
1	M2805	Button	Bone	1	2,5		0,3	2,35+ x	tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:18, pl. 119		Bone button, broken. Upper surface decorated by circular incisions and base with traces of a second hole left unfinished.	LB II	1934-1810
1	M2808	Button	Bone	0,6	1,8		0,2	1,13	tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, fig. 175:16, pl. 119		Very small spindle whorl made of bone. Reassembled from several fragments. Too small to be a spindle whorl. Surface very damaged. Polishing marks visible at the base.	LB II	1934-1813
1	M3127	Button	Bone	0,5	1,1		0,2	0,26	tomb 912 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 132		Very small bone button.	LB II	1934-2004

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M3124	Button	Bone	0,4	1,3		0,25	0,39	tomb 912 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 132		Very small bone button.	LB II	1934-2003
1	M3123	Button	Bone	0,6	1,7		0,2	0,84	tomb 912 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 132		Very small bone button.	LB II	1934-2002
1	08/K/57/AR 1	Button	Bone	0,9	2,5		0,3	4,3	Level K-9			Bone button, slightly chipped. Dark colour. Light signs of circular polishing on the dome, parallel on the base. Some signs are more evident.	LB IIA	
1	06/K/43/AR 5	Button	Bone					0,75	K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Small bone button, complete. Extremely light.	LB IIB	
1	M2438	Conical	Bone	0,8	2		0,25	1,3	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95		Very small conical spindle whorl made of bone, almost complete but made of two joining pieces.	LB II	1934-1623
1	M2440	Conical	Bone	0,8	1,6		0,2	0,93	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95, 175.		Very small conical spindle whorl made of bone, almost complete but made of two joining pieces.	LB II	1934-1625
1	1302	Conical	Bone						tomb 56	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 114		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Not perfectly symmetrical.	LB II	
1	x 98	Conical	Bone						tomb 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 153		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	LB II	
1	x473	Conical	Slate						tomb 13	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 154		Conical, slate spindle whorl, complete.	LB II?	
1	12/H/60/AR 4	Conical	Black stone	1,3	2,9		3,5	12	Sq. F9, earth debris			Conical spindle whorl, complete, made of black stone. Wear traces near the upper hole. Traces of polishing on the base and hole not perfectly round. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,4).	LB IIA	
1	06/K/5/AR3	Conical	stone	1,9	4,7		0,4	29	Level K-9			Conical spindle whorl, complete, made of a whitish stone. Highly whorl and covered by encrustation.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/11/AR 1	conical	Bone	1,5	3,8		0,4	8,6	Level K-8			Conical bone spindle whorl, fragmentary, at least 1/3 missing. Cancellous bone largely exposed.	LB IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	10/K/14/AR 4	conical	Bone	0,9	2,7		0,25	4,2	Level K-8			Conical bone spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,3). Parallel lines due to polishing visible on the base, while the upper side does not show any traces of manufacture. Hole sharply cut but not perfectly round.	LB IIB	
1	10/K/62/AR 2	Conical truncated	Basalt	1	2		0,45	8	K-9			Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete. Made of basalt or another black stone. Upper side not regular. Well polished and lower base shows usual parallel lines. Wear traces neat the upper side of the hole.	LB IIA	
1	d 8	Cylindrical	Bone	1	2,1		0,5	4,55	Locus 5002, K11, Area DD	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: pl. 172.		Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Deeply circular lines incised on the side, forming superimposing rings.	LB II (Str. VII)	39487
1	a 562	Cylindrical	Bone			1,5			2041	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Deeply circular lines incised on the side, forming superimposing rings.	LB II (Str. VII)	
1	10/K/53/AR 8	Cylindrical	Bone	1,4x1. 2	2			15	K-9			Cylindrical object made of limestone, with sloping base. Evident signs of holes manufacture.	LB IIA	
1	06/K/87/AR 4	Cylindrical	Bone						K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Cylindrical bone object, made by a fish vertebra with a hole in the middle.	LB IIB	
1	06/K/117/A R5	Discoid	Limestone					15,06	K-8?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, almost complete. Chipped on one side.	LB II	
1	10/K/60/AR 3	Discoid	Bone	0,4	3,4		0,3	2,7	K-9			Discoid or very flat dome spindle whorl, made of bone and highly ruined. Cancellous bone visible. Near the edge a band decorated with overlapping semicircles.	LB IIA	
1	06/K/96/AR 6	Discoid	Bone					5,13	K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Discoid, dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Chipped on one side. Traces of manual polishing on the surface.	LB IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	12/H/49/AR 1	Discoid	Pottery	1,5	6			33+x	Sq. E8, H- 13, F?			Discoid pottery spindle whorl, broken in half. Well shaped but not perfectly straight surfaces.	LB IIB	
4	M3574	Dome	Bone			0,6			tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Three dome spindle whorls made of bone, complete.	LB II	
1	M3584	Dome	Bone			1,1			tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete but slightly chipped near the edge.	LB II	
1	M3585	Dome	Bone			1			tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated with radial lines.	LB II	
1	M3587	Dome	Bone			0,8			tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated with radial incisions which branches near the edge.	LB II	
1	M3588	Dome	Steatite						tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	LB II	
1	M2597	Dome	Ivory	0,6	2,6		0,3	3,67	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95		Dome, ivory spindle whorl, complete. Perfectly polished dome, while base shows traces of polishing. Circular incision on the base.	LB II	1934-1639
1	M2429	Dome	Ivory	0,7	2,5		0,3	3,07	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95		Dome, ivory spindle whorl, almost complete. Only a small fragment missing. Not wheel polished, but manually polished both on base and dome, which is not perfectly rounded.	LB II	1934-1615
1	M2439	Dome	Bone	0,9	1,8		0,2	2	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95, 175		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small. Traces of wheel's polishing on the dome, manually polished on the base. Hole slightly conical (0,3).	LB II	1934-1624
1	M2893	Dome	Bone	0,4					tomb 989 A 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 98		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB II	
1	M2894	Dome	Bone						tomb 989 A 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB II	
1	M2892	Dome	Bone	0,7					tomb 989 A 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 98		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB II	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M2895	Dome	Steatite	0,7					tomb 989 A 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 98		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	LB II	
1	M2877	Dome	Steatite	0,7	2		0,3	4	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 100		Small dome steatite whorl, complete. Evident signs of wheel's polishing on the dome, manual polishing on the base. On the base small circular incision. Hole tends to slightly enlarge toward the base (0,35).	LB II	1934-2121
1	M2859	Dome	Bone	0,7	3x2,7		0,3	3,94	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Dome, bone/ivory spindle whorl, complete. Dome perfectly smoothed, base with evident signs of polishing. Hole tends to enlarge near the base.	LB II	1934-2119
1	M2836	Dome	Bone	0,5	2,3		0,25	2,6	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Dome highly worn, base with traces of polishing and a circular incision. Cylindrical hole without wear traces.	LB II	1934-2101
1	M2837	Dome	Bone	0,5	1,5		0,25	0,98	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Very small bone spindle whorl, dome shaped and complete. Hole slightly conical, larger at the base (0,3).	LB II	1934-2102
1	M2834	Dome	Bone	0,7	1,1		0,2	0,39	tomb 989 C 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 100		Very small bone button, complete.	LB II	1934-2100
1	M2809	Dome	Bone	0,4	0,6		0,2	0,84	tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 119		Very small bone spindle whorl, dome shaped and complete. Worn surface and traces of polishing on the base.	LB II	1934-1814
1	M2810	Dome	Steatite			0,5			tomb 911 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 119:16		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	LB II	
1	M3154	Dome	Steatite	0,5	1,2		0,2	1,24	tomb 912 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 132		Very small dome spindle whorl, made of steatite. Complete. Signs of polishing visible on the base and a circular incision near the edge.	LB II	1934-2023
1	M3061	Dome	Bone	0,4	2,2		0,2	1,8	tomb 912 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 132		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small. Traces of polishing very evident on the base.	LB II	1934-1949

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/F/22/AR5	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,4		0,3	3,4	Level F-9	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. No decoration. Hole slightly larger toward the base.	LB II	
1	98/F/20/AR1	Dome	Ivory	0,5	2,4		0,3	2,9	Level F-7	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.		Dome, ivory spindle whorl, complete. Chipped near the upper hole. Very flat dome. Hole slightly hourglass.	LB II	
1	a 250	Dome	Bone			0,5			2048	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Irregular spindle whorl, probably originally dome.	LB II (Str. VII)	
1	d 796	Dome	Bone			0,6			5262	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Circular incision on the dome.	LB II (Str. VIII)	
1	d 132	Dome	Bone			0,8			5020	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	LB II (Str. VIII)	
1	d 25	Dome	Black stone			0,9			5005	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Large, dome spindle whorl made of black stone. Complete. Traces of wheel's polishing on the surface.	LB II (Str. VIII)	
	08/K/89/AR 6	Dome	Ivory	0,7	2,7		0,3	4,6	Level K-9			Dome, ivory/bone spindle whorl, complete. Beautiful example. Cylindrical hole, upper surface extremely smoothed with four incised holes with dot in the middle. Base polished but not shiny, with a circular incision near the external edge. Other light circular incisions are visible, made after the manual polishing which left parallel lines. Wear traces near the upper side of the hole.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/33/AR 7	Dome	Bone	0,4	2,2		0,45	2	Level K-9?			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well-preserved. On the dome traces of circular wheel polishing, very light. On the base, evident signs of manual polishing. Wear traces near the upper side if the hole.	LB IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/K/65/AR 10	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,5		0,25	3,1	Level K-9			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well-preserved. Slightly chipped on the dome, no signs of wheel's polishing are visible. Base covered by parallel signs of manual polishing.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/72/AR 5	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,3		0,25	3	Level K-9			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well-preserved. Hole slightly larger at the base. Upper side of the hole very worn, inferior side well cut. On the dome circular wheel's incisions are visible, on the base parallel signs of polishing.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/7/AR2	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,6		0,3	5	K-9			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,4). Small chip on one side. Circular incisions due to wheel's polishing evident on the dome, parallel signs on the base. Hole is not perfectly round, small wear traces on the upper side, perfectly cut on the base.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/40/AR 1	Dome	Bone	0,6	2		0,3	2	K-9			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Highly ruined. Upper side of the hole chipped (wear traces?).	LB IIA	
1	10/K/45/AR 1	Dome	Limestone	0,9	4,4		1	22	K-9			Dome, limestone spindle whorl, chipped. Very large hole, slightly larger at the base (1,15). Wear traces near the upper side of the hole, clear at the base.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/53/AR 5	Dome	Limestone	0,7	2,3		0,25	3	K-9			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well-preserved. Very light traces of circular wheel's polishing on the dome, parallel on the base. Some scratches on the surface. Wear traces near the upper side of the hole.	LB IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	06/K/44/AR 9	Dome	Bone					3,87	K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Surface with incised concentric circles made by wheel.	LB IIB	
1	12/H/40/AR 5	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,9		0,4	5	sq. F9, brick debris			Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Several encrustations on the surface and inside the hole.	LB IIB	
1	12/H/40/AR 8	Dome	stone	0,7	2,8		0,3	8+x	sq. F9, brick debris			Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Made of black stone. Circular wheel's signs visible on the dome, parallel signs on the base. Wear traces and chips near the upper side of the hole.	LB IIB	
5	M3576	Dome/Butt on	Bone			0,7 e 0,8			tomb 1122 upper	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 84		Five bone spindle whorls, button shaped. Completed, except one which is slightly chipped.	LB II	
1	M2828	Lenticular	Ivory	0,9	2,6		0,4	4,35	tomb 877 B1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 95		Lenticular bone spindle whorl, almost complete. Surface highly worn. Hole perfectly cut on both sides, without wear traces.	LB II	1934-1647
1	M 6029	Lenticular?	Bone			1,1			Locus E 1831, S8, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172.29. Paice 2004: 167		Lenticular, bone spindle whorl. Complete. Incised decoration made of radial and circular lines forming triangles.	LB II (Str. VII)	
1	06/K/30b/A R1	Spherical	Pottery						K-8	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.	Original weight 17,14 g.	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, complete (restored). Specially made. Quite well shaped.	LB II	
1	06/K/59/AR 7	Spherical	Pottery						K-8?, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, broken. Specially made. Hole slightly off-centre.	LB II	
1	12/H/67/AR 2	Spherical	Pottery	2,5	2,3		0,6	11,4	Sq. F8, H- 13, A			Spherical (ovoid) spindle whorl, complete. Made of pottery, specially made. Surfaces are not regular, and fingerprints are visible. Several cracks.	LB IIB	
1	14/H/17/AR 2	Spherical	Pottery	2,1	2,2		0,5	12	Sq. E9, H- 14, F?			Small spherical spindle whorl, roughly shaped. Made of pottery, specially made.	LB IIB	
1	04/K/65/AR 4				4				K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 883.	Unfinished perforation	No drawings	LB III	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	06/K/79/AR1	Biconical	Pottery					19,01	K-6, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	LB III	
1	06/M/29/AR6	Button	Bone					1,59	M-6	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2.		Bone button, small and complete. Very light.	LB III	
1	12/H/14/AR2	Button	Bone	0,4	1,9		0,2	2	H-12, F		Accumulation on pavement	Bone button, broken in half and missing the upper part. Signs of wheel's manufacture on the upper surface. Parallel light incision on the base. Hole too small for being a spindle whorl.	LB III	
1	b 2235	Button	Ivory	0,5	0,9		0,2	0,69	Exc. 1936/7 Level VII A	Loud 1939: 101, pl. 15.		Ivory button, too small for being a spindle whorl. Traces of polishing on the base.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	38858
1	b 2137	Button	Ivory	0,9	1,5		0,15	0,83	Exc. 1936/7 Level VII A	Loud 1939: 100 pl. 15.		Ivory, tall button, complete. Not perfectly rounded. Too small for being a spindle whorl. On the whole surface traces of polishing.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	38830
1	13/H/2/AR1	Conical	Limestone	1,9	3,9		0,7	27	Sq. F7/E7			Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly off-centre. Surface highly worn. Brownish concretion inside the hole.	LB III	
1	04/K/43a/AR5	Conical?	Pottery					12,06 +x	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.		Broken spindle whorl, only one third preserved.	LB III	
1	06/M/38/AR4	Cylindrical	stone					61,55	M-6?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.		Cylindrical, stone spindle whorl, complete.	LB III	
1	06/M/8/AR2	Cylindrical	Pottery					17,55	M-6, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4.		Cylindrical, pottery spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	LB III	
1	12/H/11/AR1	Cylindrical	stone	1,3	2,8x3			9,9	H-12, F			Cylindrical object made of a chalky, white stone. Beginning of perforation on both sides.	LB III	
1	04/M/53/AR1	Discoid	stone					29,84	M-6	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.		Cylindrical, stone spindle whorl, complete.	LB III	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	04/M/75/AR 1	Dome	Bone					3,41	M-6	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small and light.	LB III	
1	04/K/11/AR 2	Dome	Bone					11,74	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	LB III	
1	04/K/19/AR 1	Dome	Bone					3,14	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Asymmetrical	LB III	
1	04/K/44/AR 9	Dome	Bone					1,52	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.2.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Quite flat and very light.	LB III	
1	M 5972	Dome	Bone			0,6			Locus 1817, S10, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 167		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated with radial incisions which branches near the edge.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M 5761	Dome	Bone			0,6			Locus 1787, S9, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 167		Dome (or button?) bone spindle whorl. Small and complete.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M 6059 b	Dome	Bone			0,5			Locus 1794, S9, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 167		Dome, bone spindle whorl, chipped. Decorated by a circular band of superimposed circles, and half circles in the inside side.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	M 6059 a	Lenticular?	Bone			1,2			Locus N 1835, S10, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 167		Lenticular, bone spindle whorl. Complete. Incised decoration made of radial and circular lines forming triangles.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	06/M/29/AR 1	Spherical	Pottery					21,03	M-6?, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4.		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	LB III	
1	04/K/75/AR 2	Spherical	Pottery					20,17	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4.		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	LB III	
1	98/M/12/AR 3	Spherical	Pottery						M-6, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4.	Original weight 50 g.	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, fragmentary. Only one third preserved.	LB III	
1	10/H/64/AR 2	Spherical	Pottery	2,6	2,7		0,3	18	H-12, F		Accumulatio n on	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Not perfectly modelled. No traces of wear near hole.	LB III	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											flagstone floor.			

Iron Age I

1	M 5731								Locus S=1745, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 166. Loud 1948: 151.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5747								Locus - 1740, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 166.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5784								Locus S=1802, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 166.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5785								Locus S=1802, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 166.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5793								Locus 1792	Paice 2004: 166.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5831								Locus E=1804, R8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5860								Locus 1813, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5878								Locus S=1813, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5881								Locus W=1793, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5885								Locus W=1797,	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									R10, Area CC					
1	M 5947								Locus W=1794, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5976								Locus E=1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5983								Locus 1823, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167,			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5987								Locus S=1825, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6033								Locus E=1831, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6089								Locus W=1817, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6101								Locus N=1843, R8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6105								Locus S=1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6148								Locus 1803, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6184								Locus S=1825,	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									Q9, Area CC					
1	a 561		Alabaster						Locus 2071, K8, Area AA	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5610		Bone						Locus +1754, R8-9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5615		Bone						Locus 1757, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 152.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5678		Bone						Locus E=1729, Q10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 149.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5752		Bone						Locus N=1727, Q10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 149.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5772		Bone	1,9	1,9				Locus - 1769, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 152.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5773		Bone						Locus - 1769, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 152.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5835		Bone						Locus S=1804, R8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5850		Bone						Locus 1813, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5931		Bone						Locus 1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5932		Bone						Locus 1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5954		Bone						Locus S=1799, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5964		Bone						Locus N=1815, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6051		Bone						Locus W=1817, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6102		Bone						Locus W=1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6108		Bone						Locus E=1812, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6136		Bone						Locus N=1838, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6152		Bone						Locus E=1825, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5714		Pottery						Locus N=1779, S9-10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5717		Pottery						Locus W=1779, S9-10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5730		Pottery						Locus S=1745, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 151.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5939		Pottery						Locus E=1743, Q10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 151.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5940		Pottery						Locus E=1743, Q10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 151.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5942		Pottery						Locus E=1751, R8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 152.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6075		Pottery						Locus E=1793, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6077		Pottery						Locus W=1797, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6079		Pottery						Locus S=1799, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6147		Pottery						Locus S=1803, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6182		Pottery						Locus E=1820, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6224		Pottery						Locus 1829, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6228		Pottery						Locus E=1830, R10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 6236		Pottery						Locus N=1833, R9, Area Cc	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5851		Hematite						Locus 1813, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5856		Hematite						Locus 1813, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 154.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5875		Hematite						Locus 1787, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5705		Limestone						Locus 1733, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 150.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6032		Limestone						Locus E=1831, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5945		Steatite						Locus W=1793, R9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6052		Steatite						Locus W=1817, S10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6110		Steatite						Locus S=1827, Q10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 155.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6119		Steatite						Locus N=1833, R9, Area Cc	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6131		Steatite						Locus N=1835,	Paice 2004: 168. Loud 1948: 156.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									S10, Area CC					
1	M 5805		stone						Locus N=1794, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 169. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5806		stone						Locus N=1794, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 169. Loud 1948: 153.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	06/H/56/AR 1	???	Bone					4,37	H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881.		Bone spindle whorl.	Late IA I	
1	x 655	Biconical	Serpentine	1,6	3		0,6		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:24, pl. 166. Paice 2004: 92, 168, pl. 30: 17		Biconical, serpentinite spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I	
1	96/K/73/AR 3	Biconical	Grey stone					9	Level K-4 (F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:9.		Biconical spindle whorl, complete. Made of grey stone. Large hole in comparison with external diameter.	Late IA I	
1	04/K/13/AR 2	Biconical	Alabaster					28,84	K-5	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Biconical, alabaster spindle whorl, complete.	Early IA I	
1	02/K/71/AR 2	Biconical	Limestone	2,3	4,2		1,1	46,87		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.20.		Biconical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Perfectly shaped and with large, cylindrical hole.	IA	09-255
1	x 675	Button	Bone	0,5	2		0,25		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:20, pl. 166. Paice 2004: 82, 167, pl. 30:12.		Button, bone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I	
1	x 676	Button	Bone	0,4	3		0,3		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:19, pl. 166. Paice 2004: 82, 167, pl. 30:13.		Button, bone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part. Almost broken in half.	EIA I (with intrusions)	
1	x 696	Conical	Serpentine	0,8	2		0,3		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:22. pl. 166. Paice		Conical, serpentinite spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I (with	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
										2004: 92, 168, pl. 30:19.			intrusions)	
1	x 656	Conical	Serpentine	1,3	1,9		0,3		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:23. pl. 166. Paice 2004: 92, 168, pl. 30:18.		Conical, serpentinite spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I (with intrusions)	
1	b 176	Conical	Bone	1,1	2,9		0,5		Locus 3023, K7-8, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 81, pl. 30:5.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, traces of wear/chipping near the hole.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	b 177	Conical	Bone	0,7	2,5		0,3		Locus 3023, K7-8, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 81, pl. 30:6.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	b 178	Conical	Bone		0,9				Locus 3023, K7-8, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 167, pl. 30:7.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	a 9	Conical	Bone		3				Quad N 14 - 401 (IV)	Loud 1948: pl. 172		Conical, bone spindle whorl, with convex sides. On the base concentric incisions.	IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	98/K/31/AR 1	Conical	Serpentine					4,4	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Conical, serpentinite spindle whorl, complete. Very small	Late IA I	
1	00/K/10/AR 1	Conical	Serpentine					8,3	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Conical, serpentinite spindle whorl, complete. Thickening edge.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/25/AR 3	Conical	Serpentine	1,3	2,5		0,35	8,5	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381.	Complete.	Conical spindle whorl, complete. Made of serpentinite. Well polished surface but covered by scratches. Hole slightly larger at the base.	Late IA I	2009-582
1	10/H/52/AR 1	Conical	Bone	1,5	3,8		0,5	14	Sq. E7, H-11, A			Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete but broken in two pieces. On the upper surface traces of polishing and scratchings, not visible on the base. Wear traces near the upper hole.	Early IA I	
1	x 726	Conical truncated	Bone	0,8	2,7		0,5		tomb 39	Guy/Engberg 1938: fig 175:21. pl. 166. Paice		Conical truncated, bone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I (with	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
										2004: 167, pl. 30:14.			intrusions)	
1	a 190	Conical truncated	Limestone	3	6		0,7		Locus N=2043, L8, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 96, 168, pl. 30:20.		Conical truncated, limestone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EIA I (Str. VIb)	
1	M 5551	Cylindrical	Bone	3,1	1,5		1,1		Locus 1745,R10, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 82, 167, pl. 30:10.		Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by four radial lines and small cuts near the edge.	EIA I (Str. VIb)	
1	d 462	Cylindrical	Bone	1,4	2,4		0,5		Locus 5153, K12, Area DD	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 81, 168, pl. 30:8.		Cylindrical, bone object, complete.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	a 81	Discoid	Alabaster	2	3,6		1,2		Locus 2012, K8, area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 96, pl. 30:21.		Discoid, alabaster object. Complete. Very large hole. Probably not a spindle whorl.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	96/F/48/AR5	Discoid	Grey stone	1,4	4,1		0,8	34	Level F-5 (F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:8. Da 34 di peso		Discoid spindle whorl, made of grey limestone. Perforated from one side to the other, slightly conical (0,7).	Late IA I	
1	96/K/101/AR6	Discoid	Limestone	0,8				3+x	Level K-4(F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:13	Original weight 7.5 g.	Discoid, alabaster object, broken. Very large hole. Probably not a spindle whorl.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/103/AR8	Discoid	stone	1,4	4,4x3,8			36	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Unfinished perforation	Discoid, oval pebble with central hole, started from both sides but left unfinished.	Late IA I	2009-271
1	02/M/40/AR1	Discoid	Limestone					30,9	M-4	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	Late IA I	
1	04/K/14/AR1	Discoid	Bone					2,15	K-5, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Discoid, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very light.	Early IA I	
1	98/L/10/AR1	Discoid	Limestone	1		14,3x3	0,6			Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 28,5 g.	Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, fragmentary. Hourglass hole.	IA	670020

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	10/H/16/AR 5	Discoid	stone	0,5	3	0,5	0,3	4,5	Sq. E7, H- 11, F		Destruction debris and accumulation on floor. From the same locus a loom weight 10/H/16 003 and fr. rod 10/H/16 011.	Discoid spindle whorl made of a white stone, very coarse surface with encrustations. Slightly oval.	Early IA I	
1	10/H/62/AR 7	Discoid	stone	2,2	6,4		0,8	82	Sq. E7/8, H-11, F		Accumulatio n on flagstone floor.	Discoid, stone spindle whorl, quite worn. Chalky white stone.	Early IA I	
1	x 420	Dome	Bone	0,5	3				tomb 14	Guy/Engberg 1938: 116, pl. 164. Paice 2004: 82, 167, pl. 30:11.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	EI I (mixed with earlier materials)	
1	a 494	Dome	Bone	0,7	3,1		1,1		Locus 2079, O14, Area BB	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 81, 167, pl. 29:17.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by radial lines in pairs.	EIA I (Str. VIb)	
1	M 5968	Dome	Alabaster	1,2	4,2		1,7		Locus 1760, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 96, 166, pl. 30:22.		Dome, alabaster objects, complete. Very large hole, probably not a spindle whorl.	EIA I (Str. VIb)	
1	d 636	Dome	Grey stone	1,3	2,7		0,4		Locus 5213, L11, Area DD	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 96, 167, pl. 30:16		Dome, grey stone spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	Late IA I (Str. VI a)	
1	d 635	Dome	Black stone	0,6	1,8		0,3		Locus 5216, L11, Area DD	Loud 1948: pl. 172. Paice 2004: 96, 168, pl. 30:15.		Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Made of black stone. Chipped on the side. Decorated by two concentric lines.	EIA I (Str. VIb)	
1	00/K/87/AR 1	Dome	Serpentin ite					6,5	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl, complete.	Late IA I	
1	98/K/23/AR 6	Dome	Ivory					0,75+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.	Original weight 3g.	Dome, ivory spindle whorl, very worn on the upper part.	Late IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/K/29/AR 7	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,8		0,3	4,2	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.		Dome, bone spindle whorl with a small incision on the flat base. Signs of wheel's manufacture on the surface.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/75/AR 1	Dome	Bone	0,5	3,4		0,3	5,7	k-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Left undecorated.	Late IA I	
1	08/H/34/AR 3	Dome	Limestone					32,9	H-9	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, chipped. Hourglass hole and not perfectly centred.	Late IA I	
1	04/K/61/AR 1	Dome	Bone					2,11	K-5, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by four incised circles with central dot. Very light.	Early IA I	
1	04/K/69/AR 1	Dome	Bone					2,66	K-5, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Dome, bone spindle whorl with flat top. Complete and very light.	Early IA I	
1	02/M/33/AR 2	Dome	Bone					2,7	M-4, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.3		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Something wrong on weight measuring.	Late IA I	
1	08/H/5/AR2	Dome	Bone					12,4+ x	H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.3.	Original weight 15,5 g.	Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by an incision similar to a star.	Late IA I	
1	08/H/20/AR 2	Dome	Bone					6,5	H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.3.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Chipped near the upper hole	Late IA I	
1	08/H/177/A R1	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,4		0,3	2,7	Sq. E7, H-11, F		Floor, living surface.	Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Traces of wheel's manufacture well visible on the dome. No traces of polishing on the base. Wear traces near the upper hole. Slightly conical hole, larger on the base (0,4).	Early IA I	
1	10/H/82/5	Dome	Ivory	0,6	2,9		0,4	3,5	Sq. F7/8, H11, F			Dome, ivory spindle whorl, very dark. Almost complete but chipped and worn near the edge. Lots of scratches on both surfaces.	Early IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/H/31/AR 1	Lenticular	Bone					4,15	H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.3.		Lenticular, bone spindle whorl, chipped on one side. Crossing lines on the surface, probably due to manufacture.	Late IA I	
1	98/K/24/AR 2	Spherical	Stone	3,1	2,4	1,6		13,95 +x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381.	Original weight 70 g.	Small fragment of stone (?) spindle whorl, probably spherical in origin.	Late IA I	671762
1	02/K/47/AR 26	Spherical	Pottery	2,2	2,5		0,6	10+x	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, broken on one side. Well shaped but not perfectly manufactured.	Early IA I	
1	00/K/97/AR 3	Spherical	Pottery	2,1	3,1		0,6	19,45	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.		Spherical pottery spindle whorl, broken in two pieces. Irregular, with two fingerprints on the surface and conical hole which is larger on one side (0,8).	Early IA I	09-278
1	00/K/77/AR 10	Spherical	Pottery	1,8	2,6			5,3+x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Fragmentary, original weight 11 g.	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, half missing. Quite well shaped.	Late IA I	670002
1	10/H/92/AR 4	Spherical	Pottery	2,5	2,5		0,5	11,7	H-11, F		Accumulation of floors	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, roughly shaped. Hole very irregular.	Early IA I	

Iron Age II

1	08/Q/78/AR 24		Pottery	1,4x0, 9	4,1x3, 7		0,4	18	Q-4			Broken spindle whorl, made of pottery.	Late IA IIA	
1	M 1010	Biconical	Pottery						locus 283	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:59	Found with whorl M 1012 and spatula M 5158.	Biconical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Very irregular.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 302	Biconical	Pottery						Quad Q 13	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95:16.		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, very worn and irregular.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	12/Q/82/AR 7	Biconical	Stone	1,3	2,9		1,6	14,2	Q-2?			Biconical, stone spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly irregular with wear traces. Well dressed.	IA IIB	
1	M 5047	Biconical	Pottery						locus 1582	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:19.		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4296	Biconical	Pottery						locus 1324	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.20		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete or partially chipped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 801	Biconical	Pottery						locus 261	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.14		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Roughly made.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 909	Biconical	Pottery						Quadrato R10	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.26.		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4688	Biconical	Pottery						Locus 996	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.27		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Large and flattened.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 3359	Biconical	Pottery						locus 1063	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.53		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete but irregular.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	98/L/44/AR 1	Biconical	Pottery	3,2				5,8+x	Level L-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Probably bead	Very elongated biconical object, probably a bead. Preserved for 1/4.	Late IA IIA	
1	M 5345	Button	Bone						Locus S 1682	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.34.		Button, bone spindle whorl, complete. Extremely small.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	12/Q/18/AR 1	Button	Stone	0,8	2,2		0,3	3,5	Q-2?			Button in black stone. Polished surfaces but full of scratches.	IA IIB	
1	M 1930	Button	Steatite						locus 566	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.45		Steatite button, very small.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	00/H/19/AR 1	Button	Bone	0,5	1,4		0,2	0,55+x	H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 405, fig. 18.35.	Original weight 0,7 g.	Too small to be a spindle whorl.	Late IA IIA	
1	14/Q/88/AR 2	Conical	Bone	2,4	3,9		0,7	17	Q-6			Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped. Cancellous bone partially exposed. Wear traces near the upper side of the hole.	Early IA IIA	
1	x 465	Conical	Bone						tomb 27	Guy/Engberg: fig 175:26, pl. 171		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II	
1	92/H/10/AR3 0	Conical	Black stone	1	2,8		0,6	11,5	Locus O	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.17:15	Locus 10 is a probe at the NW of the tell inside the city wall, with post-Stratum IV remains	Small conical spindle whorl made of black stone (serpentine?). Hole slightly larger at the base.	IA II	
1	M 978	Conical	Limestone						locus W 72	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:61		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 157	Conical	Limestone						quad Q 13	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:62		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 968	Conical	Limestone						Locus 282	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:63	Found with two spatulas M 972, 973	Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5184	Conical	Steatite						locus 1613	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:71		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5090	Conical	Steatite						Locus 1612	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:75		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 271	Conical	Steatite						Quad Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:77		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5186	Conical	Steatite						locus 1613	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:78		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 1176	Conical	Steatite						locus 351	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:79		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Extremely small.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 4521	Conical	Steatite						locus 1482	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:80		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Quite flat.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5394	Conical	Bone						locus 1672	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.4		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small and flat.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5209	Conical	Bone						locus 1672	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.6.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5282	Conical	Bone						locus 1672	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 145.		Conical, bone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5235	Conical	Steatite						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.20.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5221	Conical	Steatite						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.21.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Quite flat.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5328	Conical	Bone						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.22.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Quite flat.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5298	Conical	Bone						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.26.		Conical, bone spindle whorl, decorated.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5395	Conical	Limestone						locus 1621	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.29.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5396	Conical	Limestone						locus 1621	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 151.	Found with a bone spatula	Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5191	Conical	Steatite						Locus 1636	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.36.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA II (Str. V)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	94/H/12/ARI	Conical	Black stone	1,3	2,4		0,3	10	Level H-3? (F)	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.17:16.		Small conical spindle whorl made of black stone (serpentinite?). Hole slightly larger at the base (0,35). Small wear traces near the upper hole.	IA IIB	
1	98/H/34/AR1	Conical	Serpentinite	0,7	1,5		0,25	2,1	H-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 405, fig. 18.35.		Too small to be a spindle whorl.	IA IIB	
1	M 4839	Conical	Limestone						locus 1455	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.22.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Crudely worked and surface left rough.	IA IIB	
1	M 4815	Conical	Limestone						Locus 1004	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.56		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4887	Conical	Limestone						Locus 1023	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.57		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4572	Conical	Steatite						locus 1316	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4572	Conical	Steatite						locus 1316	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 127.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 779	Conical	Steatite						quad N 14	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.58		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete and well-shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4886	Conical	Steatite						locus 1251	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.59		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, quite large and tall.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4979	Conical	Steatite						locus 1540	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.10		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4772	Conical	Steatite						locus 1586	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.8.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Incised decoration on the base.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4766	Conical	Steatite						locus 1587	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.9.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5006	Conical	Steatite						locus N 1568 (P 9)	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.13.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Slightly bent.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4307	Conical	Limestone						locus 1400	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 129.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4579	Conical	Limestone						locus 1489	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.26		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Flattened and very small hole.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4901	Conical	Steatite						locus S 1529	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.31.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4607	Conical	Steatite						Locus 1534	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 135.	Found with bone spatula M 4609	Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5111	Conical	Steatite						locus N 1584	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 138.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4958	Conical	Basalt						locus E=1561	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 137.		Conical, basalt spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5001	Conical	Steatite						locus 1565	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 137.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4656	Conical	Steatite						locus 1548	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.32	Found with spatula M 4655	Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4822	Conical	Steatite						locus 1487	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.33		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4648	Conical	Steatite						locus 1542	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.36		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4749	Conical	Bone						locus 1591	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.43.	Found with spatula M 4746	Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1812	Conical	Limestone						locus 507	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1902	Conical	Limestone						locus 539	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 125.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1907	Conical	Limestone						locus 552	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 125.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1955	Conical	Limestone						locus 553	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 125.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4597	Conical	Limestone						locus 559	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 125.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4613	Conical	Steatite						locus 1507	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.55		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4956	Conical	Limestone						locus 1527	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 133.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4828	Conical	Steatite						locus 1484	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.57.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4526	Conical	Steatite						locus 1485	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 133.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 921	Conical	Limestone						locus 300	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 123.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 918	Conical	Steatite						locus 297	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.76		Conical, steatite spindle whorl,	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 925	Conical	Bone						locus 300	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.5		Conical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Flattened.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1826	Conical	Steatite						locus 500	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 124.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1573	Conical	Steatite						locus 494	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 124.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4367	Conical	Limestone						locus 1405	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.35		Conical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4884	Conical	Steatite						locus 1446	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.39		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4411	Conical	Steatite						locus 1441	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.41		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4575	Conical	Steatite						locus 574	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.42.		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 833	Conical	Steatite						quad Q 11	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.44		Conical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Quite flattened.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 1966	Conical	Limestone						locus 567	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 116.		Conical, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 3364	Conical	Limestone						locus 937	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.51		Conical limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 2618	Conical truncated	Steatite						locus 943	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.65		Conical truncated (?), steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4393	Conical truncated	Bone						locus 1486	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.17.		Conical truncated, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4515	Conical truncated	Steatite						locus 1474	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.29.		Conical truncated, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 922	Conical truncated	Limestone						locus 300	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.67		Conical truncated, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Highly damaged	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	08/H/72/AR 1	Cylindrical	Limestone	2,7	3,6		1	40,32 +x	H-7	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, fragmentary. Decorated by a	Early IA IIA	2009-570

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												series of incised lines on the side. Very worn.		
1	12/Q/93/AR 3	Cylindrical	Pottery	1,8	2,3		0,8	5				Cylindrical, pottery spindle whorl, broken in half. Quite well shaped.	Earth debris IA II	
1	M 5061	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus 1557	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:69		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5183	Cylindrical	calcite						locus 1650	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:72		Cylindrical, calcite spindle whorl, complete but worn.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 165	Cylindrical	calcite						Quad P 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:73		Cylindrical, calcite spindle whorl, complete but worn.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 2863	Cylindrical	Bone						Locus 977	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.3		Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl (?), complete. Extremely small	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5482	Cylindrical	Limestone	3	3,5		1	40,41	locus 1714	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.30.		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Oblique incised lines on the side, traces of dark painting. Hole not perfectly cylindrical.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5483	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus N 1708	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.31.		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Oblique incised lines on the side. Hole not perfectly cylindrical.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5458	Cylindrical	Steatite						Locus N 1710	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.32		Cylindrical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Shaped as having a ring on the side.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5128	Cylindrical	Steatite						Locus E 1619	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.37.		Cylindrical, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	98/H/26/AR 1	Cylindrical	Pottery	1,5	2,2		0,7	9,5	Level H-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.		Cylindrical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Badly shaped, irregular with hourglass hole.	IA IIB	2009-275
1	M 4445	Cylindrical	Steatite						locus 1454	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.35		Cylindrical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Quite large.	IA IIB	
1	M 4785	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus 1573	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.64.		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 3324	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus 597	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.1		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4695	Cylindrical	Steatite						locus 1559	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.12		Cylindrical steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4231	Cylindrical	Steatite						locus 1340	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 128.		Cylindrical, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5034	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus N 1584	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.28.		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Crudely worked and sharp-cornered.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4798	Cylindrical	Bone						locus 1545	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.42.	Found with spatula M 5120	Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very tall cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 895	Cylindrical	Bone						locus 292	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.11		Cylindrical, bone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1567	Cylindrical	Pottery						locus 489	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.17		Cylindrical, pottery spindle whorl, roughly made.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 2066	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus 555	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.31.		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 1400	Cylindrical	Limestone						locus 435	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.37		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Flattened.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 934	Cylindrical	Limestone						Quad. Q10	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.38		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Flattened.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4827	Cylindrical	Steatite						locus 1259	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.40		Cylindrical (or flattened dome) steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4414	Cylindrical	Steatite						locus 1441	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.43		Cylindrical, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Tall.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4101	Cylindrical	Hematite						locus 1260	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.66		Cylindrical, hematite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	02/M/33/AR4	Cylindrical	Stone					68,8+ x	M-4, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.	Original weight 140 g	Cylindrical, stone spindle whorl, broken in half.	Late IA I	
1	08/Q/22/AR2	Cylindrical	stone	1,4	2,7x2,5		0,35	9	Q-4			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of white stone. Roughly made, hourglass hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	M 1012	Discoid	Limestone						locus 283	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:50.	Found with whorl M 1010 and spatula M 5158.	Small discoid spindle whorl, made of limestone. Complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 1181	Discoid	Limestone						locus 323	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:68		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	IA II (Str. IV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 2114	Discoid	Limestone						locus 637	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:70		Small, discoid limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 112	Discoid	calcite						Quad Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:74		Discoid (?), calcite spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5011	Discoid	Limestone						locus 977 (Q 8)	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 142.		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 4494	Discoid	Ivory						Locus 1482	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.12.		Discoid, ivory spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 102	Discoid	Pottery						Quad Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.9.		Discoid, pottery spindle whorl, possibly a reworked sherd.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	06/L/34/AR 1	Discoid	Limestone					17,62	L-2	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete but worn surface.	IA IIB	
1	5227	Discoid	Limestone						locus 286	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96.52		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Chipped on the side.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/118/AR 121	Discoid	Stone	1,2	4,7		0,8	29	Q-3			Discoid spindle whorl, fragmentary. Made of grey stone. Well rounded and polished. Cylindrical hole slightly off-centre.	IA IIB	
1	M 3334	Discoid	Steatite						locus 1060	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 126.		Discoid, steatite spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4437	Discoid	Limestone						locus 1424	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.7		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Rounded edges.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4742b	Discoid	Steatite						locus 1591	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.56.		Discoid, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Chipped on the side.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 897	Discoid	Limestone						locus 292	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 123.		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4689	Discoid	Limestone						Locus 996	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.24		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 1895	Discoid	Limestone						locus 543	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 115.		Discoid, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	98/H/53/AR 1	Discoid	Limestone	1,2	5,5			33,4+ x	Level H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.20	Original weight 60 g.	Discoid, limestone spindle whorl, very irregular and with unpolished surface. Perforation made from one side.	Late IA IIA	670024
1	10/Q/37/AR 7	Discoid	Stone	1	3,6		0,6	20	Q-4?			Discoid spindle whorl (?), white stone (limestone). Well rounded and polished.	Late IA IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	14/Q/97/AR8	Discoid	stone	1,2	4,4x4,6		0,8	38	Q-4			Discoid, stone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	Late IA IIA	
1	06/H/15/AR2	Dome	Limestone					99,1	H-7	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Slightly concave base. Wear traces near the upper hole.	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/7/AR1	Dome	Bone					4,5	Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.18:1		Dome, bone spindle whorl, very small.	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/65/AR1	Dome	Ivory	1,3	3		0,6	9	Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.18:2		Dome, ivory spindle whorl, complete.	Early IA IIA	
1	12/Q/91/AR1	Dome	Bone	1,9	3,5		0,65	12	Q-5			Dome, bone spindle whorl, broken. Cancellous bone exposed.	Early IA IIA	
1	x464	Dome	Slate						tomb 27	Guy/Engberg: fig 175:25, pl. 171		Flat dome spindle whorl, made of slate. Complete.	IA II	
1	M 106	Dome	Limestone						Quad Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:64		Large, dome spindle whorl made of bone. Complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 1113	Dome	Limestone						Quad. O 11	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:65		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Very worn on the upper surface.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5185	Dome	Bone						locus 1613	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 144.	Found with other three whorls	Dome, bone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5099	Dome	Limestone						locus 1620	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 144.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5060	Dome	Steatite						locus 1496	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:81		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5045	Dome	Limestone						locus 1490	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 143.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5089	Dome	Bone						locus 1612	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.7		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by nine incised circles on the dome and on the base.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5098	Dome	Bone						locus 1620	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.8		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 180	Dome	Bone						Quad P 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.10.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very high.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 1269	Dome	Limestone						locus 380	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 142.	Found with basalt ring M 1179	Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5368	Dome	Bone						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.23.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5299	Dome	Bone						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.24.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5091	Dome	Bone						locus 1626	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.25.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5195	Dome	Limestone						locus 1650	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 144.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5363	Dome	Bone						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.27.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, completed. Very high dome.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	5410	Dome	Limestone						Quad Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:66		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 2021	Dome	Limestone						Quad R 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 148.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5145	Dome	Limestone						locus 1619	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.28.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Very large and high, a vertical incised sign on the side.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5335	Dome	Bone						Locus N 1684	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.33		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5644	Dome	Bone						Locus 1714	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.35.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 5643	Dome	Bone						Locus 1714	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 155.		Dome, bone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 66	Dome	bone						Locus N=37	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 149.		Dome, bone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 2609	Dome	Steatite						Locus 50	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 149.		Dome, steatite spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 2610	Dome	Bone						Locus 50	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 149.		Dome, bone spindle whorl.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 172	Dome	Basalt						Quad Q 13	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.2.		Dome, basalt spindle whorl, complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	94/H/8/AR15	Dome	Limestone	2	3,7		0,6	26,5	Level H-3 (F);	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.17:17.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Circular wheel's signs on dome and base. On the base traces of polishing. Hole slightly larger at the base. Wear traces near the upper hole, not near the lower hole.	IA IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4193	Dome	Limestone						locus 1284	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94		Error in publication.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/79/AR 18	Dome	Pottery	1,8	3		0,6	18	Q-2			Dome, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well-polished. Traces of wear near both sides of hole.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/79/AR 20	Dome	Stone	1,9	3,1		0,6	19	Q-2			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Made of grey stone. Well dressed, perfectly polished on both sides. Small chips near upper hole and external diameter.	IA IIB	
1	M 4366	Dome	Limestone						locus 959	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.30		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Large and tall.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4541	Dome	Limestone						locus 959	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 126.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4391	Dome	Limestone						locus 994	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 126.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4233	Dome	Limestone						locus 1296	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.55.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, very well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 800	Dome	Limestone						Locus 261	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.63		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well-shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5038	Dome	Limestone						locus S 1587	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.2.		Large, dome shaped, limestone spindle whorl with cracked surface.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4797	Dome	Limestone						locus W=1577	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.3.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well-shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4770	Dome	Limestone						locus E 1479	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.4.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4336	Dome	Limestone						locus 1003	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.5		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4957	Dome	Limestone						locus 1540	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.6.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and flattened.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4904	Dome	Limestone						locus 1424	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 129.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4538	Dome	Steatite						locus 1472	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.11.		Dome steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4740	Dome	Steatite						locus 1580	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.14.		Dome steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4805	Dome	Bone						locus S 1544	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.16.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4543	Dome	Bone						locus 1426	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.18.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete and well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4546	Dome	Limestone						locus 1426	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 130		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4287	Dome	Limestone						locus 1332	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 128.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4642	Dome	Limestone						locus 1469	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 131.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4707	Dome	Limestone						locus N 1552	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.24.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4170	Dome	Limestone						locus 1280	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.25		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete and well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4902	Dome	Limestone						locus S 1529	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.27		Dome, limestone (?) spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5110	Dome	Limestone						locus N 1584	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 138, pl. 94.23.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Chipped at the edge.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4708	Dome	Limestone						locus 1474	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 132.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4930	Dome	Steatite						locus 1560	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.30.		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4690	Dome	Limestone						locus E=1561	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 137.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4706	Dome	Steatite						locus E=1561	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.34.		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete and small.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4715	Dome	Limestone						locus 1484	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 133.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4486	Dome	Bone						locus 1481	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.40.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4790	Dome	Bone						locus 1571	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.41.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Quite large and very tall.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4660	Dome	Limestone						locus 1549	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.47.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4659	Dome	Steatite						locus 1549	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.53		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Incised decoration on the base: a concentric incision along the edge and radial grooves near the hole.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4742a	Dome	Limestone						locus 1591	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.51		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4735	Dome	Limestone						locus 1598	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 139.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1809	Dome	Steatite						locus 511	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.54.		Dome, steatite spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 2622	Dome	Limestone						Quad. M8	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.28.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4087	Dome	Limestone						Quad. Q8	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.29		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 1976	Dome	Limestone						locus 564	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 116.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4639	Dome	Limestone						locus 1473	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.33		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4436	Dome	Limestone						locus 1275	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.34		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4328	Dome	Limestone						locus 1393	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 120.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4258	Dome	Limestone						locus 757	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.36		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Flattish top.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4164	Dome	Limestone						locus 723	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 116.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 2910	Dome	Bone						locus 990	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.46		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Quite flattened.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4319	Dome	Bone						locus 1406	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.47		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4355	Dome	Bone						locus 1004	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.48		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4409	Dome	Limestone						locus 1441	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 120.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 3247	Dome	Limestone						locus 1019	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 118.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 3289	Dome	Pottery						locus 1033	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.50		Dome pottery spindle whorl, complete. Decorated by a series of small incisions on the edge.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 2554	Dome	Limestone						locus 934	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.52		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete but chipped or broken near the upper hole.	IA IIC (Str. II)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	5190	Dome	Bone						quad O 13	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.67		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete but chipped near the upper hole.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	00/H/36/AR1	Dome	Bone	1,7	3,8		0,4	12,6	Level H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21,	Cattle caput femoris	Dome, bone spindle whorl, quite thick and not decorated. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,6). Dome well polished while base shows the cancellous bone.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/49/AR5	Dome	Ivory	1	2,8		0,35	5,2	Q-4?			Dome, ivory spindle whorl, broken in half. Well polished dome but signs of hole manufacture are still visible. Flat side with evident signs of parallel lines crossing in various directions.	Late IA IIA	
1	M 1157	Spherical	Pottery						locus 359	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.13.	Found with bone spatulas M 1153, 1154, 1155, 1156	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Quite irregular but well rounded.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 4431	Spherical	Pottery						locus 1421	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.60		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Quite well shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4910	Spherical	Limestone						Locus 1532	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 135, pl. 94.49.		Spherical, limestone spindle whorl, roughly shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4913	Spherical	Pottery						locus E 1550	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.44.		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Roughly shaped.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5056	Spherical	Limestone						locus 1591	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 139.		Spherical, limestone spindle whorl, complete.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1896	Spherical	Bone						locus 543	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.49		Spherical (?), bone spindle whorl, chipped or broken.	IA IIC (Str. II)	

Unknown context

1	06/K/1/AR2	nn	Bone					6,3		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880				
1	08/Q/10/AR1	Biconical	Pottery	2,2	2,8		0,7	13	Surface finds			Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, complete. Roughly made.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	x 100	Biconical	Pottery			2,7			tomb 1	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 153		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl.		
1	M 97	Biconical	Pottery						tomb 73	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 163		Biconical, pottery spindle whorl.		
1	94/F/25/AR2	Biconical	Pottery	2,8	4,3		0,7	28+x	unstratified	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:4.	Original weight 112 g.	Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, fragmentary. Hole off-centre.		
1	98/J/116/AR1	Biconical	Pottery	3	4			23,1+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 46 g.	Biconical pottery spindle whorl, half missing. Well shaped.		
1	00/J/85/AR1	Biconical	Pottery	3,1	3,9		0,4	36,75		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Asymmetrica 1	Biconical, pottery spindle whorl, almost complete. Very worn. Wear traces near the hole.		
1	06/K/31/AR6	Biconical	Pottery					13,87		Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.		
1	06/K/92/AR4	Biconical	Pottery					19,81		Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.		
1	?	Biconical	stone	1,8	2,4		0,7	8,83				Biconical stone spindle whorl, complete. Perfectly polished. Cylindrical hole.		01-2932
1	04/K/58/AR2	Button	Serpentine							Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1	Original weight 20,86 g.	Serpentine button, fragmentary.		
1	04/K/81/AR15	Button	Bone					2,44		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Bone button, complete.		
1	00/F/088/AR001	Button	Ivory	0,4	3,3			1,5+x	??	Sass/Cinamon 2006, 370, fig. 18.13		Bone button (?) broken in half.		
1	96/K/I0/AR3	Conical	Black stone					4,5+x	Unstratified	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:14.	Original weight 9 g	Small conical spindle whorl made of black stone (serpentine?). Fragmentary, incised decoration on the base.		
1	3099a	Cylindrical	Limestone						tomb 59	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 157		Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/J/19/AR3	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,9	3,2	1,6		15,9+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 48 g.	Cylindrical, limestone spindle whorl, fragmentary. Well shaped.		
1	06/K/92/AR1	Cylindrical	Pottery					14,33		Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4		Cylindrical pottery spindle whorl, complete.		
1	02/K/57/AR3	Cylindrical	Alabaster					12,2		Blockman/Sass 2013: 917, fig. 15.24.		Cylindrical, alabaster object, possibly a spindle whorl.		
1	96/K/11/AR3	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,6	3,4		0,7	23,8		?		In Sass 2000 a spatula under this label.		
1	00/J/103/AR2	Discoid	Limestone		3,9		1,1	24,6+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 28 g.	Rounded pebble with hourglass hole		
1	06/K/50/AR4	Discoid	Limestone					22,95		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Discoid limestone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.		
1	3099b	Dome	Serpentine						tomb 59	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 157		Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl.		
1	x 1975	Dome	Bone						tomb 59 A	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 157		Dome, bone spindle whorl.		
1	02/K/22/AR1	Dome	Serpentine					25,2		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.		
1	98/H/20/AR1	Dome	Limestone					14,55		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Dome, limestone spindle whorl, complete. Slightly chipped.		
1	00/K/62/AR1	Dome	Ivory					1,4+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 384, fig. 18.21.	Original weight 4,2 g.	Dome/discoid fragment of ivory spindle whorl.		
1	04/K/35/AR2	Dome	Serpentine							Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1	Original weight 9,9 g.	Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl, 1/3 missing. Well shaped.		
1	04/K/50/AR3	Dome	Serpentine					9,11		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.		
1	04/M/57/AR1	Dome	Serpentine					2,59		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1		Dome, serpentinite spindle whorl. Very small.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/J/10/AR4	Dome	Bone					3,55		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.		
1	04/K/26/AR1	Dome	Bone					2,95		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.2		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.		
1	08/H/9/AR1	Dome	Bone					12,7		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.3		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Wear traces near upper hole.		
1	04/M/61/AR1	Dome	Bone					2,75		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.3		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete. Very small.		
1	06/M/45/AR1	Dome	Bone					4,39		Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.3		Dome, bone spindle whorl, complete.		
1	267	Dome	Bone	2	4,4		0,5	14,8				Dome, bone spindle whorl, almost complete. Well polished dome, base with cancellous bone exposed. Wear traces near upper hole.		I-1564
1	239	Dome	Bone	1,7	4		0,4	10,48				Dome, bone spindle whorl, almost complete. Well polished dome, base with cancellous bone exposed. Wear traces near upper hole.		I-2845
1	98/K/007/AR1	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,4		0,35	3,84				Dome, bone spindle whorl, almost complete. Well polished dome, base with signs of manufacture. Cylindrical hole.		01-2970
1	12/H/92/AR1	Dome	Bone	1,7	2,2		0,25	2,7+x	unclassified debris			Dome, bone spindle whorl, small part missing. Well polished dome, base with signs of manufacture. Four circles with central dot incised on the dome. Neatly cut hole, no traces of wear.		
1	M 69	Spherical	Pottery						tomb 73	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 161		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl.		
1	04/K/122/AR2	Spherical	Pottery					12,12+x		Blockman/Sass 2013: 881, fig. 23.4		Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, quite well shaped. 1/3 missing.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	04/J/34/AR1	Spherical	Pottery							Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4	Original weight 60 g.	Spherical pottery spindle whorl, half preserved.		
1	04/M/39/AR5	Spherical	Pottery							Blockman/Sass 2013: 882, fig. 23.4	Original weight 18 g.	Spherical, pottery spindle whorl, fragmentary.		

PERFORATED SHERDS

Early Bronze Age

1	98/J/121/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	4,1	1,7		9,78 +x	Level J-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 30 g. Occupational debris.	Half missing. Perforated sherd roughly cut, with sharp edges. Hourglass hole.	EB Ib	67005
1	04/J/42/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		1,7				J-6b, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Floor and accumulation on floor	Perforated sherd.	EB III	
1	00/J/12/AR4	Prf. sherd	Pottery					32,8 5	J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.	Brick material. Found with a weight 00/J/12/AR1	Complete, but broken in two pieces. Hole near one rim, probably not used as whorl.	EB III	
1	06/J/36/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4				J-5, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Construction fill	Fragmentary perforated sherd.	EB III	

Middle Bronze Age

1	96/F/29/AR9	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Level F-12 (A);	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:12.	Earthen rampart	Complete, quite rounded with unfinished hole.	MB II	
1	2799	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,2	6,8x 7,2		0,4	71,8				Perforated sherd, quite rounded. Hourglass hole, slightly diagonal.	MB I	I- 3304
1	613	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	6x5, 7		0,5x 0,7	37,4			T3	Perforated sherd, complete. Quite well rounded, oval hourglass hole.	MB I	I-1586

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	06/K/22/AR8	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1					K-10, F		Occupational accumulation on a compacted earth floor.	Fragment of a pottery disk, irregular shape.	MB III/LB I	
1	269	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,9x5,4		0,55	30				Perforated sherd, complete. Not well rounded, quite irregular. Hourglass hole.	MB I	I-1566
1	12/K/65/AR9	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8					K-11		Storage pit. Many stoppers from the same context.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Well rounded and smoothed edge.	MB II	
1	10/K/99/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,4		0,5	19	K-10			Perforated sherd, complete. Quite well rounded, hourglass hole.	MB III/LB I	
1	14/K/75/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	2,8			7	K-11			Reworked sherd, complete. Well rounded. Perforation not finished.	MB III/LB I	
1	14/K/101/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,6	4,9		0,9	44	K-12			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded, small chips on the edge. Hourglass hole.	MB	
1	14/K/102/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9					K-12			Perforated sherd, half missing. Hole not finished.	MB	

Late Bronze Age

1	08/K/33/AR8	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	5,7		0,3	16+x	Level K-9?			Perforated sherd, half preserved. Roughly cut, sharp edge. Hourglass hole, slightly diagonal.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/33/AR18	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	2,9x3,2		0,3	12	Level K-9?			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded and smoothed edge. Hourglass hole.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/49/AR14	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	4,4			8,5+x	Level K-9?			Perforated sherd, half preserved. Smooth but irregular shape.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/78/AR3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7		5,2		11,8+x	Level K-9			Perforated sherd, fragmentary.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/50/AR3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	5,1x3,9		0,3	17,8	Level K-9			Perforated sherd, complete. Not rounded, sharp edge. Hourglass hole.	LB IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	10/K/60/AR 8	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	4.3x4. 6		0,5	25	Level K-9			Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, sharp edge. Thick layer of encrustation on the lower surface. Hourglass hole.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/61/AR 9	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1.1	6,9		0,5	61	Level K-9			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded, smoothed edge. Hourglass hole.	LB IIA	
1	M 2531	Prf. sherd	Pottery			1			tomb 876	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 142		Perforated sherd, complete or partially chipped. Hourglass hole.	LB II	
1	04/K/111/A R7	Prf. sherd	Pottery		6				K-8?, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Mudbrick material		LB IIB	
1	04/K/119/A R7	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4				K-8?, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Occupational debris		LB IIB	
1	06/K/24b/A R2	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5				K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Mudbrick material		LB IIB	
1	06/K/25/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5				K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Mudbrick material		LB IIB	
1	06/K/100/A R4	Prf. sherd	Pottery		3				K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 883.		Hole not completed.	LB II	
1	06/K/123/A R5	Prf. sherd	Pottery		2,5				K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Occupational debris. Several grinding tools		LB IIB	
1	08/K/101/A R2	Prf. sherd	Pottery		3,5				K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Wall removal		LB IIB	
1	06/K/111/A R3	Prf. sherd	Pottery		2,5				K-7?, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Mudbrick material		LB IIB	
1	08/K/29/AR 4	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,5				K-7, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Wall removal. Several grinding tools		LB IIB	
1	02/K/62/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery					17,6+ x	K-6, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Original weight 44 g. Earth debris.	Fragmentary, hole off-centre.	LB III	
1	04/M/83/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,5				M-6, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Occupational accumulation		LB III	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	04/M/8/AR18	Prf. sherd	Pottery		8				M-6, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.			LB III	
1	02/K/82/AR6	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5,5				K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 883.	Occupational debris		LB III	
1	10/H/64/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	5,6x4,7		0,4	20	H12, F		Accumulation on flagstone floor.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, not rounded. Hourglass hole, slightly off-centre.	LB III	
1	10/H/025/AR6	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	10,4x9,6		0,9	110	Sq. F9, H12, F		Accumulation on flagstone floor. One loom weight from the same context 10/H/25 002	Large, perforated sherd, complete. Slightly chipped on the edge. Smoothed edge but irregular shape. Hourglass hole.	LB III	

Iron Age I

1	00/K/22/AR3 pt. 008	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	3,4		0,4	5,7+x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Original weight 11,5 g. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, half missing. Quite well rounded, hourglass hole, very diagonal.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/25/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	6,7		0,4	34	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Complete. Brick collapse. Found with a serpentine flywheel.	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Roughly cut. Slightly hourglass hole, well centred.	Late IA I	2009-267
1	00/K/27/AR4	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	7,3		0,4	26+x	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 43 g. Floor accumulation. Found with several grinding tools.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Quite well rounded. Hourglass hole.	Early IA I	669997

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/K/29/AR 5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	5,9		0,3	31,6	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Complete. Brick collapse. Found with a bone flywheel.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, sharp edges. Hourglass hole, small and oval.	Late IA I	2009-272
1	00/K/29/AR 6	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	6,3x6, 5		0,3	37,2+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 44 g. Brick collapse. Found with a bone flywheel.	Perforated sherd, chipped on the side. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	2009-576
1	00/K/31/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,4	11,2x 13		0,5	129,7 5+x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 200 g.	Very large, perforated sherd, partially broken. Very small hourglass hole.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/34/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	6,5			16,4+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 23 g. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, broken in different points. Hole not finished.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/42/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	5,9		0,6	18,31	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 376, fig. 18.15	Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Quite well rounded and smoothed, slightly hourglass hole.	Late IA I	09-254
1	00/K/45/AR 13	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,1	7,8x9		0,3x0, 4	99	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, complete. Central hole, hourglass and oval. Roughly cut, sharp edges.	Late IA I	2009-573
1	00/K/45/AR 6	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	5,6x6, 3		0,1	37,37	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, hole hourglass but probably not finished.	Late IA I	2009-580
1	00/K/45/AR 7	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	7,5x7		0,5	65	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut but almost round. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	2009-575
1	00/K/5/AR3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	6,2			31,45 +x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 63 g. Burnt debris.	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Smoothed edge. Hourglass hole, very diagonal.	Late IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/K/51/AR 5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	4,6x5		0,4	23,75	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Occupational debris. Found with two basalt flywheels.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut. Hourglass hole, diagonal.	Late IA I	2009-574
1	00/K/51/AR 9	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	4,6x5		0,25	17,92	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Complete. Occupational debris. Found with two basalt flywheels	Perforated sherd, complete. Oval in shape but smoothed edge. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	2009-266
1	00/K/58/AR 6	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	5,5		0,5	13,4+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Occupational debris. Original weight 30 g.	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Irregular and sharp edges. Cylindrical hole.	Late IA I	
1	00/K/64/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	6,9x6		0,5	53,2	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut but quite rounded. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	2009-579
1	00/K/99/AR 3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	5,4		0,3	35,45	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete.	Perforated sherd, complete. Hourglass hole, small and off- centre.	Late IA I	2009-578
1	00/K/99/AR 6 pt 001	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,1		0,45	8,45+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 15 g.	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Irregular edges, hourglass hole.	Late IA I	
1	02/K/36/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	4		0,5	10,9+ x	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 13,5 g. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Roughly cut, sharp edges. Hourglass hole.	Early IA I	
1	02/K/47/AR 15	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	5,2x4, 8		0,4	21,6	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 382, fig. 18.43.	Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, sharp edges. Hourglass hole.	Early IA I	
1	02/K/47/AR 17	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	4,8x5, 7		0,5x0 3	29	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, complete. Hole hourglass, off-centre.	Early IA I	2009-577
1	02/K/47/AR 22	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,8		0,4	11,25	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Complete. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, sharp edges. Hourglass hole.	Early IA I	2009-276

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	06/H/49/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5				H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Destruction debris		Late IA I	
1	06/H/50/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,5				H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Accumulation on floor		Late IA I	
1	06/H/50/AR2	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5,5				H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Accumulation on floor		Late IA I	
1	06/M/31a/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		7				M-5,F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Occupational debris.		Early IA I	
1	08/H/47/AR4	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,2	7,2x6,9		0,6	70	Sq. E6, H-10, F?		Floor, living surface	Perforated sherd, broken in two pieces, slightly chipped. Roughly cut, irregular shape. Hourglass and diagonal hole.	Early IA I	
1	08/H/19/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		9				H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Accumulation on floor		Late IA I	
1	08/H/36/AR15	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,5				H-9, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 883.	Accumulation on floor	Unfinished hole.	Late IA I	
1	10/H/8/AR2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	4,5			14+x	Sq. F9, H-11, F?		Floor, living surface	Perforated sherd, half preserved.	Early IA I	
1	10/H/8/AR3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7					Sq. F9, H-11, F?		Floor, living surface	Perforated sherd, almost 1/4 preserved. Hourglass hole.	Early IA I	
1	10/H/94/AR2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,6x4,1		0,3	20	Sq. F7, H-11, F		Occupational accumulation	Perforated sherd with very small and diagonal hourglass hole.	Early IA I	
1	96/K/101/AR10	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,5		0,6	18,4	Level K-4 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:10	Brick material in room. Found with another limestone spindle whorl.	Perforated sherd, well smoothed edge, slightly ovoid. Broken in two pieces.	Late IA I (mixed context)	
1	96/K/77/AR5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	6,1			19,59+x	Level K-4 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:11	Original weight 20 g. Mixed context. Collapse of burnt bricks.	Perforated sherd, broken. Roughly cut, hourglass hole.	Late IA I	
1	96/K/92/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,9		0,3	16	Level K-4 (F?)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:6	Brick material.	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut.	Late IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/K/100/A R2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,6		0,4	14,8		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Complete. Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, complete. Quite well shaped, central hole. Perforation made from both sides but well smoothed and almost cylindrical.		2009-583
1	98/K/120/A R4	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	3,1		0,5x0, 6	7,1	k-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Complete. Brick collapse.	Perforated sherd, small and well rounded. Off centre hole, quite oval and hourglass.	Late IA I	2009-268
1	98/K/120/A R7	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	4,1x3, 5		0,4	19,9	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Complete. Brick collapse.	Perforated sherd, complete. Irregular shape, central hole, made perforating from both sided but almost cylindrical.	Late IA I	2009-269
1	98/K/121/A R3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,2	6,8	14	0,4	42,7	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 107 g. Brick and ashy material.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Hourglass hole. .	Late IA I	671758
1	98/K/24/AR 4	Prf. sherd	Pottery					26,6+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 88 g. Accumulatio n on floor.	Fragmentary	Late IA I	
1	98/K/33/AR 7	Prf. sherd	Pottery		12			126,8 5+x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 254 g!!!!	Too large and heavy. Fragmentary.	Late IA I	
1	98/K/33/AR 8	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7				9,9+x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 33 g. Brick material.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Slightly hourglass hole.	Late IA I	
1	98/K/41/AR 14	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,1	6,5		0,5	52,9	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Complete. Occupational debris. Found with other whorls and a needle.	Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded and central and almost cylindrical hole. Perfect spindle whorl.	Late IA I	2009-273
1	98/K/41/AR 4	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	4,2		0,6	8,15+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 27 g. Occupational debris. Found with	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Hole slightly hourglass.	Late IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											other whorls and a needle.			
1	98/K/41/AR 5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,4	6			60,55	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Unfinished hole. Occupational debris. Found with other whorls and a needle.	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole unfinished.	Late IA I	671757
1	98/K/41/AR 7	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,1	6,5			53,15	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.23.	Unfinished hole. Occupational debris. Found with other whorls and a needle.	Perforated sherd, complete. Hole unfinished and drilled only from one side.	Late IA I	2009-270
1	98/K/42/AR 8	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,8			9,45+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Brick collapse. Found with two needles. Original weight 19 g.	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Unfinished hole	Late IA I	
1	98/K/45/AR 6	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	5			10,5+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385, fig. 18.22.	Original weight 23 g. Occupational debris.	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Irregular shape. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	669996
1	14/Q/13/AR 4	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9		3.3xs 2.4			Q-7			Perforated sherd, fragment.	Late IA I	
1	14/Q/162/A R1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	3,7			13	Q-7			Perforated sherd, well rounded, hole unfinished but drilled from both sides.	Late IA I	

Iron Age II

1	14/Q/157/A R2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	5,6x5, 3		0,4	33	Q-6			Perforated sherd, complete. Irregular shape not rounded. Hourglass hole, off-centre.	Early IA IIA	
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Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	96/K/45/AR 3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	4,4		0,4	17	Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:7.	Occupation debris. Found with an unbaked loom weight.	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/12/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,8			10	Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:8.	Occupation debris.	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass, ovoid, and irregular hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/H/24/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Level H-3? (F)	Sass 2000: 377.	Not illustrated. Occupational debris?	Perforated sherd, small fragment.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/15/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,2	7,1		0,7	40+x	Level H-1 (A)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:9.	Mixed context. Make up. Original weight 73 g.	Perforated sherd, irregular shape but smoothed edge. Hourglass hole but centrally cylindrical. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	52540
1	98/K/28/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	7		0,6	61,55	K-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Brown debris. Found with a bone spatula.	Perforated sherd, complete. Centred hole, perforation made starting from both sides but cylindrical.	Early IA IIA	2009-581
1	98/H/30/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	6		0,5	15,7+ x	H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 385.	Original weight 39 g. Floor accumulation	Perforated sherd, fragmentary. Quite irregular but smoothed edge. Perforation made starting from both sides but cylindrical.	Late IA IIA	
1	04/L/39/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5				L-?	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 423.			IA II	
1	06/H/67/AR 3	Prf. sherd	Pottery					6	H-7	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Beaten earthen floor		Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/08/AR 5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,4		0,4	18,44	K-3	Sass 2000: 377.	Occupation debris	Perforated sherd, quite rounded. Hole slightly off centre and hourglass.	Early IA IIA	02-947
1	13/H/10/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery		7,6	0,8	0,4	25				Perforated sherd, half preserved. Edge not smoothed. Irregular, hourglass, and diagonal hole.		
1	96/K/2/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Level K-3 (F);	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:13	Occupation debris	Unfinished hole.	Early IA IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	96/K/36/AR 3	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 377, fig. 12.19:14	Occupation debris	Unfinished hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	08/H/26/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery						H-8, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 882.	Tabun		Early IA IIA	
1	M 5027a	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1574	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 121.			IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 5027b	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1574	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 121.			IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4637	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 782	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.68		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4953	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1542	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.54	Found with spindle whorl M 4648 and another prf. Sherd M 4954	Perforated sherd, complete. Base of a vessel, as in Hazor	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4825	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1316	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.61		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4955	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1316	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.62		Perforated sherd, complete. Base of a vessel, as in Hazor	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4909	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1538	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.21		Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4896	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1561	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.45	Found with basalt ring M 4897	Perforated sherd, partially broken.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4954	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1542	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.46		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 873	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 285	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.60		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded.	IA IIB	
1	5339	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 292	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.18		Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5024a	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.68	filling	Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded.	IA II (Stra. IV)	
1	M 5187	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1613	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.15	Found with other three whorls	Perforated sherd.	IA II (Stra. IV)	
1	881	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 286	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 123			IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 4627	Prf. sherd	Pottery						locus 1406	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 129			IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	5424	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Locus 594	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95.19		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded, but oval.	IA II (Stra. V)	
1	08/Q/10/AR 2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,3	5		0,5	41	Q-2			Perforated sherd, partially rounded, complete. Central and cylindrical hole.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/22/AR 14	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,8		0,3	12	Q-4			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded, central, and cylindrical hole but very small.	Late IA IIA	
1	08/Q/68/AR 10	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,1	5,3		0,4	39	Q-4			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded. Central and cylindrical hole. Another unfinished small hole near the previous one.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/114/A R9	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,3					Q-4?			Perforated sherd, fragmentary.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/169/A R2	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	6x6,5		0,5	51	Q-4			Perforated sherd, complete. Irregular, off-centre, and hourglass hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	12/Q/80/AR 1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,8		0,5	19	Q-4			Perforated sherd, quite rounded. Central and cylindrical hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	12/Q/172/A R1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	7x6,2		0,7	53	Q-5			Perforated sherd, complete. Irregular shape. Off centre and hourglass hole.	Early IA IIA	

Unknown context

1	10/Q/91/A R26	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	5,3x 4,9		0,5	29				Perforated sherd, complete. Irregular shape. Slightly hourglass hole.		
1	96/K/48/A R5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	3,5		0,4	14,8 2	Unstratified		Mixed bricks and later disturbance	Perforated sherd, complete. Quite rounded but not smoothed and off-centre hole.		02-949
1	96/J/5/AR 12	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	3,9x 3,2		0,4x 0,6	14,6 7	Topsoil/fill	Sass 2000: 377.		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Conical hole, irregular shape.		02-1181

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	96/K/084/AR1	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	4,4x 4,9		0,4	24,6 9				Perforated sherd, roughly cut.		02-946
1	08/K/17/A R3	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,5x 3,8		0,7x 0,2	12,2				Perforated sherd, complete. Hourglass hole, oval and not suitable for inserting a shaft.		
1	5529	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5				tomb 67A	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 88				

SPINNING BOWLS

1	P. 6437		pottery						S=1820	Loud 1948: pl.70:3		Fragment of spinning bowl with two loops inside.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
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LOOM WEIGHTS

Early Bronze Age

1	00/J/35/AR1		Basalt					209,6 +x	J-1	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Fragment with irregular shape and part of a hole.	EB I	
1	98/J/32/AR2	Discoidal	limestone	1,6	6,2		0,8	53,42	J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Cylindrical pebble, irregular, with through hole made from one side. Complete.	EB III	2009-292
1	00/J/12/AR1		limestone					123,4 5	J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Irregular pebble with through hole.	EB III	
1	00/J/105/AR 2		limestone						J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Irregular shape, unfinished hole.	EB III	
1	10/J/177/AR 1	Discoid	Stone	1,1	5,9x4, 8			44,5	J-6c			Discoid object, semicircular shape. Perforation started from both sides.	EB III	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	10/J/51/AR1	Discoid	Stone (pebble)	1,6	5x5,1		0,2	56,7	J-4			Pebble with perforation near the edge, as if it was a pendant.	EB I	
1	10/J/60/AR1	Dome	Stone	3,1	6,1		1,1x1.5	157	J-6C			Weight almost complete, made of limestone. Flat base a sort of dome. On the side some grooves are present.	EB III	

Middle Bronze Age

1	d 277	Conical	Unfired clay						NE 5076	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	d 261	Conical	Unfired clay	11,1	7,7		0,7	532	5070	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Vertically perforated. Conical weight made of unfired clay, well shaped.	MB I (Str. XIII)	1939-548
1	c 535	Conical	Unfired clay						4089	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Vertically perforated. Conical weight made of unfired clay, well shaped.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	c 370	Conical	Unfired clay						4097	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	c 369	Conical	Fired clay	11,4	6,2		0,5	447	4097	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight, quite rounded, with small, horizontal hole. Made of fired clay and covered by a red slip, burnished. Base perfectly flat. Very well dressed.	MB I (Str. XIII)	1938-963
1	c 368	Conical	Unfired clay						4097	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	c 367	Conical	Unfired clay						4097	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	c 366	Conical	Unfired clay						4097	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB I (Str. XIII)	
1	06/J/107/AR2	Conical	Fired clay					494+x	J-10a, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 887, fig. 23.6.	Original weight 543 g. Found in a grave.	Conical weight made of fired clay. Broken.	MB I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	d 260	Conical	Unfired clay						5077	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay. Fragmentary Sealing on the surface.	MB II (Str. XII)	
1	b 746	Conical	Fired clay	9,6	5,9x6,2		0,5	337	S =T.3107	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight, horizontal hole. Scarab sealing on top.	MB II (Str. XI)	1937-913
1	c 244	Conical	Unfired clay						T.4056	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay. Sealing on the surface.	MB II (Str. XI)	
1	c 637	Conical	Fired clay	7,5	7,8			494+x	4063	Loud 164:3?		Conical weight, broken at the height of hole. Horizontal perforation and scarab sealing on the side.	MB II (Str. XI)	1938-991
1	94/F/30/AR1	Conical	Fired clay					187+x	Level F-12/F-11?	Sass 2000: 370, fig. 12.15:5.	Original weight 400 g	Only base, hole not preserved.	MB II	
1	96/F/26/AR5	Biconical	Fired clay					154+x	Level F-12 (A)	Sass 2000: 370, fig. 12.15:6.	Mixed context, EB/MB I-II.	Only base, hole not preserved.	MB II	
1	c 357	Conical	Fired clay	10,6	7,6		0,5	600	4019	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight, quite rounded, with small, horizontal hole. Made of fired clay and covered by a red slip, burnished. Base perfectly flat. Very well dressed.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	1938-961
1	c 107	Conical	Fired clay	10	7,7		0,4	628	4025	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight, rounded with small hole. Seal impression on top showing Egyptian figure kneeling and holding forward something (lotus flower?)	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	1938-923
1	c 199	Conical	Unfired clay						N 3147	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay. Sealing on the surface.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	b 377	Conical	Unfired clay			1,8			E 3037	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	c 84	Conical	Unfired clay						T.4007	Loud 1948: pl. 169		Conical weight made of unfired clay. Sealing on the surface.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
26	b 459	Conical	Unfired clay						E 3036	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Twenty-six conical weights made of unbaked clay. Horizontal perforation. At least one with vertical perforation.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	b 389	Conical	Unfired clay						T 3052	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Conical weight, complete. Horizontally pierced, sort of waist under the top.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	a 206	Conical	Unfired clay						T 2034	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Conical weight, complete. Horizontally pierced.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
2	a 146	Conical	Unfired clay						2025	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Two conical weights, complete. Horizontally pierced.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	b 247	Conical	Fired clay	10,4	6,3		0,6	363	3180	Loud 1948: pl. 170	Megiddo exc. 1937. Level X Tomb E=3026 n. b 247	Conical weight, horizontal hole. Scarab sealing on the side. Well shaped.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	1937-868
1	10/K/92/AR 4	Conical	Fired clay	14	6,2,		0,9	1018	K-11			Conical weight, complete. Made of fired clay, very large.	MB II	
1	14/K/23/AR 2	Biconical	Fired clay	3,2	4,3		0,8	57	K-10			Biconical weight, very worn.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	
1	14/K/34/AR 1		Fired clay	1,4	3,2	1,7			K-10			Fragments of a objects, possibly pertaining to a loom weight.	MB III/LB I (Str. X)	

Late Bronze Age

1	06/M/48/AR 6	Conical	Fired clay					210,4 5	M-7?, F?	Blockman/Sass 2013: 887, fig. 23.6.		Conical weight, made of fired clay.	LB I	
1	08/K/65/AR 15	Conical	Fired clay	7,5+x	5,2			139+ x	Level K-10?			Conical weight, horizontally pierced. Broken at half.	LB IIA	
1	M 3641		Fired clay						tomb 1100 A	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 145		No description is provided in the p	LB I	
1	c 108	Conical	Unfired clay						N=T 3169	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Conical weight, horizontal hole. Scarab sealing on the side. Well shaped.	LB I	
1	b 248	Conical	Unfired clay						T 3027	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Conical weight, made of unfired clay. Complete.	LB I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	b 246	Pyramidal	Unfired clay						T 3018 D	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Pyramidal weight, made of unfired clay. Complete.	LB I	
1	a 177	Conical	Unfired clay						N=T 2011	Loud 1948: pl. 170		Conical weight, top missing.	LB I	
1	98/F/107/AR1	Conical	Fired clay	7,3	6,3+x			239+x	F-10A	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 392, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 400-480 g.	Conical weight, well shape, base and top missing. Sealing on the side, not clearly visible.	LB I	
1	98/F/8/AR3	Discoid elliptical	Fired clay					9,85+x	F9	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Discoid elliptical weight, fragmentary.	LB IIA	
1	06/K/4/AR4	Discoid elliptical	limestone					54,2	K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 878, fig. 15.4		Natural pebble, hole near the edge.	LB IIB	
1	00/K/28/AR9		limestone					6,15	K-6, A	Blockman/Sass 2013: 878.			LB III	
1	00/K/112/AR5		limestone					61,6	K-6, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 878.		Natural pebble, hole near the edge.	LB III	
1	08/K/40/AR2		Fired clay	2,2		15,4, s3,1			K-9			Fragment of a pottery object, quite irregular but rounded.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/40/AR1	Conical truncated	Pottery	9,1	4,7		0,24	176	K-9			Conical truncated pottery weight, horizontally pierced. Very worn.	LB IIA	
1	10/H/43/AR4	Conical	stone	5,7	3		0,4	56	Sq. F8, H-12, F		Accumulation on floor.	Small conical weight, complete. Horizontally pierced, flat base.	LB III	
1	12/Q/129/AR2	Doughnut	Fired clay	5		110,1x s4,6		216+x	Q-7?			Doughnut weight, only 1/4 preserved.	LB III	

Iron Age I

1	10/H/92/AR3	Cylindrical	stone	2,2	5,7			38,2+x	Sq. E/F7, H-11, F			Cylindrical weight, broken in half. Made of white stone.	Early IAI	
1	a 143	spool	Unfired clay	7,2	6,5				Locus 2022, Area AA, Quad M8	Loud 1948: pl. 170:26. Paice 2004: 60, 161, pl. 21:2.	Oriental Institute Museum A18299	Spool, slightly waisted on the centre.	Late IAI (Str. VIA)	
1	96/K/73/AR1	Discoid elliptical	Basalt					218+x	Level K-4 (F)	Sass 2000: 370, fig. 12.15:4.	Original weight 262 g.	Discoid elliptical weight, fragmentary.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5660+								Locus E=1751, R8, Area CC.	Paice 2004: 160	Found with another loom weight		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	P 6326+								Locus N=1760, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 160	Two spindle whorls from the same locus		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	P 6392+								Locus 1803, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 160	Two spindle whorls from the same locus		IA I (Str. VI)	
1			Fired clay						Locus 1760	Paice 2004: 160			IA I (Str. VI)	
1			Fired clay						Locus 1757	Paice 2004: 160	From the same locus a spindle whorl and a needle		IA I (Str. VI)	
1			Fired clay						Locus 1754	Paice 2004: 160	From the same locus a spindle whorl and a needle		IA I (Str. VI)	
1			Fired clay						Locus W=1772, S9-10, Area CC	Paice 2004: 160			IA I (Str. VI)	
20	a 364	Cylindrical	Fired clay						Locus 2069, Quad K8, Area AA	Loud 1948: 160. Paice 2004: 161.	Stratum VIA. Oriental Institute Museum A18366	Cylindrical and perforated. It is written that they were pinched in the middle, but they are not spools. More than twenty found grouped.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5541		Fired clay						Locus 1729, Q10, Area CC	Loud 1948: 149. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5657		Fired clay						Locus 1729, Q10, Area CC	Loud 1948: 149. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5658		Fired clay						Locus 1741, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5659		Fired clay						Locus 1733, R9, Area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5660		Fired clay						Locus 1750, R8, Area CC	Loud 1948: 151. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6163		Fired clay						Locus W=1814, S9, Area CC	Loud 1948: 155. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6179		Fired clay						Locus 1825, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 6180		Fired clay						Locus 1820, R9, Area CC	Loud 1948: 155. Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	P 6115+		Fired clay						Locus E=1756, S8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	P 6313+		Fired clay						Locus 1755, R8, Area CC	Paice 2004: 161.			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5150		Fired clay						Locus 1567, Q10, Area B	Paice 2004: 161			IA I (Str. VI)	
1	00/K/13/AR 2	Cylindrical	Basalt	6,3	8,4+x			377,7 5+x	k-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381.		Cylindrical weight made of basalt, fragmentary. Very heavy, probably the original weight exceeded 1000 g.	Late IAI	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/K/32/AR 2	Conical	Fired clay	7,4	5,5+x		0,7x1	167+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 392, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 340- 500 g.	Conical weight, well shaped, fragmentary.	Late IAI	
1	98/K/32/AR 1	Doughnut	Unfired clay	3,7	5+x				k-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393.		Conical weight, well shaped, fragmentary.	Late IAI	
1	98/K/32/AR 15	Doughnut	Unfired clay	6	10,6		1,9	560,8	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.		Doughnut shaped weight made of unfired clay, almost complete. Roughly shaped.	Late IAI	
1	00/L/126/A R2	Doughnut	Fired clay	4,7	12,4		0,9	505+ x	L-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 727 g.	Doughnut shape, made of fired clay. Quite well shaped, small hole.	Late IAI	
1	00/L/126/A R3	Doughnut	Unfired clay	4,8	9,5		0,9	453+ x	L-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 500 g.	Doughnut shaped weight, made on unfired clay. Almost complete. Small hole.	Late IAI	

Iron Age II

1	00/H/37/AR 1		limestone					65,1	H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.19.		Irregular object with a through hole near one edge.	Late IA IIA	
1	98/H/46/AR 1	Doughnut	Fired clay						H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.	Fragmentary, discarded.	Doughnut shaped weight, made of fired clay.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/K/45/AR 4	Cylindrical	Unfired clay						Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:9	Mixed context.	Small cylindrical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/29/AR 1	Spherical	Unfired clay						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:10		Small spherical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary. Diagonal hole.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/K/29/AR 2	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.16:12		Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/K/29/AR 4		Unfired clay						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 374.		Fragmentary.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/H/26/AR 1	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-3	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:1		Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/36/AR 1	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:2		Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 3	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:3	96/H/44	Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	96/H/44/AR 4		Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372.		Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 5	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:4		Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 6	Spherical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:5		Small spherical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 7	Spherical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:6		Small spherical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 8	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:7		Small biconical weight, made of unfired clay. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 9		Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372.		Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 10		Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372.		Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 12		Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372.		Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 13		Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 372.		Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/5/AR1	Biconical	Unfired clay						Level H-1 (A)	Sass 2000: 372, fig. 12.16:8	Mixed context.	Small irregular weight with a biconical shape. Unfired clay.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/47/AR 1	Spherical	Unfired clay						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.16:11	Mixed context.	Small irregular weight with a spherical shape. Unfired clay. Hole not passing through.	IA IIB	
1	98/H/60/AR 1	Spherical	Unfired clay	5,5	8,3		1,8	128+ x	H-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 155 g	Small irregular weight with a spherical shape. Unfired clay. Incomplete.	IA IIB	
1	98/H/60/AR 2	Doughnut	Fired clay						H-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.		Fragmentary. Completely crumbled, impossible to measure.	IA IIB	
1	98/H/16/AR 1	Doughnut	Unfired clay	4,8	8,4		1,8x2	250		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.		Doughnut weight, made of unfired clay. Complete.		
1	08/Q/42/AR 9		Pottery	2,2					Q-4			Ring base of a vessel, like Hazor.	Late IA IIA	
1	08/Q/79/AR 4	Spherical	Fired clay	3,2	3,8		0,6	17,3+ x	Q-2			Fragment of a fired clay weight, probably spherical.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/79/AR 21	Spherical	clay	4,5	7,5		1,8	187	Q-2			Spherical weight, almost complete.	IA IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/Q/115/A R2	Spherical	Fired clay	5,6	6,5			101+ x	Q-3			Spherical weight, half preserved.	IA IIB	
1	08/Q/121/A R1	Spherical	Fired clay	4,2	7,1		1,6	182	Q-4			Spherical weight, almost complete. Fired or poorly fired clay.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/12/AR 2		Stone	5x4,5		2,1	0,8	36,8	Q-2			Weight with hole near the edge. Made of a grey stone.	IA IIB	
1	10/Q/18/AR 1		Stone (pebble)	0,6		13,2, s1,8	0,8	8,4+x	Q-4			Pierced pebble broken in half.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/26/AR 5	Spherical	clay						Q-4			Fragment of a weight, probably spherical, 1/3 preserved. Extremely worn as it was washed.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/66/AR 1	Spherical	stone	5,5	6,7		1,7	228	Q-4?			Spherical weight made of grey stone.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/73/AR 9		Stone (pebble)	2,6	5x6,6		1	128	Q-5			Pierced pebble.	Early IA IIA	
1	10/Q/91/AR 19	Spherical	Fired clay	5,4	9,2		2	345	Q-4			Spherical weight made of fired clay. Well preserved.	Late IA IIA	
1	10/Q/110/A R1	Doughnut	clay	4,1				108	Q-4			Two fragments of a doughnut shape weight, burnt.	Late IA IIA	
1	12/Q/15/AR 1	Spherical	clay		6,6		1,4	136+ x				Spherical weight made of unfired or poorly fired clay, very worn. Half preserved.	Earth debris IAIIA	
1	12/Q/18/AR 2	Spherical	clay (burnt)	3,8	4,6		0,8x1	52+x	Q-2?			Spherical weight, burnt. Fragmentary.	IA IIB	
1	12/Q/87/AR 1	Doughnut	clay	5,1	9,3		1,8x2, 1	429+ x	Q-4			Doughnut shaped weight, broken.	Late IA IIA	
1	12/Q/104/A R1	Spherical	clay	3,7	6,2		1,3	126	Q-5			Spherical weight made of unfired clay, quite well preserved.	Early IA IIA	
1	12/Q/104/A R2	Spherical	clay	5	7,4		0,5	260	Q-5			Spherical weight made of unfired clay, quite well preserved.	Early IA IIA	
1	12/Q/140/A R1	Spool	Fired clay		6,3	1,9,8, s4,6x 2,5		225+ x	Q-2			Cylindrical weight partially preserved. Possible spool.	IA IIB	
1	12/Q/152/A R1	Spherical	Fired clay	3,9		44+x			Q-2			Spherical weight, half preserved.	IA IIB	
1	14/Q/11/AR 1	Spherical	Fired clay	4,7		14,8xs 3,2		67+x	Q-2			Spherical weight, 1/4 preserved.	IA IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	14/T/14/AR 4	Doughnut	Stone	2,3x1, 8	4,8x4, 3		0,8	66	T2?			Weight made of a white stone, roughly doughnut shaped. Very worn but complete.	IA IIB	
1	14/T/26/AR 5		Fired clay	2,8	3,7	1,5			T3			Fragment of weight, possibly spherical. Burnt.	IA IIB	

Unknown context

1	4028	Spherical	Unfired clay			6,7			Tomb 73	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 162		Spherical weight made of unfired clay		
1	4122	Conical	Basalt			3,4			Tomb 80	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 174		Loom weight or mace head made of basalt; half preserved.		
1	94/F/66/AR7 == PT7.	Conical	Pottery					338	topsoil	Sass 2000: p. 372, Fig. 12.15:7.		Conical loom weight, horizontal hole. Broken.		
1	98/K/25/AR 1	Conical	Pottery	10,5	6,5		0,7	372,5 +x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 392, fig. 18.28,	Original weight 465 g.	Conical loom weight, horizontal hole. Broken.		
1	98/H/A6/AR 1	Doughnut	Fired clay					250,6		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.		Doughnut shaped weight made of fired clay.		
1	98/H/55/AR 1	Doughnut	Unfired clay	3,6	6,3		1,2	275+ x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393, fig. 18.28.	Original weight 500 g.	Fragment of doughnut shaped weight, made of unfired or poorly fired clay. Very worn.		
1	00/L/31/AR 1	Doughnut	Unfired clay	5	0,1			88,7+ x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393.		Fragment of weight, doughnut shaped made of unfired clay.		
1	00/L/49/AR 1		Unfired clay	4,1	8,4x7, 2			131+ x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 393.		Fragment of object made of unbaked clay, possibly a loom weight.		
1	06/K/55/AR 7	Conical	Fired clay					309,4		Blockman/Sass 2013: 887, fig. 23.6.				
1	98/M/13/AR 3	Conical	Fired clay					269		Blockman/Sass 2013: 887, fig. 23.6.				
1	04/M/39/AR 6	Doughnut	Fired clay					28,76		Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.6.				

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	06/M/42/AR 1	Biconical	Fired clay					30,45		Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.6.				
1	06/L/61/AR 1	Biconical	Unfired clay							Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.7.				
1	02/M/10/AR 1	Cylindrical	Unfired clay					131,9 +x		Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.7.	Original weight 175 g.	Fragmentary.		
1	10/K/66/AR 5	Conical	Fired clay	8,4	6,4		0,7	358	Mixed debris			Conical weight with horizontal hole, complete. Traces of rubbing near the hole.		
1	K/12/4/AR2	spool	Fired clay		4	2,5	0,5?	49+x	US			Spool transversally pierced. Broken in half.		
1	12/K/6/AR4	Conical	Fired clay	9,7	5,2		0,5x0, 6	207	US			Conical weight made of fired clay. Horizontally pierced. Complete.		
1	12/K/66/AR 7	Conical	Fired clay	9,3	6,1		0,7	415	Mixed debris			Conical weight made of fired clay. Horizontally pierced. Complete.		

BASALT RINGS

Early Bronze Age

1	00/J/136/AR 1	Spherical	Basalt	1,8	2,6			7,2+x	Level J-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 22 g.	Basalt ring, quite small and almost spherical. Well rounded and smooth. Fragmentary.	EB Ib	670016
1	98/J/23/AR1 pt 001	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,8	3,7		1,1	23,15 +x	Level J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381.	Original weight 57 g.	Fragmentary.	EB III	
1	98/J/60/AR3	Discoid	Basalt	1,4	3,4		1	12,95 +x	Level J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 68 g.	Basalt ring, quite large and flattish. Rough surface, hourglass hole. Fragmentary.	EB III	670010
1	04/J/20/AR1	Cylindrical	stone						J-6a, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 880, fig. 23.1.	Original weight 52,39 g.	Fragmentary.	EB III	
1	M 3905	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,2	3,8		1,2	49,9	Stage IV Exc. 1928- 33			Basalt ring, cylindrical shape, complete. Well shaped central hole, still partially hourglass.		

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	93/J/64/151/1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,3	3,7		1	18,5+ x	South of Shrine 4050; unstratified. Meg XIX	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:3.	Original weight 37g.	Basalt ring, broken in half. Well shaped, hole almost cylindrical.		531000
1	96/J/48/AR1?	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,4	3	1,1		7,88+ x	?	?		Basalt ring, quite flattish. 1/3 preserved. Hourglass hole.		530998
1	A16885/M3662	Cylindrical	Basalt						U16, Tomb 1226	Braun 2013: 101-102, pl. 75a		complete	EB I	
1	A16884/M3661	Cylindrical	Basalt						U16, Tomb 1226	Braun 2013: 101-102, pl. 75b			EB I	
1	M2555	Cylindrical	Basalt						Tomb 903 upper	Braun 2013: 101-102, pl. 75d.. Guy/Engberg 1938: 170, pl. 76:5		complete	EB I	
1	M2635	Cylindrical	Basalt						Tomb 903	Braun 2013: 101-102, pl. 75d.		complete	EB I	
		cylindrical	Basalt						B/V/1	Braun 2013: 101-102, pl. 33-34		Cache of basalt rings.	EB I	
1	10/J/92/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,5x2, 7	4,7		1,1	91	J-6bc			Basalt ring, complete. Well rounded and polished. Hourglass hole.	EB III	
1	10/J/152/AR1	Spherical	Basalt	3,2	5,3		1,3	67	J-4			Basalt ring, half preserved. Well polished.	EB I	
1	10/J/70/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,4	4,2		1,4	27,8				Basalt ring, half preserved. Well rounded but not well polished.	EB III	

Middle Bronze Age

1	M3792	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,3	4,5		1,2	60,5	tomb 1102 lower, Exc. 1931/2	Guy/Engberg 1938: 26, pl. 85:12.		Basalt ring, cylindrical, complete. Well shaped, hole slightly hourglass.	MB II	1934-2691
1	10/K/78/AR6	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,4	3,6		1,2	12,4	K-10			Basalt ring, half preserved.	MB III-LB I	

Late Bronze Age

1	M 2708	Cylindrical?	Basalt			2,1			tomb 877	Guy/Engberg 1938: 170 pl. 96		Basalt ring, hole slightly off-centre.	LB II	
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Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/F/22/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,6	3			15,7+ x	Level F-9	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 63 g.	Basalt ring, fragmentary. 1/4 preserved. Well shaped.	LB IIA	
1	08/K/33/AR16	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,3	3,5		1	23,4	Level K-9			Basalt ring, complete. Well shaped, cylindrical hole made starting from both sides.	LB IIA	
1	10/K/61/AR23	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	4,2		0,8	41	K-9			Basalt ring, complete, not perfectly rounded.	LB IIA	
1	12/Q/129/AR2	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	3,2		0,9	27	Q-9			Basalt ring, large hole compared to diameter. Well shaped.	LB IIA	

Iron Age I

1	02/K/47/AR6		Basalt					1486 +x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.	Original weight 3000 g	Pivot for drilling? Half preserved.		
1	00/K/21/AR4		Basalt					407+ x	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.	Original weight 2000 g	Pivot for drilling?	Late IA I	
1	00/K/61/AR6		Basalt					2058	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.		Pivot for drilling?	Late IA I	
1	00/K/61/AR7		Basalt					2525	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.		Pivot for drilling?	Late IA I	
1	00/K/90/AR3	Basalt ring	Basalt	2,1	4,6		1,4	31,15 +x	K-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 58 g.	Basalt ring, fragmentary. Well shaped, hourglass hole with evident signs of manufacture. Two small depressions on side.	Early IA I	670009
1	00/K/51/AR8	Basalt ring	Basalt	1,5x1, 7	4,2x3, 8		1,1	34,75	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Basalt ring, irregular shape, and thickness. Slightly squared. Hourglass hole.	Late IA I	09-261
1	00/K/051/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,1	4		1,2	41,43	K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Basalt ring, well shaped and almost cylindrical hole.	Late IA I	09-259
1	10/H/30/AR8	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,1				15,7+ x	H-11, A			Basalt ring, fragmentary	Early IA I	
1	12/Q/109/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	3,8x3, 6		1,1	30	Q-7			Basalt ring, well shaped but not perfectly rounded.	Late IA I	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
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Iron Age II

1	96/K/2/AR5	Cylindrical	Basalt					1265	Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.18:3	Diameter > 10 cm	Pivot for drilling?	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/41/AR3		limestone						Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.18:5		Fragmentary. Pivot for drilling?	Early IA IIA	
1	M 1179	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,8				locus 380	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94:82	Found with whorl M 1269	Basalt ring, quite flat. Unpolished surface.	IA II (Stra. IV)	
1	M 374	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,7				locus 203	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		very irregular. Broken? Unfinished? Maybe not an actual basalt ring.	IA II (Stra. V)	
1	M 4386	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,5				Locus 1431	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.19		Actual basalt ring, quite flattish.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1423	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,7				Quadrato Q8	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 93.25		Very regular, seem more a cylinder than a basalt ring.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4381	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,6				locus 1001	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.15		Actual basalt ring, rounded surface but seem not polished	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4881	Cylindrical	Basalt						Locus 1445	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 130.		Quite flattish	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4897	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,7				locus 1561	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.37	Found with prf. sherd M 4896.	Very rounded in shape with convex sides and quite high.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4921	Cylindrical	Basalt						locus 1542	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 135.			IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 5033	Cylindrical	Basalt						locus 15686	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 138.	Found with spindle whorl M 4772.		IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4590	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,3				locus 1461	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.38		Actual basalt ring.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	96/K/47/AR2	Cylindrical	Basalt	2x1,8	3,7		1	19+x	Level K-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 374, fig. 12.17:6.	Original weight 38 g.	Basalt ring, broken in half. Well shaped, hourglass hole but well polished.	Early IAIIA	531003
1	M 5130	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,8				locus N 1598	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.39	Found with spatula M 5127	Flattish basalt ring	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 874	Cylindrical	Basalt		2,5				locus 285	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 94.58		Oblique and irregular upper surface, probably not a basalt ring.	IA IIB	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	94/H/5/AR2	Cylindrical	Basalt					570+x	Level H-1 (A)	Sass 2000: 376, fig. 12.18:4	Original weight 2475 g	Pivot for drilling?	IA IIB	
1	M 4121		Basalt						Locus 1270	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 114	Stratum II	Pivot for drilling?	IA IIC	
1	M 4891		Basalt						Locus 1309	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 114	Stratum II	Pivot for drilling?	IA IIC	

Unknown context

1	3756		Basalt			3,4			tomb 63 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 158		Partially broken, hourglass hole apparently small.		
1	98/J/88/AR1		limestone						790,2+x	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.	Original weight 1589 g.	Fragmentary. Pivot for drilling?		
1	00/J/184/AR1		Basalt						123,7+x	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 388, fig. 18.24.	Original weight 250 g.	Unfinished perforation. Fragmentary.		
1	M 5600		Basalt						Locus E=1748, Q9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 151.				
1	M 5804		Basalt						Locus N=1794, S9, Area CC	Paice 2004: 167. Loud 1948: 153.				
1	98/J/3/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,3	4,2		1,1 ca	23,2+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006, 381.	Original weight 48 g.	Basalt ring, fragmentary. Well rounded and polished. Hourglass hole.		
1	00/F/66/AR2	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,1				21,7+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 90 g.	Basalt ring, fragmentary. Well rounded and polished. Hourglass hole.		
1	00/F/68/AR2	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,8	2,8	1,4		13,7+x		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.	Original weight 68,5 g.	Small fragment of basalt ring.		670008
1	00/K/3/AR1	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	3,2		1	26,05		Sass/Cinamon 2006: 381, fig. 18.20.		Basalt ring, complete, quite thick, and well shaped. Hourglass hole but polished.		09-258

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	12/K/14/AR 5	Spherical	Basalt	3,3	4,1		1,2	33,8				Basalt weight, spherical, very well shaped and rounded. Cylindrical hole. Half preserved.		

BONE SPATULAE

Neolithic/Chalcolithic

1	M4870	spatula	Bone						U16 stage V	Braun 2013: 99, pl.74	Uncertain chronology: Neolithic/BA	Bone spatula, complete. Long and thin, quite pointed.		
1	M4873	spatula	Bone						U16 stage VI	Braun 2013: 99, pl.74. Engberg/Shipton 1934: fig. 13M	Uncertain chronology: Neolithic/BA	Bone spatula, one end missing. Triangular point.		
1	M4874	spatula	Bone						U16 stage VII	Braun 2013: 99, pl.74. Engberg/Shipton 1934: fig. 13N	Uncertain chronology: Neolithic/BA	Bone spatula, one end missing. Pen-nib point.		

Early Bronze Age

	c 480	pin beater	Bone		10,8	1	0,5		4067 Exc. 1938			pin beater? Broken at both ends. Extremely polished.	EB I (Str. XIX)	1939-681
	96/J/21/AR3	spatula	Bone						Level J-4 (F)	Sass 2000: 379.		Fragment polished on one side.	EB Ib	
	96/J/35/AR2	spatula	Bone						Level J-4 (A)	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:1.		Rib of sheep/goat, point broken.	EB Ib	
	96/J/48/AR1	spatula	Bone						Level J-6 (A)	Sass 2000: 379.		Fragment of cattle rib, polished on one side	EB III	
	00/J/50/AR3		Bone						Level J-1	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			EB I	
	98/J/21/AR3		Bone						Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.		Fragment	EB Ib	
	00/J/123/AR1		Bone						Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			EB Ib	
	00/J/166/AR3		Bone						Level J-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			EB Ib	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
	98/J/32/AR6	spatula	Bone						Level J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29		Bone spatula, broken at both ends.	EB III	
	98/J/32/AR8	spatula	Bone						Level J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29		Fragmentary bone spatula, one end with long point.	EB III	
	00/J/125/AR4		Bone						Level J-6	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			EB III	
	98/J/20/AR2	spatula	Bone						Level J-7	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29		Small fragment of bone spatula, triangular point, asymmetrical.	EB III	
	c 206	spatula	Bone						4049	Loud 1948: pl. 198:3		Bone spatula, incomplete. Long and narrow with a triangular point.	EB Ib (Str. XVIII)	
	c 53	spatula	Bone						E=3177	Loud 1948: pl. 198:5		Bone spatula, incomplete. Long and very thin point like a pen-nib.	EB III (Str. XVII)	
	c 304	spatula	Bone	7,5	1,4	0,5			E 4049	Loud 1948: pl. 198:4		Bone spatula smoothed and shiny. One end rounded and the other pointed.	EB Ib (Str. XVIII)	1939-678
	d 610	spatula	Bone						N 5193	Loud 1948: pl. 198:6		Bone spatula, incomplete. Convex shape. Triangular point preserved.	EB III (Str. XVI)	
	d 776	spatula	Bone						N 5184	Loud 1948: pl. 198:8		Bone spatula broken at both ends. Quite peculiar shape. Right-hand edge sharpened	EB III (Str. XVI)	
	d 660	spatula	Bone						N 4040	Loud 1948: pl. 198:9		Bone spatula, long and thin, made from a rib. One end missing, the other ending with a well shaped triangular point.	EB III (Str. XV)	

Middle Bronze Age

1	2833	spatula	Bone	17	2	0,2			T 24		Megiddo exc. 1925-27 Tomb 24, n. 1833	Fragment of bone spatula, one preserved end rounded. Broken on two sides. Smoothed where preserved.	MB II	I-3063
1	2833a	spatula	Bone	13,8	1,8	0,2			T 24		Megiddo exc. 1925-27	Fragment of bone spatula, one preserve end with elongated point, well dressed and polished. Long	MB II	I-3063

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											Tomb 24, n. 1833	and this scratches on the surface. Not part of 2833.		
1	04/J/22/AR1 1	spatula	Bone						J-9b	Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.8		Small fragment of bone spatula, with the triangular point preserved, but chipped.	MB I	
1	d 524	pin beater	Bone						T.5180	Loud 1948: pl. 198.13		Pin beater. Complete, chipped on the point.	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 525	pin beater	Bone						T.5180	Loud 1948: pl. 198.12		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 460	pin beater	Bone						T.5121	Loud 1948: pl. 198.15		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 400	pin beater	Bone						T.5121	Loud 1948: pl. 198.14		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 455	pin beater	Bone						T.5125	Loud 1948: pl. 198.16		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 373	pin beater	Bone						T.5125	Loud 1948: pl. 198.17		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 300	pin beater	Bone						E 5095	Loud 1948: pl. 199.21		Pin beater, almost complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB I (Str. XIIIa)	
1	d 719	pin beater	Bone						T.5255	Loud 1948: pl. 199.22		Pin beater, complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB II (Str. XII)	
1	b 342	pin beater	Bone						3049	Loud 1948: pl. 199.23		Pin beater, complete. Cut to form a thin point	MB II (Str. X)	

Late Bronze Age

1	a 295	spatula	Bone						S 2048	Loud 1948: pl. 199.25		Bone spatula, with a rounded end and the other pointed (?).	LB II-III	
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Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	00/F/55/A R1	spatula	Bone						F-10a	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29.		Beautiful bone spatula, almost oval, both ends rounded. Groove (or fracture?) on side.	LB I	
1	00/F/31/A R1		Bone						F-9	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29.		Gazelle horn.	LB IIA	
1	06/M/8/A R15	pin beater	Bone						M-6	Blockman/Sass 2013: 887, fig. 23.5.		Beater with triangular section.	LB III	

Iron Age I

1	M 5512	spatula	Bone						E 1727	Loud 1948: pl. 199		Bone spatula with one rounded and slightly oblique end and the other pointed.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5637	spatula	Bone						E1760	Loud 1948: pl. 199		Bone spatula with a flat end and the other pointed but broken.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	12/Q/117/ AR1	Point	Bone	7	0,9				Q-8			Bone point, broken at one end. Pin beater? Surface marks compatible with manufacture-	Late IA I	

Iron Age II

1	12/Q/99/AR 1	Spatula	Bone	9,4	1,7	0,3			Q-5			Bone spatula, broken at one end, the other has a triangular point. All the surfaces appear smoothed and polished.	Early IA IIA	
1	96/K/I05/AR 8	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F);	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:2		Fragment of cattle rib, longitudinally cut and polished on both sides. One end triangular, the other missing.	Late IAIIA	
1	96/K/46/AR 5	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 379.		Bone spatula, polished on top and on sides.	Late IAIIA	
1	M 5531		Bone						under Room 1734 Area CC	Paice 2004: 81.				

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	98/K/28/AR 2		Bone						K-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			Early IA IIA	
1	98/H/79/AR 2		Bone						H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			Late IAIIA	
1	00/H/22/AR 12		Bone						H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			Late IAIIA	
1	00/H/22/AR 13		Bone						H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.			Late IAIIA	
1	00/H/39/AR 2	spatula	Bone						H-5	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, Fig. 18.29.		Bone spatula, fragmentary. Triangular point.	Late IAIIA	
1	00/L/22/AR 2	spatula	Bone						L-3	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, Fig. 18.29.		Bone spatula, complete. One end pointed, the other flat.	Late IAIIA	
1	M 276	spatula	Bone						Quad Q 13	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib point, the other flat.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5405	spatula	Bone						Locus 1493 (R 10)	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, complete. One end with an elongated point, the other rounded.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5442	spatula	Bone						Locus 1712	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, broken. One end with an elongated point, the other missing.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5293	spatula	Bone						Locus 1666	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, broken. One end with a triangular point, the other missing.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5378	spatula	Bone						Locus 1700	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5281	spatula	Bone						Locus 1660	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, broken. Large, one end with a triangular point the other rounded.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 5353	spatula	Bone						Locus 1660	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96		Bone spatula, broken. One end with a pen-nib point.	Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	96/K/11/AR 3	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:3.		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded. One side completely smoothed, the other partially.	Late IA IIA	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	a 720	spatula	Bone						N 2103	Loud 1948: pl. 199		Bone spatula, complete. One end rounded, the other with a sharp point.	Late IA IIA (Str. Va)	
1	a 4	spatula	Bone						Sq. N 14, 401 (IV)	Loud 1948: pl. 199		Bone spatula, complete. One end flat, the other with a sharp point.	IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	a 823	spatula	Bone						2081	Loud 1948: pl. 199		Bone spatula with a rounded end, the other with a sharp point.	Late IA IIA (Str. Va)	
1	96/K/28/AR 2/1	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:5.		Fragment of a cattle rib, polished on both sides. Broken at both ends.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/K/28/AR 2/2	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F)	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:4.		Bone spatula, broken. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded. Polished on both sides.	Late IA IIA	
1	96/K/28/AR 2/3	spatula	Bone						Level K-2 (F);	Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.20:6.		Fragment of bone spatula, polished on both sides, broken at both ends.	Late IA IIA	
1	00/H/72/AR 5	spatula	Bone						H-7, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.8.		Almost complete bone spatula, partially broken at one end. Well shaped triangular end, the other was probably rounded. Flat.	Early IA IIA	
1	M 1306	pin beater	Bone (gazelle)						Locus 419	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 98:13			Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 1820	pin beater	Bone (gazelle)						Sq. M 7 sup.	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 98:16			Late IA IIA (Str. V)	
1	M 4518	spatula	Bone						Locus 1478	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, one end missing, the other with a triangular point.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 350	spatula	Bone						Sq. Q 12	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, quite large and roughly made. One end with an elongated point but broken and the other diagonally cut.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 1343	spatula	Bone						Locus 338	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Long and thin spatula with a sharp point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5286	spatula	Bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96.1		Long and thin bone spatula with an elongated point and the other end flat.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5232	spatula	Bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96.2		Bone spatula, roughly cut. One end pointed and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5230	spatula	Bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 96.3		Bone spatula, one point diagonally cut, and the other end broken.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5248	spatula	bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 147.		Long and thin bone spatula with an elongated point and the other end flat. Similar to 96.1	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5269	spatula	bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 147.		Long and thin bone spatula with an elongated point and the other end flat. Similar to 96.1	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5354	spatula	bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 147.		Long and thin bone spatula with an elongated point and the other end flat. Similar to 96.1	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	M 5397	spatula	bone						Locus 1674 filling	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 147.		Long and thin bone spatula with an elongated point and the other end flat. Similar to 96.1	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	98/H/38/AR 3		Bone						H-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.	Not illustrated		IA IIB	
1	94/H/13/AR 2		Bone						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 379	Not illustrated	Fragment of a cattle rib.	IA IIB	
1	96/H/44/AR 20		Bone						Level H-3 (F)	Sass 2000: 379	Not illustrated	Small fragment polished on both sides.	IA IIB	
1	M 4426	spatula	Bone						Locus 1437	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, almost complete with triangular point.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4619	spatula	Bone						Locus 1526	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4808	spatula	Bone						Locus 1585	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, almost complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4511	spatula	Bone						Locus W 1432	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, one end rounded and the other missing.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4583	spatula	Bone						Locus 1490	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4609	spatula	Bone						Locus 1534	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Long bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib points and the other flat.	IA IIB (Str. III)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5120	spatula	Bone						Locus 1545	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4655	spatula	Bone						Locus 4655	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4514	spatula	Bone						Locus 1474	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4529	spatula	Bone						Locus 1488	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, almost complete with both ends pointed. One end well shaped, the other irregular or broken.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 871	spatula	Bone						Quad R1	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with an elongated point and the other flat.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4453	spatula	Bone						Locus 1414	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with an elongated point and the other flat.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4480	spatula	Bone						Locus 1414	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 824	spatula	Bone						Locus 272	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point and the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 336	spatula	Bone						Locus 201	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, long and thin, broken. Preserved end with an elongated point.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 1101	spatula	Bone						Locus 317	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 906	spatula	Bone						Locus 297	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 123.	Not illustrated	Bone spatula with triangular point and the other end rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 915	spatula	Bone						Locus 297	Lamon/Shipton 1939: 123.	Not illustrated	Bone spatula with triangular point and the other end rounded.	IA IIB (Str. III)	
1	M 4187	spatula	Bone						Locus 1252	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula with triangular point and the other end rounded.	IA IIC (Str. II)	
1	M 4487	spatula	Bone						Locus 1449	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 95		Bone spatula with triangular point and the other end slightly pointed.	IA IIC (Str. II)	

Q.	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Level	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
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Unknown context

1	x 623		Bone						Tomb 26 E	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 155		Bird bone		
1	1861		Bone						Tomb 59	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 157		Bird bone		
1	98/J/19/A R6		Bone							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29.		Small fragment		
1	00/J/14/A R2		Bone							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.	Not illustrated			
1	00/J/45/A R5		Bone							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395.	Not illustrated			
1	00/K/44/A R7	spatula	Bone							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 395, fig. 18.29.		Bone spatula with an elongated point. Broken.		
1	08/Q/78/A R18	spatula	Bone	6,1	1,7	0,4						Bone spatula broken at both ends, very well polished. One end probably elongated.		
1	10/Q/79/A R6	spatula	Bone	6,4	2,1	0,2						Bone spatula with a rounded end and the other missing. Very thin and fragile. Well polished on both sides.		
1	10/Q/91/A R5	spatula	Bone		ca 2,9							Bone spatula, fragmentary with a pointed end.		
1	10/K/47/A R1	Point	Bone	8,2	1,6	0,5						Not a beater nor a spatula.		
1	10/K/44/A R5	Point	Bone	7,8	1,1	0,5						Not a beater nor a spatula.		
1	10/Q/14/A R1	spatula	Bone	6,7	3	0,15						Bone spatula broken at one end, while the other end is rounded. Very thin and fragile. Well polished on both sides.		

NEEDLES AND BODKINS

Early Bronze Age

5	c 374	bodkin	Bone						Cave 4067	Loud 1948: 140, pl. 165	Above roof debris	Five needle shuttles. Five bone bodkins, fragmentary, large, and flat. Very large and rounded point which could be used as spatula. One preserved part of the eye.	EB I (Str. XX)	39679
1	c 167		Bone						Rm N 4042	Loud 1948: pl. 186.1	BA III - Stratum XVII	Bone needle, complete. Large, triangular head and tapering toward the other end which is pointed.	EB III (Str. XVII)	
1	d 522		Bronze						Quad M 12, corner SW	Loud 1948: pl. 186.2	BA III - Stratum XVI	Bronze needle, with eye missing. Thickening in the middle and one end slightly bent.	EB III (Str. XVI)	

Middle Bronze Age

1	M3228		Bone						Tomb 1014 B	Guy/Engberg 1938: 47, pl. 102	Found between bones together with two toggle pins	Bone needle, broken in several fragments. One of the ends is flat and has a round hole passing through it.	MB I	
1	d 720		Bronze						Quad N 13, corner NW	Loud 1948: pl. 186.3	BM I - Stratum XIV	Bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	MB I (Str. XIV)	
1	d 792		Bronze						5265	Loud 1948: pl. 186.4	BM II - Stratum X	Bronze needle, not complete, point missing. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	MB II (Str. X)	
1	d 683		Bronze						T.5240	Loud 1948: pl. 186.5	BM II - Stratum X	Bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	MB II (Str. X)	
1	d 127		Bronze						E 5033	Loud 1948: pl. 186.6	BM II - Stratum X	Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	MB II (Str. X)	

	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	b 297		Bronze						E 3036	Loud 1948: pl. 186.7		BM II - Stratum X Long and thin bronze shaft, no eye is visible. Bent on the upper part	MB II (Str. X)	
1	b 343		Bronze						3049	Loud 1948: pl. 186		BM II - Stratum X Toggle pin? Long and thin needle, bent, but eye not properly at the top.	MB II (Str. X)	
1	98/J/124/ar7		Bone	5,9	0,8x0,5	0,3	0,3		MB pit	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26.		Bone needle broken at one end. Hole realized by drilling from both sides.	MB	

Late Bronze Age

1	M3516		Bronze						Tomb 1100 A	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 145.6		Short and thick bronze needle. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	LB I	
1	M3484		Bronze						Tomb 1100 C	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 148.4		Bronze needle, complete. Eye (not visible from publication) obtained by bending on itself the ending part of the shaft. Shaft bent in the middle.	LB I	
1	b 224		Bronze						T.3018 D	Loud 1948: pl. 186.9		Small bronze needle with large eye obtained by bending on itself the ending part of the shaft. Complete.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	a 103		Bronze						N=T.201 7	Loud 1948: pl. 186.10		Toggle pin? Long and very thin needle, but eye not properly at the top.	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	d 641		Bronze						N 5110	Loud 1948: pl. 186.11		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	LB I (Str. IX)	
1	a 52		Bronze						N 2048	Loud 1948: pl. 187.12		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	EB II (Str. VIII)	
1	b 348		Bronze						3187	Loud 1948: pl. 187.13		Extremely long bronze shaft (eye not visible from image), bent in the middle.	LB IIB (Str. VIIB)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 6121	Bronze						N 1833	Loud 1948: pl. 187.14		Thick bronze shaft with flat end where eye should be.	LB IIB (Str. VIIB)	
1	a 1120	Bronze						2039	Loud 1948: pl. 187.15		Long and thick bronze needle, almost complete, point missing. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	LB IIB (Str. VIIB)	
1	M 5828	Bronze						N 1805	Loud 1948: pl. 187.16		Bronze needle with large eye obtained by bending on itself the ending part of the shaft. Broken.	LB III (Str. VIIA)	
1	98/F/72/A R4	Bronze						F-10	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26.		Very small and thin bronze needle	LB I	
1	98/M/12/A R2	Bronze						M-6	Blockman/Sass 2013: 885, fig. 23.5.2.		Small fragment of a bronze needle probably with large eye obtained by bending on itself the ending part of the shaft. Broken.	LB III	
1	06/K/4/AR 11	Bronze						K-8, F	Blockman/Sass 2013: 885, fig. 23.5.4.		Bronze needle, complete. with large eye obtained by bending on itself the ending part of the shaft.	LB IIB	

Iron Age I

1	b 304	Bronze	12,7	0,4				Locus 3041, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 187.17. Paice 2004: 90, pl. 29:4		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	Early IA I (Str. VIB)	
1	M 5632	Bronze	20	0,5				Locus 1761, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 187. Paice 2004: 91, pl. 29:2.		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5465	Bronze	22	0,4				Locus 1741, Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 187. Paice 2004: 90, pl. 29:1.		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA I (Str. VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5530	Bronze	15,5	0,4				Quad R 9, 1734 (V), Area CC	Loud 1948: pl. 187. Paice 2004: 90, pl. 29:3.		Long and thick bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA I (Str. VI)	
3	a 366	Bronze						2070	Loud 1948: pl. 187. Paice 2004: 81, 90, pl. 29:17.		Group of needles (3) inside of a bone needle case (7.9x1.5 cm). Needles are long 9, 10, 11 cm and 0,1 cm thick.	Late IA I (Str. VIA)	
3	a 400	Bronze						Locus 2071, Area AA	Loud 1948: pl. 187. Paice 2004: 81, 90, pl. 29:18.		Three needles very thin without a case. Length of 7,5, 8, 8,5 cm and diam of 0,1 cm.	Late IA I (Str. VIA)	
1	M 5738	Bone						Locus N=1732 area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 81	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5749	Bone						Locus 1740 Area CC	Paice 2004: 81	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5667	Ivory						Locus 1769, Area CC	Loud 1948: 152. Paice 2004: 81, 162.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	a 459	Bronze						Locus 2078, Area BB	Loud 1948: 161. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	a 935	Bronze						Locus 2101, Area AA	Loud 1948: 163. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5529	Bronze						Locus 1735, Area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5536	Bronze						Locus 1738, Area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5543	Bronze						Locus 1743, Area CC	Loud 1948: 151. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5591	Bronze						Locus 1738, Area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 5617	Bronze						Locus 1757, Area CC	Loud 1948: 152. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5669	Bronze						Locus 1769, Area CC	Loud 1948: 152. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5697	Bronze						Locus 1741, Area CC	Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5699	Bronze						Locus 1754, Area CC	Loud 1948: 152. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5736	Bronze						Locus 1732, Area CC	Loud 1948: 149. Paice 2004: 91.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5737	Iron						Locus 1732, Area CC	Loud 1948: 149. Paice 2004: 91, 162	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	M 5735	Ivory						Locus N=1732 area CC	Loud 1948: 150. Paice 2004: 81, 162.	Not drawn		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	98/K/41/AR 18	Bronze						K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26	Occupational debris. Found with four other whorls.	Small fragment of bronze needle. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	Late IA I	
1	98/K/42/AR 3	Bronze						K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26		Bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	Late IA I	
1	98/K/42/AR 4	Bronze						K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26		Bronze needle, upper part bent. Eye not visible.	Late IA I	
1	98/K/89/AR 1	Bronze						K-4	Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26		Small bronze shaft, probably needle.	Late IA I	
1	08/H/6/AR2	needle	Bronze					H-9	Blockman/Sass 2013: 885, fig. 23.5.		Bronze needle, complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	Late IA I	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	08/H/24/AR 4	needle	Bronze					H-9	Blockman/Sass 2013: 885, fig. 23.5.		Small fragment of a bronze needle. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	Late IA I	
1	00/M/38/AR 1	bodkin	bone					M-4	Blockman/Sass 2013: 888, fig. 23.8.		Bone bodkin, with point missing. Rounded section, quite thick head with a eye. Worked antler of Mesopotamian fallow deer. Considered as a beater.	Late IA I	

Iron Age II

1	a 329		Bone					Quad M 13, 404	Loud 1948: pl. 187		Round section, flattened toward head, which is very large.	IA II (Str. V?)	
1	M 5229		Bronze					Locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Quite long and thick bronze needle. Eye probably perforated through the shaft.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5234		Bronze					Locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Quite small and thin bronze needle. Eye not visible. Bent	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5315		Bronze					Locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Short and thick bronze needle. Point seems to split in two. Not visible how eye was obtained	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5236		Bronze					Locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Very thick bronze needle (?) or loop-headed pin. Complete.	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 5214		Bronze					Locus 1674	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Very long bronze needle. Complete. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA II (Str. IV)	
1	M 222		Bronze					Locus 67	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Very thin bronze needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 114		Bronze					Locus 592	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Very thin bronze needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA II (Str. V)	
1	M 4464		Bronze					Locus 728	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Long bronze needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	IA IIC	
1	M 3323		Bronze					Locus 1004	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Very thick bronze needle , point missing. Eye obtained probably by	IA IIC	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	Weight	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											bending on itself the upper part of the shaft		
1	M 4348	Bronze						Locus 1421	Lamon/Shipton 1939: pl. 84.		Long and thin bronze needle, eye obtained perforating the shaft.	IA IIB	

Unknown context

1	x624	Bronze						Tomb 26 E	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 155				
1	M 707	Bronze						Tomb 19	Guy/Engberg 1938: pl. 175		Complete.		
1	96/K/54/A R8	Iron							Sass 2000: 379, fig. 12.21: 1.		Fragmentary		
1	00/F/74/A R1	Bronze	12,4	0,3	head	0,5			Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26.		Eye not visible		
1	98/K/47/A R7	Bronze							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389.		Eye missing		
1	00/K/37/A R1	Bronze							Sass/Cinamon 2006: 389, fig. 18.26.		Not a needle		
1	98/M/12/A R2	Bronze							Blockman/Sass 2013: 885, fig. 23.5.				
1	04/K/51/A R4	Bronze							Blockman/Sass 2013: 885.		Fragment with eye.		

HAZOR

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Area Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

SPINDLES

Late Bronze Age

1	A 52071		Bone	5,8	0,7 x0,5			2,2 4	A4	L. 8286 MU			Fragment of bone shaft, broken at one end, slightly thickening toward the other but ending with a point.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	H 53		Bronze	18					H	2115	Yadin 1989, CCLXXXI II:33.		Decorated bronze shaft, probably a kohl stick, similar to those of Persian period found at Hazor, area A.	LB II (Str. 1A)	

Iron Age II

1	A 60880		Bone	7,3	0,5			3	A 5	L. 9142 M			Bone shaft, well polished. Both ends missing.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 54586		Bone	11,2	0,5-0,4			4	A4	L. 8575			Bone shaft, well polished with spiral marks on point.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 27973		Bone	nn	0,7 x0,6 min 0,4			5	A2	L. 4023 M			Bone shaft, well polished, tends to taper toward one end. Both ends broken.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIIa)	
1	A 54504		Bone	9,9	0,9			9	A4	L. 8558			Bone shaft, well polished. One end flat, the other missing. probably part of a pendent.	IA IIC (Str. IVb)	
1	A 21609		Bone	7,8	0,7-0,8			4	A2	L. 3217 M			Bone shaft, well polished, point preserved, roughly shaped. Traces of polishing manufacture on the whole surface.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 60466		Bone	4,6	0,6			1,3 5	A 5	L. 9077			Bone shaft, well polished with long and thin point. Broken in the nearby of the hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 23013		Bone	2,5	0,6 x0,7			1,4 4	A2	L. 3432 M			Small fragment of bone shaft.	IA IIC (Str. VI-V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 72788	Bone	8,1	0,7			5	M	L. 07-334			Fragment of bone shaft, cylindrical shape, and flat hole, the other end missing.	IA IIC	
1	M 72378	Bone	8,2	0,8			5,5 2	M	L. 07-329 M			Fragment of bone shaft, cylindrical with rounded point, the other end missing. Possible spindle.	IA IIC	
1	M 93332	Bone	4,6	0,7			3,2 3	M3	L. 14-520 M			Fragment of bone shaft with a flat end and traces of manufacture on the surface. Not perfectly rounded.	IA II C	
1	B 572/1	bone	13					B	3116	Yadin 1960, pl. CV:27, CLXVI:9.		Bone rod, thickening toward the middle. Both ends are rounded.	IA II C (Str. IV)	
1	B 4190/1	bone						B	3180	Yadin 1989, CCXIX:35		Bone rod, cylindrical with a rounded end and the other missing.	IA II C (Str. VI)	

Unknown context

1	A 1237	Bone	9,5	0,7			4,7 9+x	A				Thin bone shaft, broken at both ends. Well polished on the whole rod.		
1	A 12895	Bone	8,9	1,1			10	A1	L. 1344	Hazor VI Bechar: 499, fig. 8.1	Fill of uncertain date	Hollow bone, accurately polished. One end flat and the other missing. Incised ring near the end. Made of metatarsus of gazelle		
1	A 61843	Bone	19	0,8- 0,9			14	A5	L. 9278 M			Bone shaft, polished surface, one end missing and the other with a rounded point.		
1	M 34722	Bone	2	1			2,6 2	M	L. 5579 tomb			Small fragment of bone shaft broken at both ends.		
1	M 34751	Bone	7,3 ca	0,9				M	L. 5585			Two fragments of bone shafts, not matching but probably part of the same object. One has a well carved point.		
1	M 34988	Bone	3,7	0,7			1,4 6	M	L. 5603 T			Fragment of bone shaft with a rounded point.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 73115	Bone	6,5	min 0,5 max 0,8			3,3 5	M	L. 08-316 M			Fragment of bone shaft, tapering toward one end, slightly chipped. Oval section. Diagonal marks on the surface, probably due to manufacture process.		
1	A 3272/1	Bone	9	0,7			6,0 1+x	H				Fragment of bone shaft with a flat end and the other broken. Not perfectly cylindrical, even if polished.		
1	A 2312/2	Bone	4,1	0,9			4,0 6+x	A	57n			Fragment of bone shaft, broken at both ends.		
1	A 3022/1	Bone	7,2	0,7			4,7 8+x	A	57n			Part of bone shaft, one end flat and the other broken. Not perfectly cylindrical even if polished. Slightly faded area near the end.		

SPINDLE WHORLS

Middle Bronze Age

1	D 7007	dome	bone					D	9023	Yadin 1958: CII:27, CLX.12.		Dome bone spindle whorl, chipped on the side.	MB II (Str. 2)	
1	210/A1- 71/1	dome	bone					210 /A1	2005	Yadin 1989: CCXCIX:5		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete.	MB II (Str. 3)	
1	210/A1- 25/1	dome	bone		2,1			210 /A1	2012	Yadin 1989: CCXCIX:6, CCCXXXVI :13.		Dome bone spindle whorl, complete.	MB II (Str. 4)	
1	C 656b/1	discoïd	bone					C	6203	Yadin 1960: CXXVI:19.	Button ?	Extremely flat and hole seems very small from the drawing	MB II (Str. 3)	
1	C 656b/2	conical truncated	bone					C	6203	Yadin 1960: CXXVI:20, CLXXIX:21	Button ?	Extremely flat and hole seems very small from the drawing	MB II (Str. 3)	
1	C 468/1	dome	bone					C	6203	Yadin 1960: pl.		Dome bone spindle whorl.	MB II (Str. 3)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
										CXXVI:21, CLXXIX:19				
1	C 710/5	dome	bone					C	6203	Yadin 1960: CXXVI:22, CLXXIX:20		Dome bone spindle whorl.	MB II (Str. 3)	

Late Bronze Age

1	F 1302/1	button	clay					F	L 4-5	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXLIV:9.		Button made of clay, complete.	MB II- LB I	
1	49290	dome	bone						07-026	Ben Tor 2017: 559.	no fig.	Dome, bone spindle whorl.	LB (Str. XVIII)	
1	E 1143	conical	bone					E	7021	Yadin 1958: pl. CXLII:19, fig. CLXVI:15.	55n /E H43?	Conical bone spindle whorl.	LB I	
1	16873	dome	bone						1719, building 7050, fill	Ben Tor 2017: 554, fig. 12,15		Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl	LB IB- IIA (Str. XIV)	
1	17876	dome	bone (?)						1719, building 7050, fill	Ben Tor 2017: 554, fig. 12,15		Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl	LB IB- IIA (Str. XIV)	
1	17140		bone						1774	Ben Tor 2017: 558.	no fig.		LB IIA- B (Stra. XIII)	
1	47629								7780	Ben Tor 2017: 558.	no fig.		LB II (Str. XIV- XIII)	
1	49022								07-003	Ben Tor 2017: 558.	no fig.		LB II (Str. XIV- XIII)	
1	M 70416 a	dome	Ivory	0,8	2,5		0,4	5,0 3	M2	L. 6537 fill	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Bone spindle whorl, dome shaped with worn surface. Lathe rounded marks on the dome, parallel marks of polishing on the base.	LBA	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	M 70416 b	dome	bone	0,6	2,5		0,3	3,4 5	M2	L. 6537 fill		Bone spindle whorl, dome shaped with highly polished surface. Lathe rounded marks on the dome, parallel marks of polishing on the base. Small chips near the upper hole. Hole slightly conical, larger on the base (0,4).	LBA		
1	A 40979	dome	stone	1,2	2,6		0,5	10, 64	A3	L. 7050F		floor	Dome stone (serpentinite?) spindle whorl, heavily encrusted. Due concentric rings on the dome, base slightly hollow.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 12946	dome	stone	1,2	2,5		2,5	9,6 3	A1	L. 1372 F		floor	Small spindle whorl, dome shaped, made of stone (serpentinite?). Hole slightly conical, larger near the base. Small chippings near the upper hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 13723	button	bone	0,5	2,1		0,2 5	1,2 4	A1	L. 1462 F		mudbrick collapse	Small bone button, base quite worn.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	M 34618	dome	bone	0,7	2,2		0,3	3,0 7	M	L. 5571			Dome bone spindle whorl, surface abraded and worn, possibly an attempt of polishing. Polishing manufacture visible on the base. Hole slightly conical, larger near the base.	LBA destruction	
1	A 90894	conical truncated	stone	2,1	3,5		0,6	37, 42	A3	L. 9583 F			Conical truncated spindle whorl, made of stone (steatite?). Upper part very worn. Cylindrical hole.	LB II?	
1	A 45809	dome	stone	0,8	2,2		nn	1,7 3+x	A3	L. 7540 M		mudbrick collapse	Dome spindle whorl made of stone (serpentinite?), broken in half. Circular lathe marks on the dome, polishing marks on the base.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 47086	dome	bone	1	2,8		nn	3,1 5+x	A3	L. 7730 M		fill	Bone spindle whorl, more than half broken. Dome shaped.	LB II (Str. XIV- XIII)	
1	A 18641	dome	bone	2,3	4,4		0,6	18, 03	A1	W. 4013 W			Dome bone spindle whorl, quite tall. Hole very ruined on both sides.	LB II (Str. XIII)?	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 48016	button	stone	0,9	3,7		0,3	9,5 8+x	A3	L 7852 U		floor	Stone button (serpentinite) very large with small hole, slightly conical, larger at the base. Traces of polishing on the base.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 26961	spherical	pottery	2,7	2,4		nn	7,3 3+x	A2	L. 3877 M		fill	Spherical pottery spindle whorl, roughly shaped and not polished.	LB II (Str. XIV-XIII)	
1	A 55787	biconical	pottery	2,2	3,2		0,9	16, 14	A4	L. 8788 F		floor	Biconical spindle whorl made of pottery, small and roughly shaped. Ruined near both sides of hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 49415	dome	bone	1	2,9		0,3 5	9,8 2	A6	L. 12-903		floor	Dome bone spindle whorl, almost complete. Very worn on the surface. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,45).	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 92392	cylindrical	stone	2,1	3,7		nn	18, 07+x	A4	L. 80036 M		Fill	Fragment of perforated object made of stone. Very irregular but well shaped cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 42306	conical truncated	stone	1,3	2,6		0,5	13, 65	A	L. 7223 B		floor	Conical spindle whorl, made of stone (steatite?), well polished. Hole slightly larger at base (0,6). Upper part worn and chipped, inferior side of hole neatly cut. Small chippings on the side.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
	B 4994	dome	bone						B	3284	Yadin 1989: CC:29	Found with shaft/needle B 5011	Dome, bone spindle whorl with concentric incisions on the dome and on the flat base.	LB II	
	C 5118	Lenticular	bone						C	6063	Yadin 1958: LXXXVI: 21		Lenticular bone spindle whorl	LB II (Str. 1b)	
	D 11684	dome	bone						D	9044	Yadin 1958: XCV:19		Dome bone spindle whorl, quite high.	LB II (Str. 2)	
	D 2852	dome	bone						D	9017	Yadin 1958: CX: 13, CLX:9.		Dome, bone spindle whorl, decorated on the base by a circular incision.	LB II	
	C 1880	dome	bone						C	6117	Yadin 1958: LXXXIX:17, CLX:22.		Dome bone spindle whorl.	LB II	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
K 222/1	dome	limestone		3,2				K	5005	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:5, CCCXXXV:1 4		Dome limestone spindle whorl.	LB II (Str. 1a)		
C 443/1	dome	bone						C	6197	Yadin 1960: pl. CXXXVI:28, CLXXIX		Dome bone spindle whorl.	LB I (Str. 2)		
C 1101/3	dome	black stone						C	6215	Yadin 1960: CXXVII:27, CLXXIX:8		Dome spindle whorl, made of black stone.	LB II (Str. 1b)		
C 760	dome	stone						C	6214	Yadin 1960: pl. CXXXVII:34		Dome stone spindle whorl.	LB II (Str. 1 a- b)		
F 1076/11 5	dome	bone						F	8144	Yadin 1960: CXXXVII:26		Dome bone spindle whorl. Very small	LB II (Str. 1b)		
F 1076/15 4	dome	bone						F	8144	Yadin 1960: CXXXVII:27		Dome bone spindle whorl.	LB II (Str. 1b)		
F 1076/16 5	dome	bone						F	8144	Yadin 1960: CXXXVII:28		Dome bone spindle whorl, quite high.	LB II (Str. 1b)		
1	L 632	dome	bone	1,5	3,8		0,6	8,9 1+x	L	1099		YADI N, floor	Dome bone spindle whorl, worn and partially broken. On the base, cancellous bone exposed.	LB II (Str. XIV- XIII)	

Iron Age I

1	A 45746	dome	stone	0,6	2,1		0,2 5	1,6 4+x	A3	L. 7530 W		fill	Dome spindle whorl, made of grey stone, light and polished. Possibly a bead.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	
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Iron Age II

1	A 50957	conical truncated	stone	2	3,5		0,7	26,82	A4	L. 8070 MU		floor	Conical truncated spindle whorl, made of stone. Very worn, especially near the upper side of the hole.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 59149	conical	stone	1,1	2,9		0,5	12,24	A4	W. 5353 W	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Wall	Conical spindle whorl, made of stone (serpentinite?). On the base traces of polishing.	IA IIA (Str. IXb)	
1	A 50521	conical	chalk	2,6	5,7		0,8	81,04	A4	L. 8052 MU?	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 200-202, Make Up	Conical spindle whorl made of stone.	IA IIA (Str. Xa)	
1	A 54729	conical	pottery	2,7	5,4		0,7	76,05	A4	L. 8595 F	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 8158	Conical pottery spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly conical.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)	
1	A 50700	conical	Steatite	1,3	1,9		0,5	5,27	A4	L. 8029 fill	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.		Conical spindle whorl made of steatite. Small and slightly tilted but working as a whorl. Wheel traces on the surface.	IA IIA (Str. Xa)	
1	A 57970	cylindrical	pottery	2,2	4,4		0,75	55	A4	L. 9080 F		fill	Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of pottery and well shaped, hole slightly warped.	IA IIA (Str. IX)	
1	M 76167	dome	bone	0,9	2,4		0,3	4,48	M	L. 10-378 M		Standing stones complex	Dome bone spindle whorl, small chipping on the side. Wheel marks visible on the dome, traces of polishing on the base. Quite worn surface.	IA II A	
1	B 2751/1	conical	stone						B	3220	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXIII:23.		Conical stone spindle whorl. Concentric incisions on the dome and on the flat base.	IA IIA (Str. X)	
1	A 3364/2	conical truncated	bone							203d	Yadin 1989: CLXXIII:10, CCCLIX:17		Conical truncated bone spindle whorl. Small holes on the surface as decoration	IA IIA (Str. Xb)	
1	B 4180	conical	hematite						B	3251	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXVI:22.		Conical spindle whorl made of hematite.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII-VIII)	
1	A 3049/6	dome	hematite							193a	Yadin 1989: CLXXX:26.		Dome spindle whorl, made of hematite.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	
1	L 463	dome	limestone						L	L. 1072	Hazor V: 252, 253, fig. III.33: 25.		Dome spindle whorl, made of limestone.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 12507	discoid	pottery	1,6	5,3x5,6		0,5	54,09	A1	L. 1250 M		fill	Discoid spindle whorl made of pottery, specially made. Broken in two pieces. Roughly shaped but cylindrical hole.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	M 75485	biconical	pottery	3,1	3,5		0,3	33,45	M	L. 10-320 M		Biconical spindle whorl, made of pottery, complete. Very small hole.	IA IIA-B		
1	A 47668	dome	pottery	2,1	5,6		1	53,77	A3	L.7789		Pottery spindle whorl, slightly domed, very worn. Cylindrical hole.	IA II A-B (Str.VIII)		
1	L 3309	biconical	pottery	3,7	4,5		0,6	67,35	L	L. 1073	Four room houses (Hazor V)	Biconical spindle whorl, made of pottery, complete. Small hole.	IA IIA-B		
1	A 63402	conical	stone	1,4	3,4		0,4	16,45	A5	L. 50086 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Fill of moat	Conical stone spindle whorl with traces of small chippings on the upper edge.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 13057	dome	stone	1,3	4,2		0,3	20,32	A 1	L. 1395 F	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 1395	Large spindle whorl, dome shaped made of stone (hematite?). Well polished. Chipped and ruined in several points of the surface.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)	
1	A 19069	conical truncated	stone	2	3,7		0,6	33,26	A1	L. 1911 M		fill	Conical truncated spindle whorl, made of stone (steatite?), complete. Wheel traces on the whole surface. Upper side of hole very ruined. Lower side slightly irregular and flaring (0,7).	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 18643	conical	stone	1	2,6		0,4	5,97	A1	L. 1851 F		floor	Conical stone spindle whorl (steatite?), complete. Wheel traces on the whole surface. Upper side of hole very worn. Base covered by incisions, probably intended as decorative.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIIb)	
1	A 13214	conical truncated	pottery	2,2	4		0,7	34,85	A1	L. 1421 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 1373	Conical truncated spindle whorl made of pottery, quite well shaped. Upper side of hole covered by chippings; lower sides neatly cut but slightly larger (0,9).	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIIb)	
1	A 11225	conical	Alabaster	2,5	3,7		0,5	35,45	A1	L. 1111	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Fill	Conical spindle whorl made of white stone, extremely polished. No traces of manufacture are detectable, several chippings on the upper side.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 11937	conical	stone	2,3	2,7		0,5	16,41	A1	L. 1231		floor	Conical spindle whorl, made of grey stone. Cylindrical hole with chippings on the upper side. Slightly larger on the lower side (0,6).	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 12723	conical	stone	2,2	3,8		0,4	29,57	A1	L. 1311 F		floor	Conical spindle whorl made of white-brownish stone. Chippings on the upper and lower side of the hole, and on the edge. Deep traces of polishing on the base.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 57598	conical	stone	2,1	3,7		0,7	33,1	A4	L. 9031 M		floor	Conical spindle whorl, made of white stone. Deep chippings on upper edge and sides, some near the lower side of the hole.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIIa)	
1	A 1268/1		bone						A	149	Yadin 1960: LXXVIII: 28.		Completely warp	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)	
1	A 62844	discoid	pottery	1,8	6,4			35,09	A5	L. 9435 M			Discoid pottery spindle whorl, broken in half. Hole quite irregular.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 30800	button	stone	1	3,2		0,5	8,4	M	L. 5089			Button spindle whorl made of stone (serpentine?), chipped on the edge and near the upper hole. Quite large for being a button.	IA IIC	
1	A 5184	dome	stone	3,8	2,3		0,7	30,36	A1	L. 2046 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	fill	Dome stone spindle whorl, very well shaped, wheel traces on the dome. Worn and chipped on the upper side of the hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 63264	dome	bone	2,3	3,7		0,6	12,41 +x	A5	L. 50059 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 9367	Dome bone spindle whorl, quite high. Very worn.	IA IIC (Str. Vc)	
1	A 54441	conical	stone	1	2,7		0,3	8,75	A4	L. 85549 F	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 8551	Conical spindle whorl made of stone (serpentine?). On the bases traces of polishing.	IA IIC (Str. VIa)	
1	A 63263	discoid	stone	1,3	5,8		1	65,7	A1	L. 50059 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2.	Building 9367	Discoid spindle whorl made of white stone. Roughly shaped but with notches on the edge. Hole quite well rounded.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 11226	dome	stone	0,5	2,2		0,3	3,56 +x	A1	L. 1150		fill	Small spindle whorl made of stone (serpentine), chipped in several points.	IA II (Str. VII-VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 54442	dome	pottery	2,4	3,9		0,6	35,02	A4	L. 8549 F		floor	Dome pottery spindle whorl, slightly chipped near the edges, at the base and on the upper hole.	IA IIC (Str. Via)	
1	A 54502	dome	bone	1,7	3,8		0,6	15	A4	L. 8559 F		floor	Dome bone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. VIb)	
1	A 13271	cylindrical	bone	1,6	3,2		0,6	14,04	A1	L. 1425 M		floor	Cylindrical bone spindle whorl, encrusted.	IA IIC (Str. VIa)	
1	A 57231	dome	stone	1,6	2,5		0,6	12,63	A4	L. 8963 M		floor	Dome spindle whorl, made of grey stone. Quite flattened and worn near the upper hole, but no wear traces are detectable.	IA IIC (Str. VIb)	
1	A 62490 M	dome	stone	1,8	3,8		0,8	32,14	A4	L. 9385 M			Dome spindle whorl made of green stone, wheel traces on the whole surface, both sides of hole damaged.	IA IIC (Str. V)?	
1	A 61604	conical	stone	2,1	4,2		nn	23,3+ x	A5	L. 9224 M			Conical spindle whorl made of a grey, chalky stone. Half missing.	IA?	
1	A 46290	conical	stone	1,3	3,6			8,52+ x	A3	L. 7580 pit		pit	Fragment of conical spindle whorl made of white stone.	IA IIC (Str. IV)	
1	A 62449	dome	stone	2,2	3,4		0,6	15,22 +x	A5	L. 9374 M		fill	Dome spindle whorl made of a grey-yellowish stone. Well polished. Damaged at the base. Half preserved.	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	
1	A 62625	dome	stone	2	3,3		1,1	23,38	A5	L. 9399 F		floor	Dome spindle whorl made of stone (steatite?), with well dressed cylindrical hole. Wear traces on the upper side of the hole, almost nothing near the lower side of the hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 61977	dome	stone	3	4,6		0,7	60,66	A5	L. 9266 M		floor	Dome spindle whorl made of stone (steatite?), quite high. Wheel marks on the dome and on the base. Cylindrical hole. Encrusted.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 92956	dome	stone	1,6	2,5		0,6	13,78	M-west	L. 13-522 M			Dome spindle whorl made of a light stone. Well shaped with a cylindrical hole. Upper side of the hole slightly worn, lower side neatly cut.	IA II C	
1	M 78759	conical truncated	pottery	1,4	2,7		0,6	8,8	M4	L. 14-346 M			Discoïd pottery spindle whorl, burnt, very ruined and irregular.	IA IIC	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 78947	discoid	stone	1,3	4,3		0,9	15,87 +x	M3	L. 15-301 M		Spindle whorl made of stone, fragmentary. Well shaped with cylindrical hole.	IA IIC	
1	A 3599	dome	limestone	0,8	3,6		0,5	14,61	A	48	Yadin 1958, pl. LXV:19.	Dome limestone spindle whorl, quite flattish. Not perfectly rounded, but cylindrical hole, neatly cut, smoothed surfaces.	IA II C (Str. VI)	
1	A 4025/1	dome	limestone							233	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:13	Dome limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 2302/1	dome	bone							85a	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:14 ; CCCLXI:8.	Dome bone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 2478/1	dome	limestone	2	4,1		0,8	35,86	A	188	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:15	Large spindle whorl, dome shaped and made of limestone. Not perfectly symmetrical. Slightly off-centre hole but cylindrical. Base slightly convex with clear signs of polishing. Wear traces near the upper side of hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	B 4051	conical	hematite						B	3177	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXXIV:25.	Conical hematite spindle whorl	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	
1	G 740	conical	stone						G	10037c	Yadin 1989: CCL:26	Conical stone spindle whorl	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	G 567/1	dome	stone						G	10037c	Yadin 1989: CCL:27	Dome limestone spindle whorl. Concentric incisions on the dome and on the flat base.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	G 551/1	dome	limestone						G	10035b	Yadin 1989: CCLIII:12, CCCLXI:9,11.	Dome limestone spindle whorl. Concentric incisions on the dome and on the flat base.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	G 550/1	conical truncated	limestone						G	10039b	Yadin 1989: CCLIII:13, CCCLXI:10.	Conical truncated limestone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	B 908/1	dome	stone						B	3067a	Yadin 1960: pl. CV:26. From locus 3067a a batch of loom weights has been recovere	Dome stone spindle whorl. Concentric incision on the base	IA IIC (Str. Va)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											d but not described			
1	B 1107/1	dome	bone					B	3132a	Yadin 1960: CV:32, CLXVI:12.		Dome bone spindle whorl.	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	B19355	dome	bone					B	3512	Yadin 1958: 45, pl. LXXIV:34		Dome bone spindle whorl. Quite flattish.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	B 7582	dome	stone					B	South Wall	Yadin 1958: pl. LXXV:12, CLIV:5		Dome stone spindle whorl. Concentric incision on the base	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 10232	conical truncated	stone	1,8	3,4		0,4	25,68	A	L. 1045	floor	Conical truncated stone spindle whorl, made of a light grey stone. Well shaped, wheel marks on the surface. Hole slightly larger near the base. Wear traces and chippings near the upper hole.	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	

Unknown context

1	599	dome	bone	0,6	2,3		0,2	2,2 8	A	800	Yadin	Dome bone spindle whorl with very small hole. Wheel marks on the dome, polishing on the base.		
	F 1013/1	dome	bone						F		Yadin 1960, CXCVI:13.			
	F 78/1	dome	bone						F		Yadin 1960, CXCVI:14.			
1	A 5061	discoid	stone	1	5		0,5	41, 81	A1	L. 2022 M		Pebble with off-centre hole, slightly hourglass.		
1	876/98-3038	dome	pottery	1,9	3		0,6	20, 16				Dome spindle whorl, made of pottery, complete. Hole perfectly cylindrical, very well shaped whorl.		
1	A 62661	discoid	limestone	0,6		4,2 x2, 2		8,4 8+x	A5	L. 9415 M		Fragment of limestone spindle whorl, well shaped.		
1	A 46770	biconical	pottery	1,4	2,3		0,3	7	A3	L. 7690 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.2. Intrusive into LB II fill	Biconical pottery spindle whorl, small and roughly shaped. Quite damaged near both sides of hole, which is very small.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 30891	conical	stone	1,4	2,7		0,4	11,69	M	L. 5122		Conical spindle whorl made of black stone (serpentine?) with concentric rings incised on the upper part. Wear traces near the upper hole.		
1	A 51074	discoid	stone	1,7	4,2		0,7	37,98+ x	A4	B/F 11-12		Discoid spindle whorl made of stone, heavily chipped. Cylindrical hole.		
1	A 53648	dome	stone	1,8	2,7		0,4	15,3	A4	W. 1019 W	fill	Dome spindle whorl, made of white stone, well shaped. Conical hole.		
1	M 34413	conical	stone	0,9	2,1		0,2 5	5,5 5	M	5555		Conical spindle whorl made of dark stone (serpentine?) with polishing traces on the base and dome perfectly smoothed.		
1	M 37938	dome	stone	1	2,9		0,3	7,6	M1	L. 5797 M		Dome spindle whorl, made of light grey stone, broken in two pieces.		
1	M 37828	conical	stone	1,7	4,2		0,3	25,85	M1	L. 14/15 M		Conical spindle whorl made of white stone, very worn. Small and slightly conical hole.		
1	A 62390	discoid	pottery	1,8	5,9		0,7	58,16	A5	Surface		Discoid pottery spindle whorl, 1/4 missing. Roughly shaped. Cylindrical hole.		
1	M 34049	cylindrical	stone	1,4	3		0,5	18,43	M 68	L. 5510		Cylindrical spindle whorl made of grey stone, quite well shaped. Hole not perfectly cylindrical.		
1	M 37719	biconical	pottery	4,2	4,2 x4, 5		0,3	60,77	M2	L. 5772		Biconical pottery spindle whorl, not very well shaped. Encrusted.		
1	M 74688	dome	stone	1,8	3,2		0,7	21,09	M	L. 09-345 M		Dome spindle whorl, made of white-pinkish chalky stone.		
1	M 74717	dome	stone	1,9	3,6		0,6	32,26	M	L. 09-329 F		Dome spindle whorl, worn surface.		
1	A 48200	conical truncated	stone	1,6	3,2		0,6	21,69	A3	L. 7880	fill	Conical truncated spindle whorl, made of stone (steatite), well shaped. No traces of manufacturing, possibly wheel traces on the base. Upper side of hole very worn, lower side neatly		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												cut. Slightly larger at the base (0,5).		
1	?	dome	bone	1,6	4,2		0,3	14,69+ x	A			YADI N	Dome bone spindle whorl, large and damaged. On the base cancellous bone exposed. Smaller hole at the base 0,5 cm.	
1	A 3445	dome	bone	2,7	4,5		0,6	28,35+ x	A	55n		YADI N	Dome bone spindle whorl, large and damaged. On the base cancellous bone exposed. Larger hole at the base (0,8 cm).	
1	A 3072	dome	stone	1,4	3		0,4	19,31	A	55n		YADI N	Stone spindle whorl, probably made of limestone, unfinished hole.	
1	L 1007	dome	stone	1,6	3,3		0,6	21,47	L	46		YADI N	Spindle whorl made of limestone. Well shaped. Cylindrical hole. Smoothed surfaces and small chippings near the upper side of the hole. Lower base very damaged.	
1	A 2211/3	dome	stone	2	3,5		nn	14,13+ x	A			YADI N	Dome spindle whorl, made of white-pinkish stone. Quite high and broken in half. Wheel marks quite evident on the dome.	
1	4226/1	dome	bone	0,6	2,6 x2, 3		0,3	4,1		57n		YADI N	Dome bone spindle whorl, very warp. Small hole.	
1	A 6936	conical truncated	stone	1,3	1,8		0,3	3,0 2	A	L. 1047 (92a)		YADI N	Conical truncated spindle whorl. Small and off-centre hole. Surface very worn.	
1	645	dome	stone	1,8	3,1		0,6	24,6		213n		YADI N	Steatite dome spindle whorl, well shaped and polished. Cylindrical hole. Upper side of the hole flattened and rough, as it is the edge.	

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Area Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

PERFORATED SHERDS

Early Bronze Age

1	92562/6		pottery							L. 80058	Hazor VII:157, fig. 5.5 n.31		Perforated sherd, half preserved.	EB IIIB Str. XX	
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Middle Bronze Age

1	A 92083	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,2	5,5		0,8	46,66	A4	L. 80006 M			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded and smoothed. Hole slightly hourglass.	IBA (Str. XVIII)	
1	A 49301	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,1			8,10+x	A2	L. 07-026 F		floor	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Roughly shaped, hourglass hole.	IBA (Str. XVIII)	
1	A 58429	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,3		0,5	14,84	A4	L. 9084 M			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded, hourglass, and slightly diagonal hole.	MB II?	

Late Bronze Age

1	H 962/21		pottery							L. 2146	Yadin 1989: CCLXIX:28		Perforated sherd, rounded and smooth	LB I (Str. 2)	
1	F 346/5		pottery							L. 8037	Yadin 1960: pl. CXLVI:30			LB II (Str. 1)	
1	D 12080	Prf. sherd	pottery						D	L. 9024	Yadin 1958, pl. CXXIV:15			LB I (Str. 3)	
1	B 1258/2	Prf. sherd	pottery						B	L. 3112	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXXXII:21			LB I (Str. 3)	
1	A 44890	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	3,8 x4,4		0,1	18,04	A3	L. 7418 M			Perforated sherd, roughly cut, very small hole. Certainly not used as a whorl.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 90852	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	4,7		0,7	31,38	A3	L. 9572 fill		fill	Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Hole almost cylindrical, but still visible which was perforated starting from both sides.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 25065	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,4	5		0,3	36,12	A2	L. 3749 M			Perforated sherd (or vessel base?), very worn. Small and hourglass hole.	LB II (Str. XIV-XIII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	A 48694	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,6	2,6 +x		0,3	1,9 +x	A2	L. 7931		Fragment of perforated sherd. Small but cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 48872	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,6	3		0,3	6,4 4+x	A2	L. 7946 M		fill	Small fragment of perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)
1	A 27060	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,8	3,8 x4, 1		0,7	35, 42	A2	L. 3883 F		floor	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Slightly conical hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)
1	A 56432	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	5,3		0,5	28, 51	A4	L. 8848		ash layer	Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Cylindrical hole. Slightly off-centre.	LB II (Str. XIV)
1	A 53830	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,6	4,1		0,3	12, 57	A4	L. 8432 M		floor	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut, hourglass hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)
1	M 71158	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,6	3,7		0,3	4,2 3+x	M	L. 6612 M			Perforated sherd, broken at 1/3. Roughly cut, hourglass hole.	LBA courtyard
1	A 14678	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,6	5,6		0,5	53, 3	A1	L. 1574		floor	Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded with cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)
1	A 48873	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,5		0,5	6,6 4+x	A2	L. 7946 M		fill	Perforated sherd, half missing. Roughly rounded, cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIV)
1	A 25909	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	5x4 ,4		0,5	27, 5	A2	L. 3752		fill	Perforated sherd, complete. Quite well rounded and smoothed. Cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)

Iron Age I

1	L 490/8	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	4		0,4	12, 69	L	L. 1012	Hazor V: 223, fig. III.20:17.	floor	Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Perforation made starting from both sides but central part of the hole almost cylindrical.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	98-1962
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Iron Age II

1	A 26778	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	3,8		0,3	15, 25	A2	L. 3863 M		floor	Perforated sherd, well rounded. Small hourglass hole.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 58790	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,2 x4, 8		0,5	18, 29	A4	L. 9155		fill	Perforated sherd not rounded. Cylindrical hole.	IA IIA (Str.X-IX)	
1	A 13410	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	5,8 x6, 3		0,7	45, 66	A1	L. 1432 pit		floor	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Cylindrical hole.	IA IIA-B (Str.VIII b)	
1	A 12615	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	3,5		0,3	4,8 2+x	A1	L. 1248		fill	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Well rounded with cylindrical hole.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 11799	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	6,9		0,6	43, 64	A1	L. 1218		floor	Perforated sherd, quite well rounded with hole made from beneath.	IA II A- B (Str. VIIb)	
1	M 72377	Prf. sherd	pottery	2,8	4,9		0,6	14, 16+ x	M	L. 07-329			Perforated sherd, half missing. Well rounded and smoothed.	IA IIC	
1	A 53465	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	6		0,4	44, 7	A4	L. 8402 floor			Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded and smoothed.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	M 72359	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	5,3		0,5	32, 65	M	L. 07-332			Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed.	IA IIC	
1	A 91253	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	7,7		0,6	65, 08	A3	07-213		floor	Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly cut and diagonal hole.	IA IIC (Str.VI)	
1	A 48519	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,2	5x5 ,5		0,4	34, 36	A2	L.7914		floor	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str.VI)	
1	A 46615	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	4		0,3	13, 38	A3	L. 7655		Fill	Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Small hourglass hole.	IA I-II (Str. XII- VIII)	
1	A 41698	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	3,1 x3, 8		0,3	11, 94	A3	L. 7105 M		fill	Perforated sherd not rounded. Small and diagonal hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 22849	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,8	5,5			28, 26+ x	A2	L. 3386 M		fill	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Roughly cut, hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 21327	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	3,8		0,5	14, 73	A2	L. 3184 floor		floor	Perforated sherd, roughly cut but rounded. Hourglass hole damaged in the upper part.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 27725	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	4x3 ,7		0,7	17, 6	A2	L. 3580 F		fill	Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Hole quite large and well worked, still partially hourglass.	IA II (Str.VII- V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 22255	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	5,2			16, 26+ x	A2	L. 3309 M		fill	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Well rounded and smoothed. Hole quite large and well worked, still partially hourglass.	IA IIC (Str.V)	
1	M 38097	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	3,4		0,2 5	13, 8	M1	L. 5784			Perforated sherd, quite well rounded. Hole off centre, small and hourglass, perforation made almost completely from one side.	IA IIC	
1	A 82095	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	6,1 x5, 8		0,2	46, 36	A2	L. 3289 Floor O.		floor	Perforated sherd, well rounded and polished. Very small hole.	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	A 22802	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	4,5		0,8	14, 50+ x	A2	L. 3371 M (F)		floor	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Quite well rounded with hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 41652	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	3,6		0,3	14, 9	A3	L. 7105 M		fill	Perforated sherd not rounded. Small and hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 23871	Prf. sherd	pottery	2,3	4,4		nn	56, 36	A2	L. 3562 F		floor	Very thick perforated sherd, well rounded. Hole made from both sides but left unfinished.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 62502	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,5		0,4	19, 1	A5	L. 9379 M		floor	Perforated sherd roughly rounded. Cylindrical hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	

Unknown context

1	M 39106	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	3,6		0,3	15, 83	M1	L. 5907 T			Perforated sherd, almost complete. Quite well rounded and smoothed. Small hole.		
1	A 522	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	4		0,7 5	10, 81+ x	A	55n		YADI N	Perforated sherd, very well rounded. Hourglass hole.		
1	A 3804	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4		0,5	8,5 6+x	A			YADI N 55n	Perforated sherd, well rounded but not smoothed. Hole almost cylindrical.		x
1	A 48599	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	4,6 x4, 3		0,3	18, 92	A2	L. 7925 M			Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed.		
1	A 64014	Prf. sherd	pottery	2,1	6,3		0,6	83, 76	A5	06-A5-001 M			Perforated sherd (or vessel base) rounded and very worn. Hourglass hole.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	A 62475	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,2	7,5		0,4	41	A5	L. 9375 M		Perforated sherd, 1/4 preserved. Quite well rounded and cylindrical hole.		
1	A 5062	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,1	5,6 x5, 1		0,6	42, 14	A1	L. 2021 M	fill	Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.	surface	
1	A 63296	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,8	5,1		0,3	21, 38	A5	L. 50066 M		Perforated sherd, roughly cut but rounded. Hourglass hole.		
1	M 38800	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	3,4 x3, 9		0,4	9,9 1	M2	L. 5885		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.		
1	A 53719	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,6	2,7		0,5	3,8 1+x	A4	L. 8434 M	disturbed fill	Perforated sherd, well rounded. Irregular and hourglass hole.		
1	A 48934	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	5,1		0,3	28, 47	A2	L. 06-A2-012 M		Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Small hourglass hole.		
1	A 60872	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,2	5,3		1	34, 28	A5	L. 136 M		Perforated sherd. Well rounded and smooth. Large and cylindrical hole.		
1	M 31811	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	3		0,5	10, 9	M	L. 5221		Perforated sherd (?), well rounded with hourglass hole.		
1	A 58195	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,7	3,6		0,4	8,7 4	A4	W. 5332 W		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Hourglass hole.		
1	M 24766/1	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	5,5 x6, 5		0,6	38, 9	M?	B115-16?		Perforated sherd. Roughly cut. Hole off centre but cylindrical.	baulk	
1	A 42555	Prf. sherd	pottery	1	4,3 x6, 5+x			36, 9+x	A3	L. 7260 F		Perforated sherd, half preserved. Well rounded and almost cylindrical hole.	FE?	
1	A 55295	discoid	pottery	1	5,2 x5, 5		0,3	33, 26	A4	L. 8688		Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Small and hourglass hole.	Fill -no date	

SPINNING BOWL?

1	16953/1		Pottery	13	7,3	loop p 1,3	4,3			L. 1706 16/51n	Bechar 2017: 335, fig. 7.72	Fragment of bowl with loop inside. Attached to the wall and not to the bottom. Shape of a handle.	LB II Str. XIV	
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N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Area Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

LOOM WEIGHTS

Middle Bronze Age

1	A 56221	discoid	baked clay	1,5	5,1 x5, 6		0,4	42, 35	A4	L. 8836		fill	Weight/pendant made of baked clay. Hole near one edge.	MB IIB (Str. XVII- XVI)	
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Late Bronze Age

	BA 41	conical	clay						BA	4020	Yadin 1989: CCXXXVI:24		Small conical loom weight horizontally perforated on the upper part.	LB I (ph. 11, Str. XV)	
	BA 71	conical	clay						BA	4020	Yadin 1989: CCXXXVI:25		Conical loom weight horizontally perforated on the upper part.	LB I (ph. 11, Str. XV)	
1	A 55245	doughnut	baked clay	4,5	7		1,3	210	A4	L. 8635 M			Doughnut shaped weight, poorly baked clay. Complete but broken in two pieces.	LB II (Str. XIV-XIII)	
1	M 70408	flat trapezoidal	baked clay	8,9	6,5	2,7	nn	162+ x	M2	L. 6533 M			Weight flat trapezoidal. Made of baked clay, top missing, part of a hole preserved. Hole off-centre, possibly a second was present.	LBA	
1	A 48115	prf. base	baked clay	2,6	5,9		0,7	92,04	A3	L. 7866 M		Floor	Thick base of a vessel , complete. Well made and partially smoothed. Hole off-centre and irregular.	LB I (Str. XV)	
1	A 49124	prf. base	baked clay	2,3	6,5		0,9	54,26 +x	A2	L. 07-017 M		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved.	LB I-II (Str. XV- XIV)	
1	A 49153	prf. base	baked clay	2,1	5,5		0,7	23,26 +x	A2	L. 07-017 F		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Roughly cut, hole irregular.	LB I-II (Str. XV- XIV)	
1	A 53517	prf. base	baked clay	2,4	8,2		0,5	138	A4	L. 8412 fill		Fill	Perforated base of a vessel, complete. Cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 26218	prf. base	baked clay	2,3	6,3		1,1	66,64	A2	L. 3786 M			Perforated base of a vessel, no attempt to make it regular.	LB II (XIV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 49118	prf. base	baked clay	1,8	6,2		1,2	49,78 +x	A2	L. 07-008		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, almost complete. Hole well centred, large, and damaged. Well rounded edge but not smoothed.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 55793	prf. base	baked clay	1,9	6,9		0,5	78,67	A4	L. 8790 M		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, complete. Well rounded edge but not smoothed.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	16744/1	prf. base	baked clay	2,1	7,4		nn	49,49 +x	?	L.1710		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Quite well rounded.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 47927	prf. base	baked clay	2,1	6,2		2	29,13 +x	A3	L. 7826 F		Fill	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Roughly cut, large and cylindrical hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 48170	prf. base	baked clay	1,3	5,8		nn	18,27 +x	A3	L. 7851 U?		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Roughly cut, irregular hole.	LB II (Str. XIII)	
1	A 17681	prf. base	baked clay	2,4	6,8		nn	61+x	A1	L. 1746		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Hourglass hole. Very damaged.	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 17680	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,6	6,6			29,34 +x	A1	L. 1741 M		floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Smoothed edge. Hole damaged.	LB II (Str. XIV-XIII)	
1	A 13349	spherical?	clay					215+ x	A1	L. 1443		fill	Fragments of large spherical or doughnut shaped loom weight.	LB II (Str. XIII)	

Iron Age I

1	L205/3	spherical	baked clay							L. 1025	Hazor V: 221, fig. III,19:12.		Spherical/doughnut shaped loom weight only partially preserved.	IA I	
1	A 50980	prf. base	baked clay	1,9	6,1		1,1	43+ x	A4	L. 8099 M		fill	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Not symmetrical. Small oval hourglass hole.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	
1	A 51646	prf. base	baked clay	1,6	5,7		0,3	49, 88+ x	A4	L. 8224		Fill	Perforated base of a vessel, fragmentary, quite rounded edge. Very small hole.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	
1	A 49016	prf. base	baked clay	2,2	6,2			33, 10+ x	A2	L. 07-015 P		pit	Perforated base of a vessel almost half preserved. Roughly cut, irregular hole.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	L225/7	spherical	baked clay						L. 1035	Hazor V: 228, fig. III.22:5			IA IIA (X sec.)	
	B 4792/16	biconical	clay					B	L. 3295	Yadin 1989: CCXIII:18		Biconical clay object, but apparently very small.	IA IIA (Str. X)	
1	A 55660	doughnut	baked clay	2	4,7		0,9	30+x	A4	L. 8767 F		floor	Doughnut shaped loom weight, half preserved. Roughly shaped, made of baked clay. Cylindrical hole.	IA II A (Str. IXb)
1	A 11025	doughnut	baked clay	3,1	4,4		nn	29+x	A1	L. 1107		Floor	Fragment of a doughnut shaped loom weight.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)
1	A 55619		clay	3,8	9,4		1	211+ x	A4	L. 8748 F		Floor	Fragment of a loom weight. Burnt.	IA IIA (Str. IXa)
1	A 58924	cylindrical	baked clay	3	5,8		0,5	116	A4	L. 9127		floor	Cylindrical loom weight, well shaped, almost cylindrical. Small hole, slightly off centre.	IA II A (Str. IX)
1	A 18614	prf. base	baked clay	1,1	6,9		0,8x1, 1	44,68	A1	L. 1852 M		Floor	Perforated base of a vessel, quite well rounded. Large and irregular hole.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIIb)
1	A 13074	doughnut	clay	4,1	4,5			192+ x	A1	L. 1409 F		pit	Fragments of one or more loom weight, doughnut shaped. Made of unbaked clay.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII- VII)
1	A 46655	prf. base	baked clay	1,5	4,6		nn	19,66 +x	A3	L. 7671 M		fill	Perforated base of a vessel, fragmentary. Quite well rounded, cylindrical hole.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)
1	A 12644	spherical	clay					179+ x	A1	L. 1296		Floor	Fragments of loom weight, probably spherical. Made of unbaked clay.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)
1	A 13430	doughnut	clay	4,2+ x	6,5 +x			182+ x	A1	1395 F		Floor	Several fragments of a doughnut shaped loom weights (measures of the largest fragment).	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIIb)
1	A 12828	doughnut	clay	nn	nn		nn	143 +x	A1	1332F		Floor	Small fragments of a loom weight, made of clay. Probably doughnut shaped.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)
1	A 43205	spherical	clay	5,3	7,8			268	A5	L. 4041		fill	Fragments of a spherical loom weight, made of unbaked clay. Almost complete but broken in many pieces.	IA II A-B (Str. X- VIII)

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 46321	spherical	clay				148+x	A3	L. 7612 P			pit	Fragments of clay loom weights partially preserved.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 42650	spherical	clay	4,7	5,7		74+x	A3	L. 7282			floor	Spherical loom weight, half preserved.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 20898		stone	14,7	4,5	1,5	0,6	207	A2	L. 3108		Floor	Long and thin weight.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 55453	spherical	baked clay	5,4	8,3x8,7		1,2	358	A4	L. 8740	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	Building 158	Spherical loom weight, complete. Well preserved.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 12811	spherical	clay	5,4	7,8		1,9	225	A1	L. 1309 F		Floor	Spherical loom weight, broken in many pieces but complete. Made of baked clay.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)	
1	A 34809	spherical	baked clay	5,5	7,1X7,4		1,3X1,6	272	A1	L. 1225	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	Baulk N14/15	Spherical weight well preserved, not symmetrical. Made of baked clay.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 56675	doughnut	clay	5,1	7,5		1,6	249+x	A4	L. 8890 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	Building 158	Doughnut shaped loom weight, almost complete.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 14768	doughnut	baked clay	3,7	5,2			56+x	A1	L. 1570 M		fill	Doughnut shaped loom weight, half preserved.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
2	M 32258	doughnut	clay	6,2	8,2		nn	292+x	M	L. 5271			Fragments of at least two different loom weights. Measures belong to the largest and better-preserved weight. Complete hole. Second weight: h 4,3, d 7,8 w 98+x	IA IIA-B	
1?	A 12678	nn	clay	nn	nn		nn		A1	L. 1262		Floor	Small fragments of clay object.	IA IIA (Str. IX)	
1	A 12830		clay	3,8+x	8		nn	147+x	A1	L. 1332 F		Floor	Fragments of a loom weight	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)	
1	A 13046	doughnut	clay	3,7			nn	124+x	A1	L. 1395 F		Floor	Fragments of a clay loom weight	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII)	
1	A 13090	doughnut	clay	4,4	6,8		1,5	136+x	A1	L. 1405 M		Floor	Doughnut shaped loom weight, almost complete.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 28203	prf. base	baked clay	1,7	4,8		0,4	32	A2	L. 4037 pit		pit	Perforated base of a vessel, oval and hourglass hole. Certainly not a spindle whorl.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 12300	doughnut	clay				342+ x	A	L. 1225 F			Floor	Fragments of a loom weight, probably doughnut shaped.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)	
1	A 11616	doughnut	baked clay	4,9	6,2		93+x	A1	L. 1172			fill	Fragment of a weight, roughly baked.	IA II A-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 13110	prf. base	baked clay	1,4	5,5		0,4	53	A1	L. 1409 F		pit	Perforated base of a vessel, oval and hourglass hole. Certainly not a spindle whorl.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	L205/1	spherical	baked clay						L	L. 1045	Hazor V: 264,265, fig. III.41:8.			IA IIC (VIII sec.)	
1	L275/1	spherical	baked clay							L. 1045	Hazor V: 264,265, fig. III.41:9.			IA IIC (VIII sec.)	
1	L275/2	spherical	baked clay							L. 1045	Hazor V: 264,265, fig. III.41:10.			IA IIC (VIII sec.)	
1	L275/1	spherical	baked clay							L. 1045	Hazor V: 264,265, fig. III.41:11.			IA IIC (VIII sec.)	
1	L408	discoid	limestone							L.1045	Hazor V: 264,265, fig. III.41:12.			IA IIC (VIII sec.)	
1	M 31439	doughnut	clay	5,5	13,2		3,1	977+ x	M	L. 5187			Doughnut shaped loom weight almost complete. Very crumbly. Not symmetrical.	IA IIC	
1	M 30964	nn	clay	nn				290+ x	M	L. 5080			Fragments of a clay loom weight	IA IIC	
1	A 18265	doughnut	clay	3,3	5,9			47+x	A1	L. 1821 oven		pit	Doughnut shaped loom weight, half preserved. Quite well preserved.	IA IIC (Str. IV)	
1	M 30958	spherical	clay					309+ x	M	L. 5096			Fragments of a spherical clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	A 13059	doughnut	clay	4	8,1		1,7	216	A1	L. 1388 Floor		Floor	Doughnut shaped loom weight well preserved. Probably lower side partially missing.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 72927	spherical	baked clay	5,9	8,3		1,2x1, 3	233+ x	M	L. 07-374			Spherical loom weight made of baked clay, fragmentary.	IA II C	
1	A 12822	doughnut	clay	nn	nn		nn	217+ x	A1	L. 1308		Floor	Small fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC (Str. VIb)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 40669	Prf. sherd	pottery	0,9	5,1		0,4-0,3	30,62	A3	L. 7032 F		Make up	Perforated base of a vessel, complete. Smoothed edge, hole irregular.	IA IIC (Str. Vc)	
1	A 62639	spherical	clay	4,6	5,7		1,2	138	A5	L 9510 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1		Spherical loom weight, complete. Made of unbaked clay but well preserved.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 62657	doughnut	clay	4,1	6,6		1,6	186	A5	L 9390 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	The Eastern wing, floor	Doughnut shaped loom weight, almost complete.	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	A 60179	biconical	baked clay	3,6	4,2x3,6		0,3	50	A5	L. 9029 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1		Biconical loom weight, quite oval. Roughly shaped. Small and irregular hole.	IA II C (Str. VI)	
1	A 60182	biconical	baked clay	3,7	4,2		0,5	52	A5	L. 9032 M	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	fill	Biconical loom weight, quite well shaped. Hole cylindrical but slightly off centre. Possibly a spindle whorl.	IA II C (Str. V)	
1	A 20032	biconical	baked clay	4,5	6,2		1,5	104	A 2	L. 3018 floor	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1	Building 3051	Biconical loom weight, quite well shaped. Very large hole.	IA II C (Str. Va)	
1	A 60165	biconical	baked clay	2,8	3,5		0,4	27	A5	L. 9029 M floor	Cimadevilla 2012: 560, fig. 12.1		Biconical loom weight, quite well shaped. Hole cylindrical but slightly off centre. Possibly a spindle whorl.	IA II C (Str. VI)	
1	A 20139	spherical	baked clay	4,3	5,1		1	85+x	A2	L. 3017			Spherical weight, well shaped. Made of baked clay. Oval hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 62801		stone	13,7	2,5	2	0,4	160	A5	L. 9430 M		Floor	Object with parallelepiped shape, with hole at the top. Not a loom weight.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 12303	doughnut	clay	6,7	8,9		nn	381	A1	L. 1256 F		fill	Two fragments of spherical loom weight, possibly belonging to two different weights.	IA IIC (Str. VI-V)	
1	A 21507	doughnut	clay	4,7	4,2			61+x	A2	L. 3209		Fill	Fragment of clay loom weight, probably doughnut shaped.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 42259	spherical	clay	4,7	5,5		nn	61+x	A3	L. 7200 F		fill	Fragment of clay loom weight, probably spherical.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 10471	doughnut	clay	3,3	7,7		1,6	146+x	A1	L. 1080		floor	Doughnut shaped loom weight, half preserved. Quite flattened on the base.	IA IIC (Str. V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 30940	doughnut	baked clay	4,7	6,5		1,6	152+ x	M	L. 5131		Doughnut shaped loom weight, broken in several pieces. Poorly baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	M 31013	spherical	clay	4,2	5,7			73+x	M	L. 5131 make up		Fragment of clay loom weight, probably spherical.	IA IIC	
1	A 18676	spherical	baked clay	4	5,9		0,7	112	A1	L. 1861 MU?		Floor Spherical loom weight made of baked clay, complete. Quite well shaped and with cylindrical hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 30092	spherical	baked clay	3,6	4,5		0,4	53+x	M	L. 5016		Spherical loom weight made of baked clay, 1/4 missing. Elliptical shape. Cylindrical hole slightly off-centre.	IA IIC	
1	A 60138	prf. base	baked clay	1,7	7,6		1,2	45,22 +x	A5	L. 9027 M		fill Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved.	IA II (Str. VII-VI)	
1	A 336	prf. base	baked clay	1,7	6,4		nn	36,54 +x	A1	L. 1750 M		fill Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Roughly cut, irregular hole.	IA IIC (Str. IV- III)	
1	A 46648	prf. base	baked clay	1,9	6,4		nn	38,6+ x	A3	L. 7648 M		Fill Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Roughly cut, irregular hole.	XII-VIII	
1	M 56151	prf. base	baked clay	1,6	6,3		0,6	31,63 +x	A1	L. 1310 ?		Floor Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Well rounded and regular hole, almost cylindrical.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 20466	spherical	baked clay	4,8	6,9		1,4	215	A2	L. 3067		fill Spherical clay loom weight, complete. Well shaped.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 72872	spherical	baked clay	6	6,7x7, 3		1,4	219+ x	M	L. 07-356		Spherical loom weight, almost complete. Made of baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	A 62838	doughnut	baked clay	3,9	7,2x6, 7		1,5	171	A2	L. 9390 M		Floor Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 62640	doughnut	baked clay	3,9	6,5		1,2	137	A5	L. 9390 M		Floor Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 62656	doughnut	baked clay	4,5	7,3		1,5	199	A5	L. 9390 M		Floor Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay. One side of the hole very oval, similar to Tell el-Farah.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 72457	spherical	baked clay	5,1	5,9		0,6	148+ x	M	L. 07-329 M		Spherical loom weight, complete. Made of poorly baked clay. Apparently very worn.	IA IIC	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 62658	doughnut	clay	5				76+x	A5	L. 9390 M		Floor	Two fragments of a clay loom weight, probably doughnut shaped.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 1990	doughnut	clay	5,3	8,8		1,4	346+x	A7	L. 295 floor		Floor	Doughnut shaped clay loom weight, almost complete.	IA II (Str. VIIIb-V)	
1	A 20034	spherical	clay	5,5	8,7		1,7	187+x	A2	L. 3018		Floor	Spherical clay loom weight, almost 1/3 preserved.	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	M 76261	doughnut	clay	3,5	7,5		1,8	141+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Doughnut shaped clay loom weight, partially preserved.	IA IIC	
1	M 76260		clay					214+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 76262		clay					182+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 76264	doughnut	clay	5,4	7,7		1,7	186+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 76263	doughnut	clay	2,9	7,7		1,4	100+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 75265	doughnut	clay	3,8	7,9		1,7	169+x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Doughnut shaped clay loom weight, partially preserved.	IA IIC	
1	M 76158		clay					48+x	M	L. 10-326 F			Small fragments of clay loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 75423a	spherical	clay	6	4,3		1,4	277	M	L. 10-326 M above F			Spherical loom weight, almost complete. Poorly baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	M 75423b	spherical	clay	5,2	7,6		1,6	182+x	M	L. 10-326 M above F			Spherical clay loom weight, half preserved. Poorly baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	M 75455a	spherical	clay	5,3	6,2		nn	141+x	M	L. 10-306 F			Fragments of loom weight, probably spherical. Poorly baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	M 75455b	spherical	clay	6,9	8,9		nn	422+x	M	L. 10-306 F			Fragments of loom weight, probably spherical. Poorly baked clay.	IA IIC	
1	M 76345		clay	5,3	9		nn	177+x	M	L. 10-326 F		10	Lump of clay, probably belonging to a loom weight.	IA IIC	
1	M 76339		clay	4,8	8,2		nn	253+x	M	L. 10-326 F		1	Lump of clay, probably belonging to a loom weight.	IA IIC	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 76259		clay				367+ x	M	L. 10-326 F eastern enclosure			Small fragments of clay, belonging to one or more loom weights.	IA IIC	
1	M 76343		clay				127+ x	M	L. 10-326 F		8	Small fragments of clay, belonging to one or more loom weights.	IA IIC	
1	M 76340		clay	5,1	7,8		nn	226+ x	M	L. 10-326 F		2	Fragment of clay loom weight.	IA IIC
1	M 76341		clay					184+ x	M	L. 10-326 F		3	Small fragments of clay, belonging to one or more loom weights.	IA IIC
1	M 76344		clay					287+ x	M	L. 10-326 F		9	Small fragments of clay, belonging to one or more loom weights.	IA IIC
3	M 76342	doughnut	clay		8,5				M	L. 10-326 F		4-7	Four loom weights in a single lump of soil.	IA II
1	M 92815	spherical	baked clay	5	5,9		0,8	139+ x	M- west	L. 579			Spherical loom weight, almost complete. Made of baked clay.	IA IIC
1	M 75352	conical	stone	6,9	4,3		0,4	115	M	L. 09-384 M			Very peculiar object made of white stone. Conical shaped with a hole in the upper part, not passing through, but connecting to a hole on the top. Slightly concave base.	IA II C
1	M 93230		stone	7,6	4,6		0,9	181	M3	L. 14-517 U			Perforated pebble.	IA II C
1	M 93155	prf. base	baked clay	2,7	6		0,5	97	M3	L. 14-508			Base of a vessel, complete. Quite well rounded, small, and irregular hole.	IA II C
1	M 73914	doughnut	baked clay	4,5	7,3x7		2x1,5	199	M	L. 08-358 M above F			Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Roughly shaped and full of stone inclusions. Made of baked clay. Hole off-centre and quite irregular.	IA II C
1	M 73913		clay		6,3+x			82+x	M	L. 08-358 M above F			Fragments of clay object, not recognizable.	IA IIC
1	M 73047	spherical	baked clay	5,3	7,9		1,5	232+ x	M	L. 08-306 M			Weight in baked clay, almost complete, with a wide and fairly regular hole. The object is not particularly well-shaped.	IA IIC
1	M 73949	cylindrical	stone	8,4x7 ,1	8,1x8, 5		1,7x2	571	M	L. 08-345 M			Cylindrical object made of white stone, roughly cut, hole well shaped.	IA IIC

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 60450	cylindrical	stone	8,7	7x6,4		1,3x1,5	426	A5	L. 9067 M		Floor	Cylindrical object made of white stone, roughly cut, perforation started from both sides but left unfinished.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
	B 15154	doughnut	clay						B	3066	Yadin 1958: 31, 44, pl. LXXII.	In Locus 3066 a group of nine such balls were found together.	Unbaked clay	IA IIC (Str. V)	
	B 15154/2	doughnut	clay						B	3066	Yadin 1958: 31, pl. LXXII.		Unbaked clay	IA IIC (Str. V)	
	B 15154/3	doughnut	clay						B	3066	Yadin 1958: 31, pl. LXXII.		Unbaked clay	IA IIC (Str. V)	
	B 15154/4	doughnut	clay						B	3066	Yadin 1958: 31, pl. LXXII.		Unbaked clay	IA IIC (Str. V)	
	B 15156	doughnut	clay						B	3066	Yadin 1958: 31, pl. LXXII.		Baked clay	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 27812	prf. base	pottery	1,6	5,9		0,6	55	A2	L. 4004 MU		floor	Perforated base of a vessel, smoothed edge. Hole damaged.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	M 72692	prf. base	pottery	1,5	6,1		0,5	25,95+x	M	L. 07-366 F			Perforated base of a vessel, smoothed edge. Hourglass hole.	IA II C	
1	A 42444	prf. base	pottery	2	6			43,88+x	A3	L. 7243 F		floor	Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Smoothed edge, damaged hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 27812	prf. base	pottery	1,7	5,9		0,6	55,1	A2	L. 4004 MU		floor	Perforated base of a vessel, smoothed edge. Hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	

Unknown context

1	95-1572/2	spherical	baked clay	5,7	7,8		1,8x2	338 - x					Spherical clay loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay. Hole full of soil.		
1	95-1572/1	spherical	baked clay	6,2	8,4		1,7	436 - x					Spherical clay loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay. Hole full of soil.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 31096		baked clay	8,2	11x11 ,2		1,4	957	M (?)	L. 5132		4819	Peculiar object, concave, not a loom weight.	
1	M 13112	nn	clay						M	L. 1388			Fragments of clay loom weight.	
1	M 14525	doughnut	clay	4,7	8,1		2,2	200	M	L. 1029			Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Poorly baked.	
1	A 21356	doughnut	clay	4,3	6,9			80+x	A2	L. 3194			Doughnut shaped loom weight almost half preserved.	
1	M 37525	doughnut	clay	4,4	7,5		1,6	146+ x	M1	L. 5777			Fragmentary doughnut shaped loom weight. Poorly baked clay.	
1	A 1974	doughnut	clay	5	nn		nn	316 +x		L. 300 F			Fragments of one or more loom weight, doughnut shaped. Made of unbaked clay.	
1	M 37612	spherical	clay	5,9	8,2		1,5	156+ x	M	L. 5777 M			Spherical loom weight, half preserved.	
1	A 40021	pyramidal truncated	baked clay	4,8	3,2		0,3	54	A3	Taking away baulk			Pyramidal truncated loom weight, probably late.	baulk
1	A 64040	discoid	baked clay	1,7	9,8		nn	104+ x	A5	06-A5-061			Discoid loom weight (?), well shaped. Made of baked clay.	
1	M 32620		baked clay	3	88,6		0,8	191	M	L. 5292 M			Fragment of loom weight or model wheel?	
1	M 30896		baked clay	5,3	8,7	5,4		249+ x	M	L. 5122			Possible weight but no hole visible.	
1	A 62567	spherical	baked clay	4,6	7,9		1,4	147+ x	A1	L. 9375 M			Fragment of loom weight, spherical shape.	
	M 39065	conical	baked clay						M1	L. 5900			Weight with shape of a plumb bob	
	M 31099	conical	baked clay						M8	L. 5159			Weight with shape of a plumb bob	
1	M 31032	spherical	clay	3,5	4,4		0,5	55+x	M	L. 5149			Spherical loom weight, complete. Made of clay and quite worn.	
1	A 60215	spherical	baked clay	3,1	4,4		0,6	45+x	A5	L. 9039 M		fill	Spherical loom weight, 1/4 missing. Elliptical shape, hole cylindrical but off-centre.	surface
1	A 55348	prf. base	baked clay	1,5	6,2		0,3	41,91 +x	A4	L. B-E/9 M			Perforated base of a vessel.	
1	A 62501	prf. base	baked clay	19	6,5		nn	42,69 +x	A5	L. 9366 M			Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved.	
1	A 64053	prf. base	baked clay	0,8	5		0,3	18,10 +x	A5	L. 06A5-009 M			Perforated base of a vessel, almost complete. Hole near the edge. Late.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	A 12642	prf. base	baked clay	1,2	7		nn	32,82 +x	A1	L. 4910 B		Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Quite well rounded, irregular hole.		
1	A 91222	spherical	baked clay	5,6	6,5		1,3	196	A3	L. 07-172 M		Spherical loom weight made of baked clay. Complete and well shaped.		
1	M 72437	doughnut	baked clay	4,7	8x8,5		1,5	240	M	baulk B		Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Made of baked clay.	baulk	
1	A 53616	doughnut	baked clay	5,5	7,9		1,4x1,6	189+ x	A4	L. 8420 floor		Doughnut shaped loom weight, 1/3 missing.		
1	A 53614	doughnut	baked clay	5	8,5		1,3	305	A4	L. 8420 floor		Doughnut shaped loom weight, almost complete. Made of baked clay.		
1	A 63454	doughnut	clay	5	6,6		1,4	185+ x	A5	L. 50097 M		Doughnut shaped loom weight, 1/3 preserved. Made of unfired clay.		
1	34476	spherical	baked clay	5,3	6		0,8	150	M	L. 5562		Spherical clay loom weight, complete.		
1	M 30347	spherical	baked clay	4,2	5,9		1,4	107+ x	M	L. 5053		Spherical loom weight, partially preserved, made of baked clay.		
1	M 34834	doughnut	baked clay	4,1	6,4		1,7	140	M?	8M N 15-16 ?		Doughnut shaped loom weight, complete. Well crafted and made of baked clay.	baulk	
1	A 91634	prf. base	baked clay	1,6	6,4		0,4	56,7	A3	W. 03-207 W		Perforated base of a vessel, well rounded. Small and hourglass hole.		
1	A 21505	doughnut	clay	4,5	7,8		1,4	126+ x	A2	L. 3009	fill	Doughnut shaped loom weight, half preserved.	surface	
1	M 38452	Prf. sherd	pottery	1,3	7			30,22 +x	M1	L. 5858 fill		Perforated base of a vessel, half preserved. Smoothed edge, damaged hole.		

BASALT RINGS

Middle Bronze Age

47	19215		basalt							1929	Ebeling Hazor VI: 554, fig. 11.8	47 are mentioned, but	Irregular, not an actual basalt ring.	MB IIC fill	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											only one is published.			
1	C 1175/1	basalt						C	6203 T16-17	Yadin 1960: pl. CXXXVI:10			MB II (Str. 3)	

Late Bronze Age

	F 1394/27	basalt						F	8189	Yadin 1989: CCXLIV:11		Probably too big, not clear from drawings	MB II-LBI	
	H 548	basalt						H	2130	Yadin 1989: CCLXX:10			LB I (Str. 2)	
	H 1054	stone						H	2133	Yadin 1989: CCLXX:17		Very thin disc. Hole not centrally drilled.	LB I (Str. 2)	
	H 1261/1	basalt						H	2156	Yadin 1989: CCLXXXVIII:3		Irregular	LB II (Str. 1a)	

Iron Age II

	A 4140/1	basalt							243	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:11.	Too big.	More than 10 cm	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
	A 4139/1	basalt							243	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:12.	Too big.	More than 10 cm	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
	A 4362/1	basalt							255	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII:18, CCCLIX:25.		Probably too big, not clear from drawings	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
	A 306/1	basalt						A	130	Yadin 1960: LXXVIII:5		Irregular	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
	B 845/1	basalt						B	3100a/1	Yadin 1960: pl. CV:18, CLXIV:9		Cylindrical, hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
	C 1533										Too big.			

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
	C 1530											Too big.		
1	A 26507	cylindrical	basalt	1,8	3,5		1+x	14,6+x	A2	L. 3813 M		fill	Basalt ring, half preserved. Quite thick, well shaped, almost cylindrical hole.	IA IIA (Str. X-IX)
1	A 24003	cylindrical	basalt	1,5	4,6		1	13,43+x	A2	L. 3583 M		floor	Basalt ring, half preserved. Quite well shaped, almost cylindrical hole.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIa)
1	A 58408	cylindrical	basalt	2	3,6		1	17,96+x	A4	L. 9120		floor	Basalt ring, half preserved. Well shaped but slightly asymmetrical. Hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. V)
1	M 74670	cylindrical	basalt	1,7	3,9		0,9	20,4+x	M	L. 09-341 F			Basalt ring, half preserved. Quite well shaped, hourglass hole. Encrusted surface.	IA IIC
1	A 5207	cylindrical	basalt	1,4	3,2		0,9	20,38	A 1	L. 2047 M		fill	Basalt ring, complete. Quite a small, well shaped, hourglass hole.	IA IIC (Str. VI-V)
1	M 75144	cylindrical	basalt	2,2	3,7		1,1	19,9+x	M	L. 09-343 M			Basalt ring, half preserved. Almost cylindrical hole.	?
1	A 51206	cylindrical	basalt	1,2	3,2		nn	8,76+x	A4	W. 5006 W			Basalt ring, half preserved. Almost cylindrical hole.	

BONE SPATULAE AND PIN BEATERS

Middle Bronze Age

1	A 49288	Point	Bone	12	top 2,3 x1,9	1,4 x1,2			A2	L. 07-026 F		floor	Bone point with several scratches on tip and surface.	IBA (Str. XVIII)
	D 13546	Awl	bone						D	9024	Yadin 1958: CXVIII:15, CLXX:14.		Awl, apparently complete	MB II

	N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
	E 4293	Awl	bone						E	7021	Yadin 1958: CXLII:20, CXLVI:16.		Awl, apparently complete	LB I	
1	17302		bone							W. 1220	Ben Tor 2017: 559.		Rib of goat or sheep		
1	A 16784	Spatula	Bone						A1	L. 1714		floor	Fragments of bone objects, at least one was part of a spatula	LB II (Str. XIV)	
1	A 62764	Spatula	Bone	8,4	2,3	0,2			A5	L. 9421 M		fill	Bone spatula, broken in several points and one end missing. Triangular point. Smoothed on both sides.	LB II (Str. XIV-XIII)	
1	A 47808	Spatula	Bone	14,7	4,1	0,65			A3	L. 7812 M		fill	Large bone spatula, broken at both ends.	LB II (Str. XIII)	

Iron Age I

1	A 52128	beater	Bone	8	0,7		0,3		A4	8294 pit		pit	Bone beater, quite thin. Broken in two pieces.	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	
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Iron Age II

	A1749/1	Spatula	bone						A	174b	Yadin 1960: pl. LXXVIII:24, CLXVI:8.		Complete bone spatula, with a triangular point.	IA IIA (Str. X)	
1	A 3413/1	Spatula	Bone	7,9	1,8	0,2			A	208b	Yadin 1989: CLXXVI:22.		Bone spatula, fragmentary. Point was probably elongated but not preserved, another end partially broken. Polished on both sides and edge smoothed.	IA IIA (Str. IXb)	
1	A 58711	Spatula	Bone	5	2,1	0,3			A4	L. 9145		fill	Bone spatula, broken. One rounded end preserved. Upper surface and edge highly smoothed, lower surface with cancellous bone exposed, although quite worn.	IA IIA (Str. IX)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 55192	Spatula	Bone	7,9	2,6	0,1 5			A4	L. 8680 M		floor	Bone spatula, broken in two pieces, point missing. Other end is flat. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed but quite worn. Edge quite sharp.	IA IIA (Str. Xb)	
1	A 61223	Spatula	Bone	6,2 5	1,4	0,1 5			A5	L. 9184 M		fill	Bone spatula, one end missing, the other rounded. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIA (Str. X-IX)	
1	M 75453	Spatula	Bone	9,9	2,4	0,4			M	L. 10-309 M			Bone spatula, both ends missing. One side smoothed, the other with cancellous bone exposed but quite worn. Edge quite sharp. Wear traces visible on the upper side.	IA IIA-B	
1	A 18548	Spatula	Bone	a4, 8 b4, 1	a1,5 b1, 6	a0,4 5 b0, 25			A1	L. 1240		floor	Two different objects. A) Bone spatula, both ends missing, polished edge. B) Bone spatula, one end missing, the other well rounded. Polished on both sides and smoothed edge. Deep and large wear traces on both sides.	IA II A- B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 55129	Spatula	Bone	8,7	2,7	0,2			A4	L. 8675 F		fill	Bone spatula, fragmentary and encrusted. On one side cancellous bone exposed, even if worn.	IA II A- B (Str. VIII- VII)	
1	A 53178	Spatula	Bone	5,8	2,2	0,2			A4	L. 8341		floor	Bone spatula, one end missing, the other triangular. Well smoothed on one side, less on the other. Smoothed edge, less on the point.	IA II A- B (Str. VIII- VII)	
1	A 18738	Spatula	Bone	5,6	2,5	0,2			A1	L. 1871 M		floor	Bone spatula, one end missing, the other preserves a well shaped triangular point. One side polished, as the edge, the other with exposed cancellous bone. Some wear traces are detectable.	IA II A- B (Str. VII)	
1	A 55254	Spatula	osso	18, 5	2,6					L. 8684	Bechar 2012: 499, fig. 8.1.12	Pit	Bone spatula, almost complete. One triangular end, the other rounded. Broken in several pieces. Polished on both sides.	IA II A- B (Str. VII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 62834	Spatula	Bone	4,3	2	0,3				L. 9427 M		fill	Bone spatula, one end missing the other well rounded. It is well polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 55063	Spatula	Bone	5,7	2,4	0,3				L 8662 M		floor	Bone spatula, one end missing the other quite flat. It is well polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 63415	Spatula	Bone	10,6	1,7	0,3				L. 50086 M	Bechar 2012: 499, fig. 8.1.11	fill	Bone spatula, complete but broken in several pieces. Long and narrow. One end has a triangular shape, the other quite flat. Well polished on the upper side and edge, cancellous bone visible on the lower side, but very smoothed. No wear traces detectable.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 24107	Spatula	Bone	4,2 5	1,8	0,2			A2	L. 3604 M		floor	Bone spatula, one end rounded, the other missing. It is well polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 60602	Spatula	Bone	7	2,1	0,2			A5	L. 9091 M	Bechar 2012: 499, fig. 8.1.15		Bone spatula, one elongated point preserved and very well shaped, the other end missing. Polished on both surfaced.	IA IIA-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 57619	Spatula	Bone	5,3	2,8	0,3			A4	L. 9042 M		fill	Bone spatula, only triangular point preserved. Quite thick, left unpolished, edge very sharp. Lower side with cancellous bone exposed, very rough. Never used.	IA II A-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 46280	Spatula	Bone						A 3	L. 7612 M		Pit	Bone spatula broken in several small pieces but not complete. Smoothed edge where preserved.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII-VII)	
1	A 11534a	Spatula	Bone	10,8	2	0,2			A	L. 1172	Bechar 2012: 499, fig. 8.1.13	fill	Bone spatula, complete. One pen-nib point, the other rounded. Both surfaces are polishes as well as the edge. Wear traces long the whole edge.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 11865	Spatula	Bone	3,8	2,3	0,1			A1	L. 1206		floor	Bone spatula, broken. Triangular point preserved, slightly chipped. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 45831	Spatula	Bone	6,5	0,9 x0, 7			A3	L 7543			fill	Bone spatula, one pointed and the other missing.	IA II A-B (Str. VIII)	
1	A 11656	Spatula	Bone	7,6	2,2	0,2		A1	L. 1206			floor	Bone spatula, broken. One triangular end preserved, other end missing. Polished on both sides. Edge quite smoothed. Wear traces more visible near one side of the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 11657	Spatula	Bone	5,7	2,2	0,2		A1	L. 1206			floor	Bone spatula, broken. Rounded point preserved, very well shaped. Extremely polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 11534b	Spatula	Bone	8,6	2,3	0,1		A	L. 1172			fill	Bone spatula, broken. One rounded end preserved, the other missing. Very thin, well polished on one surface, less on the other. Slightly concave. Thin edge but smooth. Wear traces on the surface.	IA IIA-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 55121	Spatula	Bone					A4	L. 8662 F			floor	Bone spatula, fragmentary. One triangular point preserved, with smoothed edge. One surface polished, the other with cancellous bone exposed, even if smoothed and polished.	IA II A-B (Str. VIIb)	
1	A 63345	Spatula	Bone	5,5	2	0,2		A5	L. 50077 F			floor	Bone spatula, broken, both ends missing. Polished on both sides and on the edge. Wear traces, thin and parallel on the surface.	IA II A-B (Str. VII)	
1	A 64008	Spatula	Bone	5,5	1,8	0,3		A5	06A5-002 M	Bechar 2012: 499, fig. 8.1.14.		fill	Bone spatula, one end rounded and the other missing. Extremely polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA II (Str. VII-VI)	
1	A 41790	Spatula	Bone					A3	L. 7148 M			floor	Small fragments of a bone spatula.	IA II (Str. VII-VI)	
1	A 46057	Spatula	Bone	4,6	1,6 5	0,2		A3	L. 7567			fill	Bone spatula, only one edge and part of the point preserved. Very damaged.	IA II (Str. VII-VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	A 2388/1	Spatula	Bone						L. 3A	Hazor III-IV: pl. CLXXXVIII: 26. Hazor V: p. 144, fig. II.52: 23		Bone spatula, one end rounded and the other missing.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 53467	Spatula	Bone	10, 3	1,9	0,2			L. 8402 floor		floor	Bone spatula, broken. One end rounded and the other missing. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 61364	Spatula	Bone	6	1,9	0,2		A5	L. 9199 M		floor	Bone spatula, broken and both ends missing. Point possibly triangular. Evident traces of polishing on one side, not due to wear.	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	
1	A 40719	Spatula	Bone	3,8	1,7	0,1 5		A3	L. 7054		floor	Bone spatula, one end with a triangular point, the other missing. Quite well polished on both sides.	IA IIC (Str. VIb)	
1	A 18590	Spatula	Bone	2,1	1,8	0,1 5		A1	L. 1849		fill	Small fragment of spatula?	IA IIC (Str. IV-III)	
1	A 60448	Spatula	Bone					A8	L. 9079 M		fill	Bone spatula, broken in several small fragments. Where preserved, the edge appears not smoothed.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 62294	Spatula	Bone	3,5	2,8	0,1 5		A5	L. 9325 M		fill	Bone spatula, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. One side polished, the other less. Cancellous bone exposed, even if quite smoothed.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 63305	Spatula	Bone	5,4	1,7	0,2 5		A5	L. 50068 F		floor	Bone spatula, broken in two pieces and only part of the edge preserved. Well polished on all surfaces.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 22927	Spatula	Bone					A2	L. 3402 floor		fill	Bone spatula broken in several small fragments. Very thin and smooth on both sides.	IA IIC (Str. V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 60464	Spatula	Bone	5,4	2,1 5	0,1 5			A5	L. 9065		Floor	Bone spatula, one end with a triangular point, the other missing. Surface polished on both sides, but cancellous bone exposed on the lower surface. Wear traces on the upper surface.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	A 13227	Spatula	Bone	8,1	1,9	0,2			A1	L.1424 G		floor	Bone spatula, broken. Part of the rounded end preserved. Smoothed on both sides.	IA IIC (Str.VIa)	
1	A 11157	Spatula	Bone	6,1	1,4	0,2			A1	L. 1153		floor	Bone spatula, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. Well polished on one side, less on the other where cancellous bone is exposed, even if worn. Smoothed edge.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 74193	Spatula	Bone	5,7	1,9	0,2			M	L. 09-312 M			Bone spatula, broken. One end flat, the other missing. Well polished on both sides.	IA IIC	
1	M 75358	Spatula	Bone	2,4	2,2	0,2			M	L. 09-317 M from mudbrick wall			Fragment of bone spatula, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. Polished on both sides. Wear traces on the lower surface near the edge, which appear smoothed.	IA IIC	
1	M 74336	Spatula	Bone	4,1	1,9	0,1			M	L. 09-319 M			Fragment of spatula, with a triangular point. Very thin and smooth on both sides.	IA IIC	
1	M 73982	Spatula	Bone	4,2	1,7	0,2			M	L. 08-356 F			Fragment of bone spatula with pen-nib point. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIC	
1	M 75009	Spatula	Bone	8	2,1	0,3			M	L. 09-350 M			Bone spatula, broken but preserved for almost all length. One end with a triangular point, the other flat. Smoothed by wear on both sides, only towards the flat end cancellous bone is preserved. It becomes thinner approaching to the point.	IA IIC	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 75526	Spatula	Bone	4,1	2	0,2			M	L. 10-306 F		Two fragments of a bone spatula, not joining. No ends preserved. Polished on both sides, part of cancellous bone exposed but smoothed.	IA IIC	
1	M 75456	Spatula	Bone		2,6	0,1 5			M	L. 10-306 F		Two fragments of bone spatula. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIC	
1	M 78637	Spatula	Bone	5,2	2,7	0,2			M	L. 14-338 I		Bone spatula, broken. One end flat, the other missing but possibly with a triangular point in origin. Polished on both sides and smoothed on the edge, even the flat end.	IA IIC	
1	M 78802	Spatula	Bone	4,7	1,8	0,2			M3	W. 15-303		Small bone spatula, point missing. Polished on one side, while on the other cancellous bone is exposed, which disappear towards the point.	IA IIC	
1	A 2258/4	Spatula	Bone	8,5	2,7	0,2			A	L. 81A	Hazor III-IV: pl. CLXXXVIII: 27. Hazor V: p. 145, fig. II.53: 10	Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other is well rounded. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 2368/1	Spatula	Bone	7,9	2,4	0,2			A	188	Yadin 1989: CLXXXVIII: 25.	Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other is well rounded. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 2368/1a		Bone	3,2	2,6	0,2			A	188		Small fragment of a bone spatula, with heavy parallel signs on the surface, not due to wear.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
	B 217/5	Spatula	bone						B	3094	Yadin 1960: pl. CV:36.		IA IIC (Str. Va)	

Unknown context

1	A 91160	Spatula	Bone	4,1	1,3	0,2				L-07-208		Bone fragment of a spatula		
1	A 26682	Spatula	Bone	9,9	1,7	0,2 5				L. 3835		fill (no levels)	Bone spatula, broken. One end is probably flat but chipped, the other missing. One side is polished, the	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												other with cancellous bone exposed. Smoothed edge.		
1	A 1533	Spatula	Bone	10,2	2,3	0,3				L. B-8/R-S		Bone spatula, broken. One end flat, the other missing. One side is polished, the other has cancellous bone exposed, more smoothed towards the point.		
1	A 58452	Spatula	Bone	5,6	2,4	0,2 5				L. 9110 M		Bone spatula with small triangular point, the other end missing. Possibly a reworking. Polished on both sides, not on the edge.		
1	A 63284	Spatula	Bone	4,4	2	0,1				L. 50065 M		Bone spatula, broken. Triangular point preserved, very well crafted and still sharp. Very thin spatula and extremely polished on all sides.		
1	A 63399	Spatula	Bone	6,7	2,2	0,3			A 5	L. 50084 M		Bone spatula, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. Broken in three pieces. Well polished on all surfaces, including edge.		
1	A 60936	Spatula	osso	3,3	2,4	0,2			A5	L. 9139 M	fill	Fragment of bone spatula, broke. Well crafted triangular point preserved, the other end missing. Polished on both sides. Deep parallel signs on the surface, not due to wear.		
1	A 63041	Spatula	Bone	7,6	2,2	0,2				L. 50015 M		Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded. Polished on both sides.		
1	A 62627	Spatula	Bone	a3, 5 b4, 2	a 1,5 b2, 2	a 0,2 b0, 15			A5	L. 9409 M		Two fragments of different spatulae. A) Triangular point of bone spatula, roughly shaped but polished on both sides. Deep parallel signs on the surface not due to wear. B) Bone spatula broken at both ends, edge smoothed where preserved. Polished on both sides, near the		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												point cancellous bone is visible but very worn.		
1	A 1661	Spatula	Bone	2,1	2,3	0,2		A 7	L. 274 F11			Bone spatula, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. Polished on both sides but edge still sharp. Polishing marks visible on the surface.		
1	M 38198	Spatula	Bone	5,8	1,1	0,2		M2	L. 5801 M			Small and narrow bone spatula, broken. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is missing but probably a second point was present. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		
1	M 39456	Spatula	Bone	4,4	2,1	0,2		M1	L. 5929 pebble level			Bone spatula, broken. One end with a triangular point but rounded, the other missing. Both sides are polished but very worn.		
1	M 31802	Spatula	Bone	11,9	2,6	0,2		M	5229			Bone spatula, broken. One rounded end preserved, the other missing. Both surfaces are polished, and the lower side shows traces of cancellous bone. Upper surface with polishing manufacture marks.		
1	M 37557	Spatula	Bone	6,8	1,4	0,4		M	L. 5776			Bone spatula, complete. One end has a pen-nib point, the other rounded. One surface extremely polished, the other with cancellous bone exposed, partially obliterated by use. Smoothed edge.		
1	M 32407	Spatula	Bone	5,5	2,5	0,2		M	BM/L-10			Bone spatula, with a very thin triangular point. Polished on both sides and on the edge.	balk	
1	M 73794	Spatula	Bone	3,7	2,2	0,3		M	L. 08-311 M			Bone spatula, broken. One end flat, the other missing. Well polished on both surfaces and on the edge.	?	
1	M 75646	Spatula	Bone	8,1	3	0,2		M	L. B.M. 7/8 B ?			Bone spatula, quite broad, broken. One end rounded, the other missing. Polished on all sides.	balk	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	M 72457	Spatula	Bone	5,7	1,3	0,1 5		M	L. 10-302 M above F			Bone spatula, long and narrow with a triangular point. Polished on all sides.	?	
1	M 75528	Spatula	Bone	8,1	2,8	0,3		M	L. 10-321 M			Bone spatula, broken. One end flat, the other missing. Thickening towards the flat end. Polished on both surfaces and on the edge, excluding the flat end.	?	
1	A 22062	Point	Bone	5,5	0,9		0,4	A2	3245		fill	Bone point broken on both ends.	-	
1	A 2338/1	Spatula	Bone	6,2	2,4	0,1		A	n57		YADI N	Bone spatula, broken. One rounded end, the other missing. Polished on both sides and on the edge. Very thin.		
1	A 2056/1	Spatula	Bone	8,3	2,6	0,1		A	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, broken. One rounded end, very well crafted, the other missing. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		
1	A 11973	Spatula	Bone	5,6	1,8	0,2 5		A	55n		YADI N	Bone spatula, complete. One end roughly rounded, the other missing. Edge smoothed.		
1	A 2272/1	Spatula	Bone	10	2,5	0,2		a	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		
1	A 2412/2	Spatula	Bone	6,4	2,8	0,1 5		A	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, with a pen-nib point. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		
1	A 2212/2	Spatula	Bone	6,5	1,8	0,2		A	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, broken. One end with an elongated point, the other missing. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		
1	A 3467/5	Spatula	Bone	4,1	1,8	0,2		A	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, broken. One end with a pen-nib point. Polished on upper side, cancellous bone visible on the other, even if smoothed. Thick edge but quite smoothed. .		
1	A 2318/1	Spatula	Bone	7,2	2	0,3		A	57n		YADI N	Bone spatula, fragmentary. Point and part of the edges missing. One rounded end preserved. Polished on both sides and on the edge.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	A 2352/1	Spatula	Bone	6,5	1,5	0,2		A	57n			YADIN N	Bone spatula, broken. Triangular point and part of the central part preserved, but not the edge.		
1	A 3102/8	Spatula	Bone	2,3	2,4	0,2 5		A	57n			YADIN N	Fragment of a bone spatula.		

NEEDLES

Middle Bronze Age

1	B 5074		Bronze					B	3314, tomb	Yadin 1989: CXC VIII:14.			MB II	
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Late Bronze Age

1	F 850/1		Bronze					F	O6	Yadin 1989: CCXLIV:18		Thin needle shaft, probably incomplete.	MB II-LB I	
1	F 932/2		Bronze					F	O4	Yadin 1989: CCXLIV:19		long and thin needle, almost complete. Eye obtained perforating the upper part of the shaft, which is enlarged.	MB II-LB I	
1	H 1282		Bronze					H	2170	Yadin 1989: CCLXX:23, CCCXLIII:5		Complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB I (Str. 2)	
1	H 1012		Bronze					H	2167	Yadin 1989: CCLXX:24, CCCXLIII:3		Broken eye. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB I (Str. 2)	
1	H 770		Bronze					H	2119	Yadin 1989: CCLXXVIII:16, CCCXLIII:7		Complete, very thin. Eye obtained by perforation of the shaft, which is enlarged where the hole is done (probably when metal was still warm)	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	H 514		Bronze					H	2123	Yadin 1989: CCLXXVIII:17, CCCXLIII:2		Broken, eye not preserved	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 445/1		Bronze					K	5518	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:19.		Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1B)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	K 264/1	Bronze						K	5013a	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:20, CCCXLIII:8.		Long and thin shaft, both ends pointed.	LB II (Str. 1B)	
1	K 264/2	Bronze						K	5013a	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:21, CCCXLIII:6.		Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1B)	
1	K 264/3	Bronze						K	5013a	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:22, CCCXLIII:4.		Long and thick needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1B)	
1	K 264/4	Bronze						K	5013a	Yadin 1989: CCXCIV:23.		Both ends pointed and hole in the middle, probably a toggle pin.	LB II (Str. 1B)	
1	H 482	Bronze						H	2116	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:9.		Eye missing.	LB II (Str. 1b)	
5	K 265/2	bone, bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:10.		Needle case with 5 needles	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 265/2-1	Bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:10.		Needle from needle case. Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 265/2-2	Bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:11.		Needle from needle case. Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 265/2-3	Bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:12.		Needle from needle case. Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 265/2-4	Bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:13.		Needle from needle case. Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	K 265/2-5	Bronze						K	5010	Yadin 1989: CCCXLIII:14.		Needle from needle case. Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	
1	B 5011	Bronze						B	3284	Yadin 1989: CC:28.		Only part of shaft preserved, both ends missing.	LB II	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	41238/2	ivory							7050, building 7050, floor	Ben Tor 2017: 559.	No fig.		LB IIA-B (str. XIII)	
1	F 1037-1	Bronze						F	P4	Yadin 1960: CL:10, CXCVI:11		Needle, completed. Long and thin eye obtained perforating the shaft	LB II (Str. 1)	
1	C 7457	Bronze						C	6061	Yadin 1958: pl. LXXXVIII: 23, CLX:23		Needle, completed. Very long and quite thick. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB II (Str. 1a)	

Iron Age I

1	47217	Bronze							7717	Ben Tor 2012: 534, 536, fig. 10.5		Eye drilled	IA I (Str. XII-XI)	
1	B 4785	Bronze						B	3279	Yadin 1989: CCIV:13		Needle? Fibula? No eye visible, both ends pointed, bent in several points.	IA I (Str. XI)	
1	B 4642/1	Bronze						B	3279	Yadin 1989: CCIV:14		Needle? Fibula? No eye visible, both ends pointed, bent in several points.	IA I (Str. XI)	
1	B 4642/2	Bronze						B	3279	Yadin 1989: CCIV:15		Short needle, broken eye, rounded tip.	IA I (Str. XI)	
1	B 5148	Bronze						B	3283	Yadin 1989: CCV:8, CCCLV:18.		Short needle or ugly toggle pin. Eye in the middle of the shaft.	IA I (Str. XI)	

Iron Age II

1	B 4577/1	Bronze						B	3274	Yadin 1989: CCVII:32		Bronze shaft pointed at both ends, no trace of an eye	IA IIA (Str. X)	
1	B 4760	Bronze						B	3265	Yadin 1989: CCVII:33		Bronze shaft, rounded at one end, the other missing.	IA IIA (Str. X)	
1	B 5290	Bronze						B	3038d	Yadin 1989: CCXVI:21		Needle? Fibula? No eye visible, both ends pointed, bent in several points.	IA IIA (Str. IX)	
1	B 2447/1	Iron						B	3194	Yadin 1989: CCXXI:12		Thick needle, broken at one end. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	
1	B 1751/1	Bronze						B	3156	Yadin 1989: CCXXI:13		Long and thin needle, complete. Eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	IA IIC (Str. Vb)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	B 949/1	Bronze						B	3116A	Yadin 1960: CVI: 26.		Needle (?), completely bent	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	B 1239/1	Bronze						B	3117A	Yadin 1960: CVI: 27.		Needle (?), completely bent and fragmentary	IA IIC (Str. Va)	
1	B 4465	Bronze						B	3235	Yadin 1989, pl. CCXX:37.		Shaft with rounded end and the other missing.	IA IIC (Str. VI)	
1	A 22046	Bone/ivory	3,8	0,5x0,4				A2	L. 3208		fill	Bone/ivory point, very well crafted.	IA IIC (Str. V)	
1	M 74753	Bronze	6,1	0,15	0,5			M	L. 08-319 From cleaning winter wash			Thin bronze shaft with the upper part bent on itself to form a large eye.	IA IIC	
1	M 74193b	Bone	2,8	0,3				M	L. 09-312 M			Small bone point, probably part of a needle.	IA IIC	
1	L 32	Stone	8,6	1	0,4			L	L. 1001		YADIN	Needle (?) made of stone with a large and flat head, where a hole has been made.	IA II	

Unknown context

1	A 277	Bronze							D18 unclear provenance	Hazor V: 168, 169, fig. II.62,12.		Bronze needle, not clear how the eye has been fabricated		
1	M 77929	bone/ivory	5,6	0,35				M	L. 12-353			Thin bone shaft, probably part of a needle.		
1	M 77782	bone/ivory	6,4	0,25				M	L. 12-353			Thin bone shaft, probably part of a needle.		
1	M 34518	Bronze	7,5	0,15				M	L. 5565 M			Bronze needle, complete. Very well crafted. Eye obtained punching the upper part of the shaft.		
1	Unknown	Bronze	11,8	0,3	top 0,5x0,25						YADIN	Bronze needle, complete. Eye made by bending the upper part of the shaft on itself.		
1	Unknown	Bronze	10,2	0,5							YADIN	Bronze shaft, probably part of a needle.		
1	Unknown	Bronze	7,8	0,25							YADIN	Bronze shaft, probably part of a needle.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Area	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	A 5794	Bone	6,1	0,9	0,2 5			A				YADI N Needle broken towards the point. Large and flat.		
1	A 10112/9	Bone	5,2	0,5	0,4			A				YADI N Needle broken towards the point with small, rounded hole.		

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

BETH SHEAN

SPINDLES

1	27-10-524		bone						1251	James/McGovern 1993: 183, fig. 109.5.		Bone rod, not complete. One end is flat and the other missing. Incised decoration on the surface. Section irregular not rounded. Not tapering towards one end. It seems difficult that it could be used as a spindle.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	25-9-32		ivory						1002	James 1966: fig. 114. PPS II, I, pl. 31:46	P. 29-105-210	Bone or ivory rod, not complete. One end is rounded and the other seems broken. Incised decoration on the surface.	IA II	

SPINDLE WHORLS

Neolithic - Chalcolithic

1	33-10-1092	Dome	Limestone						below room 1881	Braun, Eliot. 2004. Early Beth Shan (strata XIX-XIII): G.M. Fitzgerald's Deep Cut on the Tell. : Page/Fig./Plate: 4.9/9	P.34-21-140		Chalcolithic/E B IA (Str. XVII)	
1	33-11-275 a	Discoid	Stone						1892		P.34-21-141		Chalcolithic/E B IA (Str. XVII)	
1	33-11-92	Discoid	Limestone						1896		P.34-21-143		Chalcolithic/E B IA (Str. XVII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	33-11-289a	Discoid	Limestone					pit N. of 1898		P.34-21-380		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-11-124a	Discoid	Limestone					below rooms 1895-1896	Braun 2004, 4.9/13	P.34-21-263		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-11-124b	Discoid	Stone					below rooms 1895-1896		P.34-21-264		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-11-226a	Discoid	Stone					1898		P.34-21-266		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-11-289a	Discoid	Limestone					1898		P.34-21-380		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-11-70a	Discoid	Stone					Pit W. of 1899		P.34-21-381		Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	
1	33-10-1092	Dome	Limestone					below room 1881	Braun 2004, 4.9/9	P.34-21-140		Chalcolithic/E B IA (Str. XVII)	
1	33-11-275a	Discoid	Stone					1892		P.34-21-141		Chalcolithic/E B IA (Str. XVII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	33-11-275b	Discoid	Stone					1892			P.34-21-142	Incomplete pierced from two sides.	Chalcolithic/EB IA (Str. XVII)	
1	33-11-92	Discoid	Limestone					1896	Braun 2004 4.9/14		P.34-21-143			
1	33-11-124c	ovoid	Stone					below rooms 1895-1896	Braun 2004, 4.8/10		P.34-21-265	Perforated pebble	Neolithic/Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)	

Early Bronze Age

1		Discoid	Limestone	0,5	nn	3,8	1,2	3,5	L 10961		M			
1	380236		Baked clay	0,9		3,5 x3,7		16,20 +x	L 38005	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 357.	M 2b	Pottery fragment of an object. Oblong and half preserved		
1	1435/457 o 14-1764	Discoid	Stone	0,7	4,2		0,7	17,56+x				Flat pebble with cylindrical hole. Broken		
1	181207	Discoid	Grey stone	1	3,8		2,7	19,78+x	10056	Mazar/Rotem 2012, 371 pl. 9.9:20		Gray stone disk. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole		
1	380094	Biconical	Baked clay	1,5	3,7		0,7	21,32	38002	Mazar/Rotem 2012, 371 pl. 9.9:16		Biconical spindle whorl. Almost complete. Ruined surface		
1	33-10-680b	Biconical	Red stone	1,2	3,2		0,6	15,7	1865	Beth Shan Exc. 1933, Level XIV, Room 1865.		Biconical spindle whorl. Red stone, well crafted and smooth. Nice elliptical hole. No wear traces.		341148
1	281137	Cylindrical?	Baked clay	1,3	4,1 x4,7		1,6	19,05	10056	Mazar/Rotem 2012, 354, fig. 9.2:1		Ring shaped object, roughly handmade, possibly a spindle whorl, complete.		
1	33-10-847	Discoid	Limestone						1847		P.34-20-939		EB I-II (Str. XV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	33-10-855	Cylindrical	Limestone					1877		P.34-20-940		EB I-II (Str. XV)	
1	33-11-792	Discoid	Limestone					below room 1931		P.34-20-704		EB Ib (Str. XIII)	

Middle Bronze Age

1		Discoid	Stone	1,1	3,3		0,4	13,45			Well crafted spindle whorl. White rough stone. External damaged surface. Hourglass hole		2008-1052
1		Discoid	Stone			14,4 x12,1xs 0,7	0,6	12,5+x			Fragment of spindle whorl, ruined. External surface looks polished. Well crafted hole		658261
1	103017/1	Discoid	Stone	1,1	2,7		0,2	9,5	10302	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:8	Complete spindle whorl. Dark stone and well crafted. Small hole. Bead?	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	2008-1041
1		Discoid	Stone	1	3,5 x3,8		1	20,4			Grey stone spindle whorl (basalt). Ovoid with hourglass hole		2008-1043
1		Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	3,1		1	22,26			Cylindrical basalt spindle whorl. Complete and pretty well crafted. Hourglass hole		2008-1042
1	658266	Discoid	Stone	1,2	3		0,5	7,7			Pebble spindle whorl. Perforated and smoothed. Broken		658266
1	785074	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,9		0,3	4,95	78514	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:4.	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Complete and partially ruined on the edges. Very damaged base. The hole is worn on the top not in the bottom.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	652631
1	285203	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,5		0,3	4,44	28533	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:5.	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Complete. On the base are clearly visible signs of polishing. On the side of the dome are visible signs of the lathe. The hole is worn on the top not in the bottom. The hole on the bottom is a bit larger than on the top (0,4)	LB I (Str. R-1b)	652639

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	485266	Dome	Bone	0,6	3,8		0,4	8,8 7+x			Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl, almost flat on the top. Very ruined surface. The hole tends to flare towards the base	MB II	652628
1	103042	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,5	3		0,7		10301	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:2.	Incomplete, convex, ring-shaped.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4a-b)	
1	103044	Lenticular	Limestone	1,2	2,9		0,7		10301	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:3.	Incomplete, polished surface. Drilled from both sides.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4a-b)	
1	983217	Discoid	Stone	0,8	4,7		0,7		88312	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:5.	Incomplete, chipped on the upper surface	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4b-5)	
1	781047	Discoid	Stone	0,6	3,4		0,6		78114	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:6.	Incomplete.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	
1	883036	Discoid	Calcite	1	3,3		0,5		88312	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:7.	Complete	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4b-5)	
1	885164	Dome	Bone	1,4	4,1		0,4	11, 23	79137	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.4:1.	Complete, polished on convex side.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	
1	285207	Dome	Bone	1,4	3,8		0,5	9,4 4	28533	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:2.	Complete, polished on convex side.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	
1	985266	Dome	Bone	0,6	3,6 5		0,5	8,7 7	98540	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:3.	Complete, polished on convex side. Worn surface	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4a-b)	
1	31-10-139a	Conical	ivory	1,1	2,7				1601		P.32-15-294	Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	31-10-139c	Dome	ivory	0,5	2			1601		P.32-15-296		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	
1	32-15-300	Button?	ivory	0,7	2,5			1648		P.32-15-300		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	
1	31-11-332	Dome	ivory	0,9	2,3			1655		P.32-15-305		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	
1	31-11-306	Dome	ivory	0,7	2,8			1614		P.32-15-306		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa-b)	
1	31-11-371	Conical	Steatite	1,4	2,2			1612		P.32-15-236		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa-b)	
1	31-11-331	Dome	ivory	0,8	2,2			1625-27		P.32-15-297		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	
1	33-11-320	Dome	Gypsum					in walls		P.34-20-110	Edge chipped.	Late MB IIb (Str. Xb)	
1	31-11-370	Dome	ivory	0,8	2,5			W of room 1612		P.32-15-298		Late MB IIb (Str. Xa-b)	
1	31-10-139b	Dome	ivory	0,5	2,6			1601		P.32-15-295	Top chipped.	Late MB IIb (Str. Xa)	

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

Late Bronze Age

1	885064	Dome	Bone	0,5	2,2		0,4	2,34	88518	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:8.		Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Complete. Very ruined surface. Decorated with radial incisions which branches near the edge. Made from the head of sheep/goat feworld.	LB I (Str. R-1b)	652638
1	285046	Dome	Bone	0,9	2,6			5,27	68123	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:7.		Complete, polished on both sides. Made from the head of a sheep feworld.	LB I (Str. R-1b)	
1	580599	Dome	Bone	0,5	2,5			3,4	58154	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 665, fig. 12.4:6.		Complete, chipped, polished on both sides. Made from the head of a sheep feworld. Worn around the central hole.	LB I (Str. R-1b)	
1	189091	Lenticular	Limestone	0,9	2,2		0,8		18913	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:11.		Incomplete, broken in half and chipped. Surface highly abraded.	LB I (Str. R-1b)	
1	580414	Discoid	Limestone	1	3,5		0,7		13,49	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:10.		Incomplete	LB I-II (Str. R-1a-2)	
1	I 3843	Cylindrical 1	Stone	1,7	3,2		0,4	30,49	L 1343		BT II	Cylindrical dark stone spindle whorl. On one of the bases a decoration made of concentric carved circles is present		
1	28-10-62	Conical	Limestone	1,7	4,2		0,4	16,96	1371	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.7.	BT II	Pottery fragment of an object, light. Conical spindle whorl. Complete. Wear/Fall damages near the top side of the hole. Rough incisions on the base, except for a kind of candelabrum	LB IIb (Str. VII)	I 3836
1		Discoid	Stone	1	3,5		0,6	12,4+x			BT	Disk spindle whorl. Red stone extremely ruined and broken. Cylindrical hole		2008-1049
1		Discoid	Stone	0,9	4,4		0,6	16,58+x			BT II	Disk spindle whorl. White stone scratched and half preserved. Well crafted and smoothed. Cylindrical hole		658268
1	285212	Discoid	Baked clay	1,1	4,5		0,8	27,8	28535	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 662, fig. 12.1:4)		Pottery fragment of an object. Disk spindle whorl. Complete except for a small notch. Well crafted. Cylindrical hole (it seems to be realised after firing)	LB I-II (Str. R-1)	2008-1047
1		Dome	Bone	0,6	2,5		0,3	3,52+x			BT II	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Partially broken. Ruined surface.		652640

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-10-811	Dome	ivory		2,1			1262	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.1, pl. 50d.	P.29-105-229	Small bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-868	Dome	Slate	0,5	2			1267	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.2.	P.29-107-771	Small steatite spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-185	Dome	Gypsum	1	4,3			1381	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.3.	P.29-107-806	Large alabaster spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shaped. Apparently not perfectly rounded	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-632	Dome	Steatite	1,2	2,6			1243	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.6.	P.29-107-769	Small steatite spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-207	Dome	Gypsum	1,1	5			1381	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.8.	P.29-107-805	Large alabaster spindle whorl, complete but chipped. Flat Dome shaped. Apparently not perfectly rounded. Chipped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-859	Dome	Gypsum					1262	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.9.	P.29-107-798	Large alabaster spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-225	Dome	Gypsum	1,5	4,3			1295	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.9.	P.29-107-800	Large alabaster spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-845	Conical	Steatite	1	2			1267	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.10.	P.29-107-770	Small steatite spindle whorl, complete. Conical shape.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-120	Conical	Steatite	1	2,2			1261	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.10.	P.29-107-772	Small steatite spindle whorl, complete. Conical shape.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-203	Dome	Gypsum	1,5	2,6			1383	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.11.	P.29-107-807	Small alabaster spindle whorl, almost complete. Dome shaped.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-80	Conical	Gypsum	1,2	2,9			1255	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.1.	P.29-107-802	Alabaster spindle whorl, complete. Conical shape with surface shaped as a sort of ring series.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	25-11-217	Conical	Steatite	1,4	2,4			1072	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.2.	P.29-107-756	Steatite spindle whorl, complete. Conical shape, base decorated with an incised circle.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-889	Button	Bone	0,9	2,7			1271	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.3.	P.29-105-231	Bone button, complete.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	25-11-342	Biconical	Steatite					1086	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.4.	P.29-107-757	Steatite spindle whorl, complete. Biconical shape, not perfectly symmetrical.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-150	Dome	Stone	1,1	4,7			1284		P.29-107-804	Hourglass perforation	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-10-811	Dome	ivory		2,1			1262		P.29-105-229		LB IIb (Str. VII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	28-10-51		Baked clay		5,2			1374		P.29-103-1066		LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-151b	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,8			1284		P.29-105-347		LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-151a	Discoid	Bone	0,5	2,5			1284		P.29-105-346	Disc shaped with boss	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-439b	Dome	Bone					1386	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.6.	Discarded	Bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shape, fire blackened.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	28-10-439a	Dome	Bone		3,2			1386	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.7.	P.29-105-194	Bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shape.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	27-11-219a	Dome	Bone					1295	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.8.		Bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shape.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	26-8-8d	Dome	Bone					1072	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.8.	P.29-105-349	Bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shape.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	26-11-2	Dome	Bone	0,75	2,5			1108	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.9.	P.29-105-324	Bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shape.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	26-8-25	Conical	Bone	0,7	1,8			1068	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 109.10.	P.29-105-232	Bone spindle whorl, complete. Conical shape	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	27-11-150	Dome	Stone	1,1	4,7			1284		P.29-107-804	Hourglass perforation	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	28-11-398	Conical	ivory		2,22			1392		P.29-105-189		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	29-105-183	Dome	ivory		2			1398		P.29-105-183		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-141	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,6			1401		P.29-105-184		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-251	Dome	ivory		3			1407		P.29-105-199	Incised circle on the base	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-8-11	Dome	ivory		2,2			1332		P.29-105-388		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-280	Dome	ivory		2,2			1385		P.29-105-196		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-11-30	Conical	Gypsum	1,2	2,9			1255		P.29-107-802		LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-9-46	Dome	Gypsum	0,8	3,9			1340		P.29-107-811		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-243	Dome	Sandstone	1,2	2,8			1401		P.29-107-778		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-16	Dome	ivory		2,57			1389		P.29-105-226	Top bearing incised decoration in four lines radiating from centre; at the ends of these radii incised chevrons.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-375	Dome	ivory		4,4			1395		P.29-105-187	Incised circle on bottom; chipped edges.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-419	Discoid	ivory		2,6			1392		P.29-105-237	Large hole.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-380	Dome	Bone		2,2			1396		P.29-105-446	Blackened by fire, highly polished	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-268	Conical	Serpentine					1385		P.29-107-776		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-9a	Dome	Serpentine	0,8	1,8			1400		P.29-107-777		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	31-9-162	Dome	Steatite	1,2	2,8			1559		P.32-15-237		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-104	Dome	ivory		2			1398		P.29-105-183		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	27-8-41	Dome	Gypsum	1,5	3,5			1170A		P.29-107-803		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	25-11-431	Dome	ivory	1,5				1088		P.29-105-256	Decorated by incised dots and circles.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-9-19	Conical	ivory		2,28			1332		P.29-105-387		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	27-11-245	Button?	Bone	0,6	1,45			1297		P.29-105-235	Bone button.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	28-11-85	Dome	ivory		2,8			1407		P.29-105-239		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-333a	Dome	ivory		3			1387		P.29-105-192		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-244	Dome	ivory		2,21			1401		P.29-105-186		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	28-10-271	Dome	ivory		2			1385		P.29-105-197		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-368	Discoid	ivory		2,9			1331		P.29-105-188		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-9-43	Dome	ivory		2,3			1340		P.29-105-386		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-139a	Dome	ivory		2,7			1407		P.29-105-198		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-139b	Conical	Bone		2,1			1407		P.29-105-233		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-441	Dome	ivory		2,4			1339		P. 29-105-238		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-9-237	Dome	Gypsum	0,5	2,3			1340		P.29-107-810	Blackened.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-337	Dome	Bone		3,9			1391		P.29-105-195		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-214	Dome	ivory		4,5			1410		P.29-105-185		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-417	Dome	Stone	1,3	5			1392		P.29-107-808		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-10-333b	Dome	ivory		2,2			1393		P.29-105-193	Half preserved.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-9-236	Dome	Limestone	1,8	2,4			1340		P.29-107-823	Flat base with several scratchings.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-179	Dome	ivory		3			1407		P.29-105-190	Roughly cut. Circle incised on the base.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	28-11-120	Dome	Bone		2,1			1398		P.29-105-447	Blackened by fire.	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	31-11-344	Conical	ivory	1,3	2,3					P.32-15-303	Top missing	LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	31-11-315	Dome	ivory	0,5	2,4					P.32-15-301		LB I-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	989130	Biconical	Baked clay	2,4	3		0,5	18,3	98920	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 159, ph. 6.3.	Complete.	LB IIb (Str. Q-2)	
1	989091	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,1		0,3	3,19	98913	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Ruined surface with lathe traces on the	LB IIb (Str. Q-2)	681878

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									2006: 160, fig. 6,2		side and sanding marks on the bottom. No wear traces visible.		
1	989082	Conical	Bone	0,5	2,3	0,3	2,44	98906	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 160, fig. 6,2		Conical bone spindle. Complete but broken in half. Sanded surfaces.	LB IIb (Str. Q-2)	681882

Iron Age I

1	28-10-427	Dome	ivory		2,5			1370		P.29-105-191		LB IIb-IA Ia (Str. VII)	
1	26-9-408	Dome	Gypsum					Tomb 211		P.29-107-813	Incised circle on top.	Early IA	
1	27-9-315	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,95			1214	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.4.	P.29-105-228	Large bone spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	IA I (Late Str. VII)	
1	27-12-143	Dome	Bone	0,65	2,5			1293	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 108.5.	P.29-105-230	Small bone spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shaped.	IA I (Late Str. VII)	
1	107174	Dome	Bone	0,6	3,5	0,4	7	88866	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 738, fig. 15.1:1.		Complete, polished. Head of a cow fewall. Extremely ruined base, wear signs on the top side of the hole	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	2014-2085
1	102124	Dome	Bone	0,95	2,7	0,4	6,4	10223	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 738, fig. 15.1:2.		Complete, polished. Chipped near the top hole. Concentric incised line along perimeter of base	IA Ia (Str. N-3a)	2014-2086
1	984174	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,2	nn	1,77+x	98435	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 738, fig. 15.1:3.		Incomplete. Almost half preserved. Head of a sheep/goat. Smoothed surfaces	IA Ia (Str. N-3a)	2014-2087
1	288312	Conical	Gypsum	2,2	3,2	0,8	30,8	18735	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 738, fig. 15.1:4.		Complete. Slightly chipped near top hole.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	
1	188153	Conical	Serpentine	0,9	1,4		3	98852	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-		Chipped on the basis, polished.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:6.				
1	987256	Dome	Basalt	1	2,3		8,9	98716	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:7.		Chipped on the basis, polished.	IA Ia (Str. S-3)	
1	887156	Cylindrica 1	Chalk	0,6	2		1,96	88711	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:8.		Chipped along edges.	IA Ia (Str. S-3a)	
1	987314	Lenticular	Chalk	1,2	5,4			98728	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:9.		Unfinished perforation. Chipped near edges. Very irregular.	IA Ia (Str. S-4-3)	
1	788107	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,2	4,3		0,7	78828	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:10.		Incomplete and chipped on both sides.	IA Ia (Str. S-3)	
1	102048/2	Cylindrica 1	Baked clay	1	4,4			10222	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:13.		Incomplete, perforation made from both sides before firing.	IA Ia (Str. N-3)	
1	107169/2	Biconical	Baked clay	3,5	3		20,6	10728a	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:14.		Complete, small part missing along crack. Found together with 107169/2	IA Ia (Str. S-3b)	
1	107169/1	Spherical	Baked clay	1,6	2,2			10728a	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:15.		Incomplete, with diagonal perforation. Low fired.	IA Ia (Str. S-3b)	
1	288317?	Conical	Gypsum	2,4	3,4		0,6	30,78			Complete spindle whorl made of gypsum. Irregular not smoothed and tilted. Centred hole, elliptical on the bottom (0,7)		2014-2088
1	104164	Dome	Steatite	1,3	3,2		0,3	16,62	10425	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739.	Dome-shaped steatite spindle whorl. Polished but slightly ruined. Wear traces at the top and at the bottom of the hole. Sanding marks on the base.	IA Ia (Str. N-3)	2014-2092
1	987256	Dome	Steatite	1,2	2,4		0,3x0,4	8,9			Dome-shaped steatite spindle whorl. Polished with some scratches. Sanding		2014-2091

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											marks on the base. Damaged on one side. Oval hole made from the base to the top		
1	182153	Conical	Stone	0,9	1,7		0,15	3			Conical dark stone spindle whorl. Polished. Flared hole at the base. Sanding marks on the base. Too small to be a spindle whorl		2014-2090
1	107169/2	Biconical	Baked clay	3,5	3		0,3	20,78			Biconical spindle whorl. Oblong with a slightly flared hole. Partially broken. The hole is damaged.		2014-2099
1	286321	Dome	Limestone	1,9	3,7		nm	11,91 +x	L 28636 Stratum P-7 Building 28636	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 476, fig. 13.3:8.	Fragment of bone (or limestone) spindle whorl. Broken in half, dome is missing. Cylindrical hole. Sanding marks on the bottom.		688695
1		Discoid	Stone	1,1	4,6		0,6	21,75 +x			Pebble spindle whorl. Perforated and ruined. Hourglass hole		2014-2096
1	788107	Discoid	Stone	1,4	4,1		0,7	32,78 +x			Pebble spindle whorl. Perforated and ruined. Hourglass hole		2014-2095
1	987314	Discoid	Stone	1,4	5,3x4 ,7		nm	23,3			Pebble spindle whorl. Perforated and ruined. unfinished hole. White and light stone		2014-2094
1	887387	Cylindrical 1	Gypsum ?	1,1	2,4		0,6	5,95			Cylindrical gypsum spindle whorl. Almost complete. Deeply engraved decoration on the side. Ring motif.		2014-2097
1		Conical	Gypsum	0,7	1,7		0,4	1,64			Conical gypsum spindle whorl (?). Broken on the top. Too small to be a spindle whorl. Cylindrical hole off-centre		2014-2089
1	788202	Lenticular	Bone	0,6	2,3		0,4	3,16	78841	Panitz-Cohen et al. 2009:	Lenticular bone spindle whorl. Complete. Wear traces near the hole, on the undecorated side. Engraved decoration consisting in a couple of parallel lines orthogonal to another couple of parallel lines. Probably made from the head of a cow fewall.	IA Ia (Str. S-3)	2014-2154
1		Button	Bone	0,8	2,7		0,25	3,76			Bone button. Complete and polished on the lathe on both sides. Slightly elliptical hole		681881
1	150686	Button	Bone	0,4	1			0,2			Small bone button. Too small to be a spindle whorl.		681883

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	1989-1881	Conical	Bone	0,8	3,1		0,25	5,8			Conical bone spindle whorl. Extremely ruined surface. Flared hole near the base. No wear traces		1989-1881
1	78731	Button	Bone	0,7	2			78740	Panitz-Cohen et al. 2009:		Bone button, complete but chipped. Polished surface. Made from a metacarpal/metatarsal of a sheep/goat.	IA Ia (Str. S-3b)	
1	31-11-321	Dome	ivory					1585	James 1966: fig. 101	Discarded	Small ivory spindle whorl, complete. Flat Dome shaped.	IA I (Late Str. VI)	
1	31-10-469	Cylindrical 1	Gypsum	1,5	3,1			1557	James 1966: fig. 114.	P.32-15-231	Large hole, complete. Incised concentrical line near the edge.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	28-9-191	Lenticular	ivory		3			1349		P.29-105-240	Chipped.	IA I (Str. VI)	
1	28-9-192	Conical	Bone		2,2			1349		P.29-105-241		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	26-9-56	Conical truncated	Bronze	1,3	1,9			1101		P.29-108-461		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	27-11-95		Baked clay					1280		P.29-103-1077		IA I (Str. VI)	
1	25-10-327	Conical	Gypsum	1,8	2,7			1044		P.29-107-790	Piercing incomplete.	IA I (Str. VI)	

Iron Age II

1	887387	Cylindrical 1	Chalk	1,1	2,5			88721	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:12.		Complete, restored. Decorative incisions.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	
1	988208	Lenticular	Gypsum	0,6	1,8		0,8	1,65	18735	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 739, fig. 15.1:5.	Complete. Perforation off centre. Too light	IA IIA (Str. S-1b-2)	
1	286354	Cylindrical 1	Limestone	2,7	3,7		0,8	43,86	L 28641	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.3:6.	Cylindrical limestone spindle whorl. Complete and well crafted. Signs of burning.	IA IIB (Str. P7)	2009-1025
1	384250	Cylindrical 1	Gypsum	2,5	3,2		1,5	35,35	L 38401	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 476,	Complete gypsum spindle whorl. Very ruined. Carved decoration consisting in	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1027

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											some wavy lines enclosed between two parallel incisions.		
1	384191/2	Conical	Gypsum	1,9	3,2x3,5		1	23,78	L 38401	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 476, fig. 13.3:9.	Complete spindle whorl made of gypsum. Irregular not smoothed and tilted. Hole slightly off-centre, elliptical on the bottom	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1024
1	28-9-218a	Dome	Serpentine	0,8	2				1350	James 1966: fig. 110.	P. 29-107-775	Small serpentine spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	IA II (Str. V)
1	28-9-218b	Dome	Sandstone	1,6	2,7				1350	James 1966: fig. 110.	P. 29-107-774	Quite large sandstone spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-2	Cylindrical	Gypsum	1,6	2,5				1002	James 1966: fig. 114.	P. 29-107-787	Shape not clear. Large hole, complete.	IA II (Str. V)
1	27-9-211	Discoid	Black stone	1,3	2,8				4	James 1966: fig. 114.	P.29-107-767	Shape not clear. Complete.	IA II (Str. V)
1	3165	Dome	Serpentine	2,1	4,4				48	James 1966: fig. 114.	P.29-107-715	Dome shaped with flattened top.	IA II (Str. V)
1	26-11-485	Dome	Gypsum	2	3,4				1075		P.29-107-793		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-11-580	Dome	Gypsum	1,5					1080		P.29-107-791		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-361	Dome	Gypsum	2,5	4				1020		P.29-107-785		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-362	Dome	Steatite	2,2	3,8				1020		P.29-107-755		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-139	Dome	Limestone	1,3	3,2				1011		P.29-107-750		IA II (Str. V)
1	28-9-217	Dome	Gypsum	1	2,7				1350		P.29-107-809		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-70	Dome	Limestone	2	3,9				1005	James 1966: fig. 114.	P.29-107-753	Limestone spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	IA II (Str. V)
1	27-9-71	Discoid	Gypsum	1,9	6				1183		P.29-107-801	Concave base	IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-231	Dome	Stone	1,8	3,7				1012		P.29-107-754		IA II (Str. V)
1	25-10-7	Conical truncated	Gypsum	1,5	2,7				1027		P.29-107-789	Hollow base	IA II (Str. V)
1	25-9-147	Dome	Stone	1,6	4,8				1011		P. 29-107-780	Blackened	IA II (Str. V)

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-9-175	Dome	Stone	1	2,8			1183		P.29-107-779		IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-268	Dome	Stone	0,8	1,6			1013		P.29-107-752	Polished	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-240	Dome	Limestone	1,9	3,7			1012		P.29-107-751	Base chipped	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-534	Conical	Gypsum	1,3	2,5			1021		P.29-107-788	Convex base	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-140	Dome	Limestone	2,2	2,9			1011		P.29-107-764		IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-212	Dome	Gypsum	1,4	3,4			1010		P.29-107-812	Wide rectangular piercing	IA II (Str. V)	
1	27-9-48		Baked clay	2,6	6			1183		P.29-103-1067		IA II (Str. V)	
1	3232	Dome	Gypsum	0,9	2,3			65		P.29-107-782		IA II (Str. V)	
1	27-9-38	Dome?	Gypsum	2,4	3,5			1183		P.29-107-822	Blackened	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-493	Dome	Gypsum	2	3,3			1021a		P.29-107-818	Hollow base	IA II (Str. V)	
1	30-11-136	Dome	ivory	1,8	3			1536		P.31-50-197		IA II (Str. V)	
1	30-12-16		Sandstone	2,1	4,5			1542		P.31-50-329	Convex base, sides contracting to a flattened top.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-239	Biconical	Baked clay	2,5	3,2			1012		P.29-103-1075		IA II (Str. V)	
1	286250	Dome	Limestone	1,6	2,5	0,5	14,31	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.3:7)		Dome-shaped limestone spindle whorl. Complete and polished. Cylindrical hole slightly flared at the bottom. Small wear traces at the top of the hole	IA Iib (Str. P7)	2009-1026
1	386247	Discoid	Limestone	0,9	3,5	0,9	10,19	L 38607	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.3:5		Incomplete, broken in half and chipped.	IA Iib (Str. P8)	
1	26-11-290	Cylindrical 1	Gypsum					1135	James 1966: fig. 118. PPS II, I, 39:16.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of gypsum. Outer edge incised with hatched line decoration between horizontal line borders.	IA Iib (Str. IV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	26-11-420	Cylindrica 1	Gypsum	1,5	3,5			1155	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-107-829	Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of gypsum. Outer edge incised with hatched line decoration between horizontal line borders.	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	25-9-45	Cylindrica 1	Gypsum					1147	James 1966: fig. 118.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of gypsum. Outer edge incised with hatched line decoration between horizontal line borders.	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-479	Dome	Gypsum	1,1	2,6			1152	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-107-796	Small gypsum spindle whorl, complete. Dome shaped.	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-32	Dome	Sandstone	1,2	3			1510		P.31-50-338		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-171	Dome	Steatite	0,9	2,2			1125		P.29-107-760		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-264	Dome	Steatite	2,5	3,7			1136		P.29-107-766		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-476	Dome	Limestone	1,3	3			East of 1152		P.29-107-794		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-19	Dome	Limestone	2,6	4,2			1109		P.29-107-765		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-289	Dome	Gypsum	1,8	3,7			1135		P.29-107-792	Chipped	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-28a	Dome	Gypsum	1,7	3,2			1507		P.31-50-331		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-24b	Dome	Steatite	1	2,9			N.W. of room 1507		P.31-50-334		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-24a	Dome	Limestone	2,3	3,9			N.W. of room 1507		P.31-50-328	Chipped	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-25b	Conical	Steatite	1,3	2,5			N.W. of room 1507		P.31-50-341		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	30-11-24c	Dome	Steatite	1	2,7			N.W. of room 1507		P.31-50-335	The upper surface bears two incised concentric circles	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	788010	Cylindrica 1	Marl	1,2	4,8		0,7	21,8	78802	Panitz- Cohen/Yahalom-	Complete but chipped and faceted	Topsoil	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									Mack 2009: 740, fig. 15.1:11.				

PERFORATED SHERDS

Neolithic - Chalcolithic

1	33-11-289a	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Pit N. of Room 1898	Braun, 2004, fig. 4.9/16	P. 34-21-376		Neolithic/ Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)
1	33-11-289b	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Pit N. of Room 1898		P.34-21-376		Neolithic/ Chalcolithic (Str. XVIII)

Early Bronze Age

1	281338	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	nn	1 3,4x2	nn	6,43+ x	L 28121	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356, fig. 9,2:6		Perforated sherd.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	
1	109218	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	nn	1,8x2 ,8	0,3	3,12+ x	L 10977	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356, fig. 9,2:7		Perforated sherd, decorated with reddish band motif.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	281202	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	nn	6,1x3 ,8	0,9	21,95 +x	L 28110	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 354, fig. 9,2:3		Perforated sherd. Well rounded	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	380553	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	4,6		0,6	17,25	L 38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356, fig. 9,2:4.		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	847170
1	380212	Prf. sherd	Pottery							Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Perforation started from both sides but not finished.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	181037/9	Prf. sherd	Pottery							Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Perforation started from both sides but not finished.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	
1	380466	Prf. sherd	Pottery							Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356		Perforated sherd, well rounded. Unfinished hole.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	281286	Prf. sherd	Pottery						Mazar/Rotem 2012: 356		Perforated sherd, hole made starting from both sides but almost cylindrical.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	

Middle Bronze Age

1	983010	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,2	4,3		1	15,2+ x	88315	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 661, fig. 12.1:2	BM II	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Well rounded and cylindrical hole. Scratches on the top. No wear signs.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4b)	658262
1	31/11/72A	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,6	4x3,7		0,5	9,38	Below Thut Level			Perforated sherd with two hourglass holes. Distance 0,3		1932-43
1	883050/5	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1	5,1x5 ,5		nn	32	88316	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 661, fig. 12.1:1)		Perforated sherd, well rounded and smoothed. Hole unfinished and made starting from only one side.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4b)	2008-1045
1		Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,6		0,3	13,49			BM II	Perforated sherd, roughly cut with sharp edges. Slightly oval and hourglass hole		2008-1044
1	883021	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,7	3x3,2		0,7	8,25	78302	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 661, fig. 12.1:3)		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded and smoothed. Hole started from one side but left unfinished.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	2008-1048
1	33-9-654	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1080		P. 34-20-142	Perforated sherd.	MB IIb (Str. XI)	

Late Bronze Age

1	189195	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,9	3,8		0,4	12,48	18954	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 661, fig. 12.1:5)		Perforated sherd, complete. Roughly rounded with unfinished edges. Hole drilled from both sides.	LB I A-B (Str. R-2)	2088-1044?
1	27-10-622	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1244	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 120.1.		Perforated sherd, complete, well rounded with cylindrical hole.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-51	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1374	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 120.2.		Perforated sherd, complete, roughly rounded with hourglass perforation.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-249	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5,2				1384	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 120.3.	P.29-103-1065	Perforated sherd, complete, roughly rounded with cylindrical perforation.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	

Iron Age I

1	25-10-202	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1021 Seti I temple		P.29-103-1072	Perforated sherd, roughly rounded	IA Ia	
1	102048/7	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,1	4,5		nn	10,42 +x			FE I	Perforated sherd, half preserved. Well rounded. Hourglass hole.		2014-2098

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

Iron Age II

1	186212	Prf. sherd	Pottery	1,5	6,2		0,7	59,48	L 18601 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.3:1.		Perforated sherd, complete. Well rounded. Cylindrical but diagonal hole.	IA IIb (Str. P-7)	2009-1020
1	888283	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,7x3 ,3		0,4	10,73	L 88862	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 475, fig. 13.3:3.		Perforated sherd, roughly cut. Cylindrical hole.	IA IIA (Str. S-1b)	2009-1022
1	386322	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,7x3 ,3		0,4	13,63	L 38626	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.3:4, 13.11c.		Perforated sherd, quite well rounded. Hole cylindrical but slightly diagonal, made starting perforation from both sides.	IA IIb (Str. P-8b)	2009-1021
1	286177/50	Prf. sherd	Pottery	0,8	7,4		0,5	52,5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.11b.		Perforated sherd, chipped. Quite well rounded. Cylindrical hole.	IA IIb (Str. P-7)	2009-1023
1	25-10-87	Prf. sherd	Pottery		4,5				1026		P.29-103-1071		IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-11-71	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1066		P.29-103-1069	Perforated sherd, well rounded.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-373	Prf. sherd	Pottery						1020		P.29-103-1073		IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-391	Prf. sherd	Pottery		3x3,5				1018		P.29-103-1074		IA II (Str. V)	
1	25-9-421	Prf. sherd	Pottery		5,5				1021		P.29-103-1076	Perforated sherd, cut from a base of a vessel.	IA II (Str. V)	

SPINNING BOWLS

Late Bronze Age

1	25-11-569		Pottery						1088	Fitzgerald 1930: pl. 41.29. James/McGovern 1993: fig. 27.11.		Base of a spinning bowls with two loops inside.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	25-10-333		Pottery					1051	Fitzgerald 1930: pl. 44.11..	Early Seti Level	Base of a spinning bowls with two loops inside.		
1	27-10-901		Pottery					1271	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 27.10.	P.29-102-488.	Spinning bowl, fragmentary. Part of the rim, base and two internal loops preserved.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-11-117		Pottery	6,5	base 7,5	14,8x 11,4	Anell o l 8,2xs 2,1xh 3,3		Exc. 1928 Level IX, Room 1403		Fragment of the base of a spinning bowl. One loop is fully preserved, partially the other. Simple bowl with thick walls. The loop is hand-made and well crafted. Wear signs on the external side of the loop.	LB Ib-IIA (Str. IX)	I. 3877
1	28-10-163°		Pottery					1381	James/McGovern 1993: 60.		Not drawn. From the same locus also two alabaster spindle whorls and three clay spools.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-108		Pottery	5,2	8,4			1273	James/McGovern 1993: 63.			LB IIb (Str. VII)	

Iron Age I

1	888237/4		Pottery					88855	Panitz-Cohen 2012: 437, fig. 13.4:2.		Spinning bowl, fragmentary. Part of the base and two internal loops preserved.	IA I (Str. S-3a)	
1	888237/6		Pottery					88855	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 46.8		Spinning bowl, fragmentary. Part of the base and two internal loops preserved.	IA I (Str. S-3a)	
1	108060/10		Pottery					10816	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 46.9		Spinning bowl, fragmentary. Part of the base and two internal loops preserved.	IA I (Str. S-3a)	
1	108060 e 108068		Pottery			L 10 x diam 23,4		L 10816			Spinning bowl, made of different fragments. Incomplete. Rim and part of a loop are preserved.		
1	108060/13 e 17		Pottery	5,3		19,5		10816			Spinning bowl, made of two parts : base and part of the side wall. On the base parts of one loop preserved.		821683
1	184257/5		Pottery					18431	Panitz-Cohen 2012: 487, fig. 13.4:3.		Spinning bowl, fragmentary. Part of the base and two internal loops preserved.	Mixed	
1	31-10-452		Pottery					1589	James 1966: pl.50	Jerusalem		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-10-9	Pottery						1224	James 1966: fig.49	Discarded	Three grooves near rim on the external side.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-10-453a	Pottery						1589	James 1966: fig.49	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-10-453b	Pottery						1589	James 1966: fig.49	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-11-57c	Pottery						1586	James 1966: fig.49	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-11-298a	Pottery						1585	James 1966: fig.49	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-11-380a	Pottery						1709	James 1966: fig.51	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	33-9-259	Pottery	9	19				1728	James 1966: fig.53	Jerusalem		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-10-474	Pottery						1185	James 1966: fig.55	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-9-158	Pottery						1195	James 1966: fig.55	Discarded		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	25-10-373	Pottery						1053	James 1966: fig.56	P.29-102-489.	Two loop handles inside.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-11-298a	Pottery	7,6		base 7,4 x 9,2. L 13,1	loop l 10,7x h 4,2 x s 2,4		Exc. 1931 Area 1585 Level VI			Part of the base of a spinning bowl. One of the two loops is well preserved. Well crafted. Clay ware rich of inclusions. Internal slip. Roughly burnished on the external side. Smoothed internal surface. Wear traces on the top of the loop, its surface appears quite shiny.	IA I	32297
1	28-9-159	Pottery	3,8	base 7	l. 13,3x 11,8	anello l 10,9x 1,8for o, s2,3, h3,5		Exc. 1928, Level VI, Room 1343			Fragment of the base of a spinning bowl with 2 preserved loops. Flat base, fine ware, internal slip also on the loops. Traces of hand-working are visible inside. Wide bowl. Wear traces inside the loops and shiny surface and one deep groove due to rubbing.	IA I	I 3830
1		Pottery	4,8	base 9,5	16,7x 14	h max 4,7		Under VI 63			Fragment of a spinning bowl. Flat base with the joints of the 2 loops visible. Irregular surface. The area beneath one of the loops is polished.		I 6005

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	33-9-259	Pottery	11	14,2				Exc. 1933 Level VI-VII, Room 1728			Fragment of a spinning bowl with two loops, one of which is complete. Side wall and edges are preserved. Pretty wide bowl. Signs of burning on the surface.	LB II – IA I	34976
1	188196/6	Pottery	3,1	14,7		2,8	L 10822	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 25.13	Ash and debris layers related to oven 10821. No other textile tools from this locus		Base and side wall of a spinning bowl. Two loops still preserved. One loop has grooves due to rubbing of fibres. The other is broken and fixed. Encrusted surface	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	816560
1	188196/3	Pottery	5	15,5		3,3	L 10822	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 25.14			Base and side wall of a spinning bowl. Two loops still preserved. On both loops grooves due to rubbing of fibres are visible.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	816561
1	104211	Pottery	5,5	11,5		3	L 10414 N-3b				Base and side wall of a spinning bowl. Two loops of which one still preserved. On the complete loop grooves due to rubbing of fibres are visible. Bowl made of different fragments.		813030
1	104041/1	Pottery	3,1 rim	6,5	3,7 loop 1,8		L 10415 N-3a				Fragment of a spinning bowl base. One loop is preserved. Wear traces are visible on the loop		813791
1	787346/1	Pottery	4,3	9		3,5 inner 1,8	78722	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 396, pl. 56.			Fragment of a spinning bowl base. One loop is preserved. Wear traces are visible on the loop	IA Ia (Str. S-3a)	823967
1	288053	Pottery	9,6			2,6x1,4	28811	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 383, pl. 49.			Part of the base, side wall and edge of a spinning bowl. One loop and part of the second are preserved. No wear traces are visible on the loop. On the external side are visible impressions.	IA Ia (Str. S-3a)	821733
1	288120	Pottery	10,2	22,6		2,9hx 11,11 x1,3f buco	28831	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 383, pl. 49.			Spinning bowl made of different fragments. Loops have been rebuilt (not original parts).	IA Ia (Str. S-3a)	821732

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	188297/6	Pottery	4,2		15	h 3,5, diam 21 11,3		L 18832, East- West Street	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 346, pl. 31.		Fragment of a spinning bowl. The base, part of the side wall and 2 loops are preserved. Deep wear traces on the loops, on both directions.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	817006
1	388087/1	Pottery	4,2	9		h3,2x 1,8for oxl6		38819	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 410, pl. 63.		Fragment of a spinning bowl. The base, part of the side wall and one loop are preserved. No wear traces.	IA Ia (Str. S-3a)	834262
1	988121/4	Pottery	5,5	7,8		h3,2x 1,8for oxl5, 7		88866	Panitz-Cohen 2009: 348, pl. 32		Part of a spinning bowl, made of different fragments. The base, part of the side wall and 2 broken loops are preserved. The area beneath one loop presents a deep slot. There is a spike under the base which destabilise the bowl.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	817031
1	187221/1	Pottery						18734	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 20.21		Wear marks on the inner part of the loops.	IA Ia (Str. S-5)	
1	687022/10	Pottery	4,3	base 7,3		l6,8x h3xfo ro1,4		68709	Panitz-Cohen 2009: pl. 69.3.		Fragment of a spinning bowl. The base, a loop broken in half and the joints of the other loop are preserved.	IA Ib (Str. S-2)	834481

LOOM WEIGHTS

Middle Bronze Age

1	33-11-346a	Conical	Baked clay	11	7,2		0,5	596			Baked clay loom weight. Conical shape	MB IIb (Lev. XB)	341285
1	33-11-346b	Conical	Clay							P.34-20-99	Baked clay loom weight. Conical shape	MB IIb (Lev. XB)	
1	985343	Conical	Baked clay	10,6	8	5,4	0,8	543	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668, fig. 12.5:5	BM	Baked clay loom weight. Conical shape but pretty flatted. Regular base. Well crafted hole		08-1066
1		Conical	Clay	9,8	5	4,5	0,6	172+ x			Incomplete conical clay loom weight. Well preserved all along its length, but a slice is missing and consumed. Small and cylindrical hole		08-1064

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	105378	Conical	Clay	8,4	6,2		0,7	305,3 2	10572	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 666, fig. 12.5:1.	Complete, unbaked clay. Poorly preserved.	MB II (Str. R-5-7)	
1	883082	Conical	Clay	8,1	6		0,5	269,8 6	88312	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668, fig. 12.5:2.	Complete, unbaked clay. Poorly preserved.	MB IIb (Str. R-4b-5)	
1	580190	Conical	Clay	9,8	5,3	4,9	0,5		58054	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668.	Incomplete, made of unfired clay.	MB IIb (Str. R-4b-5)	
1	783032	Conical	Clay	9,1	7,4	6,8	0,4	436,7 3	78304	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668, fig. 12.5:3.	Complete, made of fired clay, very friable.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	
1	783130	Conical	Clay	7,9	7,4	6,8	0,4	436,7 3	78335	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668, fig. 12.5:4.	Complete, made of well fired clay. Top slightly chipped, hole not joining from the two sides.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-3)	
1	985343	Conical	Clay	10,6	8,2	5,4	0,8	545,9 2	98542	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 668, fig. 12.5:5.	Complete, made of well fired clay. Slightly convex at the height of hole.	Late MB IIb (Str. R-4b)	
1	105133	Conical	Clay	10,5	5,1		0,4	267,0 9	98542	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 669, fig. 12.5:6	Complete, made of well fired clay. Slightly convex at the height of hole.	MB IIb (Str. R-5b)	08-1063
1	31-11-208		Clay						1627		P.32-15-211 Flat base, sides contracting slightly to a flat knob top which is pierced horizontally.	MB IIb (Lev. XB)	

Late Bronze Age

15	27-11-200	Spool	Clay	max.8 min 7	max.5 min 4				1287	James/McGovern 1993: 188, fig. 118.2a-b.	P.29-103-1056 At least fifteen spool shaped loom weights made of unbaked clay. Published as dumbbell objects. Two examples drawn. One is complete, the other partially broken. One specimen smaller than the other (3.5x3 cm).	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
3	28-9-291	Spool	Clay	10,5	6				1353	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 115.4a-c.	Spool shaped loom weights made of unbaked clay. Published as bread models.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-29	Spool	Clay	10,5	6				1372	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 115.5.	Spool shaped loom weight made of unbaked clay. Published as a bread model.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	25-11-215	Spool	Clay	10,5	6			1068	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 115.6.	P.29-103-1057	Spool shaped loom weight made of unbaked clay. Published as a bread model.	LB Iib (Str. VII)	
1	28-10-198a	Spool	Clay	10,5	6			1381	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 115.7.	P.29-103-1060	Spool shaped loom weight made of unbaked clay. Published as a bread model. They were not found in tombs.	LB Iib (Str. VII)	
1	28-11-402a	Pear shaped	Gypsum	9,3	7			1392		P.29-107-620		LB Ib-IIA (Lev. IX)	
1	28-11-402b	Pear shaped	Gypsum	9,5	7,5			1392		P.29-107-619		LB Ib-IIA (Lev. IX)	
1	28-11-402c	Pear shaped	Gypsum	9,2	5,7			1392		P.29-107-618		LB Ib-IIA (Lev. IX)	
1	28-11-402d	Pear shaped	Gypsum	9	7			1392		P.29-107-621		LB Ib-IIA (Lev. IX)	
1	27-11-236	Spherical	Baked clay					1291		P.29-103-745		LB Iib (Lev. VIII)	
1	27-8-40	Doughnut	Clay					1170A		29-103-712C		LB Iib (Lev. IX)	
1	27-8-40	Conical	Clay					1170A		29-103-712A		LB Iib (Lev. IX)	
1	27-8-40	Conical	Clay					1170A		29-103-712B		LB Iib (Lev. IX)	

Iron Age I

1	187205	Spool	Clay	6,7	5			78739	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: fig. 16.2.	Found in a secondary context	Incomplete, cylindrical shape with slightly convex sides. Poorly fired.	Str. S-3-2	
1	28-9-164	Spool	Clay					1345	James 1966: fig. 105.	P.29-103-1058	Incomplete. Cylindrical shape with slightly convex sides.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-10-451	Spool	Clay					1196	James 1966: fig. 105.	P.29-104-79	15 scarab impressions with hieroglyphs signs for imenyt "daily offering".	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-10-452	Spool	Clay					1201	James 1966: fig. 105.	P.29-104-80	6 scarab impressions with illegible signs. Flattened sphere?	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	28-10-216	Spool	Clay					1343	James 1966: fig. 105.	P.29-103-1059	Spool, complete. Cylindrical shape with convex side and a flat base, while the other seems more rounded.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	28-9-124	Spherical	Clay					1343		P.29-103-727		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-9-243	Oval	Gypsum	8,2	7,4			1212		P.29-107-575		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-9-200	Spherical	Clay					1201		P.29-103-721	Baked clay, partly bored	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	27-9-512	Spherical	Baked clay					1224		P.29-103-723		IA Ia (Lev. VI)	

Iron Age II

13	26-8-189	Pear shaped	Basalt					1084	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
2	26-11-496	Pear shaped	Basalt					1080	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
3	26-11-216	Pear shaped	Limestone					1126	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
2	25-11-73	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1066	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-9-9	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1076	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
4	25-10-394	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1048	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
17	25-10-418	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1045	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	25-10-417	Pear shaped	Stone					1045	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
8	25-10-364	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1046	James 1966: fig. 110.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
20	25-10-396	Spherical	Clay					1045	James 1966: fig. 110.			IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
12	25-10-365	Spherical	Clay					1046	James 1966: fig. 110.			IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
15	25-10-395	Spherical	Clay					1046	James 1966: fig. 110.			IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	25-9-61	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1001	James 1966: fig. 114.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	25-9-69	Spherical	Clay					1005	James 1966: fig. 114.			IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	25-9-37	Pear shaped	Gypsum					1004	James 1966: fig. 114.		Horizontally perforated	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-9-255	Spherical	Clay					1211		P.29-103-742		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-906	Spherical	Clay					1265		P.29-103-725		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-906	Discoid	Clay					1265		P.29-103-719		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-861a	Spherical	Clay					1265		P. 29-103-753		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-861b	Conical	Baked clay					1265		P.29-103-711A		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-861b	Conical	Baked clay					1265		P.29-103-711B		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-880	Spherical	Baked clay					1265		P. 29-103-704		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3162	Pear shaped	Gypsum	8,2	3,7			51		P.29-107-588		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3598	Pear shaped	Gypsum	8,3	6			48		P.29-107-612		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3655	Pear shaped	Limestone	7,5	7			300		P.29-107-613		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3631	Pear shaped	Gypsum	8,6	8			21		P.29-107-614		IA Ib-IIA	
1	3134	Pear shaped	Gypsum	5,5	4			39		P. 29-107-601		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3632	Pear shaped	Gypsum	6,5	5,8			21		P.29-107-608		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	3597	Pear shaped	Gypsum	7,5	5,5			48		P.29-107-610		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3135	Pear shaped	Gypsum	6,2	5,3			29		P.29-107-602		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3623	Pear shaped	Gypsum	8,2	6,5			21		P.29-107-606		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3161	Pear shaped	Gypsum	12	7			51		P.29-107-593		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3231	Pear shaped	Gypsum	10	8			65		P. 29-107-598		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3630	Pear shaped	Gypsum	9	5,5			21		P.29-107-607		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3619	Spherical	Clay					22		P.29-103-739		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3620	Spherical	Clay					22		P.29-103-741		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3163	Spherical	Clay					51		P.29-103-715		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3621	Spherical	Clay					22		P.29-103-737		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3654		Baked clay					299		P.29-103-731		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3617	Spherical	Clay					4		P.29-103-750	Poorly baked clay	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3628		Clay					21		P.29-103-736		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	3626	Spherical	Clay					21		P.29-103-716		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-11-109	Spherical	Clay					1269		P.29-103-744		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-905	Pear shaped	Gypsum	7,3	5,2			1265		P.29-107-617		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	27-10-879	Pear shaped	Gypsum	7,5	6			1265		P.29-107-616		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	
1	26-11-404	Doughnut	Basalt					1076		P.29-107-662		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	25-10-90		Baked clay					1026		P.29-103-703		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-9-25		Baked clay					1183		P.29-103-748		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	28-10-336	Conical	Baked clay					1389		P.29-103-717		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-10-904	Conical	Baked clay					1265		P.29-103-718		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-11-43	Spherical	Baked clay					1265		P.29-103-722		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-9-480	Spherical	Baked clay					22		P.29-103-724		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-9-238	Spherical	Baked clay					1211		P.29-103-743		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-10-881	Spherical	Baked clay					1265		P.29-103-752		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-10-862	Discoid	Clay					1265		P.29-103-749.1		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	27-10-862	Discoid	Clay					1265		P.29-103-749.2		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	26-11-157	Spherical	Clay					1116		P.29-103-747A		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	26-11-157	Spherical	Clay					1116		P.29-103-747B		IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	25-9-11	Pear shaped	Baked clay					1003		P. 29-103-710	Poorly baked clay	IA Ib-IIA (Lev. V)		
1	30-12-101	Conical	Baked clay	9,6	7		0,8	534			Conical baked clay loom weight. Complete and pretty well crafted, except for its base. On the hole is visible the slot used to fix the thread.		1 9688	
1	30-11-51	Spherical	Baked clay	4,8	4,8		0,5	89,9	Room 1509		Stratum V - Fe I	Spherical baked clay loom weight. Roughly crafted	1 9664	
1	887239	Spherical	Clay	4,3	5,3		0,8	111,7	L 88721	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 476, fig. 13.4:5.		Doughnut shaped, complete. Very much corroded.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1075

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	887355	Conical	Clay	6,3	6,4x5,3		0,7		L 88721	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 477.		Conical loom weight, made of unbaked clay. Not seen	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	
1	987036	Conical	Gypsum	9,2	7,3x5,2		1	390,6 3	L 88703	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, fig. 13.4:11		Conical gypsum (or limestone) loom weight. The hole is circular on one side and elliptic on the other. Complete	IA IIA (Str. S-1a)	2009-1064
1	687006/2	Conical	Gypsum	8,9	7,9x5,4		1	408,1 5	L 68704	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, fig. 13.4:9.		Conical gypsum (or limestone) loom weight. Well rounded hole on both sides. One side of the hole has edgy borders.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1063
1	687006/3	Conical	Gypsum	10,2	7,6x4,5		0,9x1	385	L 68704	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483.		Conical gypsum (or limestone) loom weight. The hole is well rounded on both sides, but edges are ruined. No wear traces are visible.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1062
1	384192	Conical	Gypsum	7,1	5,7		0,9	196,2 4	L 38401	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, fig. 13.4:14.		Conical gypsum (grey stone) loom weight. The hole is circular on one side and elliptical on the other. Edges seems chamfered. No wear traces. The stone shows crystal planes. Broken and burnt	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1066
1	687006/4	Conical	Gypsum	9,2	6,2x5,3		0,7	367,9 4	L 68704	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, fig. 13.4:8.		Conical gypsum (grey stone) loom weight. The hole is circular on one side and elliptical on the other. Edges seems chamfered, more on one side than on the other.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1053
1	384254	Conical	Gypsum	8,5	7,3x5,6		0,9	376	38413	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, 13.4:12.		Conical gypsum (dark grey stone) loom weight. Well crafted but unpolished. Hole presents a slot on one side.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1065
1	687006/1	Conical	Gypsum	8,8	6,9x5,9		0,7x0,9	383	L 68704	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, 13.4:7.		conical gypsum (or limestone) loom weight. Well crafted. The small hole has one side circular, the other elliptical.	IA IIA (Str. S-1)	2009-1061
1	988011	Conical	Gypsum	7,5	5,5X5,7		0,8	249	88859	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, 13.4:13.		Conical gypsum loom weight. Well crafted and polished. Slightly elliptical hole. Edges slightly chamfered. Complete	IA IIA (Str. S-1B)	2009-1068
1	386414	Spherical	Clay	4,4	5,9			115,5	L 38661	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar		Doughnut shaped, incomplete. Unfired, with a diagonal perforation. Not seen	IA Iib (Str. P8)	2009-1076

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
									2006: 477, fig. 13.4:6.					
1	386128	Doughnut	Clay	5,2	9,1		1,6	259+ x	L 38608	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 477.	Doughnut shaped, incomplete. Unfired.	IA IIb (Str. P8)	2009-1079	
1	386050	Doughnut	Baked clay	6,8	7,8		1,6	447,2 3	L 38605	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 478.	Current measures: 4,2x5,7, hole 1,3, weight 114+x. Spherical baked clay loom weight, partially broken. Cylindrical hole, fired clay.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	2009-1077	
1	106016	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,1	7,2			196,8 6	L 10608	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 478.	Complete, doughnut shape, burnt. Not seen.	IA IIb (Str. P6)		
1	286334/1	Conical	Clay	15	17,2		1,7	2360	L 28641 Building 28636	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.2:7.	Found with a batch of loom weights	Large and heavy conical object with a flat base made of unfired clay. Horizontal hole. Too heavy to be a loom weight.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	888017	Conical	Gypsum	9	7,4x4 ,3		0,7x0 ,8	304+ x	88805 topsoil	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, fig. 13.4:10.		Conical gypsum loom weight. Well crafted but a bit tilted. The stone is good looking if compared with other pieces. The hole is chamfered on both sides. One side of the hole is circular, the other slightly oval. Incomplete.	Topsoil	2009-1067
1	384140	Conical	Gypsum	9	7,5		1	43,28	38401	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 483, 13.20.		Conical gypsum loom weight. Complete but very damaged.	IA IIA (Str. S-1a)	
2	26-11-531	Spherical	Clay					107	1152	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
6	26-11-238	Spherical	Clay						1135	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-299	Spherical	Clay						1137	James 1966: fig. 118.		Unfired	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
3	26-11-366	Spherical	Clay						1138	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-203	Spherical	Clay						1131	James 1966: fig. 118.		Hole on the top	IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-210	Pear shaped	Limestone						1131	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	26-11-211	Pear shaped	Basalt					1131	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
3	26-11-381	Pear shaped	Limestone					1136	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-453	Pear shaped	Stone					1146	James 1966: fig. 118.			IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	26-12-11	Pear shaped	Limestone					1146	James 1966: fig. 118.	P.29-107-572		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	29-103-707	Pyramidal	Baked clay					1071		P.25-11-258		IA IIb (Str. IV)	
1	286278/50	Doughnut	Clay	6,4	10,5			630,1 1	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479, fig. 13.4:1.		Doughnut shaped loom weight. Burning traces. Well crafted and regular.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	2009-1080
1	286278/51	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	7,9		0,6	304,0 7	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Spherical baked clay loom weight. A part is missing. Burning traces on the surface.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	2009-1082
1	286278/52	Doughnut	Clay	4,6	6,6			148,9	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Doughnut shaped clay loom weight. Broken and ruined. Burning traces on the surface.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	2009-1083
1	286278/53	Doughnut	Clay	3,3	5			56,66	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Doughnut shaped clay loom weight. Complete. Many burning traces	IA IIb (Str. P7)	2009-1084
1	286319/1	Conical	Clay	16,8	16,9			2390	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.2:8.	Found with a batch of loom weights	Large and heavy conical object with a flat base made of clay. Slightly burnt. Horizontal hole. Too heavy to be a loom weight.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286293/1	Conical	Clay	12,4	15		1	1183	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 474, fig. 13.2:9.	Probably a jar stopper	Large and heavy conical object with a flat base made of clay. Asymmetrical hole. Surface burnt. Too heavy to be a loom weight.	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/1	Doughnut	Clay					134,9 1	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/1a	Doughnut	Clay					320,5	L 28636 Building 28636 Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/1b	Doughnut	Clay	5,3	7		381,8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/2	Doughnut	Clay				375	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/3	Doughnut	Clay	5	7,2		195,8 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/4	Doughnut	Clay	5,1	7,5		295,8 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/5	Doughnut	Clay	6,5	8,8		423,1 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/6	Doughnut	Clay	5,4	7,5		264,8 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/7	Doughnut	Clay	4,9	6,8		215,9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/8	Doughnut	Clay	7	9,1		411,2 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/9	Doughnut	Clay				229,5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/10	Doughnut	Clay				142,4 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/11	Doughnut	Clay	6	7,7		311,6 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/12	Doughnut	Clay	6	7		268,3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/13	Doughnut	Clay				349,7 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/14	Doughnut	Clay	6	7,6		303,8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/15	Doughnut	Clay	7	8,8		451,3 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/16	Doughnut	Clay	5,5	7,7		285,4 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/17	Doughnut	Clay	5,5	7,5		280	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/18	Doughnut	Clay				237,7 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/19	Doughnut	Clay				255	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/20	Doughnut	Clay	4,1	6,8		141,9 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/21	Doughnut	Clay				510,7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/22	Doughnut	Clay	6,6	7,9		280,8 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/23	Doughnut	Clay				366,8 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/24	Doughnut	Clay	6,9	7,3		355,5 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/25	Doughnut	Clay	6,6	7,6		355,5 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/26	Doughnut	Clay	5,7	7,7		302,6 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/27	Doughnut	Clay	5,2	6,8			260,4 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/28	Doughnut	Clay	6,6	8			397,5 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/29	Doughnut	Clay	5,5	7,7			271,2 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/30	Doughnut	Clay	4,9	8			263,9 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/31	Doughnut	Clay	5,3	7,4			330,4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/32	Doughnut	Clay	6	7,4			287,5 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/33	Doughnut	Clay					153,7 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/34	Doughnut	Clay					156,2 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/35	Doughnut	Clay	4,4	6,8			178,1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/36	Doughnut	Clay					200,4 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/37	Doughnut	Clay					378,9 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/38	Doughnut	Clay					380,3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/39	Doughnut	Clay	6,9	7,5			359,4 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/40	Doughnut	Clay	6,5	8			359,4 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/41	Doughnut	Clay					215,0 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/42	Doughnut	Clay	5,8	7,7			265,9 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/43	Doughnut	Clay	5,1	7,4			260,3 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/44	Doughnut	Clay					170,2 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/45	Doughnut	Clay	6,2	8,8			552	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/46	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	7,1			260,6 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/47	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	8,4			412,4 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/48	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	7			296,7 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/49	Doughnut	Clay	6,1	7,9			342,6 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/50	Doughnut	Clay	6,3	8,1			411,5 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/51	Doughnut	Clay					154,5 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.	Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/52	Doughnut	Clay	6	6,7			244,1 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/53	Doughnut	Clay	5	7,5		281,6 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/54	Doughnut	Clay	6	7,2		256,5 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/55	Doughnut	Clay	6,7	8,9		355,9 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/56	Doughnut	Clay	6,2	7,7		341,0 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/57	Doughnut	Clay	6,3	8,7		444,8 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/58	Doughnut	Clay	6,6	8,1		336,8 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/59	Doughnut	Clay	5,5	6,9		223,0 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/60	Doughnut	Clay				173,6 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/61	Doughnut	Clay	4,7	6,8		206,1 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/62	Doughnut	Clay				185,1 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/63	Doughnut	Clay				285,0 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/64	Doughnut	Clay	4,6	6,6		187,2 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/65	Doughnut	Clay	3,6	6,4		147,7 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/66	Doughnut	Clay				240,2 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/67	Doughnut	Clay	4,6	6,6		165,8 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/68	Doughnut	Clay				80,44	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/69	Doughnut	Clay	4,1	6		175,8 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/70	Doughnut	Clay	4,8	8		286,8 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/71	Doughnut	Clay	6	7,6		336,6 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/72	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	7,1		300,1 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/73	Doughnut	Clay				60,6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/74	Doughnut	Clay				201,1 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/75	Doughnut	Clay	5,8	7,3		288,6 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/76	Doughnut	Clay				156,6 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/77	Doughnut	Clay	5,6	6,3		219,7 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/78	Doughnut	Clay	4,6	6,8		205,0 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/79	Doughnut	Clay				143,7 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/80	Doughnut	Clay	5,9	7,3		273,5 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/81	Doughnut	Clay	4,9	7,5		245,6 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/82	Doughnut	Clay	6,4	7,2		271,8 1	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/83	Doughnut	Clay				131,4 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		Not complete	IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/84	Doughnut	Clay	5,1	6,7		199,3 8	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/85	Doughnut	Clay	3,4	5		57,93	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/86	Doughnut	Clay	5,3	8,5		334,1 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/87	Doughnut	Clay	6,1	8		308,4 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/88	Doughnut	Clay	5,7	7,1		231,2 4	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/89	Doughnut	Clay	5	7		219,7 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/90	Doughnut	Clay	6	6,6		223,4 6	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/91	Doughnut	Clay	6,3	9,6		482,1 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.			IA IIb (Str. P7)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	286292/92	Doughnut	Clay	5,1	6,1			159,1 7	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/93	Doughnut	Clay	2,6	4,6			43,28	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/94	Doughnut	Clay	5,4	7,7			321,3 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/95	Doughnut	Clay	5,1	6,9			298,8 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/96	Doughnut	Clay	6,7	9			450,7 5	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/97	Doughnut	Clay					358,6 9	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/98	Doughnut	Clay	6,1	8,1			354,3 3	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	
1	286292/99	Doughnut	Clay	6,4	7,5			311,9 2	L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom- Mack/Mazar 2006: 479.		IA IIb (Str. P7)	

BASALT RINGS

Early Bronze Age

1	181333	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,7	5,3		0,5	59,39	10018	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:15.	Basalt disk with hourglass hole. Complete. Polished	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	181121	Cylindrica 1	Limesto ne	0,7	3,3		0,5		10056	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:19.	Incomplete. Polished surface.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	181207	Cylindrica 1	Limesto ne	1	3,8		0,7	19,78	10056	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:20.	Slightly broken. Polished surface. Pebble?	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	380094	Cylindrical 1	Limestone	1,5	3,7		0,7	21,32	38002	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:16.	Sharpened edges. Not properly rounded in shape. Conical perforation.	EB Ib (Str. M- 2)	
1	281257	Cylindrical 1	Limestone	1,4	4		0,9		10016	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:18.	Fragment.	EB Ib (Str. M- 2)	
1	100195	Cylindrical 1	Limestone	1,1			0,8		10019	Mazar/Rotem 2012:371, fig. 9.9:18.	Fragment.	EB Ib (Str. M- 2a)	
1	170088?	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	2,4	4,3		1,2	59,52			Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole		
1	181313	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	1,9	3,8		1,2	34,51	W10006	Mazar/Rotem 2012:370, fig. 9.9:10.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 2)	
1	281117	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	1,8	3,1		0,9- 1,5	21,63	18125	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:14.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 2b)	
1	380543	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	1,4	3,6		1	28.66	38039	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:13.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	281253	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	1,7	3,5		1,2	30,4	28114	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:12.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole. Porous stone	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	380500	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	1,7	3,7		1,1	31,98	W18227	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:11.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 2)	
1	380102	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	2	3,9		1,3	42,3	38015	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:8.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 2b)	
1	380581/1	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	2,1	4,2		1,2	57,92	38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 371, fig. 9.9:5.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	380581/2	Cylindrical 1	Limestone	1,8	4,4		0,9	45,14	38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 371, fig. 9.9:7.	Complete.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	380581/3	Cylindrical 1	Basalt	2	4,2		1,3	45,55	38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 371, fig. 9.9:6.	Complete, asymmetrical	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	380572	Cylindrica 1	Tuff	2,9				38039	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 371.		Small fragment, oval.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	100088/1	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,7	4,4		1,4	61,47	10018	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:3.	Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole with some chippings nearby	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	100088/2	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,4	4,2		1,1	59,65	10018	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:4.	Basalt ring. Complete and well rounded. Hourglass hole with a wider side	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	281526	Cylindrica 1	Limesto ne	2,1	3,8		1	35,5	28121	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:9.	Basalt ring, complete. Rounded and cylindrical hole. Wear surfaces.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	380356	Spherical	Limesto ne	3,8	3,8		1,1		38033	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Incomplete.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	181047	Cylindrica 1	Tuff	2,5	4,1		1,2		10018	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Incomplete, asymmetric.	EB Ib (Str. M- 3)	
1	380123	Spherical	Tuff	2,6	2,7		nn	13,49 +x	38007	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Fragment of a spherical tuff object. Inside the hole are visible the signs of the crafting process.	EB Ib (Str. M- 2b)	IAA 850623
1	320581/3	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,1	4,2		1,3	45,48			Basalt ring. complete and well rounded. Cylindrical hole		
1	33-10-691 g.	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,9	4,1		1,1	49,17	1858		Basalt ring. Complete and well rounded. Not perfectly smoothed	Eb Ib (Lev. XIV)	341157
1	33-10-691 c	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,7	3,9		1	44,06	1858		Basalt ring. Well rounded. Cylindrical hole	Eb Ib (Lev. XIV)	341156
1	33-10-691 a	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,2	3,5		1	38	1858		Basalt ring. complete and well rounded. Not perfectly smoothed	Eb Ib (Lev. XIV)	341159
1	33-10-673 c	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,5	3,3		1,1	23,5	1873		Basalt ring. Complete and well rounded. Hourglass hole well polished.	Eb Ib (Lev. XIV)	341147
1	341444	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,6	4,7		1,1	62,06			Basalt ring. Complete and well rounded. Hourglass hole well polished.	Eb Ib (Lev. XIV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	33-10-568	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,5	4x4,3		1,2	67,78	1848		Basalt ring. Complete and slightly elliptical. Hourglass hole	Eb Ib (Lev. XIII)	341134
1	33-10-571	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,8	3		1	21,62	1848		Well crafted. Hourglass hole	Eb Ib (Lev. XIII)	341135
1	100236	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,7	8,1				10038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:1.	Unpolished, incomplete. Unfinished perforation. Not a basalt ring. Too large.	EB III (Str. M-1)	
1	380131	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1,2	3,4		1		38002	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Incomplete.	EB Ib (Str. M-2)	
1	182045	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	2,2			1,4		10964	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Fragment.	EB Ib (Str. M-2)	
1	182422	Cylindrica 1	Limestone	2,8	5		1,5		18251	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370.	Incomplete, asymmetrical.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	100029	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	3,1	4,7		1,5		94,19	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 370, fig. 9.9:2.	Complete, quite Spherical. Cylindrical hole, not hourglass perforation. Perhaps a macehead.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	

Middle Bronze Age

1	189197	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	3,1	1,8		1	22,29	18960	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:1.	Complete, ring shaped, perforated from both sides.	Late MB II (Str. R-3)	
1	189215	Cylindrica 1	Basalt	1	3,8		1	20,47	18961	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:4.	Complete, ring shaped, perforated from both sides.	Late MB II (Str. R-3)	
1	580516	Biconical	Basalt	2,9	4,4		1,5		58117	Yahalom-Mack 2007c: 663, fig. 12.3:9.	Incomplete, perforated from both sides	Late MB II (Str. R-4a)	

BONE SPATULAE AND BEATERS

Early Bronze Age

1	380580	spatula	Bone	5,7	1,5	0,3			38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:7.		Fragment of a bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	
1	281709	spatula	Bone	8,7	1,4	0,3			10056	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:3.		Bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	
1	281043	spatula	Bone	9,5	2,5	0,3			10037	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:2.		Part of a bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing. Parallel striations near the point.	EB Ib (Str. M-2a-b)	
1	281076	spatula	Bone	9,5	1,55	0,25			18104	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:4.		Part of a bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing. Cutting marks near the point.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	380113	spatula	Bone	7,1	1,7	0,4			38005	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:5.		Fragment of a bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	281578	spatula	Bone	3					10025	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:8.		Small fragment of point of a spatula	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	380411	spatula	Bone	2,3	0,8	0,2			38037	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386.		Small fragment of point of a spatula	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
1	283183	spatula	Bone	11	1,9	0,2			28320	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:6.		Two fragments of a bone spatula, both ends missing.	EB III (Str. R-12)	
1	383025	spatula	Bone	8,8	2	0,3			28328	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:1.		Bone spatula, almost complete. Triangular point, the other end missing.	EB III (Str. R-12b)	
1	281317	beater	Bone	5	1,2	0,3			28121	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:14.		Bone point, one end missing, the other apparently quite sharpened (?). Point burnt.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	
1	380580	spatula	Bone	5,7	1,5	0,3			38038	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 386, fig. 9.16:7.		Bone point, probably belonging to a spatula, triangular shape.	EB Ib (Str. M-3)	

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

Late Bronze Age

1	27-12-299		Bone	4,6	1,6				1327		P. 29-105-393	Bone spatula, rounded point, the other missing. Penn pics.	LB Ib-IIA (Str. IX)	
1	387521		Bone	3,4		0,1			38739	Panitz-Cohen/Yahalom-Mack 2009: 740, fig. 15.2.		Bone spatula, broken, with large and rounded tip. Horizontal line incised above an X.	LB IIB (Str. N-4)	

Iron Age I

1	989007		Bone	7,4	1,8				88935 Building 1500	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 161.		Bone spatula with triangular point, the other end missing. Cancellous bone visible on the lower surface.	IA Ia (Str. Q-1)	
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Iron Age II

1	286320	triangular	Bone	5	2,4	0,1			L 28636 Building 28636	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 497, fig. 13.10:3)		Small bone spatula. Broken. Triangular point. One side is smooth, the other shows cancellous bone structure. Edgy point but smoothed on the side. No wear traces are visible, except on the lower edge (they could be sanding traces)	IA IIB (Str. P-7)	681879
1	386423		Bone	6,1	2,3	0,2			L 38661	Yahalom-Mack/Mazar 2006: 497, fig. 13.10:4)		Bone broken spatula. Only the rounded edge is preserved. Slightly convex and well polished. Barely visible wear traces.	IA IIB (Str. P-8a)	681880
1	26-9-1		Bone						1076	James 1966: fig. 110.	P.29-105-286	Bone spatula, triangular point, the other partially rounded.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	3191		Bone	7,2					63	James 1966: fig. 114.	P. 29-105-429	Bone spatula, triangular point, the other missing.	IA II (Str. V)	
1	3665		Bone	10					58	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-105-440	Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	
1	NFN		Bone	5,5					273	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-105-440	Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA IIB (Str. IV)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	3612		Bone	9,5				99	James 1966: fig. 118.		Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA Iib (Str. IV)	
1	3559		Bone	7,7				254	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-105-431	Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA Iib (Str. IV)	
1	NFN		Bone					183	James 1966: fig. 118.		Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA Iib (Str. IV)	
1	26-11-367		Bone	9,3	2			1138	James 1966: fig. 118.	P. 29-105-417	Bone spatula, pen-nib point, complete. The other end is rounded.	IA Iib (Str. IV)	

NEEDLES AND BODKINS

Early Bronze Age

1	181340	bodkin	Bone	17,9	1,1	0,35		18101	Mazar/Rotem 2012: 38, fig. 9.16:9.		Long and narrow object with a rounded perforation near one of the ends. Worked and polished on both sides.	EB Ib (Str. M-2b)	
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Middle Bronze Age

1			bronze	7,5	0,5		0,3				Broken bronze needle. On the top the eye is a oval hole slightly flatted.		142258
1			bronze	6,2	0,4						Broken bronze needle point.		142259
1	985049		bronze	7,7	0,4			88568	Yahalom-Mack 2007a: 612, fig. 9.3:7.		Broken needle, two pieces preserved, point missing. Eye perforated on the shaft.	Late MB Iib (Str. R-3)	

Late Bronze Age

1	791018		bronze	10,9	0,3			2,97	79115	Yahalom-Mack 2007a: 611, fig. 9.3:6.		Bent needle, incomplete. Loop shaped eye (?)=Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft	LB I (Str. R-1b)	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	27-10-538		bronze	12,5	0,5			1252	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 150.1.	P.29-108-311	Long and thick needle, point missing. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB IIb (Str. VII)	
1	27-11-248		copper-base					1289	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 150.3.		Long and thick needle, broken in three. Large eye obtained probably by bending on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	26-10-500		copper-base					1108	James/McGovern 1993: fig. 150.4. Rowe 1940; pl. 32.18		Long and thick needle, point missing, broken in two. Large eye obtained probably by folding on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB IIb (Str. VIII)	
1	184250		bronze	13,4	0,5		11,1	18411	Yahalom-Mack 2009: 565, fig. 10.9.		Long and thick needle, complete. Large eye obtained by folding on itself the upper part of the shaft.	LB IIb (Str. N-4)	

Iron Age I

1	108196		bronze	7,5	0,7	0,5		7,1	10841	Yahalom-Mack 2009: 565, fig. 10.9.		Long and thick needle, point missing. Large eye obtained by folding on itself the upper part of the shaft.	IA Ia (Str. S-4)	
1	987333		bronze	8,8	0,4				98741	Yahalom-Mack 2009: 565, fig. 10.9.		Long shaft tapering to a point, broken in two pieces. Probably part of a needle. Upper part missing.	IA Ia (Str. S-3)	
1	27-10-450	Needle	bronze	11,3	0,5				1197	James 1966: 104.	P.29-108-310	Long and thick bronze needle, point missing. Eye pierced	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	33-9-84	Needle	bronze						1724	James 1966: 104.	P.34-20-45	Bronze needle slightly curved.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	
1	31-11-273	bodkin	bronze						1599	James 1966: 104.		Thick shaft of bronze with no eye preserved.	IA Ia (Lev. VI)	

TELL EL-FAR'AH NORTH

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
SPINDLES													
1	F 4434	bone	3,1	1,2 x 1		0,5	3	Under 656			Bone shaft, hollow, probably broken at the ends, with centred decoration. Edges are smooth but irregular. Lattice motif. Possibly not a spindle.		
1	F. 2430	ivory	6	1				L. 343 déblais	Chambon 1984, pl. 73 :11. De Vaux 1952, pl. XV :16.		Cylindrical ivory rod partially preserved. One end is flat, and the shaft seems not to taper towards the other (missing) end. Handle?	HS	
1	F. 355	bone	5,3	1				L.65	Chambon 1984, pl. 73:12.		Cylindrical ivory rod, hollow, complete. One end is flat, and the shaft seems not to taper towards the other flat end. One circular incision is the only decoration. Handle?	Period VII II-355, VIIb - IA IIA	

SPINDLE WHORLS

Chalcolithic

1	F. 4556	Biconical 1	Pottery	2,4	3,5		0,6	26, 21	L. 705		Biconical spindle whorl, well shaped. Complete, made of pottery. Hole is slightly oval on one side, perfectly round on the other.	Chalcolithic	
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Early Bronze Age

1	F. 1208	Spherical	Stone	3,4	4,8		nn	39, 16+ x	L. 110 C3 SE, 37.50		De Vaux Eneol.	Spherical spindle whorl, broken in half. Made of grey stone. Cylindrical hole with clear traces of manufacture.	EB I	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W		Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 3987	Cylindrical	White stone	3,2	4,4		0,9	104		L. 619		Nice and polished white stone, hourglass hole. Mace head?	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4393	Conical	Grey stone	1,3	5,5		0,6	28,39		L. 683		Conical spindle whorl, almost complete but chipped. Made of a grey, friable stone. Upper hole with traces of wear, lower hole perfectly cut.	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 4686	Spherical	Grey stone	2,9	4			20,12+x		Tr. 692 (1)		Spherical spindle whorl, more than a half missing. Made of a grey stone.	EBA	
1	F. 4964	Discoid	Stone	0,7	4		0,6	9,6+x		L. 784		Discoid spindle whorl, half preserved. Made of a grey stone, well rounded and polished. Well cut cylindrical hole. Worked from a pebble.	EBA	
1	F. 4101		Black stone	1,7	4,2		1	40,08+x		Under 628		Very fine stone, more than half missing. Extremely polished and smooth. Mace head?	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 3195	Cylindrical	Stone	3	4,6		1,3	78		L. 274		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Made of light grey stone. Large, conical hole.	EBA	

Middle Bronze Age

1	F. 4838	Cylindrical	Stone	2,8	4,6 x4,8		1	87,21		L. 734 demolishing		Asymmetrical cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Made of a whitish stone. Hourglass hole but well polished.	MB	
1	F. 3675	Cylindrical	White stone	1,8	4,3		0,7	39,18		Under 585	Mallet 1973: 12:5. Mallet 1988: fig. 22.5.	Spindle whorl/loom weight. White stone roughly made. Oblique cylindrical hole	(MB) Period V IIN.BM 505 (B,4)	
1	F. 4738	Cylindrical	Grey stone	2,1	2,6		0,7	14,55		Under 733		Spindle whorl/bead. Gray stone with cylindrical hole. Decorated on the top with a concentric ring motif	Period V III-733	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W		Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	F. 2913	Dome	Bone	0,6	2		0,2 5	0,9 3+x		L. 245	Mallet 1973: 22,12, Mallet 1988, fig. 32,12		Tiny bone spindle whorl, broken in half and damaged. Polished on the dome	Period V IIN.BM 245 (B,2)	
1	F. 2123	Dome	Bone	1,8	4,3		nn	14, 47+ x		Under 208(=226)			Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Damaged. On the bottom cancellus bone is exposed	MB (de Vaux), Period VI Dc	
1	F. 4514	Cylindrical	Pottery	1,5	3,6		1,1	13, 08+ x		Ext. De 694			Spindle whorl (?) Cylindrical, pottery? Asymmetrical, broken	MB	

Late Bronze Age

1	F. 104	Dome	Bone	0,8	2,3		0,2	3,1 3		C4, 1m			Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Damaged. Hole diameter and weight are too small to belong to a spindle whorl.	Period VI Dc	
1	F. 1950	Lenticular	White stone	0,9	2		0,4	4,9 1		Loc. 198			Spindle whorl/bead. White stone	Period de Vaux RB, Period VI Dc. Scavo 1950.	
1	F. 739	Dome	Bone	0,5	2,5		0,4	2,3 9		T4 (14)		BR	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Complete, damaged. Cylindrical hole	Period VI Dce, PL. LBA II ?	
1	F. 3589	Conical truncated	Stone	1,8	3,7		0,7	33, 33		Loc. 526 1955		Period VI Dce	Stone spindle whorl, irregular, Tronco conical. Hourglass hole		
1	F. 3650	Cylindrical	White stone	1,4	3,8		0,9	27, 55		Under 539 1955		Period VI Dce	White stone spindle whorl. Irregular with cylindrical hole	T 68	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 3477	Dome	Stone	1,1	3		0,3	9,9 1	L. 480 1955		Period VI Dce	Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Brown stone (bone?) damaged at the base. The hole slightly	Bronze Recent le temple?
1	F. 3507	Spherical	Stone	2,1	2,8		0,8	15, 09	L 504 1955		Period VI Dce	Biconical spindle whorl, grey stone. Damaged at one side. Cylindrical hole. Wheel signs create a decorative motif	
1	F. 236	Conical	Bone	1,2	2,6		0,3	6,8 1	C1 W, - 2,25m			conical bone spindle whorl. Concave base, with spiral incision.	Period VI Dc

Iron Age

1	F. 3491	Cylindrical	Stone	1,1	3,1		0,8	10, 25+ x	Under 487 1955			Stone cylindrical spindle whorl, the base is missing. Cylindrical hole	Period VI/Period VIIa - IA I/IIA
1	F. 1519	Lenticular	White stone	1,1	1,9		0,4	4,3 2	L. 150	Chambon 1984, 75:21		White stone spindle whorl/bead. Biconical and polished. Cylindrical hole. Possibly made of bone	VII d - IA IIB
1	F. 1666	Dome	Black stone	0,8	1,7		0,4	2,3 2	L. 164 (con un peso)	Chambon 1984, 74:12		Black stone spindle whorl/bead. Dome-shaped with ring carving.	VII b - IA IIA - IA IIA
1	F. 2455	Lenticular	Limest one	0,9	2,1		0,4	5,2	sotto 321=369	Chambon 1984, 75:20.		Limestone spindle whorl/bead. Lenticular shape, polished, with cylindrical hole.	VII b - IA IIA
1	F. 1474	Cylindrical	Schist	2,2	3,4		0,8	32, 26	L. 113 destruction	Chambon 1984, 75:37		Schist cylindrical spindle whorl with decoration on its side. Ring motif	VII e - IA IIC
1	F. 2941	Dome	Bone	0,6	2,2		0,3	3,1 2	Under 414	Chambon 1984, 75:1		Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Damaged. Hole diameter and weight are too small to belong to a spindle whorl.	VII c - IA IIB

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W		Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 1495	Conical	Pottery	1,1	2,1		0,3	4,2 1	L. 125 ext,	Chambon 1984, 75:11		Conical spindle whorl. Damaged, made from pottery. Well crafted at the origin	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 3356	Dome	Bone	0,65	2,6				L. 447	Chambon 1984, 75:2.		Small bone spindle whorl, complete.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 2908	Dome	Limestone	0,5	2				L. 407	Chambon 1984, 75:3.		Small stone spindle whorl, chipped.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 393	Conical	Grey stone	1	2,5 5				L. 19	Chambon 1984, 75:4.		Small stone spindle whorl, complete. Circular line incised near the edge.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1432	Dome	Grey stone	1	2,5				L. 126	Chambon 1984, 75:5.		Small stone spindle whorl, complete.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 1787	Conical	Limestone	0,9	2				L. 162 Under	Chambon 1984, 75:6.	Louvre	Small stone spindle whorl, complete.	VII	
1	F. 3219	Conical	Grey stone	0,7	1,2				L. 441	Chambon 1984, 75:7.		Small stone spindle whorl, complete.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1528	Conical	Limestone	2,7	4,2				L. 151	Chambon 1984, 75:8.		Stone spindle whorl, complete. Quite large and high.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 3384	Conical truncated	Pottery	1	2,2				L. 458	Chambon 1984, 75:9.		Pottery spindle whorl, chipped.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 2446	Conical truncated	Stone	1	2,8				L. 335	Chambon 1984, 75:10.		Small stone spindle whorl, complete.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 1700	Button	Pottery	1	2,5				L. 158	Chambon 1984, 75:13.		Small pottery spindle whorl, complete.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 391	Conical truncated	Grey stone	1,1	1,5 5				L. 19	Chambon 1984, 75:14.		Small stone spindle whorl, complete. Circular line incised on the surface.	VII b - IA IIA	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 3465	Biconical	Grey stone	2,1	3,3			L. 432	Chambon 1984, 75:15.		Stone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 3220	Biconical	Grey stone	2,1	3,5			L. 442	Chambon 1984, 75:16.		Stone spindle whorl, complete. Four radial incisions on the surface.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2470	Biconical	Pottery	1,8	4,1			L. 350	Chambon 1984, 75:17.		Pottery spindle whorl, complete. Quite irregular.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F. 2949	Cylindrical	Schist	1,2	2,9			L. 418	Chambon 1984, 75:18.		Stone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 1711	Lenticular	Pottery	0,9	2,1			L. 175	Chambon 1984, 75:19.		Pottery spindle whorl, complete. Quite irregular.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2776	Discoid	Limestone	1	3,6			L. 346	Chambon 1984, 75:23.		Stone spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 1667	Cylindrical	Pottery	1	2,4			L. 173	Chambon 1984, 77:24.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with very small hole.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 1592	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,8	3,3			L. 140	Chambon 1984, 77:32.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Bent hole.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2777	Cylindrical	Schist	0,9	3,3			L. 346 Under	Chambon 1984, 77:33.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. One side shorter than the other.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 1671	Cylindrical	Stone	1,2	2,4			L. 173	Chambon 1984, 77:34.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Irregular sides.	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2361	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,4	4,2			L. 444	Chambon 1984, 77:35.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Chipped.	VIIe - IA IIC	
1	F. 1647	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,9	3,9			L. 149b Under	Chambon 1984, 77:36.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Two circular lines incised on the side.	VIIa - IA I/IIA	
1	F. 3390	Cylindrical	Schist	0,9	3,2			L. 456 Under	Chambon 1984, 77:38.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. One circular line incised on the side.	VIIb - IA IIA	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 2449	Cylindrical	Schist	2	2,8			L. 367	Chambon 1984, 77:39.		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Two circular lines incised on the side.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 1705	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,8	2,3			L. 173	Chambon 1984, 75:22.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with hourglass perforation.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1704	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,6	2			L. 158	Chambon 1984, 75:25.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with hourglass perforation.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1697	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,7	2,4			L. 158	Chambon 1984, 75:26.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with hourglass perforation.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1676	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,9	2,2			L. 173	Chambon 1984, 75:27.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with cylindrical perforation.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1675	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,6	1,2			L. 173	Chambon 1984, 75:28.		Cylindrical object with very small cylindrical perforation. Certainly not a spindle whorl.	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 1413	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,9	1,7			L. 124	Chambon 1984, 75:29.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with cylindrical perforation.	VII e - IA IIC	
1	F. 2370	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,7	1,8			L. 444	Chambon 1984, 75:30.		Cylindrical object with hourglass bent perforation. Certainly not a spindle whorl.	VII e - IA IIC	
1	F. 1698	Cylindrical	Pottery	0,6	2,1			L. 158	Chambon 1984, 75:31.		Cylindrical spindle whorl with cylindrical perforation.	VII b - IA IIA	

Unknown context

1	F. 4433	Biconical	Pottery	2,9	4,5		0,6	42,68		Under 656		Biconical spindle whorl, made from pottery. Well preserved. Wear traces near the hole edges		
1	F. 142	Lenticular	Pottery	0,7	1,9		0,5	2,53		Tr. V, C1		Decorated bead		
1	F. 4210	Spherical	Stone	3,4	3,9		1,2	102		Under 651		Red stone mace head. Polished with cylindrical hole. Small.		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W		Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 39694	Dome	Bone	0,7	2,9		0,2	3,9 1				Dome-shaped bone spindle whorl. Damaged. Hole diameter is too small to belong to a spindle whorl.		
1	F. 264	Cylindrical	Limestone	1,9	4,6		1,4	23, 44+ x	C1, 37m			Limestone cylindrical spindle whorl, with cylindrical hole. Broken		
1	F. 2887	Lenticular	White stone	1,1	1,9		0,4	4,6 9				White stone spindle whorl/bead. Lenticular, polished with cylindrical hole.		

PERFORATED SHERDS

Early Bronze Age

1	F 4001	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,9	3,1		nn	10, 39	L. 614			Small perforated sherd, rounded, with incomplete hole on both sides.	EBA Period 3	
1	F 4092	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,2 x2, 6		0,4	7,1 2	L. 646			Small perforated sherd roughly made. Hourglass hole	EBA Period 3	
1	F 2874	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,8	3,4 x3, 7		0,3	10, 46	L. 240			roughly made. Hourglass small hole	BA	

Middle Bronze Age

1	F 2920	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,6	4,3		0,3	26	L. 246	Mallet 1973: 12:4, Mallet 1988, fig. 25,6		Perforated sherd with small, tilted hourglass hole	Period V, IIN.BM 246 (B2)	
1	F 5021	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,6 x4		0,5	14, 43	Under 791	Mallet 1988: fig. 4:8.	phase villageoise 2	Perforated sherd roughly made. Hourglass hole	Period V IV.BM 791 (A,2)	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	F. 4871	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,6	1,9 x2, 1		0,4	3,8		L. Under 751		Tiny, perforated sherd. Hourglass hole	(BM) Period V III.758	

Late Bronze Age

1	F. 3974	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,3	5,5 x6		0,6	46, 65		Under 543 trou	L. 543 BA according to Mallet p. 74.	Perforated sherd, broken. Thick disk, hourglass hole	Niveau de Vaux BR/F?	
1	F 4354	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,5		0,5	9,4 8		Under 673 inf.		Perforated sherd roughly made. Conical hole, off-centre	Period VI Dc	
1	F 4387	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,6	1,9		0,4	2,9		Under 681		Tiny, perforated sherd. Cylindrical hole	Period VI Dc	
1	F. 3294	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1	3,6		0,2	14, 68		Trou 279-280		Perforated sherd roughly made. Tiny hourglass hole. Possibly not a spindle whorl.	Period VI Dce, LBA II?	

Iron Age

1	F 4303	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,5	4,2 x4, 9		0,4	29, 75		Under 654		Perforated sherd roughly made. Hourglass hole	Period VII II-307, VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 3393	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,9	3,4 x3, 6		0,3	10, 91		L. 460	Chambon 1984, 77:1	Perforated sherd roughly made. Oblique hourglass hole	Period VII, II-460, VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3201	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1	3,8 x3, 5		0,4	15, 3		L. 440	Chambon 1984, 77:5NRc	Perforated sherd roughly made. Hourglass hole	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2980	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1	4,4					L. 418	Chambon 1984, 77:3.	Discoid perforated sherd with hourglass perforation. Incomplete. Base of a vessel.	VIIb - IA IIA	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 2480	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,2	3,8			L. 365	Chambon 1984, 77:4.		Discoid perforated sherd with Discoid perforation.	VIIe - IA IIC	
1	F. 1663	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,6	5			L. 167	Chambon 1984, 77:4NR.		Discoid perforated sherd with Discoid perforation.	VIIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 1471	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,2	6,6			L. 120	Chambon 1984, 77:4NRa.		Discoid perforated sherd with Discoid perforation.	VIIe - IA IIC1	
1	F. 1355	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	5,3			L. 113	Chambon 1984, 77:5.		Discoid perforated sherd with very small hourglass perforation.	VIIe - IA IIC	
1	F. 1464	Perforated sherd	Pottery		5,8			L. 135	Chambon 1984, 77:5NR.		Discoid perforated sherd with very small hourglass perforation.	VIII d - IA IIB	
1	F. 3033	Perforated sherd	Pottery		3,6			L. 427	Chambon 1984, 77:5NRa.		Discoid perforated sherd with very small hourglass perforation.	VIII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 3371	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,8	4,3			L. 456	Chambon 1984, 77:5NRb.		Discoid perforated sherd with very small hourglass perforation.	VIII d - IA IIB	

Unknown context

1	F 4918	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,2	4,2		0,7	20,68	L. 773		Perforated Sherd well rounded. Cylindrical hole. Perforation from both sides.		
1	F 4061	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1	3,8		0,6	13,66	Under 619		Perforated Sherd well rounded. Cylindrical hole. Perforation from both sides.		
1	F 3102	Perforated sherd	Pottery	2	5,5x4,9		0,5	48,9			Perforated sherd roughly made. Oblique hole, off-centre. Possibly a loom weight		
1	F 2896	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,4x3,7		0,3	10	nn		Perforated sherd roughly made. Small conical hole		
1	F 4305	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	2,5		0,4	6,63	Under wall 651		Perforated sherd roughly made. Small hourglass hole		
1	F 4093	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	3,2x2,6		0,4	7,12			Perforated sherd roughly made. Small hourglass hole		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA		
1	F 3761	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1	4,9x4,5		nn	26		Under 429			Perforated sherd well rounded. Incomplete perforation from both sides.		
1	F. 3224	Perforated sherd	Pottery	0,7	2,2		0,2	5,71		Under 272			Perforated sherd roughly made. Tiny hourglass hole. Possibly not a spindle whorl		
1	F. 2988	Perforated sherd	Pottery	1,2	3,6			15,85		L. 284			Perforated sherd well rounded. Incomplete perforation from both sides.		

LOOM WEIGHTS

Early Bronze Age

1	F. 4402		Grey stone	1,3	3,3x3,5		0,4	20		L. 683			Loom weight, or possibly a pendant	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 4074	Spherical	White stone	5,2	5,1x5,6			179		L. 638			White stone loom weight, incomplete. Hourglass hole	EBA Period 3	
1	f. 4509	Spherical	White stone	3,7	4,3		0,6	38,81+x		Tr. 686, niveau interm			White stone loom weight, irregular shape. Hourglass hole, well crafted.		

Middle Bronze Age

1	F 3695	Conical	Unbaked clay	10,6	7,3		1	360		L. 511	Mallet 1973: 13,4. Mallet 1988: fig. 24.4		Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Unbaked clay, almost complete. Lower part missing	(MB) Period V IIN.BM 511 (B,3)	
1	F 4826	Conical	Unbaked clay	7,7	6,2		0,7	233		L. 721 démolit.			Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Unbaked clay, smaller than usual. Broken at the hole, split into two parts.	(MB) Period V III.721, Period V	
1	F 4679	Conical	Unbaked clay	7,8	6,8		0,9	166+x		L. 721			Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Unbaked clay. Broken below the hole. Slot on the top, possibly to hold the shaft where the warp threads are fixed. Unique exemplar.	Period de Vaux MB, Period V III,721	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 3894	Spherical	Baked clay	3,9	5,3		25+x	L. 600	Mallet 1973: 3:5. Mallet 1988: fig. 14:5, pl. LXXXII,4		fragment of a loom weight, baked clay, possibly spherical. Together with a second fragment of a different loom weight.	Period V IIN.BM 600 (B.1)	
1	F 2936	Conical	Baked clay	10,2	6,1	0,3	375	Under 229 N	Mallet 1973: 14:5. Mallet 1988: fig. 24:5	T 110	Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Baked clay, small hole, almost complete. On the top there is a Hyksos scarab imprint.	Period V, IIN.BM 229	
1	F 3876	Conical	Baked clay	9,5	5,7	0,3	275	Under 596	Mallet 1973: 14:1. Mallet 1988: fig. 24:1, pl. LXXXII,1.		Conical loom weight, well crafted, horizontally perforated. Polished, small hole. Wear traces due to warp threads hanging.	Period V, IIN.BM 601(B,1)	
1	F 3755	Conical	Unbaked clay	11,1	6,7	0,9	413+x	L. 571	Mallet 1973: 14:3. Mallet 1988: fig. 24:3, pl. LXXXII,3.		Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Unbaked clay, almost complete.	MB Period V IIN.BM 571 (B.2)	
1	F 3829	Conical	Unbaked clay	11,1	7,5	0,9	446	Under 571	Mallet 1973: 14:2. Mallet 1988: fig. 24:2, pl. LXXXII,2.		Conical loom weight, horizontally perforated. Unbaked clay, well crafted. Pointed top	Period V, IIN.BM 592(B,1)	

Late Bronze Age

1	F. ?	Discoid	Stone	2,9	8		1,8	167+x	Under 681		11/9/59 Under 681 p. 143	Stone loom weight, broken in half. Roughly made	Period VI Dc	
1	F. 4389		White stone	1,6	2,8x3,2		0,4	15,95	Under 681			White stone loom weight, irregular. A drilled stone	Period VI Dc	
1	F 1915	Spherical	Baked clay	5,5	7,6		1,7	232	Under 189		T 83	Baked clay spherical loom weight. Almost complete. Made of two pieces.	Period De vaux RB, Period VI Dc	
1	F 4665		White stone	9	7,2		1,4	630	L. 720			White stone loom weight, irregular with off-centre hole. Horizontally perforated, well crafted.	(MB) RB I de Vaux, Period VI Dce	

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

Iron Age

1	F. 4774	Discoid	Grey stone	1,7	5,6x6,6		1	68,87		Under 736			Grey stone loom weight, disk-shaped, broken, with hourglass hole.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-01	Spherical	Baked clay	6,6	8,2		1,6	391		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	From the same locus as spindle whorl	About one hundred of unbaked clay loom weights. Mostly broken.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-02	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,2	5,3		nn	94		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)			VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-03	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,2	8		1,9	194+x		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Big loom weight of which a small part is preserved	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-04	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,2	6,6		nn	123+x		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		loom weight broken in half	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-05	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5	6,6		1	115+x		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		broken loom weight, 1/3 is missing	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-06	Cylindrical	Unbaked clay	4,3	6			121		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		unbaked clay loom weight, almost complete but worn. The hole is missing	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-07	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5	5,6		1,5	142		L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Complete baked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 1510-08	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,5	6,2		119	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		unbaked clay loom weight, almost complete but worn. The hole is missing	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-09	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,5		114	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		unbaked clay loom weight, almost complete but worn. The hole is missing	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-10	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,7	5,7		117+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Unbaked clay loom weight, broken in half.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-11	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,5	7,2		122+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-12	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,7	1,1	109	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-13	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	4,8x5,3	1,4	81	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-14	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,5	nn	102+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-15	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,5	nn l. 5,5	nn	68+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 1510-16	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4	5,5		1,6	63+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-17	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,1	6		nn	81+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight. The diameter is deducible.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-18	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,5	6,2		1,1x1,5	100+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Well preserved loom weight, worn	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-19	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,5	7,2		1,5	131+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	half of a loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-20	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	5,2	7,4			124+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	half of a loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-21	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	6,1			48+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-22	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,8x5,6		1,1x1,3	124	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-23	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,3	6,1			151	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 1510-24	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,2	5,6		1,5	97	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-25	Spherical	Baked clay	4,7	5,9		1,5	85+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Baked clay loom weight, broken in half	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-26	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,8	6,9			113	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Unbaked clay loom weight, broken in half.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1510-27	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,6	6,2			105+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-28	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,3	6,2		1,4	125	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-29	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,3	5,7			84+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-30	Spherical	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,7x5,1		1,6	105	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-31	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,2	5,5		1,6	94+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)	2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 1015-32	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,7	5,8		70+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-33	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	5,4		78+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-34	Spherical	Baked clay	4,5	6,3		166	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete baked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-35	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,2	6,4	1,5	155	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-36	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,3	5,8		152	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-37	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,9	5,5x5,9		147	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-38	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,3	5,7		63+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-39	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,1	6	1,4	170	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Complete unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	F 1015-40	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,5	4,9		90+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB		
1	F 1015-41	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,4	6,1		157	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB		
1	F 1015-42	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,1	5,5		1,5	109+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-43	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,7	6,7		1,5	155+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-44	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,3	5,4			63+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-45	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,4	6,5			191+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete, but deformed, unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is almost close at one end.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-46	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,6	6,8x5,7		1,6	155+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		2/3 of an unbaked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-47	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,4	5,1			63+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Fragment of a loom weight, unbaked clay	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 1015-48	Doughnut	Baked clay	3,7	6,3		89+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		About half of a baked clay loom weight.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-49	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,6	6,2		140	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost complete unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-50	Doughnut	Baked clay	3,5	5,5		57+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		About half of a baked clay loom weight.	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-51		Baked clay	4,9	6,8		73+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Fragment of a loom weight, baked clay	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-52	Spherical	Baked clay	4,5	6,2		56+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Almost half of a baked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-53	Doughnut	Baked clay	3,7	5,7		45+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		1/3 of a baked clay loom weight	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-54		Unbaked clay	3,7	4,5		56+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		Fragment of a loom weight, unbaked clay	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F 1015-55	Spherical	Baked clay	4,4	6		68+x	L. 150	Chambon 1984: 76:2 (1510), 6 (1510a), 7 (1510b)		About half of a baked clay loom weight.	VIIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 3053	Spherical	Baked clay	4,8	6x6,3		1,1x1,2	148	L. 429	De Vaux 1955 : fig. 19.1; Chambon 1984 : 76 :5 NRb		Spherical baked clay loom weight, irregular. Oval hole with wear traces.	VIIId - IA IIB
1	F 3141-01	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,9	6,6x6,8		1,5	201	L. 430	Chambon 1984: 76:1	batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical unbaked clay loom weight with deformed hole. Possibly made on purpose. Wear traces near the hole	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-02	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,7	5,6		1,3	123	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Complete spherical unbaked clay loom weight	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-03	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,3	5,3x5,8		1,2	128	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-04	Doughnut	Baked clay	4	6,1x5,5		1,5	117	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped baked clay loom weight. Almost complete, the hole is filled.	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-05	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,7	6,2x6,4		1,7	145	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped baked clay loom weight. Big hole	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-06	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,9	6,7			144+x	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Apparently washed. Mostly missing.	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-07	Spherical	Baked clay	4,7	5,9		1,2	144	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical baked clay loom weight, complete	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-08	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,8	7,1			171	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical baked clay loom weight, complete	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA
1	F 3141-09	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,5	7,5x7,1		1,5	201	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical baked clay loom weight, complete	Period VII, II-

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
												430 VIIb - IA IIA		
1	F 3141-10	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,8	7,4		1,7	180	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Apparently washed. Mostly missing.	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-11	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,3	5,8		0,7	161	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical unbaked clay loom weight with through hole. Small and irregular hole	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-12	Cylindrical	Unbaked clay	5	5,2		1,6	140	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Cylindrical unbaked clay loom weight. One side of the hole is deformed, almost closed	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-13	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,7	5,9x5,7		1,4	122	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical unbaked clay loom weight. Almost complete. The hole is full of soil.	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-14	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,2	6,1		1,5	142	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-15	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,8	6,2x5,8		1,7	131	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-16	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	3,9	5,9x6,2		1,5	153	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-17	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,4	5,8		1,4	146	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Spherical unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-18	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,7	6,6		1,6	163	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-19	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5	5,9		1	132	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight	Almost complete spherical unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	Period VII, II-	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-20	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,6	6,3		1,7	151	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-21	Doughnut	Baked clay	5,1	8,1		1,8	213	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped baked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-22	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,6	7,2		1,5	190	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped baked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-23	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,1	5,8		1,5	116	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-24	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,7	6,8		1,4	185	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Almost complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-25	Cylindrical	Unbaked clay	5,5	7,3x5,6		1,2x2,1	227	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Cylindrical unbaked clay loom weight. One side of the hole is deformed.	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-26	Spherical	Unbaked clay	4,3	5,9		1x1,8	135	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Spherical unbaked clay loom weight. The oval hole is full of soil	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-27	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,6	6,1x6,7			159	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut unbaked clay loom weight. The oval hole is full of soil	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-28	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,4	6,1		1,6	138	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. Complete	Period VII, II- 430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-29	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5	6,2		1,7	138	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Almost complete spherical unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	Period VII, II-	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
												430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-30	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,3	6,2		1,7	150	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Almost complete doughnut-shaped unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-31	Spherical	Unbaked clay	5,1	6,1		1,5	160	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Almost complete spherical unbaked clay loom weight. The hole is full of soil	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 3141-32	Doughnut	Baked clay	4,6	7,5		1,7	202	L. 430		batch of 32 loom weight Almost complete baked clay loom weight.	Period VII, II-430 VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 2349	Cylindrical	Baked clay	5,4	7,2		1,2x1,6	238	L. 308	Chambon 1984, 76:3		Almost complete baked clay loom weight. Cylindrical hole, well crafted	VIIb - IA IIA
1	F. 19	Spherical	Baked clay	6,2x5,6	6,6x7		1,4	261	L. 17	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:3NR.			VIIId - IA IIB
1	F. 1368	Spherical	Baked clay		10				L. 158	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:4.	Louvre	Baked clay loom weight, spherical.	VIIb - IA IIA
1	F. 2611	Spherical	Baked clay		8,5				L. 371	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:5.	Louvre	Baked clay loom weight, spherical.	VIIb - IA IIA
1	F. 416	Spherical	Baked clay		2,5				L. 68	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:5NR.		Baked clay loom weight, spherical.	VIIId - IA IIB
1	F. 2340	Spherical	Baked clay		7,6				L. 307	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:5NRa.		Baked clay loom weight, spherical.	VIIb - IA IIA
1	F. 1638	Spherical	Baked clay	6,3	7,2				L. 158	Chambon 1984, fig. 76:8.	Louvre	Baked clay loom weight, spherical.	VIIb - IA IIA

Unknown context

1		Spherical	Baked clay	7,6	10		1,9x2,4	576				Spherical baked clay loom weight. No name	
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N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA			
1	F. 209	Cylindrical	Stone	2,5	5,2		1,4	80,2		C1 -3,5m				Circular stone loom weight. Cylindrical hole, well crafted.		
1	F. 4123	Spherical	Baked clay	4,9	5,9			91,1+x		L. 652				Spherical baked clay loom weight. Almost half is preserved		
1	F. 4175	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	4,4	8		1,2	254		641, trou avec 4172				Doughnut unbaked clay loom weight. Almost complete. Fragile		
	F. 4175b	Doughnut	Unbaked clay	5,2	7,9		0,8x1	269						Doughnut unbaked clay loom weight. Almost complete. Fragile		
1	F. 4924	Spherical	White stone	4,5	5,1		0,8	85,5+x		L. 779				Half of a loom weight. White stone. Tendency to delamination.	Niveau Iva	
1	F 3091	Spherical	White stone	5,4	5,8		0,8	206		Under 245-246, 1954				Spherical white stone loom weight. Small through hole. The hole is tilted, hence not a mace head.		
1	F 162	Discoid	Baked clay	2,4	8,4		0,6	209		Carrè 2 1946				Disk-shaped baked clay loom weight. Broken, oblique hourglass hole.		
1	F 156	Discoid	Stone	0,7	9,7		0,8	252		Carrè 2 1946				Disk-shaped white stone loom weight. Polished. Flat base made from a pebble. Hourglass hole.		
1	F. 33	Spherical	Baked clay	2,8	8,7		1,7	145+x		Carrè 1 SW		T 68		Fragment of a spherical loom weight, baked clay. Only one side, with the hole, is preserved.		
1	F. 32	Spherical	Baked clay	4,9	7,2		1,2	236		Carrè 1 SW		T68		Spherical baked clay loom weight, almost complete. Made of two pieces.		
1	F. 265	Cylindrical	Stone	1,9	4,3		nn	30,48+x		C1, 37m				Fragment of a stone loom weight. Cylindrical, irregular.		
1	F. 210		Stone	1,8x2,6	3,5		0,5	35,77		C2, -3,50				Irregular loom weight, made from a perforated stone.		

BASALT RINGS

Early Bronze Age

1	F. 1194	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,5	3,6		1,2	28,61		L. 108 C6 38,50				Basalt ring with asymmetrical big hole, almost cylindrical.	Eneol. Sup. B	
1	F. 4416	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	4,2		1,4	43,3		L. 684				Basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole. Perforation from both sides	EBA Period 1	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 4060	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,6	3,7		1	15,78 +x	L. 640		Basalt rings, broken in half. Asymmetrical		
1	F. 3920	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,5	4,3		1,2	21,64 +x	L. 606		Basalt ring, broken in half	EBA	
1	F 2969	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,7	4,3		1,5	39,58	L. 254			EBA Period 5	
1	F. 827	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	3,3		0,9	29,14	L. 86 C 6 C, 39,80, De Vaux		Basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole	EBA II	
1	F. 865	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,3	4,1		1	35,85	L. 97 C3 NE, 38,75		Basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole. Flatted on both sides	EBA interm.	
1	F. 873	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,9	4,3		1,2	53,46	L. 97 C3 NE, 38,75		Basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole	EBA interm.	
1	F. 3899	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,4	3,6		1,1	42,74	L. 605	L. 605 Periods I-IV, thèse P. de Miroschedij	Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole, polished inside		
1	F. 3898	Cylindrical	Basalt	3,1	5,5		1,7	116	L. 605	L. 605 Periods I-IV, thèse P. de Miroschedij	Basalt ring, big and thick. Hourglass hole. Coarse stone		

Middle Bronze Age

1	F. 4739	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,6	4,3		1,1	38,06	L. 571	Mallet 1973: 17,3. Mallet 1988, fig. 27,3, fig. 27.3 pl. LXXXI.7 (F.3749)	Basalt ring, well crafted. Asymmetrical hourglass hole. Polished inside	MB de Vaux, Period V IIN.BM 571 B,2)	
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Late Bronze Age

1	F. 4352	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,6	3,8		1,2	32,98	Under 673 inf.		Basalt ring, well crafted.	Period VI Dc	
1	F. 3468	Cylindrical	Basalt	2	4		1,2	37,8	Loc. 489 1955		Basalt ring, well crafted. Quasi- cylindrical hole	Period VI Dce	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 4714	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,7	4,4		1,1	55	L 728		Basalt ring, well crafted.	Period VI Dce	
1	F. 428	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,5	3,6		1,1	31,53	C8.E 41,50		Basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole	RB II de Vaux, Period VI JB	
1	F. 189	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,6	4,7		1,3	73,05	C1 -1,75m		Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	Period VI Dc	
1	F. 106	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,6	3,8x3, 5		1,5	31,73	C4, 0,5-1m		Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	Period VI Dc	

Iron Age

1	F. 384	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,3	3,7		1	44,85	57	Chambon 1984: 75.40	Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 338	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,5	2,6		0,8	13,6	345		Rom de vaux Small basalt ring, well crafted. Cylindrical hole	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F. 2423	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,7	4,6		1,2	49,9	332	Chambon 1984: 75.42	Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	332 VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F. 1535	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,6	4		1,2	26,34 +x	Under 112	Chambon 1984: 75.43	Basalt ring, well crafted with cylindrical hole. Broken in half	VIIId - IA IIB	
1	F. 1737	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,7	4		1,2	35,6	151	Chambon 1984: 75.41	Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 3379	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,75	3,5				L. 451	Chambon 1984: 75.44	Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	VIIId - IA IIB	

Unknown context

1	F. 4578	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,9	4,3			19,98 +x	L. 715		Dark stone spindle whorl (basalt?), broken in half. Wide hole, possibly a loom weight		
1	F. 201	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,3	3,9		1,1	50,6	C2 -2,50m		Basalt ring, well crafted with hourglass hole. Polished inside	Period VI	
1	F. 263	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,4	3,7		1,1	28,48	Sond 36,80		Eneolithique Moyen? Basalt ring not perfectly round and symmetrical. Well crafted. Hourglass hole		
1	F. 4938	Cylindrical	Basalt	2,8	4,6		1,6	73,6	L. 775		Basalt ring, thick, well crafted. Big quasi-cylindrical hole		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 3149	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,5	4,2		1,2	40		Under 259 1954			
1	F 5025	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,7	3,7		0,9	35,54		Under 793		Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	T 110
1	F 3748	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	4,4		1,2	49,22				Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole, off-centre.	
1	F. 262	Cylindrical	Basalt	1,8	4		1,2	43,85		Sond. 37,00		Basalt ring, well crafted. Hourglass hole	

BONE SPATULAE AND BEATERS

Early Bronze Age

1	F 1181	Spatula	Bone	12	1,9	0,4				L. 107 ou108 C3 SW 37,50		Bone spatula. Almost complete. One end with a triangular point, the other missing. One side is polished, the other has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed toward the point. Smoothed edges near the tip.	Eneol. Sup.	
1	F. 4110	Spatula	Bone	6,1	1	0,3				Under 609		Bone spatula made from a narrow rib. Triangular point. Smoothed on one side, less on the edges and on the other side. Many parallel scratches on the tip. One end is broken.	EBA Period 3	
1	F 1161	Beater	Bone	8,3	2,5 top, 1,7	2 top, 1,6				L. 99 maison de potier C8 N 38,75	AB I	Whole bone made to get a sharp point. Not particularly smooth	EB I	
1	F 876	Beater	Bone	8,3	2,5 top, 1,8	1,5 top, 1,2				L. 93 C3 N.38,75	AB interm	Whole bone made to get a sharp point. Not particularly smooth	EB interm	
1	F. 3267	Beater	Bone	8	1,8	0,5				L. 276		Bone point without the handle. Almost flat on the preserved end. The tip is polished but not lucid.	EBA Period 2	
1	F. 3983	Beater	Bone	6,9	1,3	0,6				L. 620		Bone point without the handle. Smoothed. Some carvings on the surface with no defined pattern.	EBA Period 3	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 4241	Beater	Bone	8	1	0,6		L. 637			Bone point broken in several parts.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4247	Spatula	Bone	8,8	1,7	0,9		L. 673			Bone point broken in several parts.	EBA Period 1	
1	F 4236	Spatula	Bone	4,3	1,2	0,3		L. 671		L. 671 RB 1961, pl. XXXIII	Small triangular point broken near one end. One side and the edges are smooth. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, rough.	De Vaux EBA Period 1	
1	F 4226	Spatula	Bone	8,4	1,9	0,3		L. 671		L. 671 in RB 1961, pl. XXXIII	Bone spatula with a long point. One end is missing and smoothed alongside the edge. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed toward the point, rough on the other part. Many scratches on the surface	De Vaux EBA Period 1	
1	F. 4202	Spatula	Bone	5,9	2	0,3		L. 659			Bone spatula with a slightly concave point. One side and the edges polished, lower part has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed. The surface near the point is polished.	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 4108	Spatula	Bone	4,8	1,2	0,4		L. 639			Bone spatula with a long-broken point. Smoothed on edges and on one side. The other has rough cancellus bone exposed. Smoothing is better as getting closer to the point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4026	Spatula	Bone					L. 617 dans canal			4 fragments, possibly of the same spatula. Long point, the other end is missing. The spatula is long and narrow. On side is smooth, the other has cancellus bone exposed, rough. Curved point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 3985	Spatula	Bone	6,9	2,2	0,3		L. 622			Bone spatula with long and rounded point. Smooth on one side and on the edges. The lower part has cancellus bone exposed, rough also near the point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4426	Spatula	Bone	5,8	7,7	0,3		L. 685			Bone point of a spatula, broken in 2 pieces. Long point. Smoothed on one side and on the edges. The other side has cancellus bone exposed,	EBA Period 1	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											smoothed toward the point, rough elsewhere.		
1	F. 4334	Spatula	Bone	10	1,9	0,2		L. 673			Bone spatula without the tip. The other end is rounded. Smooth on one side and on the edges. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, ruined.	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 5014	Spatula	Bone	8,9	1,3	0,3		L. 776			Narrow bone spatula. Complete. Long point while the other end is flat. One side is smoothed, the other has cancellus bone exposed, slightly concave and smooth.	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 269	Spatula	Bone	6,9	1,8	0,4		37,50		Period de Vaux AB, Period I-IV?	Bone spatula with triangular tip. On one side is smoothed, the other has cancellus bone exposed. Dirty. Possibly it was smoothed on the tip on both sides.		
1	F 3234	Spatula	Bone	6,6	2,3	0,3		L. 268			Bone spatula with long sharp point. Broken at one end. Smoothed on one side and on the edges, the other side has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed near the point, rough elsewhere.	EBA Period 3	
1	F 3233	Spatula	Bone	11	18	0,4		L. 268			Long and narrow bone spatula. Complete. The other end has just roughly made. Smoothed on one side, the other has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed near the point. Deep scratches near the point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F 3211	Spatula	Bone	5,6	2,2	0,2		Under 268			Fragment of a bone spatula with triangular point. Thin, with one side smoothed. The other has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed near the point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4969	Beater	Bone	13	2	1,3		L. 778			Bone cut in half and roughly sharpened. Polished but not smoothed.	EB/BM	
1	F 3026	Spatula	Bone	6,2	2,3	0,4		L. 271			Fragment of a bone spatula. Only the long point is preserved. Polished on one side, the other has cancellus bone exposed, not well smoothed. Dirty.	EBA Period 3	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F. 3699	Beater	Bone	8,4	1,3	2,1		L. 561			Complete pin beater. One end is left unworked while the other has been cut, polished.	EBA	
1	F. 290	Beater	Bone	8,7	1,5	1,3		C1 37,50		Eneol.	Whole bone with well crafted point. Polished surface with foulings.		
1	F. 279	Beater	Bone	8,2	1,9	1,5		36,20	De Vaux 1947, pl. XII.	Eneol. Period I-IV	Whole bone with well crafted point. It has foulings.		
1	F 4196	Spatula	Bone	9,7	2	0,3		L. 665			Bone spatula with long triangular point. The other end is missing. Concave. One side is polished, the other has cancellus bone exposed, lucid and rough. Smoothed edges	EBA 1	

Middle Bronze Age

1	F. 4968	Beater	Bone	10	1,2	0,9		L. 778			Bone cut in half. Smoothed	EB/MB (Mallet)	
1	F 554	Beater	Bone	6,2	0,9	0,5		C7 SW 41,20			Fragment of a bone with long and thin point. Many oblique signs on the surface	MB IIB	
1	F. 4144	Spatula	Bone	7,2	1,8	0,5		Under 634			Bone spatula with long broken point. The other end is broken. Polished on one side and on the edges, the other has cancellus bone exposed. Smoothed near the point, rough elsewhere	Period V IIN.BM 245 (B,2)	
1	F. 4242	Spatula	Bone	7,2	2,2	0,2		L. 584			Peculiar bone spatula. Edges are damaged, so it's hard to say what the original shape was. Possibly it was polished on one side, the other with cancellus bone exposed	MB (Mallet)	
1	F 3890	Spatula	Bone	8,2	1,9	0,3		L. 600	Mallet 1973: 22,1. Mallet 1988, fig. 32.1, pl. LVXXXIII,4	Period V IIN.BM 600(B,1 ou av.)	Long point, probably belonging to a polished spatula	MB (Mallet)	
1	F 3835	Spatula	Bone	6,9	1,8	0,5		L. 596	Mallet 1973: 22.5. Mallet		Long point, probably belonging to a polished spatula	Period V, IIN.BM	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
									1988: fig. 32,5.			596 (B1ou2)	
1	F 4790	Spatula	Bone	8,5	2,2	0,4		Under 737			Bone spatula partially polished. Smoothed on the point.	Period V, IIS-JM	
1	F. 3656	Beater	Bone	7,1	1,3	0,8		Tombe U(4)		Niveau de Vaux 4	Bone polished point. Sharp tip.		
1	F. 5049	Spatula	Bone	8	1,7	0,3		L. 778			Bone spatula/pin beater, broken at both ends. Polished on both sides. No wear traces, as brand new	EB/MB (Mallet)	
1	F 3780	Beater	Bone	7,2	2,7	1,7		Under 574	Mallet 1973: 22.11. Mallet 1988, fig. 32,11, pl. LVXXXIII,20.		Cut bone to gat a sharp point. Polished	Period de Vaux MB, Period V IIN.BM 576 (B,3)	
1	F 3834	Beater	Bone	11	1,4	0,4		L. 596	Mallet 1973: 22.9. Mallet 1988, fig. 32,9, pl. LVXXXIII,18.		Bone point broken into three pieces but complete. Thin and polished point	Period V IIN.BM 596 (B2ou1)	
1	F 3687	Beater	Bone	8,5	2,3	1,3			Mallet 1973: 22.14. Mallet 1988: fig. 32.14		Whole bone made on the point. Cut to get a thin point. Polished. The shape suggests it could be useful for delicate works.	(MB) Period V IIN.BM 511 (B,3)	
1	F 3743	Beater	Bone	7,8	2	2,1		L. 569	Mallet 1973: 22.10. Mallet 1988, fig. 32,10, pl. LVXXXIII,13.		Whole bone partially made to get a point. Almost entirely polished. Possibly a pin beater.	MB de Vaux, Period V, IIN.BM 569 (B.2)	
1	F 4676	Beater	Bone	6,2	1,3	0,5		L. 719			None point broken at one end. Polished. Wear traces on one side.	De Vaux MB, III-719	

N. Typology Material H D Th Hole W Locus Bibliography Notes Description Dating IAA

Late Bronze Age

1	F. 4291	Spatula	Bone	8,4	1,2	0,3				Under 654		Excav. 1950	Bone spatula. Complete even if broken in many pieces. Triangular point. One side is polished, the other not. Smoothed edges	Period de Vaux RB, Period VI Dc.	
1	F. 4356	Beater	Bone	7,1	1,6	0,8				Under 679			Borer	Period VI Dc	
1	F 3638	Beater	Bone	8	2	1,5				Under 539			Whole bone made to get a point. Almost entirely polished. Possibly a pin beater.	Period VI Dce	Period VII I-68, VIId - IA IIB
1	F 3456	Beater	Bone	6,9	2	1,4				L. 457			Whole bone made to get a point. Almost entirely polished. Possibly a pin beater.	Period VI Dc	
1	F 3648	Beater	Bone	7,2	1,5	1				L. 530			Whole bone made to get a point. Almost entirely polished. Damaged	Period VI Dce	
1	F 4719	Beater	Bone	5,8	1,6	1,2				L. 729			Bone point ruined on the lower side.	Period VI Dc	
1	F 4637	Beater	Bone	8	1,3	0,8				L. 723			Bone point, long and narrow. Damaged on the lower side.	Period VI Dc	

Iron Age

1	F 2431	Beater	Ivory	4,2	1,5	0,2				L. 342, N5b Est	Chambon 1984, 73:13	Period du Fer II Niveau 2 (de Vaux), Period VII, II-342 VIId - IA IIB	Bone point. Long and polished on both sides. Smoothed edges	Iron Age	
1	F 2375	Spatula	Ivory	6,5	2	0,1				L. 322	Chambon 1984, 73:14		Bone spatula partially preserved. The preserved end is rounded; the other one is missing.	Period VII II-322, VIIe - IA IIC	
1	F 1529	Spatula	Ivory	7,5	3,5	0,2				L. 151	Chambon 1984, 73 :15. De Vaux 1951, pl. XVII:7.		Bone spatula, almost complete. The preserved end is rounded; the other one is missing but was probably rounded too.	Period VII II-151, VIId - IA IIB	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA	
1	F. 4213	Spatula	Bone	4,8	1,8	0,4				Under 644		Bone spatula with triangular concave tip. One side is smoothed, the other is rough. Smoothed edges	Period VII II-419, VIIIb - IA IIA	
1	F. 4141	Spatula	Bone	5,9	1,4	0,3				Under 626		Bone spatula with a long point well preserved. One end is missing. Polished on both sides, one has cancellus bone exposed. Smoothed.	Period VII II-150, VIIIb - IA IIB	
1	F. 4102	Spatula	Bone	5	2,2	0,3				Under 628		Fragment of a bone point, possibly belonging to a wide spatula. Polished on one side and on the edges. The other has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed near the point.	Period VII II-173, VIIIb - IA IIA	

Unknown context

1	F. 4217	Spatula	Bone	5,3	2	0,3				Under 653		Three fragments of bone spatula. One has a smoothed end, one is knife-shaped and thick edges. Measures refer to the biggest fragment.		
1	F. 4224	Spatula	Bone	4,7	2	0,2				Under 653		Bone spatula with a well-crafted triangular point. Both sides and edges are smoothed. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed.		
1	F. 4134	Spatula	Bone	6	1,1	0,3				L. 650		Bone spatula with triangular point, made from a narrow rib. Smoothed on both sides, broken at one end.		
1	F. 4125	Beater	Bone	4	1,1	0,2				L. 652		Fragment of a bone triangular point, possibly belonging to a spatula of long-and-narrow family. Damaged but smoothed		
1	F. 4095	Beater	Bone	4,5	1,6	0,3				Under 622		Triangular bone point, sharp. One side and the edges are smoothed. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, polished near the point.	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 3975	Spatula	Bone	8,5	2	0,3				Under 566		Bone spatula with pen-nib point. One edge looks like it has been broken in ancient times, for the		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											fracture is smoothed too. Lower side has cancellus bone exposed, rough. Many scratches on the point.		
1	F. 4279	Spatula	Bone	3,8	1,3	0,3		L. 674			Bone point of a spatula, long and narrow. Polished on both sides and edges.		
1	F. 4517	Spatula	Bone	12	1,7	0,4		L. 701			Bone spatula, sharpened at both ends. One side is smoother than the other.		
1	F. 4841	Spatula	Bone	ca 25	ca 2,5			L. Under 734			Long bone spatula, broken. Rough. Natural finishing on upper side, sharp edges. The other side has cancellus bone exposed, rough.		
1	F. 4949	Spatula	Bone	12	1,5	0,4		L. 789			Long and narrow bone spatula. Broken. Polished on one side and partially on the other, where it has cancellus bone exposed. More polished near the broken end.		
1	F. 4930	Spatula	Bone	7,3	1,7	0,3		L. 783			Long point spatula, broken along edges and at one end. One side is smoother than the other that has cancellus bone exposed, more polished near the point		
1	F. 4915	Spatula	Bone	6,8	1,5	0,2		L. 772			Pen-nib point spatula. Only the point is preserved. Very sharp. Broken along the edge. One side is smoother than the other side that has cancellus bone exposed. They are increasingly smooth as approaching to the point.		
1	F. 4847	Spatula	Bone	10	1,6	0,5		L. 736			Bone spatula (?) without both ends. Made from a whole bone cut in half. Sharp edges.		
1	F 3212	Spatula	Bone	9,9	1,9	0,4		Under 268			Bone spatula with triangular point. One side is polished, the other side has cancellus bone exposed, rough. Smoother on the point.		
1	F 3083	Spatula	Bone	6,3	1,4	0,3					Long and narrow bone spatula with long point. Broken at one end. Polished on one side, The other side has cancellus bone exposed,		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											polished. Deep scratches on the surface		
1	F 3301	Spatula	Bone	5,1	1,4	0,3		Under 280			Fragment of a bone spatula with long point. Polished on both sides. One side has cancellus bone exposed		
1	F 3228	Spatula	Bone	6,7	1,9	0,4		Under 269			fragment of a bone spatula with triangular point. Slightly concave, smoothed edges with cancellus bone exposed, rough.		
1	F 3236	Spatula	Bone	6,5	1,9	0,3		Under 265			Fragment of a bone spatula. Only the long point is preserved. Polished on one side, The other side has cancellus bone exposed, rough		
1	F 1187	Spatula	Bone	5,3	1,5	0,3		L. 107			Fragment of a bone spatula. Only the long point is preserved. Very rounded. Polished on one side, The other side has cancellus bone exposed, smoothed.		
1	F. 4183	Beater	Bone	7,3	1,4	0,7		Under 652			Bone point with epiphysis. Possibly a borer. Polished just near the point.		
1	F. 4290	Beater	Bone	8,4	1,4	0,8		Under 637		T85	Possibly a borer. Sharp point		
1	F. 4292	Beater	Bone	9,7	2	0,6		Under 654			Bone pin beater almost complete. Big, damaged in several areas, but with lucid wear traces		
1	F. 4294	Beater	Bone	6,4	1,5	0,8		Under 643			Small bone pin beater. Many wear traces on the polished surface.		
1	F. 5094	Beater	Bone	4,7	1,2	0,5		L. 805			Polished point. Sharp and lucid.		
1	F. 4950	Beater	Bone	8	1,7	0,5		L. 789			Whole bone cut and sharpened. One end is missing. Smooth		
1	F 3150	Beater	Bone	6,3	2	1,7		Under 254			Whole bone, short, cut and made to get a point. Smoother near the point.		
1	F 2877a	Beater	Bone	12	Top 1,5; 0,9	0,8		Est de 221			Whole bone, long and narrow, made only at the point. Cut transversely to get a smoothed and thin point. The shape suggests it could be useful for delicate works.		

NEEDLES

Early Bronze Age

1	F 3148		Bone	5,7	0,2x0,3					L. 267			Probably the tip of a bone needle. Polished.	EBA Period 5	
1	F 1167		Bone	7,1	0,5					L. 105 C8 N 38			Probably the tip of a bone needle. Polished.	Eneol. Sup. B	
1	F. 866		Bone	5,8	0,3					L. 97. C3 NE, 38,75		AB interm	Probably the tip of a bone needle. Polished.	EBA interm	
1	F. 4017		Bone	3,5	0,9	0				L. 618 dans briques écroulées			Bone needle with flat head and circular hole. Broken	EBA Period 3	
1	F. 4599		Bone	3	1,5	1				L. 718		De Vaux Chalcolithique supérieur	Bone needle with flat head and circular hole. Broken	EBA (Mallet) Mallet	
1	F. 5029		Bone	9	0,3					L. 776			Bone needle with a small hole. Flatted eye.	EBA Period 1	
1	F. 5018		Bone	3,2	0,8	0				L. 555			Eye needle with incomplete hole. Flat head	BA/BM	
1	F. 229		Bone	8,2	0,7x0,5					C2 -3,50		Period de Vaux AB, Period I-IV?	Bone needle without eye		

Middle Bronze Age

1	F 2814		Bronze	8,8	0,3					Sotto 364 (=394)		MB/RB Niv. 4	Thin bronze needle. Complete. The eye is formed by bending the upper part of shaft on itself.	Period V	
1	F 2914		Bronze	11,1	0,2					L. 245	Mallet 1973: 21,3. Mallet 1988: 31,3.	From the same locus one spindle whorl	Thin bronze needle. Complete. Slightly bended	BM (B,2)	
1	F. 4827		Bone	6	0,5x0,3					L. 721 démolit.		From the same locus conical loom weights	Small bone needle with rectangular and flatted head. Complete	Period V	
1	F. 4874		Bone	6,2	0,3					L. Under 751		From the same locus	Part of a bone object, maybe a needle. Broken. No hole	Period V	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
											one perforated sherd		
1	F. 3705		Bone	5,2	0,3x0,4			L. 568			Probably the tip of a bone needle	BM Mallet	

Late Bronze Age

1	F 2115		Bronze	11,9	0,2			sotto 149 (=229)			Thin bronze needle, slightly bended with eye preserved. The eye is some cm below the top. Possibly a toggle pin	Period VI	
1	F 2121		Bronze	8,4	0,2			Sotto 206 (=231)			Thin bronze needle. Broken near the eye	Period VI	
1	F 2745		Bronze	15,8	0,3			Sotto 306 (=376)		RB Niv. 4	Fragment of the point of a bronze needle	Period VI	
1	F 329		Bronze	8,1	0,2			C3 SW			Thin bronze needle, slightly bended with eye preserved. The eye is some cm below the top.	Period VI	
1	F 2744		Bronze	6,7	0,2			Sotto 306 (=376)		RB Niv. 4	Thin bronze needle. Broken near the eye	Period VI	
1	F 2800		Bronze	9	0,3			Sotto 306 (=376)		RB Niv. 4	Thin bronze needle, bended and damaged. Corroded near the eye	Period VI	
1	F. 191		Bone	4,1	0,8			C1, -2,50 m			Short bone needle without the point. Wide and flat with circular hole	Period VI	
1	F 3494		Bronze	10,4	0,2			Under 489		From the same Locus one basalt ring	Bronze needle broken near the eye. Very thin	Period VI	
1	F 3419		Bronze	9,5	0,2			Under 458		From the same Locus one spindle whorl	Bronze needle. Complete. Bended, the eye is a hole in the body	Period VI	
1	F 3541		Bronze	11,8	0,3			Under 233			Bronze needle. Complete. Bended, the eye is a hole in the body	Period VI	
1	F 3524		Bronze	7	0,25			Under 482			Bronze needle broken near the eye. Bended.	Period VI	
1	F 3584		Bronze	4,4	0,2			Under 474			Bronze needle without the tip. Bended. The eye is formed by bending the shaft on itself	Period VI	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Locus	Bibliography	Notes	Description	Dating	IAA
1	F 4671	Bronze	13,8	0,25				L. 723		From the same Locus a beater	Long bronze needle with a big, thin eye	Period VI	

Iron Age

1	F. 3381	Bronze	4,7	0,4					Chambon 1984, 71:30.		Short and thick bronze needle, complete.	VII b II-448	
1	F 2345	Bronze	115,6	0,4				L4d (Sud) L. 307	Chambon 1984: 71,18		Long bronze needle with eye. Bended	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 2747	Bronze	7,4	0,25				Sotto 352 W, =372	Chambon 1984: 72,5		Bronze needle. Broken. The eye is formed by bending the shaft on itself	VIIb - IA IIA	
1	F 2412	Bronze	8,2	0,2				N5b, NW, Loc. 345	Chambon 1984: 72,8	From the same Locus one basalt ring	Thin bronze needle. Complete. The eye is formed by hammering and punching the shaft.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F 2419	Bronze	9,2	0,4				N5b, SE, L. 339	Chambon 1984: 72,7		Big bronze needle. Complete. The eye is formed by bending the shaft on itself	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F 403	Bronze	8,3	0,5				L. 68	Chambon 1984: 71,31		Big bronze needle without eye. Due to its rectangular section, possibly not a needle.	VII d - IA IIB	
1	F 423	Bronze	8,5	0,3				L. 71	Chambon 1984: 71,6		Thin bronze needle. Bended to 90°. The eye is formed by bending the shaft on itself	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F 2987	Bronze	6,5	0,3				L. 419	Chambon 1984: 72,4		Thin bronze needle, broken and bended. The eye is formed by bending the shaft on itself	VII b - IA IIA	
1	F. 4142	Bone	4,5	1,3	0			L. 150			Bone bodkin with circular hole. Flat	VII d - IA IIB	

Unknown context

1	F. 4136	Bone	4,9	0,6x0,3				L. 654			Possibly the tip of a bone needle. Polished	VII b - IA IIA?	
1	F. 5015	Bronze	11,7	0,3				L. 555 déblais			Bronze needle. Complete. Well crafted, probably late.		

LAHUN

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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SPINDLES

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	AN 1889.1198A	Spindle		Wood	12	0,9					Spindle preserved for only part of the length, broken at both ends.	Ashmolean Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	4,7		0,7	19,7		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Heavily encrusted on one surface, quite clean the other and with clear traces of Manchester Museum.	
		Fibres		Flax							Several threads wrapped around the shaft under the spindle whorl, some very fine, some doubled. They all appear quite worn. They show all a S-twist, one is certainly plied.	
1	30.a	Spindle		Wood	38,3	1,13			37		Wooden spindle, complete. Tapering toward the point. Top with long spiral groove.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,4	5,2		1,04			Cylindrical spindle whorl, near the top. Highly damaged and hole broadened on both sides. Some thread stuck in the hole.	
		Fibres		Flax							Thread in the hole, not clearly visible.	
1	30.b	Spindle		Wood	23,7	1,46			32		Wooden spindle, complete. Top with a long and deep spiral groove. Tapering toward the point. Some areas of the shaft appear damaged.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,65	4,98		1,04			Cylindrical spindle whorl, near the top of the spindle. Well shaped, slightly encrusted on the upper surface. Hole slightly warped.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
		Fibres		Flax						Several coils of thread around the shaft under the spindle whorl. It is S, 2s. Quite worn. One knot is also present. Angle of twist of the best-preserved point is between 39 and 46°. Thread diameter between 0,4 and 0,5 mm.	
	30.c.1	Spindle		Wood	34,3	0,86			14+x	Wooden spindle, complete. Top with a long and deep spiral groove. Tapering toward the point. Some areas of the shaft appear encrusted.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,48	4,3			0,84	Cylindrical spindle whorl, half preserved. Heavily encrusted on upper and lower sides.	Manchester Museum
	30.c.2	Spindle		Wood	12,6	0,95			18	Wooden spindle, broken at both ends. Slightly covered by a patina on the surface.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,61	4,66			0,8	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	
1	30.c.3	Spindle		Wood	24,7	1,19			41	Wooden spindle broken at the point, top preserved a very well crafted spiral groove. Well preserved wood but slightly worn where thread was wound up.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3,1	4,8			1,1	Wooden spindle whorl, complete. Thick and well shaped. Covered by patina and encrustations on all sides.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	30.c.4	Spindle		Wood	13,2-x	1			24+x		Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken. Long spiral groove which makes almost two laps. Spindle whorls much lower than the groove, probably not in original position.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	5		1,1				Middle Kingdom	
	30.c.5	Spindle		Wood							Middle Kingdom		Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl		Wood								Middle Kingdom	
	30.c.6	Spindle		Wood							Middle Kingdom		Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl		Wood								Middle Kingdom	
	30.c.7	Spindle		Wood							Middle Kingdom		Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl		Wood								Middle Kingdom	
	30.c.8	Spindle		Wood							Middle Kingdom		Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl		Wood								Middle Kingdom	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	30.c.9	Spindle		Wood						Middle Kingdom	Manchester Museum	
		Spindle whorl		Wood						Middle Kingdom	Manchester Museum	
	30.c.10	Spindle		Wood						Middle Kingdom	Manchester Museum	
		Spindle whorl		Wood						Middle Kingdom		
1	686.d	Spindle		Wood	16,8	0,92			20	New Kingdom XX dyn.	Wooden spindle broken at both ends.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,63	4,85		0,84			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and preserved. Covered by a thin patina on all sides. Lower side of the hole slightly warped.	
1	UC7310a	Spindle		Wood	23,7	0,97			9,34	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, complete but damaged. Long and deep spiral groove at the top, shaft tapering toward the point.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310b	Spindle		Wood	21,8	0,93			3,96	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken. Top missing and quite damaged. Tapering toward the point.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7306i	Spindle		Wood	23,7	1,27			31	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, complete. One end preserves a long and well carved spiral groove and the other tapers to the point.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3,1	4,4		1,36x 1,19			Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite thick. Well preserved wood, with traces of encrustation on both sides, especially on the upper part, and on part of the shaft. Traces of fibres visible on the encrusted surface. Irregular hole.	
1	UC7306ii	Spindle		Wood; linen	22,9	0,8			28	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, almost complete but broken along the spiral groove at the top. Modern flax spun by Ivor Willard of Passmore Edwards Museum, 1983.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3,2	4,6		0,95			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very thick and with worn surfaces.	
1	UC7307a	Spindle		Wood	9,87	0,88x 1			27,7	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. Top with a spiral groove and traces of fibres.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,92	4,87		0,84x 0,99				
1	UC7307b	Spindle		Wood	9,45	1,1			25,75	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. Top with a spiral groove	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3	4,96					Cylindrical spindle whorl, very thick. Worn surface. One side covered by a thick encrustation, the other clear.	
1	UC7307c	Spindle		Wood	10,37	0,98			18,29	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. Top with a spiral groove. Good quality wood, different from that of the whorl.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3	4,65		0,98			Cylindrical spindle whorl, very thick. Worn surface. One side covered by a thick encrustation, the other clear.	
1	UC7307d	Spindle		Wood	11,36	1,18			27,58		Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. No groove.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,18		1,15			Cylindrical spindle whorl, not particularly thick. Well preserved wood, no traces of encrustation, only a light patina. Irregular hole.	
1	UC7307e	Spindle		Wood	11,26	1,15			4,83+x		Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. Top with a spiral groove	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,52	4,84		1,06	21,44		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved wood with only a thin patina on the surface. Hole very warped. Mark on the side of the whorl.	
1	UC7307f	Spindle		Wood	11,07	0,99			21,94		Wooden spindle partially preserved. Top with long spiral groove, very well crafted.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,94	4,98		0,97			Cylindrical spindle whorl, not particularly thick. Well preserved wood, with traces of encrustation. Irregular hole.	
1	UC7307g	Spindle		Wood	13	0,94			24,68		Wooden spindle, broken just beneath spindle whorl. Top with a spiral groove	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,75	4,61		1,08			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved wood with thin layer of a patina on both sides. Hole very warped.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7307h	Spindle		Wood	8,14	0,99			3,16+x	Late Middle Kingdom	Fragment of a wooden spindle with long spiral groove preserved. Place of whorl (not preserved) evident on the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7308a	Spindle		Wood	9,54	0,77			11,31	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,14	4,44		0,7			Small and thin spindle whorl, very damaged. Wood very different than other whorls, more compact.	
1	UC7308b	Spindle		Wood	10,68	0,81			12,03	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken. At the top a v-shape notch.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,4	4,37		0,7			Small and thin spindle whorl, very damaged.	
1	UC7308c	Spindle		Wood	8,9	0,95			14,79	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken beneath spindle whorl. Preserved end is flat with v-shape notch. Light wood, tends to delaminate.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,58	4,77		0,76			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick, well-preserved wood, compact. Wooden Manchester Museum visible on the surface. Hole broadened and warped.	
1	UC59380a	Spindle		Wood	20,3	1,12			29,9	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden spindle, almost complete. Top with a spiral groove, shaft thickening in the middle and tapering toward the point which is missing. .	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,54	5		1,08			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Upper surface covered by patina, lower by a thick layer of encrustation.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC59380b	Spindle		Wood	24,6	1,08			21,45		Wooden spindle, complete. One end rounded, the other pointed, central part thickened. Top with a spiral groove. Badly damaged by insects. Traces of fibres on the shaft.	Petrie Museum	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,83	4,84	0,82x 0,7				Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete but damaged by insects. White dots on the surface, possibly a mould.		
1	UC59380c	Spindle		Wood	17,3	0,92			13,33		Wooden spindle, broken at the lower end. Top with a roughly cut notch.	Petrie Museum	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,55	4,58	0,74x 0,82				Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Heavily encrusted on the upper surface, clean on the lower one. Quite warped.		
1	EA50979 EA50979c	Spindle		Wood	12,2	0,8			38,01		Ficus sycomorus	Wooden spindle with a groove for fastening fibres covered by a second spindle whorl. Broken beneath spindle whorls.	British Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,2	4,4	1,2			Cartwright 1998: 99	Pinaceae family, probably Abies sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Both whorls are well attached to the shaft, even if Spindle becomes difficult to use. Encrusted surface.	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	4,7	1,2				Ficus sycomorus	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Encrusted on the lower surface. Incised X mark on the side.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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SPINDLE WHORLS

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	AN 1889.1198B	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,8	5		0,5	8,5		Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl chipped and cracked. Soft wood, quite worn. Small hole, highly ruined.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1198C	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,6	4,6		0,6	11,1		Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, slightly chipped on the side. Cut from a small branch. Soft wood better preserved than B. tree ring well visible. Hole warped probably by wedges.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1198D	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,2	4,8		0,8	11,5		Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with a small fragment of spindle inside the hole. Dirty surface, not encrusted but just dirty.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1203	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone	2,3	6,5		1x1,2	98,3	Petrie Museum, Kahun, Gurob and Hawara, pp. 27-28.	Middle Kingdom	Very large and short spindle whorl, well shaped, chipped in several areas. No wear traces are clearly detectable. Smooth surface.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1204	Spindle whorl	Conical	Limestone	3,2	4,5		0,7x0,8	65	Petrie Museum, Kahun, Gurob and Hawara, pp. 27-28.	Middle Kingdom	Conical shaped limestone spindle whorl, chipped on one side and near the upper hole. Traces of Manchester Museum highly visible, not polished. Wear traces on the upper hole.	Ashmolean Museum
1	EA70885	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,4	3,8		0,9	10,16	Cartwright 1998: 99 (listed as 70585)	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick, good quality wood even if worn on one side. Warped hole.	British Museum

N.		Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	EA70884	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,7	1,1	20,45	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped, encrusted on both sides. Incised cross shaped mark.	British Museum
1	EA70883	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,2	1,2	12,51	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Ficus sycomorus	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Encrusted on all sides and quite worn and damaged by insects. Incised cross-shaped mark.	British Museum
1	EA70889	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,4	4,5	1,2	18,71	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle-whorl, complete. Thick, well shaped but not perfectly rounded. Hole very warped. On one surface traces of Manchester Museum are visible. Partially encrusted. Incised mark.	British Museum
1	EA70888	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	4,4	0,9	16,65	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick, with traces of encrustation on all sides. Signs of Manchester Museum on one sides. Incised mark.	British Museum
1	EA70887	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,8	5,4	1,2	22,6	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick, traces of Manchester Museum on one side. Hole warped on one side probably by wedges. Partially encrusted. Incised mark.	British Museum
1	EA70886	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,4	4,1	1,2	13,78	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick, worn on one side. Warped hole. Incised mark.	British Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	EA70882	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	3	4,8	1,1	29,6	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick and well shaped. On one side shows traces of Manchester Museum, on the other a thin layer of patina. Well rounded hole, only partially warped. Incised mark.	British Museum
1	30.c.11	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0,97	3,7	0,3x0,38	5,2		Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite small with a small hole. Different type of cut and wood from other whorls. Very well shaped.	Manchester Museum
1	30.c.12	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,62	5,2	1,3	23,8		Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Large and thick, with large and cylindrical hole. Slightly warped.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7309a	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,32	4,7	1,08	15,08		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Covered by a thin layer of patina. Hole warped probably by the use of wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309b	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,52	4,4	1,07	17,58		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Covered by a thin layer of patina. Hole slightly warped probably by the use of wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309c	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,47	4,6	1,08	18,5		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Slightly encrusted on both sides. One hole on the surface, probably caused by an insect.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309d	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,09	4,8	1,16	15,78		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Good quality, compact wood. Slightly encrusted on one surface, the other appears worn. Hole slightly warped.	Petrie Museum

N.		Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7309e	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,54	4,7	1,09	16,14		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Good quality, compact wood. Slightly encrusted on one surface, the other appears worn. Hole slightly warped but not due to wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309f	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,84	5,2	1,04	23,56		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, very well shaped and preserved. Covered by a thin layer of patina. One side with evident signs of Manchester Museum. Hole warped probably by the use of wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309g	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,25	5,5	1,21	23,75		Late Middle Kingdom	Large, cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. One side quite worn. Traces of encrustation on the surface. Warped hole, not due to wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309h	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,37	4,5	1,32	13,61		Late Middle Kingdom	Small cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite thick and well preserved. Traces of Manchester Museum on the surface. Hole completely warped by wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309i	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,85	4,5	0,83	9,92		Late Middle Kingdom	Small cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Surface covered of scratches, possibly signs of Manchester Museum. No traces of patina or encrustation. Small and warped hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309l	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,65	4	1,18	12,79		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small, thick, quite well preserved. Thick layer of encrustation on both sides.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7309m	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,74	4,2	1,02	12,51		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small, thick, very well preserved. Traces of Manchester Museum on one side. Hole warped by use of wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309n	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,5	1,26	15,08		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite small, thick and well preserved. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation on both sides. Hole warped by use of wedges.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309o	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,76	4	0,79	7,86		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small and clean, with incisions on one surface, possibly signs of Manchester Museum: on the other side, hole completely damaged and oval.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309p	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,83	4,2	0,8	8,15		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small and clean, with traces of Manchester Museum on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7309q	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,25	3,4	1,05	8,8		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small, thick and well preserved. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation on both sides.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310c	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,44	3,9	0,85	6,83		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very worn and with warped hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310d	Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	2,47	5x4,1 2	1,03x 1,1	21,09		Late Middle Kingdom	Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete. Damaged in several points, especially on the hole. Woodknot on the side. Traces of encrustation.	Petrie Museum

N.		Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7310e	Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	2,35	4,8x4,26		1,06	15,92		Late Middle Kingdom	Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete. Perfectly shaped. Encrusted on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310f	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,62	4,3		1,06	16,04		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved, traces of Manchester Museum on both sides. Slightly encrusted on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310g	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,37	4,7		1,3	14,99		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Worn and rotten wood.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310h	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,42	4,6		1,4	13,78		Late Middle Kingdom. K28	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved but warped hole. Covered by a thin layer of patina.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310i	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,7	4,7		1,25	18,91		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite well preserved but hole slightly warped. Covered by a whitish patina.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310l	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,31x5,01		1,19x1,23	15,95		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Slightly diagonal sides. Hole slightly warped. Traces of encrustation on the side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7310m	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,13	5		1,19	19,03		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very well preserved, hole warped. Covered by a thin layer of patina.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7305	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Limestone	3,5	4,4		1,28	84,25		Late Middle Kingdom	Domed limestone spindle whorl. Very thick and flattened top.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7311a	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,67	4,1	0,8x0,7	15,64		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well preserved. One side encrusted and the other covered by a thin patina.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7311b	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,49	4,27x4,54	1,17	13,39		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite well preserved, traces of encrustation on both sides. Warped hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7311c	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,6	1,31x1,1	17,24		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite well preserved, traces of patina on both sides. Warped hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7311d	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,36	4,2	0,87	13,47		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite well preserved, traces of patina on both sides. Warped hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7311e	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,04	3,99x4,1	0,38	5,45		Late Middle Kingdom	Small and thin cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small hole. Traces of a pinkish material on the surface.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7311f	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,56	5,03x5,18	0,59	14,78+x		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole and traces of a thread (modern?). Quite well preserved. Whitish substance on the surface.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7470 ii	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,1	6,93x6,45	0,72	20,48		Late Middle Kingdom	Dome spindle whorl, complete. Very smoothed wood, completely different from other whorls. Very large and thin. Lid?	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7470	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	0,68	6,1	0,46	13		Late Middle Kingdom	Dome spindle whorl, complete. Very smoothed wood, completely different from other whorls. Very large and thin. Hole neatly cut, no traces of wear or wedges. Lid?	Petrie Museum
1	UC7471	Lid	Discoid	Wood	1,07	6,1	0,4	19,88		Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden disc with a circular area roughly cut out, remains of central peg. Lid?	Petrie Museum
1	UC7283		Conical	Wood	5,59	8,5	1,19	92,79		Middle Kingdom	Not a spindle whorl.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7304	Spindle whorl?	Dome	Limestone	3,3	6,6	0,9x1,1	137		Late Middle Kingdom	Domed limestone spindle whorl, complete. Very large and heavy. Hole slightly larger on the base, upper side with wear traces. Thin radian incisions on the base. Slight incised marks on base.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 i	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,7	4,8	1	20,5		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped with one side of the hole well rounded and the other warped by wedges. On one side two small holes and a wood knot. Deeply incised mark.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 ii	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	4,7	1,15x1,2	13		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, one surface and side completely worn with traces of a whitish substance (paint or mould?). Other surface less worn and with no traces of this substance.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC63840 iii	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,8	5,2	1,2x1,3	23,1		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped with holes slightly warp (like it was used with a rope, but it is probably an error of cut since it is deeper inside the hole). Quite well preserve with just small traces of dirt and a whitish substance. Incised mark on the side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 iv	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,7	1,19x0,9	15,6		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, not perfectly rounded, clean surfaces, side dirty. Two vertical incisions on the side might be marks. Some traces of Manchester Museum are also detectable on one surface. Hole completely warps at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 v	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,39	5,2	1,17x1,24	21,7		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped, different wood with clear wood rings. Some signs of Manchester Museum are also detectable. Traces of wedges are visible. Two parallel lines incised on the side might be a mark. Wood perfectly preserved	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 vi	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	5,3	1,09x0,95	16,6		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped, low quality wood, completely worn and with several holes made by insects. Two marks scratch on the side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 vii	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,56	4,8x4,9	1,2x1,17	17,8		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped but oval, good quality of wood, well preserved. Quite dirty on all the surfaces. Hole warp by wedges. Two marks seem to have been scratched on the side, very thin lines.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC63840 viii	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,9	5,1x5,25	1,2x1,4	28		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped but oval, good quality of wood with wood rings still visible. Surfaces are clean. Big hole, specially on one side, quite warp. Mark incised on side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 ix	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,9	1,3	20		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well shaped, worn surfaces. Wood rings very visible. One surface is dirtier than the other. Big hole with worn <i>holes</i> . Mark incised on the side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840x	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	4,6x4,26	1,19x1	17,9		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite well shaped but oval, one surface is perfectly clean as if recut recently. Side and the other surface are dirtier. Hole tapering towards one end completely warp. Deep mark incised on the side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840xi	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	4,4	9,6x10,1	17		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, very well shaped, all surfaces are dirty. Tapering hole perfectly round. Mark on the side, very lightly incised.	Petrie Museum
1	UC63840 xii	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,7	5	9x1	27,5		Late Middle Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, very well shaped. All surfaces are slightly dirty, but some signs of Manchester Museum are detectable. Tapering hole well rounded with just a few signs of wedges on the smaller side. Mark on the side, very lightly incised.	Petrie Museum
1	EA50972	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	5,1	1,3	23,31	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle-whorl, complete. Wood very damaged with traces of burnt spots.	British Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	EA50971	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,1		1,2	19,85	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle-whorl, slightly larger at one side. Hole larger on one side (1,4), probably due to use of wedges. Traces of Manchester Museum.	British Museum
1	EA50973	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,5	4,4x4,8		0,8	14,58	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle-whorl, complete. Quite thick, damaged by insects and covered by encrustation. Hole warped by wedges.	British Museum
1	EA50974	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,1		1,2	13,64	Cartwright 1998: 98	Probably <i>Ficus Sycomorus</i>	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very worn wood with traces of burnt spots. Cylindrical hole, quite clear-cut. Incised mark on the side.	British Museum
1	EA50975	Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	2,6	4,6x5,4		1,1	26,53	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete. Warped hole due to wedges. Incised mark on the side.	British Museum
1	EA50977	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,7	5,2		1,1	22,56	Cartwright 1998: 98	<i>Ficus sycomorus</i>	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very worn, damaged by insects. Incised mark on the side.	British Museum
1	EA50976	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,3	5,1		1,2	17,82	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Encrusted on all sides. Incised mark on the side.	British Museum
1	EA50978	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,7	4,9		1,3	20,71	Cartwright 1998: 98	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Thin layer of patina on one side. Burnt spots. Incised mark on the side.	British Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution									
1	431	Spinning bowl								Kahun, Gurob and Hawara. pl. XIII, 58. Griffith, A S. 1910. p. 41. Early Mediterranean Migrations, p. 28.	Pottery	13	base 4,6 bordo rim					Middle Kingdom	Pottery bowl with two loops fixed in the bottom but not joining together. Complete, just chipped on the rim. Under the loops wear traces due to thread rubbing are not visible but can be felt. Slightly leaning.	Manchester Museum
1	UC6665	Spinning bowl and wooden models	Model								Wood	1,4	3,2					Middle Kingdom. From Lahun West Hill Tomb N17, the only burial equipped with wooden models at Lahun.	Small model of a spinning bowl with two loops on the bottom and a hole to fix it to the workshop model (not preserved).	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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FIBRES

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	56.21.335	Thread								Knotted length of natural flax mixed with red and black wool. Linen threads are of two types. One type is S, 2s quite worn with traces of probable splicing. Another fragment was spun S, 2z and some fibres were not spun or twisted at all. Knots are also presents. Thread diameter varies a lot, between 0,4 and 0,8 mm, because it is highly worn.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.21.333	Thread								Similar to 335. Knotted length of natural flax mixed with few black wools. Linen threads are of two types. One type is S, 2s, quite worn with visible splicing points. Another fragment was spun S, 2z. Thread diameter varies a lot, between 0,38 and 0,7 mm, because it is highly worn.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.21.332	Thread								Ball of yarn made of unspun flax, which is mixed with other spun threads, much more worn. Fibers were joint using splicing in z direction and twisted in s direction. Fibers appear darker and shinier than threads. Several different threads are included, the thicker has a Z-ply with three or more s-spun threads. The other threads appear as S, 2s. Threads diameter varies a lot from point to point, due to their preservation. The thinner thread has a diameter of 0,4 mm (35.5°), the thicker 1 mm (35°).	Liverpool World Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	56.21.334	Thread								Ball of yarn of extremely fine linen, extremely worn. Some fibres are present on the surface, both unspun flax (?) and red wool. On one side there is an orange stain. It seems that under the threads were thicker threads and a sort of padding. Thread appear S-ply, single twist not visible. Thread diameter varies a few, between 0,2 and 0,25. Angle of twist ° and 45°, definitely tight. between	Liverpool World Museum
1	693	Yarn						Griffith 1910, 61.	New Kingdom (XVIII-XIX Dyn.)	Length of fine, natural-coloured flax thread, knotted at both ends. Skein of thread (looks like it is ready for dyeing) in orange colour, doubled but very fine. Maybe different threads, some single, some doubled. Spectacular. What look like clearly doubled threads are splice points.	Manchester Museum
1	6194	Artefact								Piece of leather twisted as if to form part of a handle; mingled with this is a fragment of dark blue wool. Objects 6171 to 6195 were found together.	Manchester Museum
	114.b.i	Fibres						Griffith 1910, 19. Cooke 1993, 14.	Medieval	Weavers' reuse. Combining of wool, blue, red and white.	Manchester Museum
	114.b.ii	Fibres							Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.c	Fibres							Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	114.d	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.d.i	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.d.iiia	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.d.iiib	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.e.i	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
	114.e.i	Fibres		Wool					Medieval	Woolen fibres.	Manchester Museum
1	114.e.iii	Textile		Wool/lin en				Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Medieval?	Dark blue wool fragments which are less than 1 cm sq.	Manchester Museum
1	114.e.iv	Fibres		Wool/lin en				Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Medieval?	Dark blue wool fragments which are less than 1.5 cm sq.	Manchester Museum
	114.f	Textile		Linen						Linen textile wound up, with woollen fibres on the surface.	Manchester Museum
	114 A	Fur								Fur.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.a.i	Ball of threads		Linen				Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Small ball of yarn very, fine but highly worn. S-plied where visible.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	114.i.a.ii	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Small ball of yarn very, fine but highly worn. S-plyed where visible.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.i	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom		Manchester Museum
1	114.i.ii	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Ball of unspun yarn, fibres spliced and prepared for actual spinning or plying.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.iv	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Threads wound around tow, possibly part of a net since knots are present.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.ix	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Small ball of thread, core not visible. Yarn highly worn, s-twist where visible.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.vii	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Ball of unspun thread, prepared for spinning through splicing.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.x	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Ball of unspun yarn, fibres spliced and prepared for actual spinning or plying.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.xi	Ball of threads		5,4x4				Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Thick yarn wound around a pottery sherd. Z-cabled.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.xii	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Group of different yarns, some very fine. Some are clearly z-spun, S-plyed.	Manchester Museum
1	114.i.viii	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Small ball of yarn, core not visible. Yarn very worn, where visible s-twist.	Manchester Museum
	114.I.ii	Thread								Remains of a yarn, completely worn.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	114.I.2.ii	Ball of threads								Ball of yarn made of at least two different threads. A darker one S, 2s; a lighter one Z, 2s.	Manchester Museum
	114.I.xvi	Thread								Bag full of a mixture of threads, soil and wood.	Manchester Museum
1	694.a	Yarn						Griffith 1910 p. 61.	New Kingdom (XVIII-XIX Dyn.)	Skein of linen threads, different between each other. Mostly S, 2s, some Z, 2s.	Manchester Museum
1	694.b	Yarn						Griffith 1910 p. 61.	New Kingdom (XVIII-XIX Dyn.)	Knotted end of a length of natural-coloured flax thread, with some red thread also knotted in it. S-plied.	Manchester Museum
1	695.a	Ball of threads					94	Griffith 1910 p. 61.	Middle Kingdom	A large ball of finely twisted linen thread, with part of a netting needle stuck in it. S-plied.	Manchester Museum
1	695.b	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 61.	Middle Kingdom	A large ball of finely twisted linen thread, s-spun, S-plied.	Manchester Museum
1	695.c	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	A large ball of finely twisted linen thread, s-spun, S-plied.	Manchester Museum
1	695.d	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910 p. 19.	Middle Kingdom	Textile wound around thick and coarse threads (?) and pottery fragments.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7509a	Bunches						Cartwright 1998: 101.	Late Middle Kingdom	Five strips of flax fibre for the preparation of linen yarn.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7509b	Bunches	Flax	23				Cartwright 1998: 101.	Late Middle Kingdom	Five strips of flax fibre for the preparation of linen yarn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7509c	Bunches	Flax	17				Cartwright 1998: 101.	Late Middle Kingdom	Five strips of flax fibre for the preparation of linen yarn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7509d	Bunches	Flax	12				Cartwright 1998: 101.	Late Middle Kingdom	Five strips of flax fibre for the preparation of linen yarn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7509e	Bunches	Flax	14				Cartwright 1998: 101, 109.	Late Middle Kingdom	Five strips of flax fibre for the preparation of linen yarn	Petrie Museum
1	UC7511	Balls	Linen		3,9			Cartwright 1998: 101, 109.	Late Middle Kingdom	Ball of yarn wound around a pottery sherd. 5 Z-cabled threads, single twist s.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7511 ii	Balls	Linen		3,6			Cartwright 1998: 101.	Late Middle Kingdom	Ball of yarn, S, 4s.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7511		Linen						Late Middle Kingdom	Knotted skein of yarn. S, 2s.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7511		Linen						Late Middle Kingdom	Skein of yarn, S-plied, very worn.	Petrie Museum
4	UC8496 A i a	Bunches	Flax							Knotted bunches of flax; from a batch of plant material UC 8496 divided into two parts, A retained in Petrie Museum, B sent to Kew for identification, 1973 and never come back.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
UC8496 A i b	Bunches	Flax								Knotted bunches of flax; from a batch of plant material UC 8496 divided into two parts, A retained in Petrie Museum, B sent to Kew for identification, 1973 and never come back.	Petrie Museum
UC8496 A i c	Bunches	Flax								Knotted bunches of flax; from a batch of plant material UC 8496 divided into two parts, A retained in Petrie Museum, B sent to Kew for identification, 1973 and never come back.	Petrie Museum
UC8496 A iii	Thread	Goat hair								Red yarn made of short and thick fibres.	Petrie Museum
UC8496 A ii	Thread	Goat hair								Undyed yarn made of short and thick fibres.	Petrie Museum
UC8496 A iv	Piece of bronze	Bronze								Unknown purpose, put in box with 8496 A i-iii.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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WEIGHTS AND HEDDLE JACKS

N.		Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	EA67669	Net sinker	Semi-discoid	Limestone	6,5	10,8		1,9	439		Middle Kingdom	Limestone net-sinker; two boreholes. Traces of thread rubbing near holes. Deep groove on the base.	British Museum
1	37	Weight	Discoid elliptical	Clay	10	9,5	4,6		457		Middle Kingdom	Discoid elliptical weight, pierced at the top. Complete, made of unfired clay. Quite flattish, not possible to make it stand.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7352	Net sinker	Central groove	Limestone	5,76	5,54	4,11		140		Middle Kingdom	Limestone net sinker, quite crumbling. Incised groove around it.	Petrie Museum
2	UC7353 i	Net sinker	Central groove	Limestone	5,8	3,7	2,8		70,8		Middle Kingdom	Limestone net sinker. Very deep and large grooves, crudely cut, while the other groove is slightly incised.	Petrie Museum
	UC7353 ii	Net sinker	Central groove	Limestone	6,54	4,5x1,9	2,3		68		Middle Kingdom	Limestone net sinker with two parallel grooves around the body and a third lengthwise. Groove crudely made. Other scratchings on the surface. Soft stone, they might have been caused by the thread rubbing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16752	Net sinker	Central groove	Limestone	6,7	4,9	2,8		138		Middle Kingdom	Grooved limestone fishing-net weight. One long and large groove lengthwise. Nicely shaped. Groove made with a sharp tool, but on one side are visible signs of the thread rubbing.	Petrie Museum
1	EA70881	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	8,4	3,7			40,06	Cartwright 1998: 99.	Pinaceae family, probably <i>Abies</i> sp.	Model of heddle jack. Height flat support 4,5, with irregular surface. Head roughly cut, base quite flat. Proto-canaanite inscription.	British Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	50.a	Heddle jack	Wood	36,8	base 8,8	waist 4,75		473		Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Not polished. Base irregular, it cannot stand erect. Height flat support from base 20,1. Rim slightly higher. Good quality wood, light and resistant.	Manchester Museum
1	50.b	Heddle jack	Wood	36,9	base 7,16	waist 4		270		Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, almost complete but part of the shaft missing and decayed wood. Support for heddle slightly diagonal toward the half. Height support 20,1 cm, but very different from 50.a.	Manchester Museum
1	50.c	Heddle jack	Wood	32	base 6,7	waist 5,4		563		Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Not polished. Base irregular, it cannot stand erect. Height flat support from base 18,7. Rim slightly higher. Good quality wood, heavy and resistant.	Manchester Museum
1	50.d	Heddle jack	Wood	29,8	base 6,5	waist 4,3		340		Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Not polished. Base irregular, it cannot stand erect. Height flat support from base 19,5. Rim slightly higher. Good quality wood, heavy and resistant.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7278	Heddle jack	Wood	ca 30	base 7,58	waist 4,07		375	Petrie Museum 1927 <i>Objects of Daily Use</i> . 48 (no. 138)	Late Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Not polished. Base irregular, it cannot stand erect. Height flat support from base 19. Rim slightly higher. Good quality wood, heavy and resistant. Triangle incised on the back.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7279	Heddle jack	Wood	ca 25,5	base 8,58	waist 6,54		274	Petrie Museum 1927, 48 (no. 132)	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden heddle jack, surface worn at base of notch, used as a mallet to beat on a peg. Light wood. Height flat support 15,7.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7280	Heddle jack		Wood	ca 34,7	base 7,14	waist 3,94		281	Petrie Museum 1927, 48 (no. 134)	Late Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Not polished. Slim waist. Height flat support from base 21,8. Rim slightly higher.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7281	Heddle jack		Wood	ca 27,2	base 5,9	waist 3,4			Petrie Museum 1927, 48 (no. 135)	Late Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, incomplete. Lower part missing, split vertically. Polished on the top. Height of flat support 18,3.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7282ii	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	7,98	2,22			11,14		Late Middle Kingdom	Model of heddle jack. Height flat support 5,56. Head roughly cut, base quite flat.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7291	Heddle jack		Wood	ca 24,7	base 8x6				Petrie Museum 1927, 48 (no. 136)	Late Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Height flat support 16,6. Used as a mallet to beat on a peg. Rectangular mark on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC 16704	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	8,98	2,51			28,38		Late Middle Kingdom	Model of heddle jack. Height flat support 6,82.	Petrie Museum
1	UC 16705	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	6	1,38x2			7,34	Petrie Museum 1927, 48 (no. 131)	Late Middle Kingdom	Model of heddle jack. Height flat support 4,39. it cannot stand erect.	Petrie Museum
1	UC59022	Heddle jack		Wood	ca 30cm	6,3			451		Late Middle Kingdom	Heddle jack, complete. Big and heavy, worn wood. Height flat support 20,5	Petrie Museum
1	UC59021	Heddle jack model	Model	Wood	11,97	3,9			46,4		Late Middle Kingdom	Model of heddle jack, complete. Height flat support 8,4.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
2	UC7282	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	11,6	3,38		39		Late Middle Kingdom	Model of heddle jack made of wood (soft and light). No wear traces are visible. (on pencil written T2 66 Kahun). Height flat support 7,9	Petrie Museum
	UC7282 ii	Heddle jack	Model	Wood	8	2,1		11,2		Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden model of heddle jack. Soft and light wood. No wear traces are detectable. There was a written-on pencil but is not possible to read it anymore. Height flat support 5,5.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16703	Heddle jack		Wood	27,4	10x5,9		710		Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden heddle jack, complete. very thick. Wooden surface very worn. It stands erect but leaning towards the front, as the support for heddle. No traces of a more damaged or worn part at the base. Height flat support 18,5.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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NEEDLES AND SPATULAE

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	56.21.363	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow, broken. One end missing, point preserved. Peculiar shape. Not cut in half. Cancellous bone partially visible where bone is more worn.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.12.362	Spatula								Bone spatula (?), long and narrow. One end with an elongated point, the other broken. Lower side of point extremely polished and smoothed.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.21.361	Spatula								Bone spatula, complete. One flat end, the other with a triangular point. Central part of lower side highly polished, slightly less near the point. Cancellous bone not smoothed near the flat end.	Liverpool World Museum
1	61	Netting needle						Griffith 1910, 14.	Middle Kingdom	A netting needle, split at both ends for netting, to a depth of 3.0 cm.	Manchester Museum
1	97	Needle						Griffith 1910, 18.		Needle case, consisting of a hollow bird bone with reed and textile bound around it. Contains a threaded copper needle and a wooden pin or bodkin. Thick thread, Z-cabled (3 yarns), each S-plied, s-spun.	Manchester Museum
1	233.a	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye.	Manchester Museum
1	233.b	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	233.c	Needle		Bronze	8,3	0,18				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Oval hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.d	Needle		Bronze	8,7	0,21				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye.	Manchester Museum
1	233.e	Needle		Bronze	9,62	0,21				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, almost complete, point chipped. Oval hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.f	Needle		Bronze	6,2	0,15				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken and bent. Eye not preserved.	Manchester Museum
1	233.g	Needle		Bronze	0,66	0,18				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at both ends. Possibly two eyes were originally present.	Manchester Museum
1	233.h	Needle		Bronze	0,6	0,23				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle(?), broken at one end, the other possibly with a small spatulated end.	Manchester Museum
1	233.i	Needle		Bronze	0,75	0,14				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye.	Manchester Museum
1	233.j	Needle		Bronze	4,72	0,13				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Fragment of needle point.	Manchester Museum
1	233.k	Needle		Bronze	8,26	2,54				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.l	Needle		Bronze						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Two fragments of a needle, one with traces of a broken eye.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	233.m	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.n	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.o	Needle							Middle Kingdom	Copper needle, with eye at one end for threading.	Manchester Museum
1	233.p	Needle							Middle Kingdom	Copper needle, with eye at one end for threading.	Manchester Museum
1	233.q	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete and wavy. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.r	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Oval hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.s	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at the point. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft, the other side almond shape.	Manchester Museum
1	233.t	Needle						Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft, the other side almond shape.	Manchester Museum
1	233.u	Needle							Middle Kingdom	Copper needle, with eye at one end for threading.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	233.v	Needle							Middle Kingdom	Copper needle, with eye at one end for threading.	Manchester Museum
1	233.w	Needle		0,12				Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete but bent. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.x	Needle		0,25	6,3			Griffith 1910, 29.	Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete but bent. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.1	Needle		0,21	6,7				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.2	Needle		0,2	9				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.3	Needle		0,22	8,7				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete and wavy. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.4	Needle		0,22	9,2				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at the point. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	233.5	Needle		0,15	8,7				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye and chipped at the point.	Manchester Museum
1	6192.a	Needle		0,3	9				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete, quite thick. Eye preserved but Manchester Museum not detectable.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	6192.b	Needle		Bronze	8,9	0,2				Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole punched through the shaft.	Manchester Museum
1	695.a.i	Spatula		Bone	4,4	0,7	0,17			Found with 695.a	Fragment of bone spatula with elongated point, with evident wear traces.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7377 i	Needle		Bronze	5,58	0,23				Late Middle Kingdom	Small bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7377 ii	Needle		Bronze	8,9	0,19				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7377 iii	Needle		Bronze	9	0,29				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, eye missing. Slightly curved.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7377iv	Needle		Bronze	6,22	0,2				Late Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, broken at eye.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7262i	Needle		Bronzo	7,65	0,34				Late Middle Kingdom	Small bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7262ii	Needle		Bronze	8,4	0,24				Late Middle Kingdom	Small bronze needle, point missing. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7262iii	Needle		Bronze	9	0,2				Late Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Quadrangular head. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7262iv	Needle		Bronze	9,2	0,22				Late Middle Kingdom	Small bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft. Point extremely thin.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7260	Needle		Bronze	7,6	0,15			Petrie Museum 1890, 28, pl.XVII, 14	Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle. Slightly curved. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261i	Needle		Bronze	8,4	0,16				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261ii	Needle		Bronze	8,5	0,19				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, point missing. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261iii	Needle		Bronze	9,06	0,19				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261iv	Needle		Bronze	9,68	0,16				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261v	Needle		Bronze	10,14	0,16				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7261vi	Needle		Bronze	10,18	0,21				Late Middle Kingdom	Long and thin bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC28273	Netting needle		Wood	21	1,43				Cartwright 1998: 101, 108.	Dynasty 12?	Wooden netting needle? Bound around with thread in a complicated arrangement; both ends incomplete, one charred. Thread appears as modern, H. Granger-Taylor suppose has a late date. S-twisted and 7 Z-plyed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7255	Needle		Bronze	10	0,14					Dynasty 12	Copper needle, thickness 1.3 cm. Very long and thin with tiny eye.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7256	Needle		Bronze	8,9	0,15					Late Middle Kingdom	Very thin copper needle with small eye pierced on the shaft.	Petrie Museum
0	UC7257	Needle		Bronze	8,4	0,3					Late Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
0	UC7258	Needle		Bronze	7,8	0,26					Late Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7259	Needle		Bronze	11,8	0,3					Late Middle Kingdom	Bronze needle, complete. Round hole made by punching the upper part of the shaft.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7264	Netting needle		Wood						Petrie Museum 1927, 53, pl.LXVI, 130.	Late Middle Kingdom	Wooden netting needle with mark incised on the surface.	Petrie Museum
1	AN 1889.1202	Weaver's slay		Wood	18,8	2,7	0,8			Petrie Museum 1890, 27-28.	Middle Kingdom	Flat piece of wood, rounded at one end, pointed at other.	Ashmolean Museum

GUROB

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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SPINDLES

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7812a	Spindle		Wood	16,9	0,83			23,32	Thomas 1981, 38.		Spindle shaft, broken at the thicker end, the other is rounded and preserves traces of encrustation and of fibres.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812b	Pin		Wood	10,66	0,65			1,78			Wooden pin with a pointed end and partially covered by an incised decoration.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812c	Spindle		Wood	23,8	0,46		0,37	2,24			Extremely thin wooden shaft, complete. One end is rounded and immediately below a notch for the thread is preserved, the other end is pointed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7810	Spindle		Wood	24	1,04			0,88	36		Wooden spindle, broken in the upper part, the other end is pointed. Shaft thickens in the middle.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	2,8	5,5			0,8			Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Partially covered by a thin layer of patina.	
1	UC7814ia	Spindle		Wood	13,6	0,74			0,74	20,62		Shaft broken at around half of the length (presumably) and extremely worn. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation in several areas.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,21	4,58			0,7		Thomas 1981, 38.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but slightly ruined. Upper surface covered by a thick layer of encrustation, same type found on Deir el-Medina spindle whorls.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7814ib	Spindle	Wood	4,05			0,58	21,06		Small fragment of spindle preserved inside double spindle whorl.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	1,84	4,66				Large spindle whorl, complete. Conical truncated shape. Clean surfaces.	
		Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	1,39	3,68				Smaller spindle whorl, complete. Conical truncated shape. Clean surfaces. Traces of manufacture visible on the upper (?) surface.	
1	UC7814ii i	Spindle	Wood	3,73	0,64			10,88		Part of shaft broken immediately under the spindle whorl. Upper tip preserved and rounded, with a cylindrical groove incised.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,48	4,44		0,77		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Upper surface and side covered by spots of encrustation. Lower surface clean with evident traces of manufacture.	
1	UC7814iij	Spindle	Wood	4,73	0,72			17,64		Part of shaft broken immediately under the spindle whorl. Upper tip preserved and rounded, with a cylindrical groove incised.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,79	5,12		1,1		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Upper surface and side covered by spots of encrustation. Chipped on one side.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7809	Spindle		Wood	24,5	0,41		0,3	5,04	Thomas 1981, 38, pl. 5.		Complete spindle with whorl. Long and thin shaft, hard and perfectly preserved wood, with a small spiral notch to fasten the fibres. Shaft slightly thicker in the middle.	Petrie Museum
		Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,4	2,06						Domed spindle whorl, complete. Hard wood perfectly preserved. Very small and light.	
1	523	Spindle		Wood	24,7	0,76			26	Griffith 1910, 48.		Long and thin shaft of a spindle, almost complete. The upper part seems burnt and does not preserve the notch. The other end is pointed.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,83	5,03		0,65x 0,76				Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but not polished, traces of manufacture are visible on the lower surface. Partially encrusted on all sides. Warped hole.	
1	524.a	Spindle		Wood	14,25	0,96			19	Griffith 1910, 48.		Shaft broken at both ends. It tends to thicken toward one of the broken end, the one without whorl.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,81	4,53		0,8				Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and clean, cut from a quite large branch.	
1	524.b	Spindle		Wood	10	0,7			14			Shaft broken few cm under the spindle whorl. The upper end still preserves part of the groove for the fibres, but it is partially broken.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,8	4		0,66			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but partially cracked. Upper surface covered by a thin layer of encrustation, which is much more thick on the lower side.	
1	524.c	Spindle		Wood	19,1	0,99		14			Shaft broken on the upper part, where the notch should be. The other end tapers toward a point but is partially missing.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	4,8		0,8			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Covered by a thin patina on all sides.	
1	526.a	Spindle		Wood	10,4+x	0,8		0,65	14,9+x		Part of a wooden spindle, 1/3 of length preserved. Quite worn surface, on the preserved end a groove was probably present.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,87	4,3x4,7				Griffith 1910, 48.	Conical spindle whorl, slightly oval, complete. A thin layer of patina on the surface.	
		Thread		Linen							Large quantity of linen thread wound around the shaft in two different points, under the spindle whorl and on the lower end of the shaft. Mostly unspun, but a worn yarn (Z, 2z) is visible.	
1	526.b	Spindle		Wood	5,53+x	0,4		11+x			Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Spindle whorl still present.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
		Spindle whorl	Conical		2,38	4,56		0,57			Conical spindle whorl, complete. Well made but worn on the upper surface. Covered by a thin layer of patina.	
1	526.g	Spindle		Wood	5,57	0,57			4,5+x		Small fragment of wooden spindle, broken beneath the spindle whorl. Very thin shaft. Spiral groove still preserved immediately above whorl. Other end tends to slightly thicken and shows traces of burnt.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,78	2,45		0,36x 0,46			Conical spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. A large burnt area is present.	
1	526.i	Spindle		Wood	23,2	0,94			16+x		Wooden spindle, almost complete, one end missing. Shaft thickening towards a point, near which whorl is placed (contrary to normal position). No groove is present. Hard and good quality wood, very well preserved. Possible low whorl spindle?	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,17	3,52		0,57			Conical spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. Perfectly cylindrical hole, while shaft on which it is placed would better fit a conical hole.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	526.l	Spindle	Wood	23,3	0,54		8			Wooden spindle, complete, perfectly preserved. Very thin shaft, one end with a small notch, the other pointed. Shaft thickens in the middle, tapers towards the pointed end.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,922	2,48	0,37x 0,42			Conical spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. Thin traces of polishing visible on the surface.	
1	526.m	Spindle	Wood	33,4	0,88		24			Wooden spindle, almost complete. Chipped at the grooved end. Shaft slightly thicker on the middle, tapers towards the point. Small traces of encrustation on the lower part of the shaft.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,04	4,5x4, 9	0,61x 0,75			Dome spindle whorl, slightly chipped on the side. Encrusted on the surface.	
1	526.n	Spindle	Wood	26	0,67		20			Spindle almost complete, point missing. Upper part of the shaft presents a small notch. Shaft tapers towards the missing point.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,7	3,77	0,6			Conical spindle whorl, complete. Surface covered by a thick layer of encrustation and damaged by insects. Wedge on the upper side of the hoe, traces of fibres/yarn near the lower side, on the shaft.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	526.o	Spindle		Wood	21	0,57			22		Wooden spindle, complete. Thin shaft, quite short, with a small notch on the upper end. Modern thread wound around the shaft.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,69	4,91		0,55			Large, conical spindle whorl, complete. Some incisions on the base, but not pertaining to a mark.	
1	526.p	Spindle		Wood	19,3	0,6			16		Wooden spindle almost complete, chipped at the top. Shaft tapering towards the other end, which is pointed.	Manchester Museum
		Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,28	3,84		0,63			Conical spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. Traces of encrustation on the dome. Wedge in the upper side of the hole.	
1	526.q	Spindle		Wood							Manchester Museum	
1	526.r	Spindle		Wood							Manchester Museum	
1	527	Spindle		Wood	18,3	0,55			14	Griffith 1910, 48. New Kingdom (XVIII-XIX dyn)	Wooden spindle, broken at both ends but preserved for almost all length. Beneath the whorl, some thread wound around the shaft is preserved. Most of the fibres appear as not spun, but at least a thread with s-twist is visible. Covered by encrustation.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
		Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	1,67	4,2x3,1	0,2x0,7			Conical truncated spindle whorl, complete and well preserved. Covered by encrustation on all sides.		
1	UC27873iii a	Spindle		Wood	17,8	0,94		4,5	Thomas 1981, 35.	New Kingdom	Part of shaft of a spindle (very likely) tapering towards the point which is ruined. Other end missing. Good quality wood, well preserved.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27873iii b	Spindle		Wood	17,8	0,87		4,1	Thomas 1981, 35.	New Kingdom	Part of shaft of a spindle (very likely) tapering towards the point which is ruined. Other end missing. Good quality wood, well preserved. Very similar to a.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27873iii c	Spindle		Wood	23,9	0,77		7,6	Thomas 1981, 35.	New Kingdom	Shaft of a spindle missing the point. The other end is flat and preserves the notch to fasten fibres. Good quality wood, well preserved. Slightly darker spot where whorl was probably originally placed. Spot is 2,3 cm long and shaft diameter in this point ranges between 0,5 to 0,63 cm. Shaft thickens towards the broken point.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27873iii d	Spindle		Wood	23,2	0,87		5,5	Thomas 1981, 35.	New Kingdom	Complete shaft of a spindle without whorl and without a notch for fastening the thread. Good quality wood, well preserved. Point is slightly chipped. Slightly darker spot where whorl was probably originally placed. Spindle whorl was at least 2 cm thick.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC27873iii e	Spindle		Wood	31,5	1			8,5	Thomas 1981, 35.	New Kingdom	Wooden spindle, broken at the upper part of the shaft. Notch not preserved. Very well preserved wood, shaft tapers towards the preserved end, which is pointed.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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SPINDLE WHORLS

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7812d	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,06	3,63	0,65	9,29			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped, triangular hole at the base with incisions, probably linked to process of manufacture. Concentric signs on the dome.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812e	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,29	4,03	0,6	10,75			Conical spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly damaged by wedges at the base, smaller than on the upper side. Large lateral hole on the dome.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812f	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,43	4,17	0,57	13,42			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Hole slightly larger at the base (0,64). Well polished on all surfaces.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812g	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,61	3,39	0,65	10,8			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Base roughly polished. Worn near the upper side of the hole.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812h	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2	4,17	0,53	10,86			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Well polished on all surfaces.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812i	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,91	2,97	0,4	0,71			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Small and highly worn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812j	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,49	3,36	0,45	9,64			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped, flat base polished with traces of manufacture.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812k	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,95	3,64	0,64	6,66			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Quite large, wood very worn.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7812l	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,95	3,95		0,62	6,56		Dome spindle whorl, partially broken.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812m	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,36	4,14		0,61	4,17		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped, large crack at the base. Hole slightly larger at the base. Upper side of the hole with evident signs of manufacture.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812n	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,17	3,8		0,61	6,06		Conical spindle whorl, part of the dome missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812o	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,93	3,18		0,42	5,54		Dome spindle whorl, partially damaged on the dome and very worn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812p	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,29	3,59		0,7	2,19+x		Dome spindle whorl, very warp and damaged.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812q	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,27	3,31		0,39	7,02		Dome spindle whorl, slightly chipped on the side. Hole slightly larger at the base.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812r	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,19	3,48		0,56	4,41		Dome spindle whorl, very worn and with a lateral hole. Full of soil.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812s	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,76	3,32		0,59	2,62		Dome spindle whorl, complete. Base roughly shaped.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812t	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,58	2,26		0,4	2,65		Tiny dome spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole. Roughly shaped.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7812u	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,56	2,42	0,48	0,4			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Small, very well shaped and polished.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812w	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	2,17	2,47	0,44	5,72			Dome spindle whorl, complete. Quite small, perfectly shaped and polished. Hole slightly worn on the upper side. Wear traces?	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812x	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,91	2,51	0,43	5,68			Dome spindle whorl, complete but very worn.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7812y	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,95	2,44	0,43	4,56			Dome spindle whorl complete. Small, with a fragment of spindle inside the hole. Worn surface.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iia	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,84	4,77	0,58	15,45	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped, wood well preserved and clean.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iib	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,71	4,94	0,61	13,6		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped, wood quite worn and cracked. Clean surfaces.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iic	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,82	4,49	1,33	0,78		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Hole on the side. Clean surfaces.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iid	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,18	4,67	0,81	17,26		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped, covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7814iie	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,77	4,63	0,72	15,75		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped, covered by a thin layer of encrustation.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iif	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,64	4,48	0,77	10,5		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but worn wood, especially on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iig	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,71	4,5	0,75	16,36		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, chipped. Well shaped and clean.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iih	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,42	4,29	0,89	12,78		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but worn and encrusted.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iik	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,63	4,58	0,78	13,3		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped but worn wood.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iil	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,61	4,82	0,72	13,02		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped with evident traces of manufacture.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iim	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,04	4,82	0,85	20,14		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped with evident traces of manufacture.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iin	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,18	4,9	0,76	19,73		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and clean.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7814iio	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,73	5,42	1,37	26,39		New Kingdom	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and very large.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	AN 1889.1199A	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,2	5		0,8	15,6		Conical wooden spindle whorl, highly worn.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199B	Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood	2,4	5,6		1x1,1	32,1		Conical truncated spindle whorl, well preserved but cracked. Lots of signs on the basis, I do not think they have been made for working but rather for decoration. Mark on one side. Very dense and heavy wood.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199C	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	spindle 2,3 1,6	3,8		0,7	4,7		Wooden conical spindle whorl, quite ruined, small fragment of a spindle inside.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199D	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,5	2,2		0,3x0,4	3,2		Small wooden spindle whorl, good quality wood but not so dark like that of the Petrie Museum. Upper hole chipped like stone examples.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199E	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2	3,7		0,6	10,3		Large conical spindle whorl, well preserved, clear cut hole.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199F	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,35	2,5		0,4	1,8		Small wooden spindle whorl from Gurob, good wood but not so dark like that of the Petrie. Upper hole chipped, like stone examples. Soft wood.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1199G	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,5	2,2		0,3	1,4		Small wooden spindle whorl from Gurob, soft wood and squeezed. Completely warp.	Ashmolean Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	525.a	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,19	4,28	0,7x0,8	15,3	Griffith 1910, 48.	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped, one side covered by a thick layer of encrustation, less thick on the other side.	Manchester Museum
1	525.b	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,49	4,8x4,6	0,8x0,96	12,3		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Large lateral crack. Conical hole warped by wedges. Covered by a thin patina on all sides.	Manchester Museum
1	525.c	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,83	4,72	0,8	12,9		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Highly worn wood, encrusted on one side, covered by a thin patina on the other.	Manchester Museum
1	525.d	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,74	4,72	0,67x0,74	14,3		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Covered by a thin layer of patina and by a spot of thick encrustation, rich of vegetable fibres and possibly a thread.	Manchester Museum
1	525.e	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	5,4	0,7	12,8+x		Cylindrical spindle whorl, broken on one side. Completely clear wood but quite worn.	Manchester Museum
1	525.f	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,6	4,9	0,97	22		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Quite worn surface, but traces of manufacture still detectable.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	525.g	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,21	4	0,8	6,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and preserved. Covered by a thin patina on all sides.	Manchester Museum
1	525.h	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,46	4,83	0,8	12,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle preserved inside the hole. One side encrusted. Cut from the middle of a small branch.	Manchester Museum
1	525.i	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,92	4,3	0,59x 0,67	12			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and preserved. Covered by a thin layer of patina on both surfaces, not on the side.	Manchester Museum
1	525.l	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,45	4,65	0,9	18,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole. One side covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other by a thin patina.	Manchester Museum
1	525.m	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,42	5,25	0,8	10,1			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Hole incomplete (?). Second, off centre hole possibly caused by insects. One side encrusted, all the others covered by a thin patina.	Manchester Museum
1	525.n	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,18	5,24	0,7x0, 87	25,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole. Well preserved but cracked. Covered by a thin layer of patina. Cut from the middle of a small branch.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	525.o	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,37	5,5	0,7	16,3			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole. Well preserved but cracked. Covered by a thin layer of patina. Cut from the middle of a small branch.	Manchester Museum
1	525.p	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,67	4,8	0,8	8,9			Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. Wood quite worn, covered by a thin layer of encrustation. Cut from a quite large branch.	Manchester Museum
1	526.c	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,43	4,11x 3,78	0,62	6,5			Conical spindle whorl, complete. Extremely worn and cracked.	Manchester Museum
1	526.d	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,24	3,38	0,53	9			Conical spindle whorl, chipped on the side. Upper side of the hole very worn, possibly wear traces (?). Lower side neatly cut.	Manchester Museum
1	526.e	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,39	4	0,72	7,4			Conical spindle whorl, complete. Quite flat. Upper side of the hole slightly worn, lower side neatly cut. Thick encrustation on the lower side with fibres (hair?) embedded.	Manchester Museum
1	526.f	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,68	2,39	0,53	5,3			Conical/dome spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved except at the top, which is highly worn and possibly flattened.	Manchester Museum
1	526.h	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,36	4,21	0,78x 0,85	6,7			Conical spindle whorl, quite flat. Highly worn and chipped. Conical hole larger at the base.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	528.a	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,14	3,6		0,61	9	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Highly worn wood, base covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Manchester Museum
1	528.b	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,98	2,45		0,44	4,6	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped and preserved although several cracks are present.	Manchester Museum
1	528.c	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,76	2,6		0,4x0,42	2,9	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, broken on one side. Completely blackened by fire.	Manchester Museum
1	528.d	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,36	2,42		0,37	3,3	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Small fragment of spindle inside the hole (0,3x1,6).	Manchester Museum
1	528.e	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,54	2,1x2,3		0,47	3,6	Griffith 1910, 48.		Dome spindle whorl, complete. Very well preserved, slightly oval.	Manchester Museum
1	528.f	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood	1,28	2,58		0,36x0,41	4,3	Griffith 1910, 48.		Dome spindle whorl, complete. Well shaped and well preserved. Very good quality wood. Traces of manufacture visible at the base.	Manchester Museum
1	528.g	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,4	4x3,5		0,7	6,5	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete but very worn and damaged. Traces of encrustation.	Manchester Museum
1	528.h	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	2,59	3,8		0,6	9,9	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Quite well preserved even if slightly warped. Covered by encrustation and a whitish patina. Hole with soil. Fragment of thin spindle.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	528.i	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,75	3,5x3,2	0,4x0,43	4,3	Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete but quite damaged and warped. Highly worn wood.	Manchester Museum
1	528.l	Spindle whorl	Conical	Wood	1,6	2,6	0,39x0,44		Griffith 1910, 48.		Conical spindle whorl, complete. Very well shaped and preserved. High quality wood.	Manchester Museum
1	529.a	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone	2	7,63	0,87	133,2	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, with four radial lines roughly incised from the centre as decoration. Quite flattish. Very large and heavy. Upper hole worn but no wear traces are detectable.	Manchester Museum
1	529.b	spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone	2,1	6	0,74x0,9	81,8	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, almost complete with small chippings. Radial lines incised on the dome. Hole slightly conical, larger at the base of the whorl. Wear traces on the upper side of the hole.	Manchester Museum
1	529.c	spindle whorl	Conical	Limestone	2,98	6	1x1,2	88,4	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, conical, with several irregular lines incised from the centre. Very worn on the upper side.	Manchester Museum
1	529.d	spindle whorl	Conical	Limestone	2,57	4,51	0,69x0,79	57,7	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, conical and complete. Very well shaped and polished. Both sides of hole show small chippings.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	529.e	spindle whorl	Conical	Limestone	3,78	5,5x5,2		0,73x1,1	112,3	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, conical, with two incised lines. Quite oval in shape. Lots of chippings near upper side of the hole, probably linked to process of manufacture. Conical hole, larger at the base.	Manchester Museum
1	529.f	spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone	2,54	5,7x5,9		0,96	84,9	Griffith 1910, 49.		Limestone spindle-whorl, dome shaped, with numerous lines deeply incised and a spiral line running around the base. Complete, slightly shipped. Perfectly flat base. Upper side of the hole worn, with wear traces, while lower side is neatly cut.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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FIBRES

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	AN 1889.1182 A	Textile						Petrie 1890, 35.	New Kingdom	Ball of textile with fringes. Quite coarse textile, dense tabby weave. S, 2s threads on the textile, one thread Z-plied between fringes, most of fringes unplied.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1182 B	Ball of yarn						Petrie 1890, 35.	New Kingdom	Coarse textile which is attached to or surround a ball of yarn. Textile: s-cabled. Ball of yarn made of very fine threads s-spun (0,15 mm), mixed with few S-plied yarns (0,3 mm).	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1182 C	Balls of threads						Petrie 1890, 35.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn made of very fine threads mixed with few plied threads and at least one thick and cabled thread. Extremely fine yarns, s-spun (0,08 mm), S-plied yarns (0,2 mm), Z-cabled yarn very worn (0,84 mm).	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1889.1182 D	Balls of threads						Petrie 1890, 35.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn which mixed different threads and different materials (probably unspun wool). Most of the ball is made of very thin s-spun threads (0,08 mm), but several S-plied (0,26 mm) and S-cabled threads (0,56 mm) are also present. Atleast a Z-plied thread is recognizable.	Ashmolean Museum
2	502.a	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn, well preserved. Thick thread, Z-cabled (0,75 mm). Catalogue says that one of the two balls contains a bone spatula, but it was not present.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	502.b	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn, well preserved. Thick thread, z-spun and Z-plied, but also some thicker Z-cabled threads (0,87 mm).	Manchester Museum
1	496.a	Net/net sinker						Griffith 1910, 46.	New Kingdom	Fishing net, z-cabled. Catalogue affirms that a mud net sinker is attached to the net, but it is no longer visible.	Manchester Museum
1	500.a	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910, 46.	New Kingdom	Rove of flax, fibres prepared for spinning and with evident spliced fibres. Well preserved. Spliced fibres are single s and plied S.	Manchester Museum
1	500.b	Flax fibres						Griffith 1910, 46.	New Kingdom	Knotted piece of flax fibres.	Manchester Museum
1	500.c	Yarn						Griffith 1910, 46.	New Kingdom	Length of flax fibre wound around a piece of pottery (three fragments). Several different threads some S-plied, other 2S, 4S. Large cabled thread with Z-twist.	Manchester Museum
13	503.a	Ball of threads						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of threads partially wound around a piece of fabric, tabby weave. Mostly S-spun, very thin (0,17 mm) and not plied, some Z-plied.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
503.b	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Well preserved ball of yarn but single threads appear quite worn. S-spun, S-ply well preserved although the thread appears more worn. S-ply, single twist not visible.	Manchester Museum
503.c	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Well preserved ball of yarn, very fine threads all s-spun. Orange colour.	Manchester Museum
503.d	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Linen threads of light blue colour. Most of them are s-spun (0,22 mm) and left unplied, while others are S-ply (0,37 mm).	Manchester Museum
503.e	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn very worn. Some yarn are s-spun but not plyed, others are S-ply. Mixed with coarse fibres.	Manchester Museum
503.f	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn, quite worn. Most of the yarn are very thin, s-spun, some are S-ply. One is Z-cabled.	Manchester Museum
503.g	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of whitish yarn, very worn and fluffy and covered by another thread, darker and better preserved. Both are s-spun. White thread has various thickness, where measurable is 0,38 mm. Darker thread is 0,23 mm.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
503.h	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Whitish ball of yarn, very worn and fluffy. Mixed with other threads, better preserved. All are s-spun, some very fine, some coarser, some s-plyed.	Manchester Museum
503.i	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Whitish ball of yarn, very worn and fluffy. Covered by a finer (0,23 mm), brownish thread. S-spun and in some cases S-plyed.	Manchester Museum
503.j	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn. Whitish thread, very fine but worn. Mixed with different threads and fibres. Where visible, s-spun and S-plyed thread. At least another thread z-spun and Z-plyed.	Manchester Museum
503.k	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn. Whitish thread, very fine but worn. Mixed with different threads and fibres. Where visible, s-spun and S-plyed thread.	Manchester Museum
503.l	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn made of brownish threads. Well preserved. s-spun and S-plyed.	Manchester Museum
503.m	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn made of brownish threads. Well preserved. s-spun and S-plyed.	Manchester Museum
503.n	Ball of threads	Flax						Griffith 1910, 47.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn made of whitish threads. Very worn and extremely fine. Wound around tow. S-spun.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC27884 i	Linen						Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Hank of flax of worn fibres and some threads. Threads are very thick, s-spun and S-plied.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27884 ii	Linen						Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	String. Final twist Z.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27883 i	Skein	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Skein of linen threads, quite fine but very different from each other. S-spun.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27883 ii	Skein	Linen; wood					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Skein of linen threads, partially wound around a reed. Made of different threads. S-spun and S-plied.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27883 iii	Skein	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Skein of string. Cabled, final twist S.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27882i	Ball of thread	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn, extremely fine (0,1 mm). Very worn thread, s-spun, and in one case S-plied.	Petrie Museum
2	UC27882iia-b	Ball of threads	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Two ball of threads, made of very mixed materials. A) small ball of threads, made of s-spun, S-plied yarns, closed by a thick, Z-cabled, completely worn yarn. B) larger ball of threads, made by a thick, Z-cabled, completely worn yarn (possibly the same used for fastening A), mixed with s-spun and S, 2s threads.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
4	UC27882iii	Ball of threads	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Four ball of yarns, very badly preserved and subjected to degradation. Impossible to separate and analyse without further compromising them. All are s-spun and S-plyed (thickness 0,5 mm). One seem wounded around a sherd.	Petrie Museum
1	UC27882iv	Ball of threads	Linen					Gurob	Thomas 1981, 39.	New Kingdom	Ball of yarn well preserved, although yarn appear worn in several points. Made of different type of threads (th. 0,8-1,1 mm). S-spun threads, S, 2s threads, mostly S-cabled. Several knots visible. Is it possible that form a sort of net?	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7937	Net sinker								Petrie 1917, 49,10. Thomas 1981, 32, pl. 1.	Dynasty 18	Lead netsinker, domed ring.	Petrie Museum
1	UC28274	Net sinker								Thomas 1981, 32.		Limestone net sinker. Oval pebble with a large and deep groove around waist.	Petrie Museum
4	UC7938	Net sinker								Thomas 1981, 32, pl. 1.			
1	UC7939	Net sinker								Thomas 1981, 32.			

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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NEEDLES AND SPATULAE

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	AN 1890.1006A	Bobbin		Bone	7,2	0,4				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Short bone stick with a flat end and the other round or slightly pointed, with a through hole. Bone blackened by fire. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006B	Bobbin		Bone	7,2	0,5	0,4			Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Chipped at the basis, burnt at the top. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006C	Bobbin		Bone	7,3	0,5				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Burnt at the top. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006D	Bobbin		Bone	7	0,5				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Bone blackened by fire. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006E	Bobbin		Bone	7,2	0,4				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Bone blackened by fire. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006F	Bobbin		Bone	7,1	0,5				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Bobbin, function not clear. Bone blackened by fire. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	AN 1890.1006G	Bobbin		Bone	1,8	0,7				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Fragment of one end of a bobbin, function not clear. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006H	Bobbin		Bone	4,5	0,6				Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Half of a bobbin, function not clear. Bone blackened by fire. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006I	Bobbin		Bone						Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	group 1. Two fragments of bobbins. A) 3,5 B) 3,1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1006J	Bobbin		Bone	3,9	0,5	0,5			Petrie 1891, 18. Gasperini 2018, 215, 234-5.	New Kingdom (Seti II)	Fragment of one end of a bobbin, function not clear. Group 1.	Ashmolean Museum
1	UC7720	Needle		Bronze	7,81	0,29					From Gurob Tomb 125 (Brunton excavations).	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7795i	Needle		Bronze	10,4	0,23				Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7795ii	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7797i	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7797ii	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7797iii	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7797iv	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7798i	Needle						Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Very thin shaft. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7798ii	Needle					Head 0,24x 0,2	Thomas 1981, 40, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7798iii	Needle		Bronze	10,7	0,2				Thomas 1981, 41, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Perfectly straight shaft. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7798iv	Needle		Bronze	10,6	0,116				Thomas 1981, 41, pl. 6.	Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Very long and thin shaft. Eye missing. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 I	Needle		Bronze	4,86	2,36	0,2			Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Long shaft of bronze, warp, no indication that an eye was present.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 II	Needle		Bronze	4,26	0,96	0,2				Dynasty 18	Long shaft of bronze, broken on one end, bent, no indication that an eye was present.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 III	Needle		Bronze	2,9	0,36	0,2				Dynasty 18	Small part of bronze needle, broken, point missing, eye present but closed by oxidation.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 IV	Needle		Bronze	2,62	0,39	0,14				Dynasty 18	Long shaft of bronze, broken on one end, bent, no indication that an eye was present.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 V	Needle		Bronze	8,5	0,12					Dynasty 18	Long shaft of bronze, broken on one end, bent to form a hook, no indication that an eye was present.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 VI	Needle		Bronze	6,1	0,18					Dynasty 18	Long shaft of bronze, probably a needle with point still present. Eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 VII	Needle		Bronze	10	0,14					Dynasty 18	Needle, complete and cleaned. Partially broken eye.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7799 VIII	Needle		Bronze	9,6	0,14				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 IX	Needle		Bronze	10,3	0,25				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 X	Needle		Bronze	10,7	0,22				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, eye missing. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XI	Needle		Bronze	10,7	0,22				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, eye missing. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XII	Needle		Bronze	8,7	1,48				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XIII	Needle		Bronze	9	1,82				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XIV	Needle		Bronze	7,9	0,14				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XV	Needle		Bronze	5,5	0,2				Dynasty 18	Short bronze needle, eye missing. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7799 XVI	Needle		Bronze	6,7	1,64				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, eye missing. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XVII	Needle		Bronze	0,6	0,33				Dynasty 18	Part of a thick shaft of bronze.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XVIII	Needle		Bronze	5,2	0,15				Dynasty 18	Part of a thin shaft of needle. Both ends broken.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XIX	Needle		Bronze	5,6	0,14				Dynasty 18	Part of a thin shaft of needle. Point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XX	Needle		Bronze	5,1	0,18				Dynasty 18	Part of a thin shaft of needle. Point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXI	Needle		Bronze	7,6	0,18				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXII	Needle		Bronze	5,2	0,21				Dynasty 18	Part of a thin shaft of needle. Point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXIII	Needle		Bronze	7,3	0,27				Dynasty 18	Part of a thick shaft of bronze. Broken at both ends	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXIV	Needle		Bronze	6,4	0,28				Dynasty 18	Thick bronze needle, point missing. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Flattened eye.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXV	Needle		Bronze	7,9	0,24				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point missing, eye obliterated by oxidation.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7799 XXVI	Needle		Bronze	6,3	0,21				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXVII	Needle		Bronze	7	0,13				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXVIII	Needle		Bronze	7,2	0,14				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXIX	Needle		Bronze	6,1	0,23				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete, eye obliterated by oxidation.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXX	Needle		Bronze	8,25	0,23				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXI	Needle		Bronze	5,9	0,14				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXII	Needle		Bronze	0,71	0,2				Dynasty 18	Bronze shaft broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXIII	Needle		Bronze	9,7	0,2				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXIV	Needle		Bronze	8,8	0,16				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, point preserved, eye missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXV	Needle		Bronze	8,4	0,23				Dynasty 18	Needle, complete, eye obliterated by oxidation.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXV	Needle		Bronze	7,9	0,24				Dynasty 18	Needle, point missing, eye obliterated by oxidation.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7799 XXXVI	Needle	Bronze	9	0,32				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXVII	Needle	Bronze	8,4	0,18				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXVIII	Needle	Bronze	8	0,23				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XXXIX	Needle	Bronze	8,9	0,14				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Long and thin shaft. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other. Cleaned and treated.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XL	Needle	Bronze	9,1	0,19				Dynasty 18	Needle, almost complete, just a little fragment of the point missing. Eye closed by oxidation.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLI	Needle	Bronze	10	0,17				Dynasty 18	Long and thin needle, complete but quite ruined along the shaft. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLII	Needle	Bronze	10,9	0,22				Dynasty 18	Bronze needle, complete. Hole made perforating the shaft from one side to the other.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLIII	Needle	Bronze	10,6	0,15				Dynasty 18	Long and thin needle, complete, cleaned with eye partially broken.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	UC7799 XLIV	Needle		Bronze	9,9	0,2				Dynasty 18	Needle, small round eye. Near the point a thick layer of oxidated bronze, point probably broken but not detectable.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLV	Needle		Bronze	11,3	0,18				Dynasty 18	Long and thin needle, complete. Eye completely closed by oxidation, recognizable just for being flattened.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLVI	Needle		Bronze	10	0,49				Dynasty 18	Thick shaft of bronze, probably not a needle.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLVII	Needle		Bronze	4,6	0,32				Dynasty 18	Bronze point. Broken.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLVIII	Needle		Bronze	4,56	0,15				Dynasty 18	Part of a needle shaft, broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 XLIX	Needle		Bronze	4,6	0,17				Dynasty 18	Part of a needle shaft, broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 L	Needle		Bronze	4,4	0,23				Dynasty 18	Bronze point, broken, probably of a needle.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 LI	Needle		Bronze	4	0,18				Dynasty 18	Part of a needle shaft, broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 LII	Needle		Bronze	4	0,15				Dynasty 18	Part of a needle shaft, broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7799 LIII	Needle		Bronze	3,3	0,19				Dynasty 18	Part of a needle shaft, broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution		
1	UC7799 LIV	Needle		Bronze	3	0,22				Dynasty 18	Part of bronze quadrangular shaft. Broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum	
1	UC7799 LV	Needle		Bronze	2,9	0,17				Dynasty 18	Bronze point, quadrangular section and flattened point.	Petrie Museum	
1	UC7799 LVI	Needle		Bronze	2,1	0,22x 0,19				Dynasty 18	Part of bronze quadrangular shaft. Broken at both ends.	Petrie Museum	
1	AN 1890.1084	Needle		Bronze	13,5	0,4	0,3			Gasperini 2018, 249.	Burnt group 3	Long and thick "needle", flat with oval section. Flattened head with a round eye.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1085	Needle		Bronze	7,9	0,2				Gasperini 2018, 249.	Burnt group 3	Long and quite thin needle with broken eye.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1124	Needle		Bronze	10,4	0,15				Petrie 1891, 17-18, pl. XVIII 36, 37. Gasperini 2018, 126.	Burnt group 4, Ramesses II	Long and thin needle with a round eye perforated from one side. Very sharp point.	Ashmolean Museum
1	AN 1890.1125	Needle		Bronze	12,1	0,2				Petrie 1891, 17-18, pl. XVIII 36, 37. Gasperini 2018, 126.	Burnt group 4, Ramesses II	Very long and quite thin needle with a sharp point and a rounded eye perforated from one side.	Ashmolean Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	AN 1890.1126	Needle						Petrie 1891, 17-18, pl. XVIII 36, 37. Gasperini 2018, 126.	Burnt group 4, Ramesses II	Long and thin needle with an oval eye perforated from one side.	Ashmolean Museum
1	UC7806	Netting needle						Thomas 1981, 43.	Dynasty 18	Wooden netting needle, complete and quite big. Not perfectly smoothed inside "tweezers".	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712i	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41, pl. 7.	Dynasty 18	Bone spatula, almost complete. Small chipping on the point. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is rounded. Upper side highly polished, lower side covered by deep parallel marks. Cancellous bone exposed only at the rounded end.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712ii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Bone spatula, almost complete. Small chipping on the point. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is flat. Upper side highly polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed in several points.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712iii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Bone spatula, broken. Small chipping on the point. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is missing. Upper side highly polished, lower side with cancellous bone completely exposed and not smoothed.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7712iv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Bone spatula, broken. Small chipping on the point. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is missing. Upper side highly polished, lower side with cancellous bone completely exposed and not smoothed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712v	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Bone spatula, almost complete. Small chipping on the point. One end has a pen-nib point, the other is diagonally cut. Upper side highly polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed in several points, but very smoothed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712vi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Wear marks.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712vii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Wear marks near the pointed end.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712viii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Wear marks.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712ix	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Wear marks.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712x	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Partly cracked and pointed end broken. Wear marks.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712xi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	Pointed end broken. Wear marks.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC7712xii	Spatula	Bone	6	1,1	0,1		Thomas 1981, 41.	Dynasty 18	End of the point missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712xiii	Spatula	Bone	10,9	2,2	0,2		Thomas 1981, 42.	Dynasty 18	Pointed end broken. Wear marks.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712xiv	Spatula	Bone	11,5	1,9	0,1		Thomas 1981, 42.	Dynasty 18	Crudely shaped. Wear traces near the edges. Point missing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712xv	Spatula	Bone	10,3	1,2	0,1		Thomas 1981, 42.	Dynasty 18	Rounded end chipped. Diagonal traces on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7712xvi	Spatula	Bone	16,5	1,2	0,2		Thomas 1981, 42.	Dynasty 18	Rounded end missing. Diagonal wear marks visible on both sides.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768i	Spatula	Bone	8,6	2,6	0,32		Thomas 1981, 42.	Dynasty 12?	Bone spatula, broken at one end, the other is a pen-nib point but chipped. Polished on one surface, while the other is covered by wear traces. In some point highly wear cancellous bone is exposed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768ii	Spatula	Bone		3,37	0,19		Thomas 1981, 42.		Bone spatula, very thin, pen-nib point broken, and broken on all other sides. On the bottom cancellous bone completely exposed and not wear.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768iii	Spatula	Bone	6,5	2,3	0,29		Thomas 1981, 42.		Broken bone spatula, only part of the pen-nib point preserved. Parallel lines on the point, over and side, but underneath cancellous bone exposed and not polished.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC16768iv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Fragment of a bone spatula broken at both ends. On the upper surface parallel lines due to the bone structure, on the bottom cancellous bone and wear traces on the opposite part from the point.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768v	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Bone spatula, almost complete, point chipped. One end has an elongated point, pen-nib shape, the other has a sort of triangular form. Quite short. Lower surface completed cover of wear signs, generally long, thin and parallel lines. Cancellous bone only partially exposed due to more intense use on that point (polished part is at a higher level than cancellous bone).	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768vi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Broken spatula with a thin and long point still preserved. One side is polished, the other is not clear since it seem broken and cancellous bone came to light. But point is worn and seems that it has always been like that.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768vii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, almost complete, point chipped. Wear traces not clear. Polished on both sides.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC16768viii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, almost complete but broken into two pieces, with the pointed end missing. Slightly curved. One side is polished and shows numerous wear marks, while the other side has exposed cancellous bone, which is smooth and completely obliterated near the preserved end.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768ix	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, broken at both ends, curved. Both surfaces are polished but has clearly visible signs of wear.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768x	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, broken at both ends, curved. Upper surfaces are polished, the other has cancellous bone exposed, but quite smooth	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, broken at both ends, flat. Both surfaces are polished but has clearly visible signs of wear.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long and narrow bone spatula, broken in two pieces, one end missing and the other is rounded. Polished on both sides. No signs of wear.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC16768xiii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		long and narrow bone spatula, triangular point. Polished on the upper surface, on the lower surface cancellous bone has been obliterated by use and has completely disappeared.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xiv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Long point of a bone spatula, broken. Upper surface is polished, lower surface has cancellous bone exposed, but quite smooth.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Bone spatula, broken in two parts and missing one end. Peculiar shape, with a long point. Both surfaces are polished, the lower one has cancellous bone exposed but almost cancelled by wear. Edges completely blunt.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xvi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Broken bone spatula, both ends are missing. Upper surface polished, but with wear traces near the broken point. Lower surface with worn cancellous bone. Two small cuts on one side.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xvii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 42.		Fragment of a bone spatula. One side is polished but covered of signs and the other has cancellous bone exposed, not smooth.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC16768xviii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Bone spatula, broken at one end, long point. Thick and curved. One side is polished and the other has cancellous bone exposed, especially in the central area where friction could not reach it.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xix	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Long and thick point of a bone spatula, polished on one side, the other has cancellous bone exposed, which is slightly smoother near the point.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xx	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Fragment of a bone spatula, one side is smooth and the other has cancellous bone exposed.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xxi	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Small fragment of a bone spatula, one side is smooth and the other has cancellous bone almost completely obliterated and wear signs.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xxii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Fragment of a bone spatula, polished on one side while the other has cancellous bone exposed. Quite smooth.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xxiii	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Thin fragment of a bone spatula, polished on one side, the other with smooth cancellous bone.	Petrie Museum
1	UC16768xxiv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Small fragment of a bone spatula, one side is polished, the other has cancellous bone exposed.	Petrie Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	UC16768xxv	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Small fragment of a bone spatula, both ends are missing but side are preserved. Smooth on both surfaces, on the lower one cancellous bone is appearing.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7713	Spatula						Thomas 1981, 43.		Wooden spatula, complete. Shape is similar to bone examples, convex as ribs. Slightly thicker than those made of bone. Parallel striations due to wear on both sides.	Petrie Museum
1	56.20.149	Spatula								Bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib point, the other flat. Both sides polished, one with several parallel wear marks.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.24.366	Spatula								Bone spatula, broken and worn. Point probably pen-nib in origin. Lower side with cancellous bone exposed and not smoothed.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.21.364	Spatula								Bone spatula, quite complete, chipped in several points. One end with a long and thin pen-nib point, the other flat. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed, not smoothed.	Liverpool World Museum
1	56.21.365	Spatula/beater								Bone spatula/beater, elongated point, convex. Broken. Cancellous bone exposed inside concave surface. Smoothed edges and point.	Liverpool World Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
1	555.i	Spatula		Bone	10,8	3,42	0,25				Bone spatula, one end with a pen-nib point, the other missing. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed, not smoothed (except on the point).	Manchester Museum
1	555.ii	Spatula		Bone	8,8	2,3	0,26				Bone spatula, one end with a pen-nib point, the other rounded. Upper side polished, lower side polished but cancellous bone exposed near the rounded end. Parallel marks due to wear on the surface.	Manchester Museum
1	555.iii	Spatula		Bone	8,9	2	0,26				Bone spatula, one end with a pen-nib point, the other rounded. Upper side polished, lower side polished but cancellous bone exposed near the rounded end and in the middle. Parallel marks due to wear on the surface.	Manchester Museum
1	555.iv	Spatula		Bone	8,4	2	0,28				Bone spatula, point missing, the other end round but chipped. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed but quite smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.v	Spatula		Bone	12	1,8	0,57				Bone spatula, one end with a triangular point, the other rounded. Upper side polished but damaged, lower side with cancellous bone exposed.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.vi	Spatula								Bone spatula, one end with a triangular point, the other missing. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed and not smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.vii	Spatula								Bone spatula, complete but pen-nib point chipped. The other end is rounded. Both sides polished, cancellous bone almost disappeared on the lower side. Traces of a glossy substance on the surface with vegetable fibres embedded.	Manchester Museum
1	555.viii	Spatula								Bone spatula, almost complete but damaged on the side and on the upper surface. One end with a pen-nib point, the other quite rounded. Upper side with polished surface, lower side with cancellous bone exposed but smoothed. Spot with thick wear traces.	Manchester Museum
1	555.ix	Spatula								Bone spatula, elongated point, the other end missing. Polished on the upper side, lower side with cancellous bone exposed but smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.x	Spatula								Bone spatula, one end with a pen-nib point, the other missing. Polished on both sides. Very thin and delicate spatula.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.xi	Spatula	Bone	8	1,7	0,22				Bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib point (slightly chipped), the other well rounded. Polished on both sides, but on the lower side, cancellous bone is clearly evident where surface is less worn by use.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xii	Spatula	Bone	6,4	1,8	0,35				Small bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other rounded. Quite thick and solid. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed and not smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xiii	Spatula	Bone	9,7	2,25	0,27				Bone spatula, highly damaged. One end with a chipped pen-nib point, the other missing. Upper side quite polished, lower side with cancellous bone partially exposed and partially obliterated by use.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xiv	Spatula	Bone	10,89	2,3	0,27				Bone spatula, complete. One end with thin, long, pen-nib point, the other roughly rounded. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone almost obliterated by use.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xv	Spatula	Bone	12,2	2,42	0,35				Bone spatula, almost complete. One end with a chipped pen-nib point, the other roughly rounded. Upper side well polished, lower side with cancellous bone almost obliterated by use. Parallel striation visible on lower side and on the point.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.xvi	Spatula	Bone	6,5	2,38	0,3				Bone spatula, broken. One end with a chipped pen-nib point, the other missing. Upper side well polished, lower side with cancellous bone almost obliterated by use.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xvii	Spatula	Bone	7,7	1,19	0,25				Fragment of bone spatula with triangular point. Quite polished by use.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xviii	Spatula	Bone	14,6	1,7	0,3				Long and narrow bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib point, the other rounded. Surface highly damaged. Convex rib. Upper side polished, lower side with smoothed cancellous bone exposed, almost obliterated in the central part.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xix	Spatula	Bone	5,3	2,6	0,4				Fragment of a bone spatula with broken pen-nib point.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xx	Spatula	Bone	5,6	1,2	0,36				Small fragment of a pen-nib point with evident parallel striation due to wear.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxi	Spatula	Bone	8,9	1,54	0,26				Bone spatula, highly damaged, one end rounded, the other incomplete. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed except in the central part, where it has been obliterated by use.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.xxii	Spatula								Bone spatula, one end with a pen-nib point, the other broken. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed and not smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxiii	Spatula								Fragment of bone spatula, both ends missing. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed and not smoothed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxiv	Spatula								Small bone spatula, very well shaped. One elongated point, the other end rounded. Both sides polished and covered by parallel striation due to wear.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxv	Spatula								Bone spatula, complete, both ends rounded. Both sides polished, worn especially near one edge.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxvi	Spatula								Bone spatula, both ends missing. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxvii	Spatula								Very long bone spatula, complete but broken in three pieces. One end with a triangular point, the other roughly rounded. Damaged surface. Lower side with cancellous bone exposed, partially smoothed. Wear traces evident on all surface, especially on the centre of lower side.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.xxviii	Spatula	Bone	7	1,3	0,3				Elongated point of a spatula, broken. Very well polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxix	Spatula	Bone	9,8	2,7	0,7				Fragment of a point of spatula. Not cut in half, where broken cancellous bone is clearly visible. Wear traces visible on the point.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxx	Spatula	Bone	7,3	1,42	2,1				Small bone spatula, complete. One triangular point, the other end rounded. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxxi	Spatula	Bone	7,9	1,7	0,17				Small bone spatula, complete. One end with a pen-nib point, the other rounded. Upper side polished, the other with cancellous bone partially exposed (and not smoothed) and partially obliterated by wear (especially in the central part). It clearly shows that cancellous bone was left untreated and when smoothed, it is due to wear.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxxii	Spatula	Bone	8,1	1,3	0,34				Fragment of bone spatula, well polished on the upper side, lower side with cancellous bone partially disappeared.	Manchester Museum
1	555.xxxiii	Spatula	Bone	6,6	1,3	0,15				Small bone spatula, complete. One end with a triangular point, the other end rounded. Highly polished on the upper side, less on the lower side, especially near the rounded end.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.a	Spatula						Griffith 1910, 51. Petrie 1891, pl. XVIII n. 21.		Bone spatula, long and narrow, broken at both ends and on the side. Upper side quite polished, lower side with smoothed cancellous bone exposed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.a.ii	Spatula						Griffith 1910, 51. Petrie 1891, pl. XVIII n. 21.		Small bone spatula, complete, slightly chipped on one side. Both ends are rounded. Polished on both sides and covered by parallel striations due to wear. 5 small notches on one edge.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.i	Spatula						Griffith 1910, 51. Petrie 1891, pl. XVIII n. 21.		Small fragment of bone spatula, both ends missing.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.ii	Spatula								Bone spatula with one end rounded, the other missing. Upper side quite polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.iii	Spatula								Bone spatula, both ends missing. Highly polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.iv	Spatula								Bone spatula, broken at both ends. Upper side and edges well polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed but smoothed.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.b.v	Spatula								Bone spatula, one end rounded, the other missing. Surface quite rough but were traces well detectable. Lower side with cancellous bone exposed, partially obliterated near one edge.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.vi	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow. One end rounded, the other missing. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.vii	Spatula								Bone spatula, one end rounded, the other missing. Long and narrow. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.viii	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow. One end rounded, the other missing. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.ix	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow. One end with a triangular point, the other missing. Polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.x	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow. One end with a triangular point, the other missing. Upper side polished, lower side with cancellous bone exposed, more polished near the preserved point.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.xi	Spatula								Bone spatula, complete. Long and narrow, with a triangular point and the other end rounded. Well polished on both sides.	Manchester Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	555.b.xii	Spatula								Bone spatula, both ends rounded. Upper side well polished, lower side polished near the ends, less in the middle. cancellous bone partially visible.	Manchester Museum
1	555.b.xiii	Spatula								Bone spatula, both ends rounded. Upper side well polished, lower side polished near the ends, less in the middle. Cancellous bone partially visible. Very curved.	Manchester Museum
1	EA90071	Spatula								Bone spatula, long and narrow. One end slightly pointed, the other rounded. Extremely polished on both sides. Cosmetic spatula?	British Museum

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
1	522	Weaving comb	Wood	12,5	10			Griffith 1910, 49.	New Kingdom (?)	Wooden weaving-comb, used to card the flax fibres (?). The wide, flat end is cut into 18 teeth.	Manchester Museum
1	530	Warp spacer	Wood	24	2,7	2,9x2,7		Griffith 1910, 49.	New Kingdom (XVIII-XIX dyn)	Part of a warp spacer, used to set the spacing of the yarn on a loom. Broken at both ends. Groove distance variable, on average 0,75. 27 grooves in total.	Manchester Museum
1	UC7807	Warp spacer	Wood	57,5				Thomas 1981, 39.			Petrie Museum
1	UC7808	Weaver's slay		106				Thomas 1981, 40.		Broken in three pieces	Petrie Museum
1	UC7824	Weaver's slay		40				Thomas 1981, 40.		Broken	Petrie Museum
1	UC27867	Rod	Wood					Thomas 1981, 35.		Possibly used to support the loom.	Petrie Museum
1	UC7926	Peg	Wood					Thomas 1981, 39.		Possibly used to support the loom.	Petrie Museum

DEIR EL-MEDINA

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0311	Spindle		Wood	26,5	1					Spindle almost complete, top broken. Pointed shaft, covered with a sort of patina. Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, well made. Surface quite clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical			5,5	1,7		24			
DeM_2024_M23_0312	Spindle		Wood	13,1	1					Spindle broken at the middle of the shaft. Darkened wood, pretty ruined spindle whorl. A lot of thread wounds around it.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical			4,4	1,7		13			
DeM_2024_M23_0313	Spindle		Wood	17,4	1					Spindle broken in the middle of the shaft. The shaft has the bark preserved. Flat top. Not very well-prepared shaft. Well rounded spindle whorl cut from a small branch. Some residues of a light yellowish substance on both top and bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical			5,5	1,5		19			
DeM_2024_M23_0314	Spindle		Wood	12	1,1					Spindle broken at 1/3 of the shaft. Top rounded with a deep incision for the thread, covered by fibres. Spindle whorls heavily encrusted on the top, much less on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical			5,4	1,5		19			
DeM_2024_M23_0316	Spindle shaft		Wood	24,8	1,1				9	Spindle shaft, almost complete, very badly preserved. Spiral notch at the top. Completely covered by a substance and hardened by it, so now it is fragile.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0317	Spindle shaft		Wood	17,4	1				5	Spindle shaft, broken at 2/3. Long spiral notch at the top, and trace of where the spindle whorl was placed.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0318	Spindle shaft	Wood	16	1			4			Spindle shaft, broken at 2/3. Long spiral notch at the top, and trace of where the spindle whorl was placed. Much thinner at the height of the whorl (0,7).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0319	Spindle shaft	Wood	12,2	1,1			4			Spindle shaft, broken at 1/3. Surface very dirty, some traces of threads slightly visible below the place where the whorl was originally placed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0320	Spindle shaft	Wood	28,9	1			7			Spindle shaft, almost complete. Cracked along the length. Notch not preserved but still visible.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0321	Spindle shaft	Wood	20,2	0,9			6			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Cracked on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0322	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,8	0,9			4			Spindle shaft, 1/2 preserved. Surface is dirty. Notch is well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0323	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,2	1			4			Spindle shaft, 1/2 preserved. Surface is dirty. Notch is well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0324	Spindle shaft	Wood	8,9	1			3			Small fragment of spindle shaft with a long spiral notch and a thick layer of incrustation.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0325	Spindle shaft	Wood	7,5	0,9			1,8			Small fragment of spindle shaft with a long spiral notch and some incrustation. A thread is wound around the spindle.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0326	Spindle shaft	Wood	12,7	0,9			2,5			Spindle shaft, broken at 1/3. Spiral notch at the top, clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0327	Spindle shaft	Wood	3,3	0,9			0,4			Small fragment of spindle shaft with rounded top preserved. Small peg attached with some fibres.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0328	Spindle shaft	Wood	2,7	0,6			0,4			Small fragment of spindle shaft with flat top preserved. Small peg attached with some fibres.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0329	Spindle shaft	Wood	18,6	1			6			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Fibres wound around the spiral, mark on the shaft.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0330	Spindle shaft	Wood	10,2	1			2,8			Spindle shaft, 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Flat top.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0331	Spindle shaft	Wood	14,7	1,1			6			Spindle shaft, half preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Flat top.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0332	Spindle shaft	Wood	21,9	0,9			5			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. Only the bottom is preserved and has a quite sharp point.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0333	Spindle shaft	Wood	19	0,8			3			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. Only the bottom is preserved and has a quite sharp point.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0334	Spindle shaft	Wood	10,1	9			3			Spindle shaft, 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved, almost complete.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0335	Spindle shaft	Wood	16,9	0,9			5			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. It is probably the rounded tip preserved. Very thick layer on incrustation close to the point. Thinnest 0,6.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0336	Spindle shaft	Wood	13	0,8			4			Spindle shaft, 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Flat top. Quite clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0337	Spindle shaft	Wood	8,4	0,9			2			Spindle shaft, only the top is preserved. Spiral notch well preserved. Slightly dirty except for the area where the spindle whorl was placed.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0338	Spindle shaft?	Wood	14,2	0,9			5			Shaft, possibly from a spindle shaft. Both edges are missing, and it is straight. Several incisions on the shaft, not clear its use.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0339	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,7	1,1			6			Spindle shaft, more than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch partially preserved. Top flat. Wood clear.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0340	Spindle shaft	Wood	18,6	1			7			Spindle shaft, 2/3 preserved. Top and bottom missing.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0341	Spindle shaft	Wood	16	1			5			Spindle shaft almost half preserved. Top was probably not much longer. It has a lot of deep incision next to the top, going in different directions. Their purpose is not clear.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0342	Spindle shaft	Wood	19,5	0,8			5			Spindle shaft, thickening in the middle. Top and bottom not preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0343	Spindle shaft	Wood	18,2	0,9			5			Spindle shaft, thickening in the middle. Bottom not preserved. Top almost preserved, just chipped. A few traces of fibres are visible.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0344	Spindle shaft	Wood	24	0,9			7			Spindle shaft, almost complete, top and bottom missing.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0345	Spindle shaft	Wood	17,8	0,8			3			Spindle shaft, only the tip is preserved. Rounded point.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0346	Spindle shaft	Wood	17,2	0,75			4			Wooden shaft, no edges preserved, but one (top) looks as almost complete.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0347	Spindle shaft	Wood	16,5	0,72			5			Wooden shaft, half preserved. The rounded bottom tip is preserved.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0348	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,2	0,8			1,7			Wooden shaft, only the bottom point preserved, quite sharp.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0349	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,3	0,8			2,1			Wooden shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch perfectly preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0350	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,6	1			3,1			Wooden shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Bottom tip well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0351	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,3	1			4,5			Spindle shaft?, less than 1/3 preserved, no edges preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0352	Spindle shaft	Wood	16,8	1			4,8			Spindle shaft?, less than 1/3 preserved, no edges preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0353	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,7	0,6			1,3			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved, tip preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0354	Spindle shaft	Wood	18,3	0,9			10,7			Spindle shaft more than half preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0355	Spindle shaft	Wood	15	1			3,8			Spindle shaft, around half preserved, one edge almost preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0356	Spindle shaft	Wood	15	1			4,4			Spindle shaft, around half preserved, one edge almost preserved, with a spiral notch roughly cut.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0357	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,2	0,9			2,4			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved, broken along the spiral notch. Clear trace of where the spindle whorl was placed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0358	Spindle shaft	Wood	8	0,7			1,3			Spindle shaft, only the tip preserved. Heavily encrusted.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0359	Spindle shaft	Wood	8	0,8			3,1			Spindle shaft, only the tip preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0360	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,9	0,9			2,2			Spindle shaft?, less than 1/3 preserved, no edges preserved. Deep incision on the surface, probably due to the rubbing of a thread (not used as spindle)	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0361	Spindle shaft	Wood	15,8	1			7,8			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved, broken along the spiral notch.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0362	Spindle shaft	Wood	14,2	0,8			3,1			Spindle shaft preserved less than half, tip preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0363	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,5	0,9			4,5			Spindle shaft preserved less than half, top preserved with a spiral notch on top.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0364	Spindle shaft	Wood	8,6	0,9			2,4			Spindle shaft, small part preserved. Spiral notch very roughly preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0365	Spindle shaft	Wood	12	0,98			4,8			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Broken under the notch, as the part where the whorl was present is clearly visible as it is cleaner. Heavily encrusted in the middle with traces of fibres under it.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0366	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,2	0,8			3,6			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0367	Spindle shaft	Wood	10	0,8			1,9			Small fragment of shaft with fibres wounded around it. No edges preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0368	Spindle shaft	Wood	13,8	0,9			3,9			Spindle shaft, top broken along the notch, less than 1/3 preserved.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0369	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,4	0,7			1,3			Spindle shaft, top preserved? With several rounds of fibres along it and one yarn.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0370	Spindle shaft	Wood	8,9	0,6			1,1			Spindle shaft, only the tip is preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0371	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,4	0,9			2,8			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0372	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,4	0,7			1,2			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Rounded tip well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0373	Spindle shaft	Wood	12,5	0,7			1,7			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip quite preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0374	Spindle shaft	Wood	6,5	0,7			2,2			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0375	Spindle shaft	Wood	11	0,6			3,4			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip quite preserved. Roughly cut, not rounded nor smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0376	Spindle shaft	Wood	11,1	0,9			2,4			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip quite preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0377	Spindle shaft	Wood	10,9	0,85			2,7			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. No edge preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0378	Spindle shaft	Wood	10,7	0,85			1,9			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip quite preserved. Wood not well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0379	Spindle shaft	Wood	7,6	0,65			0,6			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip quite preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0380	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,5	0,7			1,1			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip almost preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0381	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,6	0,67			1,2			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip almost preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0382	Spindle shaft	Wood	8	0,85			2			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. No edge preserved. Well rounded and smoothed. Area where the spindle whorl was placed is cleaner.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0383	Spindle shaft	Wood	4	1			1,1			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0384	Spindle shaft	Wood	7	0,8			1,1			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0385	Spindle shaft	Wood	9	0,5			0,6			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed. Thread wound around the shaft.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0386	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,8	0,7			1,1			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0387	Spindle shaft	Wood	6,5	0,7			0,8			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0388	Spindle shaft	Wood	6	0,8			1,7			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0389	Spindle shaft	Wood	10	0,8			3,6			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. No edge preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0390	Spindle shaft	Wood	3,3	0,7			0,6			Small fragment of spindle shaft with spiral notch well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0391	Spindle shaft	Wood	7,2	0,9			2			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Rounded tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0392	Spindle shaft	Wood	8,4	0,9			1,6			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. No edge preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0393	Spindle shaft	Wood	9,1	1			3,8			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Pointed tip well preserved. Not very well rounded but the surface is heavily encrusted and ruined.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0394	Spindle shaft	Wood	6,5	0,75			1,4			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. Rounded tip well preserved. Well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0395	Spindle shaft	Wood	8	0,9			2,7			Spindle shaft, less than 1/3 preserved. No edge preserved. Not well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0396	Spindle shaft	Wood	3,5	0,8			0,9			Spindle shaft, fragment. Tip almost preserved. Not well rounded and smoothed. Heavily encrusted.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0397	Spindle shaft	Wood	12,1	0,53			1,3			Spindle shaft, fragment. Tip almost preserved. Not well rounded and smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0462	Spindle	Wood	22,3	1						Spindle, almost complete. Shaft preserved for a long part; spiral notch preserved but encrusted. Fibres wound around the top.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,5		17		Spindle whorl rounded and smoothed, top encrusted, patina on the bottom.	
DeM_2024_M23_0463	Spindle		Wood	10,6	0,8			18,1		Shaft preserved for a 1/3, spiral notch not visible. Top heavily encrusted. Fibres wound around the top with a peg. Spindle whorl rounded and smoothed, top encrusted, patina on the bottom. A spiral groove around the bottom of the shaft might belong to a secondary used.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,9					
DeM_2024_M23_0464	Spindle		Wood	12,3	0,8			9,6		Shaft preserved for a 1/3, spiral notch well preserved. Spindle whorl rounded and smoothed, top and bottom almost clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_0465	Spindle		Wood	12,8	0,9			17,7		Shaft preserved for a 1/3, spiral notch well preserved. Top heavily encrusted. Spindle whorl rounded and smoothed, top heavily encrusted. Thread wound around a small peg.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_0466	Spindle		Wood	17	0,9			14		Shaft preserved for quite a long piece; spiral notch well preserved. Top heavily encrusted. Spindle whorl rounded and smoothed, top and bottom heavily encrusted. Thread wound around a small peg.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,9					
DeM_2024_M23_0467	Spindle		Wood	4,7	0,8					Shaft preserved for a small piece, with a lot of thread wound around it. Spindle whorl complete, heavily encrusted, on the bottom several	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,5		13,1		incised lines, possibly of manufacturing.	
DeM_2024_M23_0468	Spindle		Wood					17,5		Spindle whorl with a small fragment of shaft inside the hole. Almost complete, a small part burned. Covered by patina on all sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,8	2,1	1				
DeM_2024_M23_0469	Spindle		Wood	2,6	0,7					Spindle whorl with a small fragment of shaft inside the hole. Complete, well rounded and smoothed. Covered by encrustation on the top, almost clean on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,25		4,3			
DeM_2024_M23_0470	Spindle		Wood	10,5	0,85			12,1		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a U notch clean and well preserved. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Almost clean. Thread wound around the bottom of the whorl.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,2	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_0471	Spindle		Wood	11,1	0,86					Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top and bottom not preserved. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Covered by a thin patina, with whitish dots. Mark on one side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_0472	Spindle		Wood	13,8	0,8			19		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top rounded with a spiral notch and fibres wound around a peg. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation on top and side, bottom clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,7					

N.	Typology		Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0473	Spindle		Wood	14,4	0,1						Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top almost preserved. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Covered by a thin layer of encrustation on top and side, bottom clean. One side slightly burned.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,4		21				
DeM_2024_M23_0474	Spindle		Wood	10,1	0,8						Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, broken on both sides. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Clean on both sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,4						
DeM_2024_M23_0475	Spindle		Wood	23,5	0,8			23			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large part, top almost preserved. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded and smoothed. Covered by a thin layer of encrustation on top and side, bottom with a thicker layer and some whitish substance.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6	1,8						
DeM_2024_M23_0476	Spindle		Wood	7	0,8			10			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, rounded edge preserved, possibly the bottom. Spindle whorl incomplete, very damaged. Loose on the shaft.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,4						
DeM_2024_M23_0477	Spindle		Wood	6,2	1,8	0,8		16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Covered by a thin layer of patina on top and edge, bottom clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,8						
DeM_2024_M23_0478	Spindle		Wood	5	0,9			17			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a spiral notch well carved. Covered by a thin layer of patina on top and edge, bottom clean. Cut from a large branch.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,4						
DeM_2024_M23_0479	Spindle		Wood	20,2	0,9			20			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large part. Flat top with a spiral notch. Covered by a thin layer of patina on the edge, top and bottom clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	2						

N.	Typology		Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0480	Spindle		Wood	16	0,98			21			Spindle, shaft preserved for quite a large part. Flat top with a spiral notch. Covered by a thick layer of patina on the top and edge, and bottom clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	2,1						
DeM_2024_M23_0481	Spindle		Wood	10,5	1			19			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded. Covered by a thick layer of patina on all sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,7						
DeM_2024_M23_0482	Spindle		Wood	12	0,65			14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded. Thin layer of patina on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,7						
DeM_2024_M23_0483	Spindle		Wood	14	0,9			16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Top and bottom missing. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded. Thick layer of encrustation on the top and patina on the bottom and on the shaft.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,6						
DeM_2024_M23_0484	Spindle		Wood	3,2	0,75			16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Top and bottom missing. Spindle whorl incomplete, 2/3 preserved, well rounded. Thick layer of encrustation on the top and partially on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	2,1						
DeM_2024_M23_0486	Spindle		Wood	4,2	0,7						Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Rounded top with a spiral notch. Spindle whorl incomplete, 2/3 preserved, well rounded. Thick layer of encrustation on the top and patina on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,5		13				
DeM_2024_M23_0489	Spindle		Wood	9,7		0,8		17			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Spindle whorl complete, well rounded. Thick layer of	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,7				encrustation on the top and a white substance on the bottom and on the side. Several cracks on the edge	
DeM_2024_M23_0490	Spindle		Wood	7,9	0,9					Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Rounded top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, but warped and ruined.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_0491	Spindle		Wood	15,5	0,9		17			Spindle, shaft preserved for quite a large part. Rounded top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, top covered by traces of encrustation, bottom and shaft by a thin patina.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_0492	Spindle		Wood	14,5	0,7		17			Spindle, shaft preserved for quite a large part. Rounded top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, top and side covered by traces of encrustation, bottom by a thin patina.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_0493	Spindle		Wood	9,8	0,8		12			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Rounded top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl almost complete, top and side covered by a whitish substance. Wood darkened, possibly by fire?	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,9					
DeM_2024_M23_0494	Spindle		Wood	2,1	0,7		9			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, top and side covered by encrustation. Bottom clean.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,1					
DeM_2024_M23_0495	Spindle		Wood	5,5	6,7		11			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Top pointed with a carved spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, almost clean, but with holes and ruined.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_0496	Spindle		Wood	6,7	1		10		blue ink 89	Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Top pointed with a carved spiral groove. Spindle whorl	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,6				complete, covered by a thick layer of encrustation and a thin patina on the bottom.	
DeM_2024_M23_1100	Spindle		Wood	13,7	1		16		blue ink 99?	Spindle, shaft preserved for a long part. Both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, clean. Lotus flower carved on top, blue ink on the bottom.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_1101	Spindle		Wood	12,7	0,75		15		blue ink not understandable	Spindle, shaft preserved for a long part. Flat top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, with a thin layer of encrustation on top and side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,8					
DeM_2024_M23_1102	Spindle		Wood	11,7	0,9		14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, with a thin layer of encrustation on top and side. Mark on the bottom, in the shape of a small circle, roughly made.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_1103	Spindle		Wood	9,7	0,9		16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part. Flat top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, with a thick layer of encrustation on top. Possible mark on the bottom, in the shape of a star, roughly made. Fibres wound around the shaft; some have a knot.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,8					
DeM_2024_M23_1104	Spindle		Wood	12	0,9		15		blue ink 66 or 99	Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, broken along the groove. Spindle whorl complete, with a thick layer of encrustation on all sides. Possible mark on the bottom, roughly made.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,8					
DeM_2024_M23_1105	Spindle		Wood	8	0,9		10		blue ink 58	Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, with a thick layer	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,2				of encrustation on all sides. Possible mark on the bottom, in the shape of an A.	
DeM_2024_M23_1106	Spindle		Wood	9,6	0,8		9			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl almost complete, clean but very ruined.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,4					
DeM_2024_M23_1107	Spindle		Wood	10,2	0,7		10		blue ink 55, black ink [Ab 89] EN or [Ab 8 ^a] EN	Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top rounded with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, covered by encrustation on all sides. Schematic mark of a lotus flower.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_1139	Spindle		Wood	12,2	0,8		15			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by encrustation on all sides. White paint visible on the side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_1140	Spindle		Wood	7	0,8		11			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top flat with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, covered by encrustation on the top, almost clear on the other sides. White dots on top of the encrustation.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,8					
DeM_2024_M23_1141	Spindle		Wood	8,6	0,9		16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top flat with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, covered by encrustation on the bottom, almost clear on the other sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,5					
DeM_2024_M23_1142	Spindle		Wood	10,1	0,9		20			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by encrustation on all sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,9	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_1143	Spindle		Wood	4,5	1		21			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,7				whorl complete, covered by encrustation on all sides.	
DeM_2024_M23_1144	Spindle		Wood	9,1	8,6		21			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by traces of encrustation on one side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6	1,8					
DeM_2024_M23_1148	Spindle		Wood	8,4	0,8		13			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, rounded part with spiral preserved. Spindle whorl complete, covered by traces of encrustation on top and edge, bottom clear.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,4					
DeM_2024_M23_1149	Spindle		Wood	9,4	0,7		16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by traces of encrustation on one side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	2					
DeM_2024_M23_1150	Spindle		Wood	3,5	0,9		14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl incomplete, 2/3 preserved, covered by traces of encrustation on one side. White substance (paint?) on all sides	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,6					
DeM_2024_M23_1151	Spindle		Wood	9,5	0,8		12			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, one edge with spiral groove almost complete. Spindle whorl complete, large crack from hole to edge, covered by traces of encrustation on one side. Yellowish substance on all sides. Wooden wedges inside the hole.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,1					
DeM_2024_M23_1152	Spindle		Wood	11,5	1,1		26			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, one edge with spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, covered by traces of encrustation on all sides. Very heavy whorl and thick shaft.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	2,3					

N.	Typology		Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1153	Spindle		Wood	11,5	0,8			9			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by traces of encrustation on one side. Very light spindle. White dots on the surface.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,4						
DeM_2024_M23_1154	Spindle		Wood	10,2	0,7			12			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, spiral groove preserved. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thick layers of encrustation on one side and a thin layer on all the others. Loose whorl.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,5						
DeM_2024_M23_1155	Spindle		Wood	10,2	0,8			10			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, spiral groove preserved. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thin layers of encrustation on the bottom, clear on top.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,6						
DeM_2024_M23_1156	Spindle		Wood	4,2	0,8			14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thin layers of encrustation on one side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,8						
DeM_2024_M23_1157	Spindle		Wood	4	0,9			11			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thin layers of encrustation on one side.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,2						
DeM_2024_M23_1158	Spindle		Wood	8	0,8			18			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thin layers of encrustation on one side, a thick layer on the other.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,5						

N.	Typology		Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1159	Spindle		Wood	8	0,8			14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, top preserved with fibres wound around the shaft and a peg. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thick layer of encrustation on the top and on the edge.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,7						
DeM_2024_M23_1160	Spindle		Wood	10,4	1			21			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, top preserved a long spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, covered by thin layer of encrustation a whitish substance. Second spindle whorl made of fibres (weight 8,9) but mud is also present.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,7						
DeM_2024_M23_1161	Spindle		Wood	15,7	1,2			21			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large section, top preserves a long spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, covered by a thick layer of encrustation on all sides and on the shaft.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,5						
DeM_2024_M23_1162	Spindle		Wood	12,4	1			33			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large section, top preserves a long spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, covered by a thin layer of encrustation and a whitish substance. The shaft and the whorl seem to be joint by mud(?) on purpose. Very heavy, possibly because is less deteriorated than the others (De Marco, pers. comm.).	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,9	2						
DeM_2024_M23_1163	Spindle		Wood	9	0,8			13			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large part, top preserves a long spiral notch. Spindle whorl complete, covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,5						

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1164	Spindle		Wood	4	0,8			10		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small fragment, no edges preserved. Spindle whorl complete, almost clear. A wooden peg inserted in the hole.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_1165	Spindle		Wood	9,9	0,7			12		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, top preserves a long spiral notch. Spindle whorl almost complete, covered by a thick layer of encrustation. Wounded threads.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,4					
DeM_2024_M23_1166	Spindle		Wood	10,4	0,8			14		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl almost complete, covered by a thin layer of encrustation.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,7					
DeM_2024_M23_1167	Spindle		Wood	5,5	0,9			15		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl almost complete, almost clean. Cut from the middle of a branch.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,5					
DeM_2024_M23_1168	Spindle		Wood	3,2	0,8			15		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl complete, almost clean. Cut from the middle of a branch. Splied thread inside the hole.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	2,1					
DeM_2024_M23_1169	Spindle		Wood	2,9	0,7			6		Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing. Spindle whorl almost complete, almost clean but extremely worn.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,9	1,8					

N.	Typology		Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1170	Spindle		Wood	6	0,9			13			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both edges missing but broken along the spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,4						
DeM_2024_M23_1171	Spindle		Wood	8,6	0,9			16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, rounded top with a spiral groove. Spindle whorl complete, traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,5						
DeM_2024_M23_1172	Spindle		Wood	2,9	0,9			16			Spindle, shaft preserved for a small part, both ends missing. Spindle whorl complete, traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. White paint on both sides.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,6						
DeM_2024_M23_1220	Spindle		Wood	16,5	0,7			14			Spindle, shaft preserved for a large part, one end with a flat top and a cylindrical notch. Spindle whorl complete, traces of encrustation on all sides. Fibres wound around the top and knotted to a peg.	On site - M23
	Spindle whorl	Conical truncated	Wood		4,6	1,8						
S. 07526/001	Spindle		Wood	16	1			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, point broken. Top with a spiral groove. Linen threads (one S-plyed and one Z-plyed) around the top, with a wooden peg to secure the knot. Cylindrical spindle whorl at the top of the shaft, surface with encrustation and white spots.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.1		0.9x1					
S. 07526/002	Spindle		Wood	19	0.9							Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.3		0.9	19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, point broken. Top with a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl set on the middle of the shaft.	
S. 07526/003	Spindle		Wood	24.9	0.9			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at one end, the other tapered to a point. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the preserved point, coarse and irregular.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0.9	5.1		0.9					
S. 07526/004	Spindle		Wood	32.4	0.9			21	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle with almost entire length preserved, but both ends chipped. Cylindrical spindle whorl near one end	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	4.9		0.8					
S. 07526/005	Spindle		Wood	16.6	1			22	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while the other one has a groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, well-shaped, with traces of encrustation. Spindle and spindle whorl have burnt marks.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.3		1					
S. 07526/006	Spindle		Wood	10.8	0.9			10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while the other one has a groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-shaped, near the top of the shaft. On the lower surface, there are some black lines, probably painted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.5		0.9					
S. 07526/007	Spindle		Wood	21	0.8			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the top, while the other end has a tapered point. Cylindrical spindle whorl, near the bottom end. Well-preserved and clean, longitudinal cut of a quite large log/branch	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.8		0.8x0.9					
S. 07526/008	Spindle		Wood	22	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the top, while the other end has a tapered point. Cylindrical spindle whorl, near the bottom end. Both shaft and whorl have traces of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.5		0.9x0.8					

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/009	Spindle		Wood	16.3	1		15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the top, while the other end has a tapered point. Cylindrical spindle whorl, attached near the bottom end. Shaft with traces of encrustation, whorl with yellowish spots on the side. Whorl is made from quite a large log/branch. Very clear wood vases on its surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.7	1x0.9					
S. 07526/010	Spindle		Wood	11	0.9		13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at one end, while the other end has a large, rounded point. There are no traces of the groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl very encrusted on the entire surface and placed near the preserved end	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.8	0.9					
S. 07526/011	Spindle		Wood	14	0.8		12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, broken at both ends, but at the top there are traces of the groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl at the top of the shaft; upper surface encrusted, lower surface with a slight coating of foreign material.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	4.9	0.7x0.8					
S. 07526/012	Spindle		Wood	10.9	0.9		10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl at one end of the shaft. Spindle and spindle whorl poorly preserved, probably due to insect damage.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.9	0.9					
S. 07526/013	Spindle		Wood	10.2	0.9		15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the top (?) while the other end tapers to a well-shaped point. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the preserved point. Spindle and spindle whorl slightly encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	5	0.9x0.8					
S. 07526/014	Spindle		Wood	9.8	0.8		20	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, broken at the bottom. Flat top is well-preserved, with a deep groove for fastening the thread. Cylindrical spindle	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	4.8	0.8					

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										whorl near the top of the shaft, encrusted on the upper surface.	
S. 07526/015	Spindle		Wood	14.7	1.1		20	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, broken at the bottom. Top with a groove to fasten the thread but which is covered by a thick layer of encrustation; encrusted material covers also remains of fibres which are slightly visible. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, very encrusted and with white spots.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.1	5		1.1				
S. 07526/016	Spindle		Wood	11	1.1		20	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Top with a break along the groove used to fasten the thread, but a thick layer of encrustation covers it; it also covers remains of fibres, slightly visible.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.3		1.1		Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, encrusted on its upper surface.		
S. 07526/017	Spindle		Wood	10.7	0.8		10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near one of the broken ends, heavily encrusted on the upper surface. Small and well-shaped.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.1		0.8				
S. 07526/018	Spindle		Wood	13.8	1		18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Top with groove covered by a thick layer of encrustation, where there are impressions of fibres. Cylindrical spindle whorl, encrusted on the upper surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.8		0.9x1				
S. 07526/019	Spindle		Wood	10.6	0.9		18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl near one of the broken ends, slightly encrusted on both surfaces.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.5		0.8x0.9				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/20	Spindle		Wood	18	0.9			21	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation on the upper surface. Lower surface clear with marks from manufacture. Inside the hole, there are visible traces of vegetal fibres, which appear on all sides of the hole.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.6		0.9				
S. 07526/021	Spindle		Wood	16.4	1			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, very thin and well-shaped, placed at the top of the shaft.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.5		1				
S. 07526/022	Spindle		Wood	14.5	0.9			19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Top with a groove highly encrusted and with traces of fibres. Cylindrical spindle whorl at the top of the shaft, well-shaped and with a thick layer of encrustation. There are traces of pink paint (?).	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.1		0.9				
S. 07526/023	Spindle		Wood	27.4	1.3			23	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at one end, while the other end, only partially preserved, is thick and rounded. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the middle of the shaft with a thin layer of patina. On the shaft, under the spindle whorl, there is an incised mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5		1x1.1				
S. 07526/025	Spindle		Wood	14.8	1			22	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle, broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered with a thin layer of patina on both sides.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.3		1				
S. 07526/026	Spindle		Wood	12.5	1			18			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4	1		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while the other end is flat with a groove to fasten the thread. Near the groove, the shaft is heavily encrusted. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation on the upper surface and on the side.	
S. 07526/027	Spindle		Wood	20.3	0.9		19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle almost complete, part of the shaft is missing, but the entire length is preserved. Flat top with a long spiral groove. The shaft is encrusted and has a thread stuck in the hole of the spindle whorl. The thread is made of linen, is plied and has an S-twist. On the shaft, there are traces of burning. Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-shaped, near the top of the spindle.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.5	0.9					
S. 07526/028	Spindle		Wood	7.6	0.9		8.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle missing the lower end, while the top is rounded and has a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl, very worn, placed near the top of the shaft. Both shaft and spindle whorl bear traces of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	4.4	0.9					
S. 07526/029	Spindle		Wood	7.7	0.9		10.5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, which should have been near the top of the shaft. Both shaft and spindle whorl have traces of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.1	0.8					
S. 07526/030	Spindle		Wood	7.7	1.1		16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, which should have been near the top of the shaft. Both shaft and spindle whorl have traces of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.2	1.1x1					

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/031	Spindle		Wood	5.1	0.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the end of the shaft, while the top is flat and it presents a cylindrical groove. Shaft is broken immediately under the spindle whorl; on the side of the whorl there are two incisions. Furthermore, the spindle whorl has two cracks across it, one of which is very deep and almost arrives at its hole.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	5	0.8		0.9				
S. 07526/032	Spindle		Wood	6.4	0.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is flat and has a groove. Under the spindle whorl, around the shaft, is still preserved part of a linen yarn: it is S-plied, its single twist is not visible. Beside the yarn, there are also non-spun fibres. A cylindrical spindle whorl sits near the top of the shaft; it has a break across it and traces of yellow paint (?) on its upper surface	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	5.8	0.9		0.9				
S. 07526/033	Spindle		Wood	14.6	0.7			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, top rounded with a groove to fasten the thread. On the upper part of the shaft there is a thread which holds a wooden peg; yarn is plied with a Z-twist, direction of single twist is not visible.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	4.5	1.5		0.7	Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a whitish layer of encrustation on the upper surface, while the lower surface is clean. It is secured to the spindle by fibres and/or wooden fragments visible inside the hole.			
S. 07526/034	Spindle		Wood	17.4	0.9			18			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.3		0.9			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and groove to fasten the thread. Near the top, under the spindle whorl, there is a single thread, S-plied, single twist not visible. A cylindrical spindle whorl is placed near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation on its upper surface, while the lower surface is clean with an incised mark.	
S. 07526/035	Spindle		Wood	15	0.9			15		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Top was likely broken in ancient times, as a thread is fastened to the break; this thread holds a wooden peg and is S-plied, single twist not visible. The yarn is quite encrusted and partly stuck in the hole of the spindle whorl. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation on the upper surface, while lower surface and side show a thin layer of patina. From the lower side of the hole emerges yarn.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	5.2	1.1		0.9					
S. 07526/036	Spindle		Wood	13.3	0.9			15		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and an incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, small and thick, with a lateral break, and a very worn surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.4		0.8x0.9					
S. 07526/037	Spindle		Wood	12.9	1			15		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and an incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with upper surface covered by a thick coat of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.8		0.9x1					

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/038	Spindle		Wood	14.4	0.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a groove to fasten the thread. Shaft grows thicker towards the break. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with the upper surface covered by a thick layer of encrustation with whitish efflorescence.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.1		0.9				
S. 07526/039	Spindle		Wood	15.7	0.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and an incised groove. On the shaft, under the spindle whorl, there are traces of unspun fibres, which make two complete rotations, but there is no twist seen in them. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with the upper surface highly encrusted. Deep break on the side.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.8		0.9				
S. 07526/040	Spindle		Wood	11.7	0.8			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, not encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.5		0.8				
S. 07526/041	Spindle		Wood	10	0.8			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and an incised groove. On the shaft a mark is incised. A cylindrical spindle whorl is set near the top of the shaft; encrusted on the upper surface	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.8		0.8				
S. 07526/042	Spindle		Wood	9.7	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends with fibre traces on the shaft. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top (?) of the shaft, with one surface covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.8		0.9				
S. 07526/043	Spindle		Wood	9.4	0.9			18			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.3		0.8x0.9			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, with one surface covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	
S. 07526/044	Spindle		Wood	8.9	0.7			16			Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl attached, with one surface covered by a thick layer of whitish encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.2		0.7			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		
S. 07526/045	Spindle		Wood	15.4	1.2			16			Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and an incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft covered by a thin patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.2		1.2			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		
S. 07526/046	Spindle		Wood	19	1			17			Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is broken along the groove used to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl near the top of the shaft, with a large hole on the side, probably produced by insects.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		0.9x1			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		
S. 07526/047	Spindle		Wood	21.4	1			14			Wooden spindle almost complete, point missing, while top is broken along the groove to fasten the thread. A cylindrical spindle whorl is placed near the top of the shaft, with clean surfaces and four radial incisions on its lower side.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.1		1			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		
S. 07526/048	Spindle		Wood	21.7	1			14			Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and a groove to fasten the yarn. Cylindrical spindle whorl on the top of the shaft; on the lower surface there is a mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.5		0.9x1			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		
S. 07526/049	Spindle		Wood	5.4	1			17			Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl highly worn but clear of encrustation. On one side there are traces of a pinkish paint.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.3		1			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/050	Spindle		Wood	5.7	0.8			14.4	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken immediately under the spindle whorl; flat top preserved with an incised groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, quite thick and with a thin layer of patina on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.1	4.5		0.8				
S. 07526/051	Spindle		Wood	11.1	1.2			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top, covered by a thin layer of patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	6.1		0.8				
S. 07526/052	Spindle		Wood	11	0.9			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and incised groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top, covered by a thin layer of patina. Small wedges of wood in the hole which fastens the spindle whorl.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.9				
S. 07526/053	Spindle		Wood	7.6	0.7			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite thick and clean. Wood slightly warped.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.8		0.7				
S. 07526/054	Spindle		Wood	8.9	0.8			12.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle whorl broken at the bottom, with rounded but chipped top and an incised groove to fasten the threads. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, quite encrusted and with a mark incised on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.5		0.8				
S. 07526/055	Spindle		Wood	18	0.9			21	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends, but most of its shaft is preserved. At the top, there are still traces of the groove to fasten the fibres. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of shaft, quite encrusted on its whole surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.2		0.9				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07526/056	Spindle		Wood	11	0.8			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at one end, while the other ends with a sharp point. Spindle whorl placed near the break and had two short, incised lines on one surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5		0.8				
S. 07526/057	Spindle		Wood	19.1	0.8			22	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends, the upper one along the groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, slightly encrusted and with a lateral break.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.4		0.8				
S. 07526/058	Spindle		Wood	10.9	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and an incised spiral groove to fasten the fibres. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, covered by a very thin patina. On the lower surface some marks (?) are incised.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.8		0.9				
S. 07526/059	Spindle		Wood	11.4	0.7			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and a spiral groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, covered by a thin layer of patina. On the lower surface there are traces of the manufacturing process.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.2		0.6				
S. 07526/060	Spindle		Wood	16.9	0.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends, but most of the shaft probably preserved. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near one end of the shaft, covered by a thin layer of patina and with a lateral break. Hole warped on its edges. Flax fibres are visible in the lower part of the hole.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.7		0.9				
S. 07526/061	Spindle		Wood	21.7	0.9			13			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.2		0.9		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and a very well-preserved spiral groove. Shaft almost complete. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, covered by a thin layer of patina on the upper surface and with a lateral break.	
S. 07526/062	Spindle		Wood	15.4	0.8			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at one end, the other seems to finish with a sharp point. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near sharp tip and covered by a thin layer of patina. On this side there is an incised mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	4.8		0.8				
S. 07526/063	Spindle		Wood	11.7	1			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is flat with an incised groove on it. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft; on the lower surface, there is an incised mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.6		0.9				
S. 07526/064	Spindle		Wood	6.8	0.8			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft covered by a thin layer of patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.9						
S. 07526/065	Spindle		Wood	9.2	1			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Near one of the breaks there is an incised mark. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft encrusted on the upper surface with whitish material. Between shaft and spindle whorl there are traces of vegetable fibres.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.5		1				
S. 07526/066	Spindle		Wood	11.4	0.8			17			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.2			0.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while the other end is rounded, with a spiral groove, but highly encrusted. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft with a thick layer of encrustation on the upper surface. Some incisions (wear marks?) on the lower surface.	
S. 07526/067	Spindle		Wood	10	1			18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom with a rounded end with an incised spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, slightly encrusted and cracked.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	5.1							
S. 07526/068	Spindle		Wood	6.6	0.9			10.5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, large and flat, with some marks on one surface, some of them covered by a whitish substance.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.1			0.9				
S. 07526/069	Spindle		Wood	9.9	0.9			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and an incised spiral groove. Wood perfectly preserved. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft covered by a thin patina and some traces of a pinkish paint.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.4			0.7				
S. 07526/070	Spindle		Wood	15.6	1			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends, with rounded top and spiral groove. Thick traces of encrustation on the top. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, encrusted on the upper surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	4.8			1				
S. 07526/071	Spindle		Wood	8.6	0.9			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.6			0.7				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										with encrustation on the upper surface.	
S. 07526/072	Spindle		Wood	8.8	0.8		12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while the other end is slightly pointed and has a small groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft with lateral breaks. Encrusted on the upper surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	4		0.8				
S. 07526/073	Spindle		Wood	3.9	0.8		8.5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom immediately under the spindle whorl, with a flat top and a groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl, large and flat, encrusted on the upper surface. On the lower surface are traces of painted radial lines.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.3		0.8				
S. 07526/074	Spindle		Wood	22	1		18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Complete wooden spindle pointed bottom and rounded top. On the top, there is a long spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.1	5		1				
S. 07526/075	Spindle		Wood	12.7	1		17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is rounded with a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft. Cylindrical spindle whorl, not very well shaped, is completely clean and with a mark incised on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.5		1				
S. 07526/076	Spindle		Wood	18.8	0.8		14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the top (probably), while the other end tapered to a rounded point. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed almost at the middle of the surviving length of the shaft, quite	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	4.6		0.8				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										near to the point. Small hole on one surface.	
S. 07526/077	Spindle		Wood	14.6	0.9		16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft (only partly preserved) with encrustation on the upper surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.2		0.9				
S. 07526/078	Spindle		Wood	14.2	0.9		18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and an incised spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a very thick layer of encrustation, which partly covers the upper part of the shaft too.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.1		0.9				
S. 07526/079	Spindle		Wood	7.8	0.7		15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a very well-preserved flat top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl, not perfectly rounded, placed near the top of the shaft and slightly encrusted on the upper surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.3		0.7				
S. 07526/080	Spindle		Wood	10.3	0.8		13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with top that still preserves the groove to fasten the thread. Wood very worn. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, chipped laterally.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.9		0.8				
S. 07526/081	Spindle		Wood	8.5	0.7		9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Well-shaped cylindrical spindle whorl.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.6		0.7				
S. 07526/082	Spindle		Wood	11.1	0.9		8				Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.4		0.9		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is partially broken along the spiral groove. This groove still preserves some vegetable fibres and threads under a layer of encrustation. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, upper surface encrusted, lower surface clean with traces of manufacture and three small holes (probably caused by insects).	
S. 07526/083	Spindle		Wood	8.6	0.8			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and large, spiral groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft with a thin patina on its surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.3		0.8				
S. 07526/084	Spindle		Wood	9	0.7			9.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, one face encrusted, the other covered by a thin patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.4		0.7				
S. 07526/085	Spindle		Wood	4.6	0.8			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, immediately under the spindle whorl, rounded top with a groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a very thick layer of encrustation, which covers its upper surface and part of the shaft. Traces of fibres under the encrustation and a small fragment of wood attached to it. Lower surface covered with just a thin patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.2		0.8				
S. 07526/086	Spindle		Wood	12.2	0.7			11.7			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	4.6		0.7		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom and rounded top with spiral groove, which is much encrusted. Traces of vegetable fibres under the encrustation. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation on the upper surface, while a thin patina covers the lower surface.	
S. 07526/087	Spindle		Wood	10.2	0.9			18.5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a cylindrical groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl once placed at the top of the shaft (there is still an area of different colour on the wood), now near the break. Surfaces quite clean.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		0.9				
S. 07526/088	Spindle		Wood	13	0.7			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near one of the breaks in the shaft and slightly encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.6		0.7				
S. 07526/089	Spindle		Wood	10	0.7			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near one of the breaks in the shaft, clean but extremely worn. Incised mark on one surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.5		0.7				
S. 07526/090	Spindle		Wood	8.2	0.8			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with rounded top and spiral groove to fasten the thread. The shaft's wood has been extracted from a large log, which is evident from the growth rings. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with clear surfaces.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5		0.8				
S. 07526/091	Spindle		Wood	9.7	0.8			16			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.3		0.8		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and a spiral groove. Wood and top well preserved. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with the upper surface quite worn.	
S. 07526/092	Spindle		Wood	17.8	1			21	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top, partially broken along the groove. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, very encrusted on the upper surface, less on the lower.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.8				
S. 07526/093	Spindle		Wood	21	1			20	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken and cracked at the bottom, with a flat top and a long, almost vertical, groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.7		0.9x1				
S. 07526/094	Spindle		Wood	15	0.9			19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a small groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the (probable) centre of the shaft, with a large lateral break. A thick layer of encrustation covers the upper surface while the lower surface is clean.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.6		0.9				
S. 07526/095	Spindle		Wood	18.4	1.1			19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken and cracked at the bottom, with a flat top and a spiral groove. The spindle has been extracted from a large log, there are 3-4 visible rings. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near top of the shaft, highly worn. Spindle and spindle whorl are made of different woods.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.4		0.9x1				
S. 07526/096	Spindle		Wood	11.3	1.1			17			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		0.9			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a rounded top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft. Mark on the upper surface	
S. 07526/097	Spindle		Wood	9.5	1			15		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, clean and with evident wood pores.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.5		0.9					
S. 07526/098	Spindle		Wood	8.1	1.1			11		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite irregular in shape with whitish encrustation on the surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.7		1					
S. 07526/099	Spindle		Wood	9.8	1			15		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom end, with a rounded top and a spiral groove. Head covered by encrustation and whitish efflorescence. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft. On the upper part of the shaft there is a thread preserved for a few centimetres, which continues in the hole of the spindle whorl. Thread is S-pliced.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.9		0.9					
S. 07526/100	Spindle		Wood	8.9	1			13		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with an incomplete top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, quite clean and with visible wood pores.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	4.8		0.8x0.9					
S. 07526/101	Spindle		Wood	5.6	1.1			16		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-shaped, with one encrusted side and the other one clean.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.4		0.9x1.1					
S. 07526/102	Spindle		Wood	3.8	0.8			13			Turin-ME	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.1		0.8		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with the upper surface very encrusted. On the lower surface a mark is incised. Chipped on the side.	
S. 07526/103	Spindle		Wood	4.2	0.8			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends, but a spiral groove is preserved. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, chipped on the side. The upper surface is encrusted while the lower one is clean, and wood pores are visible.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5		0.8				
S. 07526/104	Spindle		Wood	5.8	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl slightly encrusted on both sides.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.7		0.9				
S. 07526/105	Spindle		Wood	5.7	0.8			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a rounded top and a spiral groove. Domed spindle whorl, with large and thick engraving on the lower surface, along the external diameter. It is placed near the top of the shaft. Upper part of the spindle and spindle whorl show a thick layer of encrustation, from which traces of fibres appear. In the hole there are wedges to fasten the spindle whorl to the shaft.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.1	4.8		0.9				
S. 07526/107	Spindle		Wood	3.7	0.6			14.5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a rounded top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl, roughly cut, placed near the top of the shaft. Encrusted on the upper surface, clean on the other	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5		0.6				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										side with evident traces of manufacture.	
S. 07526/108	Spindle	Wood	21.1	1.1			19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, complete. Flat top with a very long spiral groove to fasten fibres and a pointed end. Shaft shows several spots, probably due to mould. Cylindrical spindle whorl, remarkably worn, placed near top of the shaft, with encrustations on the upper surface and several holes probably caused by insects. Inside the hole, there are wedges and remains of threads. On the side of the spindle whorl a textile fragment is preserved, probably attached by encrustation. It measures 1.72x1.91 cm, it is a tabby weave with a count of 13x10 threads per cm. 2. Thread is S-twist.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.2	5.8		1.3x1.1				
S. 07526/109	Spindle	Wood	25.5	0.9			21	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with a flat top and a spiral groove. Shaft almost complete. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with both surfaces covered by a thin patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.6		0.8x0.9				
S. 07527/05	Spindle	Wood	7	1.1			19	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom near the spindle whorl, with a flat top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with encrusted upper surface and a mark incised on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	5.2		1.1				
S. 07527/08	Spindle	Wood		0.8			15				Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.4		0.8		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral crack filled by a little wooden peg. Other smaller cracks are also present. Mark incised on the lower surface.	
S. 07527/12	Spindle		Wood	4.6	0.8			10.7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, immediately under the spindle whorl, with a rounded top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with encrusted upper surface and several marks incised on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5		0.8				
S. 07527/15	Spindle		Wood	5.1	1			15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, immediately under the spindle whorl, with cracked top and a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, with worn upper surface and a lotus flower incised on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.9		1				
S. 07528/049	Spindle		Wood	3.2	0.7			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-shaped, with one surface more encrusted than the other one.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5		0.7				
S. 07528/052	Spindle		Wood	nn	nn			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-shaped, with one surface encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.1						
S. 07528/054	Spindle		Wood	1.8	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, warped, with a long radial crack to the central hole. Covered by a thin patina.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.3		0.9				
S. 07528/065	Spindle		Wood	2.2	0.9			11			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5		0.9		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered by encrustation.	
S. 07528/067	Spindle		Wood	nn	nn			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl with a fragment of spindle preserved inside the hole. Encrusted surface with whitish efflorescence.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	5.2	1.2		0.8				
S. 07528/069	Spindle		Wood	2.3	0.9			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small part of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered on one surface by encrustation and whitish efflorescence	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.3		0.9				
S. 07528/071	Spindle		Wood	nn	0.9			8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with long radial fracture, covered by a thin patina	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.4		0.9				
S. 07528/072	Spindle		Wood	3.4	0.9			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends with traces of a spiral groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, covered by encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.5		0.9				
S. 07528/080	Spindle		Wood	1.3	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered by encrustation	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.1		0.9x0.7				
S. 07528/084	Spindle		Wood	1.4	0.9			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl encrusted on one side, covered by a thin patina and whitish efflorescence on the other. Incised mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.9		0.9				
S. 07528/085	Spindle		Wood	3.3	0.7			14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, warped, with a radial crack to the hole.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	4.5		0.7				
S. 07528/086	Spindle		Wood	3.7	1.1			16			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.8		1x1.1		Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle with a groove for fastening the fibres still preserved. Cylindrical spindle whorl encrusted on the surface, with traces of vegetable fibres inside the hole.	
S. 07528/087	Spindle		Wood	2.4	1			12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with traces of manufacture	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.4		0.9				
S. 07528/088	Spindle		Wood	2.8	1			9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle with lateral crack and encrusted surface	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.2		1.4				
S. 07528/090	Spindle		Wood		0.8			11.6	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, warped, with traces of encrustation	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.9		0.8				
S. 07528/091	Spindle		Wood	5.2	1.1			17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, warped, with traces of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.6		0.9				
S. 07528/094	Spindle		Wood	4	0.7			5.7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl, warped, with traces of encrustation. Five thin radial lines incised near the edge, perhaps a mark.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	4.7		0.7				
S. 07528/095	Spindle		Wood	3.5	0.9			21.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl slightly encrusted	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.2		0.9				
S. 07528/097	Spindle		Wood	3.1	0.9			13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with a thin layer of encrustation.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	4.8		0.9				
S. 07528/098	Spindle		Wood	1	0.6			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with a radial crack.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.9		0.6				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07528/100	Spindle		Wood	3.4	0.7			13.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered by a thick layer of encrustation on one side while the other is clean.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.2		0.7				
S. 07528/101	Spindle		Wood	2.5	0.9			14.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken immediately under the spindle whorl. Top preserved with groove to fasten fibres. Cylindrical spindle whorl with encrustation and two radial cracks.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.5		0.9				
S. 07528/102	Spindle		Wood	3.8	0.7			14.6	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Small fragment of wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl with a thin layer of patina, made of different wood from that of the shaft.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5		0.7				
S. 09978/1	Spindle		Wood	20.3	1			20	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle, well-preserved, with only the bottom missing. Flat top with a coarse groove with which to fasten fibres.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.4		1			Cylindrical spindle whorl, thicker than most others. It shows a crack on the side with a peg in it, probably an ancient restoration. Wooden wedges are quite visible, which fasten the whorl to the shaft. Under one wedge a thread is caught, it is S-plyed.	
S. 09978/2	Spindle		Wood	12.5	0.9			11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at both ends. Cylindrical spindle whorl covered by a whitish substance on one surface and on the side.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.9				
S. 09978/4	Spindle		Wood	15.8	0.8			14			Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.1	4.9		0.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle badly preserved. Tapering towards one end with no traces of the groove. Cylindrical spindle whorl with some cracks and holes. Surface covered by encrustation and a white-yellowish substance. On one side an incised mark is present. Whorl complete but not firmly fastened on the shaft.	
S. 09978/5	Spindle		Wood	27	1			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle well preserved. Flat top with a spiral groove to fasten the thread. It is covered by a thick layer of encrustation which leaves the groove clean. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near top of the shaft and covered by a thick layer of encrustation and whitish efflorescence.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.4		1				
S. 09978/6	Spindle		Wood	17.4	0.9			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, with flat top and a spiral groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft and deep lateral break. Upper surface encrusted, lower surface quite clean. Hole of the whorl irregular and it is fastened to the shaft with wooden wedges and vegetable fibres.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.5		0.9				
S. 09978/7	Spindle		Wood	35.8	1.2			Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, complete and well-preserved. Flat top with a spiral groove to fasten the thread, while the other end tapers to a point. Traces of brown encrustation are preserved on the top, on the shaft and inside the groove. A cylindrical spindle whorl is placed near the top of the	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4.6		1.2				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										shaft, is chipped and with a lateral hole.	
S. 09978/8	Spindle		Wood	23.8	0.8			22	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle broken at the bottom. Pointed top with a spiral groove to fasten the thread. Both spindle and spindle whorl are covered by a thick layer of encrustation. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft with a small hole on the lower surface.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		0.8				
S. 09978/9	Spindle		Wood	19.9	1			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle, badly preserved and broken at the bottom. Flat top with a spiral groove to fasten the thread. Cylindrical spindle whorl placed near the top of the shaft, the whorl has a large lateral break and a hole.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.4		1				
S. 09978 /1 (bis)	Spindle		Wood	30.5	1.1			34	Donadoni Roveri 1988, 109. Donadoni Roveri, 2001, 18. Donadoni Roveri, 1987, 188, tav. 260. Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Wooden spindle, badly preserved and broken at the bottom. Flat top with a spiral groove to fasten the thread. Two spindle whorls are attached to the shaft, but it is not possible to determine if one was added at a later time, but it is highly probable.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	4.8		0.8	Spindle whorl 1: cylindrical, upper surface encrusted, side and lower surface only partially encrusted. Placed near the top of the shaft.			
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	6		1.05	Spindle whorl 2: cylindrical, warped hole but without wedges. Upper surface clean, lower surface			

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										and side encrusted (normally the contrary is seen).	
S. 09978/4 bis	Spindle	Wood	25.7	1			18	Donadoni Roveri 1988, 109. Donadoni Roveri, 2001, 18. Donadoni Roveri, 1987, 188, tav. 260. Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at one end while two spindle whorls are attached at the other end, which tapers to a point. Two spindle whorls are preserved but probably did not originally belong to this spindle. Shaft quite encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.7		0.9x0.8		Spindle whorl 1: cylindrical with a warp hole without wedges to adapt it to the shaft. Several breaks are present; one filled with a whitish substance.		
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0.9	3.8x4		0.9x1		Spindle whorl 2: cylindrical but very warped, hole is not in the centre, and it is deformed, probably by previous wedges, here not present. Encrustation not present but surface covered by areas of whitish efflorescence.		
S. 09978 /3 bis	Spindle	Wood	32.4	1.1			37	Donadoni Roveri 1988, 109. Donadoni Roveri, 2001, 18. Donadoni		Wooden spindle slightly chipped at the top along the groove used to fasten the thread and also at the bottom, which is rounded and not pointed. Shaft is encrusted with two breaks, perhaps due to a restoration.	Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.4		0.9	Roveri, 1987, 188, tav. 260. Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		It shows two spindle whorls on the shaft, one in the original position, near the groove, the other one probably added at a later time. Spindle whorl 1: cylindrical, fastened to the shaft with wooden wedges. A light patina covers all sides and whitish efflorescence are present on the upper surface.	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2	5.1		1.1			Spindle whorl 2: cylindrical, hole irregular. It shows encrustation on all sides and a lateral break. Lower surface is much more worn than the upper.	
S. 09978/5 bis	Spindle		Wood	37.2	1.1		31	Donadoni Roveri 1988, 109. Donadoni Roveri, 2001, 18. Donadoni Roveri, 1987, 188, tav. 260. Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle, complete. Flat top with a spiral groove to fasten fibres and tapered towards the bottom. Both spindle whorls are placed near top of the shaft and cover the groove. Shaft slightly encrusted.	Turin-ME
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.7		0.8			Spindle whorl 1: cylindrical with irregular hole. Very encrusted on all sides, especially the lower one (in contrast to the other objects). Lateral break with wooden peg.	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.7		1			Spindle whorl 2: cylindrical, complete, with a thin patina on all sides.	
S. 09978/2	Spindle		Wood	34	0.9		30	Donadoni Roveri 1988, 109. Donadoni Roveri, 1987, 188,		Wooden spindle broken and chipped at the bottom. Rounded top with a spiral groove, very well shaped. Spindle whorls do not seem to belong to this shaft but to be added at a later time.	Turin-ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.5		1.3		tav. 260. Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Spindle whorl 1: cylindrical, with one side of the hole large and irregular, while the other side is regular. All sides slightly encrusted with a lateral break.	
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.3		1.1			Spindle whorl 2: cylindrical, with a chipped side. Small holes on all surfaces, perhaps caused by insects, and a lateral break. Lower surface with an incised cross.	
S. 07526/024	Spindle		Wood	8.4	1		3.1	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at the bottom, while top is flat and has a deep spiral groove.	Turin-ME
S. 07526/106	Spindle		Wood	10.2	0.9		2.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Wooden spindle broken at both ends.	Turin-ME
C5110_tissage_4.1	Spindle shaft		Wood	20,5	1,05		0,72	10	Sampling with a (shaft) and b (whorl)	Wooden shaft, broken at the bottom part, but should have been very long. Not perfectly straight. Top with a quite long, spiral notch.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,18	4,04		0.85 max			Upper face with some thick incrustations, lower and side part covered by a patina. Transversal cut.	
C5110_tissage_4.2	Spindle shaft		Wood	10,3	0,89		0,74	15,3	Sampling with a (shaft) and b (whorl)	Wooden shaft, broken at both extremities. Straight shaft, almost no changing in diameter. In the upper part, the brake follows the spiral notch not anymore visible.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,83	5,13		0,84			Complete spindle whorl, well crafted. Wood worn on the sides, on the lower part and a large hole on the top. Covered by a thin patina on all sides, a whitish substance is present mostly on the lower part and on the sides, but in a smaller part also on top. Transversal cut.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
C5110_tissage_4.3	Spindle shaft	Wood	12,35	0,69		0,62	14			Shaft broken at the bottom part, most of it missing. Thin and straight shaft. Top with a very long spiral notch.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,53	5,2		0,68			Well preserved spindle whorl, one large lateral fracture, three more small lateral fractures. Upper surface completely covered by a thick layer of incrustation, lower and lateral side covered by a very thin patina. Traces of manufacture on the side? Transversal cut.	
C5110_tissage_4.4	Spindle shaft	Wood	10,8	0,82		0,77	6			Shaft broken at the bottom part, most of it missing. Quite thin and straight shaft, although a little bit ovoidal. Top with a very long spiral notch. Spindle whorl not fixed to the shaft.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,1	3,93		0,82			Small spindle whorl, quite ruined. It misses small parts of the sides and have some holes on the surface. Upper surface and sites covered by a white substance, that partially extends also on the bottom, together with a thin brownish patina. Incised mark on the lower side. Transversal cut.	
C5110_tissage_4.5	Spindle shaft	Wood	7,73	0,91		0,81	9			Shaft broken few cm under the spindle whorl. Long spiral notch at the top. Whitish substance where it is broken at the bottom.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,6	4,97		0,89			Complete spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Wooded worn on the lower part and a with a small hole on the top. Covered by a thin patina on the top, and by a thick layer of incrustation on the bottom. Transversal cut.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
C5110_tissage_4.6	Spindle shaft		Wood	8,16	0,81		0,76	8		Shaft broken few cm under the spindle whorl. Long spiral notch at the top. Covered by a thin layer of patina.	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,7	5,2		0,8			Completed spindle whorl but wood is much worn on all sides, and some parts of the edge are missing. All surfaces are covered by a patina. Transversal cut.	
C5110_tissage_4.7	Spindle shaft		Wood	13,6	0,96			5		Broken shaft of a spindle, only the upper part is preserved. Cylindrical shaft with a very little variation in diameter through all the length. Long, spiral notch. One side is covered by a layer of incrustation	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.8	Spindle shaft		Wood	18,8	0,92			5		Broken shaft of a spindle, only the upper part is preserved. Broken in two pieces. Cylindrical shaft with a very little variation in diameter through all the length. Long, spiral notch, crudely carved and partially doubling. Thin layer of patina through all the length.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.9	Spindle shaft		Wood	19,5	0,99			5		Broken shaft, probably 3/3 of length preserved. Large part of the shaft is ruined. Very long spiral notch, well crafted. Covered by a whitish efflorescence in the middle.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.10	Spindle shaft		Wood	19,3	0,95			6		Broken shaft, probably 3/3 of length preserved. Upper part not preserved; lower part almost complete but the point is bent. Small part of the shaft is ruined. Covered by a thin patina.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.11	Spindle shaft		Wood	11,2	0,89			3		Broken shaft of a spindle, only the upper part is preserved. Fractured on the length. Long, spiral notch,	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										thin layer of patina through all the length.	
C5110_tissage_4.17	Spindle shaft	Wood	1,56	0,94			8			Small fragment of shaft inside the hole of the spindle whorl	IFAO
	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical Wood	1,56	4.7x5						Complete spindle whorl, well crafted. Wooded worn on the sides, on the lower part and a large hole on the other. Covered by a thin patina on all sides, a whitish substance is present mostly on the side. Tangential cut.	
ÄM 23904	Spindle shaft	wood	36	1,1			28	Gurna & DeM 1913, FJ 386		Wooden spindle, complete, just a small portion of the point is missing. The upper part of the shaft has a groove in z direction. A thread is knotted on the top in a similar way of those of Turin, with a stick in the middle of the knot. Traces of manufacture partially visible (not perfectly smoothed) but the shaft is covered by a brownish patina. The thread is not spun, and it is partially covered by the patina	ÄM
		whorl	wood	1,6	5,7		1,1			Wooden whorl, well carved. Completely covered by a deep incrustation on the top and by a patina on the bottom. Part of the incrustation has been covered by a whitish substance. Two wedges are visible in the lower hole.	

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
E 16543	Spindle	wood	24,5	0,9			18		A note saying "273."	Spindle with whorl, not complete. One end is preserved; it is flattish and has a spiral notch for the insertion of the thread. On the shaft there is a carving, like a capital I, but it does not seem a property mark. Transversal cut of the wood, probably coniferous. Spindle whorl quite dirt, with a long radial break. On the lower surface and on the side some traces of a yellowish layer of "encrustation". The upper surface is clean, but wood is poorly visible. The hole shows some irregularities, and the shaft has a hollow where it is inserted in the hole, partly filled with a yellowish substance.	Louvre
	Spindle whorl	cylindrical	wood	1,3	5		0,9				
E 16542	Spindle	wood	27,3	0,7			19		A note saying "272."	Spindle with whorl, almost complete. One end of the spindle is preserved. It is relatively flat and features a spiral notch for thread insertion. The notch appears to have been made twice, with the first attempt abandoned. The spindle is made from a transverse cut of wood, likely from a conifer, and is not perfectly round. There is some dirt near the tip, which is more rounded—possibly due to use. The spindle whorl is quite worn, showing a long radial crack and a knot. There are traces of a whitish substance on one side. The upper surface is clean, but the wood grain is barely visible. The lower surface is more clearly defined and reveals that the whorl	Louvre
	Spindle whorl	cylindrical	wood	2	4,9		0,7				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										was cut from a small branch. The central hole is irregular. The spindle is not well balanced and is significantly weighted toward the whorl. A piece of thread remains at the top of the hole.	
E 16541	Spindle	wood	34,4	0,9			22		A note saying "271."	Spindle with whorl, complete. The spindle is complete. One end is relatively flat and features a spiral notch for thread insertion: the opposite end tapers to a rounded point. The wood appears to be from a transverse cut, likely from a coniferous species, and is not perfectly round. There is some dirt near the pointed end, which may be due to use. The spindle whorl is quite worn and has a long radial crack as well as a knot in the wood. The upper surface is clean, though the wood grain is barely visible. The lower surface is more clearly defined, indicating that the whorl was cut from a small branch. The central hole is irregular, and there are traces of thread inside the lower opening.	Louvre
	Spindle whorl	cylindrical	wood	1,8	5,1		0,8				

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
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SPINDLE WHORLS

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0216	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,1	2,1	0,7	105		Blue writing 38?	Dome spindle whorl in stone, with a few parts missing. Decorated with engraved vertical lines and a mark on the dome (D37 Gardiner).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0217	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,7	2,1	1,18	55		Black writing 84	Dome spindle whorl in stone, half missing. Upper part heavily damaged. On the bottom a mark with a hourglass and a triangle (similar to one of Turin).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0218	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,7	2,1	1,1	50		Black writing 103	Dome spindle whorl in stone, partially broken on the dome and on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0219	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,8	2,7	1,1	114		Blue writing 89	Dome spindle whorl in stone, Surface completely ruined, chipped o the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0220	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,5	2,4	0,9	83			Dome spindle whorl in white limestone. Preserved for 3/3. Area around the hole is highly ruined.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0221	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,1	2,3	1	74			Dome spindle whorl in stone. Chipped at the edge and on the bottom. Abdo says it is limestone blackened by fire.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0222	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,1	3,6	0,98	110			Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, complete but a little bit chipped at the edge	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0223	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7	3,3	0,98	75		Blue writing 77	Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, half preserved. Engraved hieroglyph writing of neb tawi. According to Ben Haring it is a very common identity mark in the village from 18th dynasty to Ramesside period.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0224	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,3	3,7	1	50			Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, ¾ preserved. Hole is hourglass and wide traces of drilling are visible on both top and bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0225	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,2	3,5	0,9	61			Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, partially preserved. The hole is very much hourglass, and the bottom is hollow.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0226	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,5	3	1,2	80		Blue writing 81	Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, half preserved. One incised radial line is the only decoration on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0227	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,3	2,7	1	120			Dome spindle whorl in white limestone, chipped on one side and on the bottom. Hole is more chipped on the top than on the bottom, but considering the storage system, this is normal. It is a very soft limestone, very easy to incise.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0228	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,9	2,7	0,9	60		Blue writing 77	Dome spindle whorl in limestone, half preserved and chipped on one side and on the bottom. Blackened on the surface. Two marks are visible on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0229	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,1	2,9	0,95	107			Dome spindle whorl in limestone, almost all preserved and chipped on one side and on the bottom. Blackened on the surface. The hole is conical (bottom 1,7).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0230	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,63	2,5	1,1	52		Blue writing 80?	Dome spindle whorl in limestone, half preserved and chipped on the edge. Blackened on the surface. One mark is visible on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0231	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,2	2,1		51		Black writing 83	Dome spindle whorl in limestone, almost half preserved. Slightly blackened on the surface. Decorated with two radial incisions on the dome. Criss cross pattern visible on the bottom and on the dome that might be related to production marks.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0232	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,9	1,8		21			Dome spindle whorl in limestone (more greyish), almost half preserved. Chipped on the dome, edge and bottom. Heavily incised inside the hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0233	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,6	2,6	1,1	64		Black writing KS. Blue writing 74	Dome spindle whorl in limestone, more than half preserved. Chipped on the edge and on the bottom. Incised decoration on both dome and bottom. The pattern resembles that of a lotus flower.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0234	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,5	2,7		50		Blue writing 83	Dome spindle whorl in limestone, half preserved. Chipped on the edge and bottom. Criss cross pattern (of manufacture?) is visible on the bottom. Heavily engraved mark present on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0235	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,4	2,1	0,9	52			Dome spindle whorl in limestone, more than half preserved. Chipped on the bottom. Blackened on the surface. Hole worn on the top, perfect on the bottom. Parallel round incisions inside the hole that might suggest the use of a drill. Criss cross pattern visible on the bottom and on the dome that might be related to production traces.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0236	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,3	2,7	0,8	75	y		Dome spindle whorl, almost all preserved but the surface is completely worn out and there are several big, chipped areas. The hole appears hourglass. Some more heavy incised straight lines might be what is left of the original marks.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0237	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,7	1,7	0,99	39	y	Black writing 106	Dome spindle whorl, almost all preserved but heavily chipped on the bottom. Upper hole is slightly worn, lower is more well preserved. Criss cross lines on the bottom, possibly production traces.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0238	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,1+x	3,4+x	1	53		Black writing 105	Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Criss cross pattern slightly visible on the dome (production traces?).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0239	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,2	2,3	0,9	46		Blue writing 25?	Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. The lower part is gone. The dome with a floral pattern and an incised line parallel to the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0240	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,5	2,7	1,03	53			Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Chipped on the edge. Two radial lines incised on the dome. Possibly a mark in the shape of a A, but poorly preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0241	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5+x	2,8	0,9	56			Dome spindle whorl, 3/4 preserved. External surface largely gone.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0242	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,2	2,3	0,9	40			Dome spindle whorl almost half preserved. Grey stone. Bottom is slightly chipped. Criss cross lines visible on both top and bottom, possibly from manufacture. No lines visible on the hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0243	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,7+x	2+x	1	63			Dome spindle whorl, heavily ruined on edges and on the bottom. Upper hole heavily worn.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0244	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,9	2,5	1	94		Pencil (black) 104	Dome spindle whorl partially preserved. Bottom is almost completely gone.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0245	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,6	2,5	1	98	y		Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Chipped on the bottom. Very worn around the upper hole and also on the bottom one. Very dirty on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0246	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,5	2,4	0,9	44			Dome spindle whorl, half preserved. Bottom almost gone. Surface blackened. Hole is pretty clean on both sides, but in the middle some crudely made lines are visible.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0247	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,2	2,4	1,3	49		Black writing 101	Dome spindle whorl, 3/4 preserved. On the dome two incised radial lines are visible. Hole measure is from the bottom, as the top is not preserved. Some deep incised lines on the dome might belong to a secondary use.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0248	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,7	1,8	1,1	41	y		Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Hourglass hole, hollow on the bottom. Surface completely worn.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0249	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,3	2,3	0,9	36		Black writing 106? 704?	Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Conical hole, 1,1 on the bottom. Limestone, blackish on the surface. Upper hole completely worn out, while lower one more clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0250	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,7	2,3	1,1	95			Dome spindle whorl, two big areas missing and chipped on the bottom. Two identity marks on the dome. Conical hole, bottom 1,3	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0251	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7	2,3	0,9	60			Dome spindle whorl, half is preserved. Chipped on the bottom. Conical hole 0,9 top and 1,1 bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0252	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,9	2,8	0,7	60		Black writing 76	Dome spindle whorl, half is preserved. Four deep stripes on the outer side. Chipped on the	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										bottom Conical hole 0,7 top and 0,9 bottom.	
DeM_2024_M23_0253	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,2	3,4	0,9	67		Dome spindle whorl less than half is preserved. One deep stripe on the outer side. One black dot on top of the dome. Conical hole has horizontal marks.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0254	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,9	2,7	1	61		Dome spindle whorl, half is preserved. The surface is very smooth. The conical hole is very damaged. The stone is very grey.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0255	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,7	2,4	1,1	65		Dome spindle whorl, more than 3/4 is preserved. The bottom is very chipped. The conical hole is 1,1 at the top and 1,3 at the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0256	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,5	2,1	1,1	68		Dome spindle whorl, more than 3/4 is preserved. The bottom is very chipped. Big piece is missing on the side of the dome.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0257	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,1	1,2	0,7	17		Dome spindle whorl, more than 3/4 is preserved. Very small. The bottom is very chipped and one larger piece is missing. Surface has many lines/scratches(?).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0258	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,8	2,6	1,1	52		Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Limestone with a darkened surface. There is a radial, incised line on the dome. Surface has a sort of patina, also present on one chipping on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0259	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,8+x	2,6	0,8	45		Blue writing 87 Dome spindle whorl, less than half preserve. Hole is very irregular, but still usable as a spindle whorl. Incised lotus flower on the dome.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0260	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5+x	2,4	33			Dome spindle whorl, 1/4 preserved. Radial incised line on the dome. Possible mark on the base but broken.	On site - M23	
DeM_2024_M23_0261	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		3,9	1,7	0,7	23	y	Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Chipped on the top. Straight hole, cylindrical shape. Upper hole very worn, lower hole more intact.	On site - M23	
DeM_2024_M23_0262	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,1	1,6	0,9	25	y	Dome spindle whorl almost entirely preserved. Chipped on the dome and on one edge. Two deep incisions at opposite side of the edge. Hole slightly off centre and shape not specular. Conical hole, bottom 1.1.	On site - M23	
DeM_2024_M23_0263	Spindle whorl	Dome	Alabaster		4,4	1,2	1	16		Dome spindle whorl, half preserved. Extremely well polished. Two short radial incision on the edge.	On site - M23	
DeM_2024_M23_0264	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		7,1	2,8+x	1,1	146		Dome spindle whorl, partially preserved as the dome is almost completely gone. Several parts are also missing from the bottom and the edge. One deep radial incision is on one side.	On site - M23	
DeM_2024_M23_0265	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,4	2,4	1	37		Blue writing 98 or 86	Dome spindle whorl, 1/3 preserved. Dome preserves three radial incisions from hole to edge; bottom is not preserved. hourglass hole? It seems to become smaller inside.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0266	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,5	3,4	0,7	73		Black writing 66 or 99	Dome spindle whorl? Hole off centre, it was part of a larger object. Upper hole much worn. Bottom hole smaller than top, 0,6 cm.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0267	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,6+x	1,1		12			Dome spindle whorl might be something else. Less than half preserved. Several circular signs on both sides of the hole and around it. Hole pretty large	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0268	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6	3,2	0,8	81		Blue writing 91 or 16	Dome spindle whorl, 3/4 preserved. Very tall dome, a little bit rough on the surface, not smooth. Decorated on the base with a line along the edge and several radial incisions.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0269	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,7	2,4		48			Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Very well smoothed on the dome. A fragment of a textile is glued on the inside.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0270	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,4+x	2,4		49			Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Well smoothed surface, but chipped on many parts of the edge, bottom and near the upper hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0271	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,4	1,7	0,8	49	y		Dome spindle whorl almost completely preserved. Surface completely covered with concretions. Conical hole, 0,9 at the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0272	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,7	1,3	0,8	29	y		Dome spindle whorl almost completely preserved. Two incisions on the edge not very well oriented with the hole. Cylindrical hole, on the top a large part of the surface is no longer preserved but in some areas the hole is neatly cut. On the bottom instead there is a large area of possible wear around the hole.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0273	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,6	2,3		30		Black writing 85	Dome spindle whorl 1/4 preserved. Smoothened surface with crisscross pattern visible. Deep incisions on the bottom, possibly radial incisions or a mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0274	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		3,8	1,5	1	22		Blue writing, not understandable	Dome spindle whorl, almost complete. Chipped on the edge and on the bottom. The hole seems to have a secondary opening on the bottom that does not seem to be produced by a string. Top opening heavily ruined on the entire circumference.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0275	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,8+x	1,7		35		Blue writing 108 (or 801)	Dome spindle whorl almost half preserved. Slightly chipped on the bottom and on the edge. Not perfectly rounded but surface smoothened.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0276	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6+x	1,9		33			Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Slightly chipped on the bottom and on the edge. Not perfectly rounded but surface smoothened. Criss cross pattern visible especially on the bottom and parallel lines on the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0277	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,7	2	1	36			Dome spindle whorl, half preserved. Chipped on the bottom. Pretty well done but very dirty.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0278	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,4+x	3,6		31			Dome spindle whorl, only a fragment preserved. Tall dome and one deep radial incision preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0279	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		4,1	1,8	1,2	18			Dome spindle whorl, half preserved. Hole larger at the top, bottom measures 1. Surface not smoothened and upper hole worn out, lower hole clearly cut. Inside	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										the hole deep incision of the manufacturing, random directions.	
DeM_2024_M23_0280	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		3,5+x	2,2+x	1	25		Dome spindle whorl, just a fragment preserved. Hole is preserved. One deep radial incision on the top.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0281	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		3,6+x			13		Dome spindle whorl (?), just a fragment.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0282	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		2,3	0,4	0,3	0,7		Dome spindle whorl, extremely small. Hole is perfectly clean, surface is smoothed. Many scratching on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0283	Spindle whorl	Dome	Stone		6,4	0,8	0,5	25	Blue writing 88	Stone spindle whorl more than half preserved. Two marks incised on both surfaces.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0284	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		5,7+x	4,5		31		Almost a 1/4 preserved. Dome spindle whorl, made of limestone. Criss cross lines visible on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0285	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		6,5+x	2,4		26		Dome spindle whorl less than half preserved. Upper hole very clean. Surface was smoothed with rounded edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0286	Spindle whorl	Lenticular	Ceramic		7,6	2,2	0,8	88		Ceramic spindle whorl, lenticular. Made on purpose, not reworked sherd. Both sides of the hole are slightly enlarged and a little bit worn. Chipped on the edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0287	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic		5,9	1,3	1,3	34		Perforated sherd, complete but chipped. Hourglass hole. Not perfectly rounded but with smoothed edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0288	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Ceramic		3,2	1	6,7	12		Rounded pottery spindle whorl? Made on purpose. Perforated from one side to the others.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0289	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	5,1x4,6	1,1	0,56	26		Blue writing 109	Perforated sherd, complete. Hourglass hole. Not perfectly rounded (oval) but with smoothed edges. One notch on the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0290	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	5,5	1,3	1,56	39			Perforated sherd, almost complete, chipped on the edge. Made from a base. Slightly hourglass hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0291	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	3,2	0,82	0,47	8			Small perforated sherd, slightly oval. Straight hole. Smoothened edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0292	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	3,5x3,1	0,9	0,5	9			Small perforated sherd, slightly oval. Hourglass hole. Smoothened edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0293	Spindle whorl?	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	4,3x4	1,3	0,5	24,2			Small perforated sherd with one hourglass hole and a second not finished.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0294	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	3,3	0,6	0,37	8,4			Small perforated sherd, slightly oval. Hourglass hole. Smoothened edges.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0295	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	5,1	1	0,4	24			Perforated sherd, edges not smoothed. Hourglass hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0296	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic	3	1,1	0,5	10			Perforated sherd, edges not smoothed. Hourglass hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0297	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Stone	6	1,1	0,8	43			Discoid spindle whorl made of stone. Surface completely rough, possibly sandstone. Not perfectly rounded. Hole slightly hourglass. Complete.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0298	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone	4,2x3,9	1	0,5	19,2			Discoid spindle whorl made of limestone. Not perfectly rounded. Hole straight. Complete.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0299	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		4,5x4,7	0,9	0,9	25,7			Discoid spindle whorl made of limestone. Not perfectly rounded. Hole straight. Complete.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0300	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		3,9	0,9	0,5	13,1			Discoid spindle whorl made of limestone. Perfectly rounded and smoothed. Might also be a stopper. Hole straight. Almost complete.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0301	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		3,6	0,9		16,3		Black writing 73	Discoid spindle whorl made of limestone. Not finished hole and edges rounded but not smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0302	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		4,9	1		29		Black writing 93	Discoid spindle whorl made of limestone. Not finished hole and edges rounded but not smoothed.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0303	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		2,4x2	1	0,4	5,6			Small object made of stone, roughly rounded with a through hole. It has a string still attached on it.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0304	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Limestone		3	0,9	0,7	9,3			Small object made of stone, roughly rounded with a through hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0305	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Sandstone		2,9	0,6	0,43	6,4			Small object made of stone, roughly rounded with a through hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0315	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6,1	1,3	0,8	17			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Very dirty on both sides. A strip of textile with a seam is knotted on it. It is very likely a fragment of a loincloth.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0398	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,7	1,3	0,8	9,1			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, 2/3 preserved. Very dirty on both sides. Possibly some marks on the surface, not very visible.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0399	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,5	0,6	10,2			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Very dirty on one side, the hole is stuck.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0400	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,8	1,8	0,88	19,3			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Very dirty on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0401	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1	0,95	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Very dirty on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0402	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,7	0,7	18,8			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, Complete. Rings of the branch very well visible. Hole slightly squared.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0403	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,4	0,8	12,8			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, Complete. Rings of the branch very well visible. Hole slightly squared.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0404	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,7		14,3			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Very dirty on one side, patina on the other. No hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0405	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		0,56	1,9	0,8	12,5			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, incomplete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. Possibly a second hole was started.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0406	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,8	0,9	14,1			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0407	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	2	0,9	14,3			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. Deep incision on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0408	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	11,7			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Heavily	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										encrusted on one side, patina on the other.	
DeM_2024_M23_0409	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,8	1,5	0,8	14,7		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, incomplete. Traces of encrustation on one side, clean on the other. Hole has been enlarged, possibly by a wedge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0410	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,3	0,9	10,5		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. Deep incisions on one side, a sort of rough decoration.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0411	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,3	1,2	0,7	8,6	Black ink[3.178] FM. On the other side blue ink 18	Spindle whorl? made of wood. A cut on one side. Surface almost clean, irregular, with some traces of production.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0412	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,4		11,2		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Chipped on one edge. Heavily encrustations on both side, hole not visible.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0413	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,5	7,4	11	Blue writing, not understandable	Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Patina on one side and on the edge. Mark on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0414	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,4	0,8	9,2		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. Cracked and hole near the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0415	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,5		11,1		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides. Hole not yet made. Unfinished.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0416	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		2,3	0,5	0,28	1,4		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_0417	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,4	0,8	5,1		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, half preserved. Traces of encrustation on both sides. Two holes, one in the middle.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0418	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,5	4,6	4		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, 2/3 preserved. Traces of encrustation on both sides. Two deeply incised parallel lines. Hole warped.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0419	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7+x	1,6		3,9		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, 1/3 preserved. Almost clean on both sides. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0420	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,3	0,7	4		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, half preserved. Patina on one side. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0421	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,2	0,9	8,3		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Patina on both sides. Hole warped.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0422	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,7	1,4	0,9	4,3		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides. Two holes, one in the middle.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0423	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,2	1,3	0,5	5,1		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0424	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,8	1,4	1,1	14,5	Black writing 83	Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0425	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4	1,2	0,6	4,3		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on both sides. Mark in shape of a T.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0426	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,8	0,87	12,6		Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of encrustation on one side, patina on the other. Mark in shape of a A, difficult to see.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0427	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,6	0,7	8,4			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of patina on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0428	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,3	0,9	10			Spindle whorl made of wood, not well rounded, complete. Heavy encrustation on both sides. Two holes, one in the middle.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0429	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,5		8			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of patina on one side. Tree rings well visible, cut from a larger branch.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0430	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,3		3,4		Blue ink 47	Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, incomplete. Almost half preserved. Traces of encrustation on one side. Mark on the surface in the shape of two triangles.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0431	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,7	1,4	0,7	5		Black ink difficult to read	Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, incomplete. Almost half preserved. Traces of encrustation on one side. Mark on the base.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0432	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,2	0,98	0,9	3			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, incomplete. Almost half preserved. Traces of encrustation on one side. Mark on the base in the shape of ka.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0433	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,4		4,7			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, half preserved. Traces of patina on one side. Mark with monogram of Kha.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0434	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4+x	1,3		2,5			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, 1/4 preserved. Traces of patina on one side. Mark with a ka and part of another.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0435	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,6	0,8	11,8		Pencil 121	Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, almost complete. Traces of patina on both sides.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0436	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,1	0,8	5			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, more than half preserved. Traces of patina on both sides. Mark in the shape of a star.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0437	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,5	0,8	15,1			Spindle whorl made of wood, well rounded, complete. Traces of patina on both sides. Mark in the shape of three triangles	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0438	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,1	0,7	4,1			Spindle whorl made of wood, more than half preserved. Traces of patina on both sides. Several marks incised on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0439	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,4	0,7	12,6		Blue ink 4	Spindle whorl made of wood, almost complete. Traces of patina on both sides. One mark incised on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0440	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4+x	1,2		46		Blue ink 59	Spindle whorl made of wood, 1/3 preserved.. Traces of patina on both sides. One mark incised on the surface, in the shape of a star.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0441	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,6	0,6	8,4			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on one side, the other side is almost clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0442	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1	0,7	10		Blue ink not understandable	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Almost clean on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0443	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,5	0,8	11,9			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on one side, the other side is almost clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0444	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,6		9			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Patina on one side, the other side is almost clean. Hole not made. Cut from the middle of a branch.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0445	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,6	0,6	9,2			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on both sides. Two holes, the central one has still part of the shaft inside.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0446	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,6	1,8	0,7	10,5			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on both sides. The hole has still part of the shaft inside.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0447	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,7	1,7	0,8	9,8		Pencil 78	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top. The hole has still part of the shaft inside.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0448	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,3	1,9	0,8	15,7			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top. The hole has still part of the shaft inside. It is partially burned.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0449	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,5	2	0,5	11,4			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top. Cut transversally. Roughly made or ruined.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0450	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,2	0,7	8,8			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top. Small piece of shaft still in the hole. Mark in the shape of a hourglass on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0451	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,4	0,8	8,9			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on both sides. Small piece of shaft still in the hole and a wedge in the shape of a second shaft. Possible marks on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0452	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,8	0,8	8,1			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on both sides. Second hole near the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0453	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,4	0,7	8,4			Spindle whorl(?) made of wood, cut transversally. Almost squared. White substance on one side.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0454	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,2	0,8		3,6			Spindle whorl(?) made of wood, cracked on one side. Hole not made.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0455	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	2,5	1,4	18,1			Spindle whorl(?) made of wood, complete. Very large hole. Painted in white and red on top and side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0456	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	6,6			Spindle whorl made of wood, 1/3 preserved. Encrusted on one side, patina on the other side. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0457	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,9	1,7		4		Blue ink 50	Spindle whorl made of wood, 1/3 preserved. Encrusted on both sides. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0458	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4+x	1,5		3,9			Spindle whorl made of wood, 1/3 preserved. Patina on both sides. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0459	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,6	1,4		4,4			Spindle whorl (?) made of wood, complete. Clean on both sides. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0460	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,2	0,9	4,7			Spindle whorl made of wood; half preserved. Encrusted on one side. Second hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0461	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,4	0,7	1		Hole 0,7x1	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on both sides. Reused with a hole in the form of a shaft.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0485	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,8	0,7	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Fragment of the shaft inside the hole. Traces of patina on the surface. Cut from a quite large branch.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0487	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,6	0,6	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Fragment of the shaft inside the hole. Traces of encrustation on the surface.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_0488	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,4	0,8	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Fragment of the shaft inside the hole. Traces of encrustation on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0497	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6	2	0,8	11		Black ink 6011	Spindle whorl made of wood, almost complete. Surface very ruined but painted in white with a red and black decoration.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0498	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	15		Blue ink A2?	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Surface covered by encrustation on all sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_0499	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,4	0,9	6+x			Spindle whorl made of wood; half preserved. Surface quite ruined, marks incise, one clear the others not understandable.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1108	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,9		15			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete but no hole. Clean, carved from a larger branch.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1109	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,5	0,8	11			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Covered by a patina on all sides. Incised mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1110	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,5	0,76	9			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Covered by a patina on all sides. Incised mark and painted in red on the other side (4 perpendicular lines visible).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1111	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation on the top, patina on the bottom. Hole warped.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1112	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,4	0,8	15		Black ink GMN 20.1.51	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Clean on all sides. Marks on one side	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_1113	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	15			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation on the top, patina on the bottom. Possibly a mark on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1114	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,7	0,8	11		Black ink G.M. [N. 14 ¹⁸]???	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Covered by a thin layer of encrustation on the top, patina on the bottom. Mark of a star on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1115	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,14	0,9	8		Black ink not understandable	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Almost clean. Mark on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1116	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,1	0,6	6		Blue ink 38?	Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top, clean on the bottom. Mark of a star on the clean side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1117	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,6	0,8	12			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Encrusted on the top, patina on the bottom.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1118	Spindle whorl		Wood		5	1,7	0,9	10			Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Burnt on one side. Possibly originally covered by a yellow paint and some red. Mark on one side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1119	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		6,7	2,9	0,7	28			Spindle whorl made of wood; half preserved. Incised decoration on all sides. Dots around the hole, concentric circles around the edge and rows of large circles on the base parallel to the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1120	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,6	1,6	nn	5			Spindle whorl made of wood; half preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1121	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,4		14			Spindle whorl made of wood, almost complete, hole not carved. Covered by a thin layer of patina	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										on one side, very ruined on the other. Cut from a small branch.	
DeM_2024_M23_1122	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,6+x	1,2	0,8	3		Small fragment of a wooden spindle whorl. Incised mark on one side	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1123	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,4	1,7	0,77	10		Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Well rounded and smoothed. Heavily encrusted on the top. Patina on the edge and on the bottom	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1124	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,1		4	Black ink 30	Spindle whorl made of wood, incomplete, almost half preserved. Well rounded and smoothed. Some traces of encrustation on the surface. Mark in the shape of a star.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1125	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,6	0,9	13		Spindle whorl made of wood, complete. Well rounded and smoothed. Some traces of encrustation and burnings on the surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1126	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,7	1,2	0,6	7		Spindle whorl made of wood, almost complete. Surface completely ruined and parts of the whorl missing.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1127	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		3,9	1,2	0,6	2		Spindle whorl made of wood, almost complete. Surface completely ruined and parts of the whorl missing.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1128	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,1	1,3		5		Spindle whorl made of wood, less than half preserved. Two holes. Encrusted on one side and on the edge, clean on the other with an incised mark.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_1129	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,5		6		Black ink 63	Spindle whorl made of wood, less than half preserved. Patina on all sides, several incised lines as marks.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1130	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		3,34	1,4	0,4	3			Spindle whorl made of wood, more than half preserved. Traces of patina on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1131	Spindle whorl	Discoid	Ceramic		7,6	1,4	0,9	73			Spindle whorl made of ceramic, made on purpose. Chipped on one side, but otherwise complete. Quite well rounded but one surface is irregular. Hole made by inserting a shaft in the hole, slightly protruding on the opposite side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1132	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic		4,4x5,1	0,9	0,6	22			Spindle whorl made by a reused pottery sherd. Edges are irregular, not rounded nor smoothed. Hourglass hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1133	Spindle whorl	Lenticular	Ceramic		5	1,9	0,6	39		Ink, not understandable	Spindle whorl made of ceramic, made on purpose. Complete. Quite well rounded but one surface is irregular. Hole made by inserting a shaft in the hole, slightly protruding on the opposite side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1134	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Ceramic		4,8	1,9		47			Spindle whorl made of ceramic, by a reused sherd. Complete. Quite well rounded but one surface is irregular. Not perforated, but one side has a socket that might be a hole perforation not finished.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1135	Spindle whorl	Lenticular	Ceramic		6,8	1,8	0,7	61		Ink, 110	Spindle whorl made of ceramic, made on purpose. Complete. Quite well rounded but one surface is irregular. Hole made by inserting a shaft in the hole,	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
										slightly protruding on the opposite side.		
DeM_2024_M23_1136	Spindle whorl	Dome	Limestone		3	0,8	1	6		Black ink 113 or 115	Spindle whorl made of limestone, complete. Well rounded and smoothed, hole very large compared to the rest of the whorl.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1137	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		7	1,4	1,7x2	24			Spindle whorl made of wood, almost clean on both surfaces, very large hole. Might not be a spindle whorl.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1138	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic		6,7	1	1	49		98 or 86	Perforated sherd, complete. Quite well rounded and smoothed. Cylindrical hole. Concave shape.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1145	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Clay		5,3	1,4	0,74	50			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of unbaked clay, roughly rounded and flattened. Hole not perfectly centred but well rounded and no visible wear.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1146	Spindle whorl	Perforated sherd	Ceramic		6,2	0,9	0,75	25			Discoid spindle whorl, half preserved. Well rounded, hourglass hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1147	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Clay		4,3	1,2	0,5	22			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of baked clay, well rounded and flattened. Hole centred well rounded and no visible wear.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1173	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,2	0,8	11			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded and flattened. Hole centred well rounded and no visible wear. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation. Traces of a red line on one side.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1174	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6	1,3	0,9	16		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded and flattened. Hole centred well rounded and no visible wear. Covered by a thin layer of patina.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1175	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,8	0,8	11		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded and flattened. Hole centred well rounded and no visible wear. Covered by a thin layer of patina on one side. Evident traces of manufacture on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1176	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	2	0,9	12		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Hole centred well rounded and no visible wear.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1177	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,2	0,9	6		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Thick layer of encrustation on one side, chipped on the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1178	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,5	0,9	15		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Thin layer of encrustation on one side, cracked on the edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1179	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,9	1	22		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Thick layer of encrustation on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1180	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,8	1,3	0,9	17		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Thick layer of patina on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1181	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,1	0,8	7		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Thick layer of patina on both sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1182	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,7	1,2	0,7	11		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Clean surface, cut from transversal.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_1183	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,3	0,9	12			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Clean on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1184	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,6	1,9	0,8	21			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Clean on one side, patina on the other.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1185	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,8	0,9	20			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Long crack from hole to edge. Patina on all sides. Hole due to the presence of a NODO, which has been repaired with a white substance. White substance also on the other side and inside the crack.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1186	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,7	1,6	0,9	15			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Partially broken. Patina on all sides as well as a whitish substance.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1187	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,9	1,6	1	18			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Partially broken. Patina on all sides as well as a whitish substance.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1188	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,8	0,7	15			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Complete. Patina on all sides and some small traces of thick encrustation.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1189	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,3	1	12			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Complete, with a crack on the edge. Patina on all sides. Hole heavily warped and slightly off centre.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1190	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,4	0,9	7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Almost complete. Patina on all sides.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1191	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,5	1,1	0,8	11			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, well rounded. Complete. Thick layer of encrustation on one side.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_1192	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6,2	1,9	1,3	17			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Incomplete, very roughly done.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1193	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,5	1,5	0,9	17			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, layer of encrustation on all sides. Clean hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1194	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,2	1,6	0,8	9			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, layer of encrustation on all sides. Clean hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1195	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,8	1,1	19			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, layer of encrustation on all sides. Clean hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1196	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,2	0,9	10			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, almost clean.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1197	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,3	0,7x1	7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, almost clean surface. Warped hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1198	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,3	1,3	0,9	11			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Complete, one clean surface.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1199	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,2	1,8	0,8	14			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Almost complete, one clean surface, the other traces of encrustation.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1200	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,6	0,7	8			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Almost complete, one clean surface. White dots.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1201	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5,4	1,4	0,9	13			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood. Almost complete, one clean surface and the other encrusted. White dots.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
DeM_2024_M23_1203	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4	1,2	0,5	5		Pencil 18	Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, small and complete. Very well carved, except the hole that is oval. (0,5x0,65).	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1204	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,2	0,8	8,1			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, small and complete. Very well carved. 4 red lines painted as a radial cross.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1205	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		6	2,2	0,9	20,8		Pencil 86 or 98 or 28	Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, large and almost complete. Cracked on one edge and a little hole. Covered by a thick encrustation on one side and one edge.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1206	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,7	1,5	0,7	13,6		Pencil 132	Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, complete, slightly cracked on the edge. Hole very sharp and round, but second hole (not pierced through) on one side. One side is covered by a very thick layer of encrustation.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1207	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,3	0,8	10,1			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, complete, slightly cracked on the edge. Hole very sharp with clear signs of cuts. One side is covered by a thin layer of encrustation the other one is clean as it was new. Coniferous wood.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1208	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,1	0,7	5,4			Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, small and complete. Small chip on one edge. Very well carved. White dots on one surface and on the edge and inside the crack, they look like efflorescence.	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
DeM_2024_M23_1209	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		5	1,1	0,7	7		Cylindrical spindle whorl, made of wood, small and complete. Very well carved. Thin layer of encrustation on one side (a small X?), almost clean on the other with signs of manufacture. Large peg next to the hole.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1210	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,8	1,5	0,7	13,7		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well carved, almost complete. One small piece missing. One side encrusted. A whitish substance covers part of the two flat surfaces and a small part of the edge. Identity mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1211	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,6	1,8	0,7	8,3	Blue ink 45. black ink [22a4] EM	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well carved, complete. Almost clean, encrusted on the edge. Identity mark.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1212	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,4	0,7	10,2	Black ink [F31 ⁸] E.M. Blue ink 35	Cylindrical spindle whorl, well carved, complete. All sides encrusted, badly preserved. Possible identity mark, in the shape of <i>ms</i> .	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1213	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood		4,9	1,6	0,8	11		Cylindrical spindle whorl, incomplete. All sides covered by patina, badly preserved. Possible identity mark on the side.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1214	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,4	1,5		5,6+x		Dome spindle whorl, incomplete, less than half preserved. Wood not well preserved. Encrusted on all surfaces	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1215	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,8	1,9		8,9+x		Dome spindle whorl, incomplete, less than half preserved. Wood quite well preserved.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1216	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,6	2,3		8,7		Dome spindle whorl, incomplete. Wood very worn, with traces of clack paint on the surface. Hole is visible but very worn out and fill	On site - M23

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										with mud. Possibly not a spindle whorl.	
DeM_2024_M23_1217	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		5,2	2	0,8	6+x		Dome spindle whorl, half preserved. Wood quite clean but worn.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1218	Spindle whorl	Dome	Wood		4,1	1,5	0,8	6		Dome spindle whorl, light and apparently warped. Fragment of the shaft inside the hole. Painted in red and yellow with a circle around the edge and 6 radial lines.	On site - M23
DeM_2024_M23_1219	Spindle whorl	Lenticular	Ceramic		4,4	1,5	0,6	18,8		Lenticular spindle whorl, almost complete, chipped at the edge in two points. Hole made with a stick passing through, edges thickened. Not perfectly made.	On site - M23
S. 07527/01	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5		0.7	7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl partially broken. Clean surfaces with a mark incised on one side.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/02	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5		0.9	8.3	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with an incised mark on one surface. One surface encrusted the other covered by a patina. One side of the hole is warped.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/03	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	6		0.8	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl with an incised mark on one surface. On the same side there are several thin incised lines, but no precise sign is recognizable. One side of the hole is warped (same side of mark).	Turin - ME
S. 07527/04	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.4		0.7	8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with a mark on one side and a lateral break. Covered by a thin patina.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07527/06	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.1		0.8	11.9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with an incised mark on one side and several small notches on the opposite surface. Clean surface. Cut from the central part of a tree trunk.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/07	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.5		0.9	15.8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with three marks incised on one side; the other surface is covered by a thin patina	Turin - ME
S. 07527/09	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	5.1		1	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with marks on both sides. One surface encrusted.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/10	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.4		0.6	8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with a mark incised on one side. Surface clean and hole warped.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/11	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	6.2		0.8	18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with several marks incised on one side. Warped hole and holes caused by animals. Both surfaces are clean.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/13	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.9		0.8	10.4	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with marks on one side. Surfaces not encrusted but with traces of burning.	Turin - ME
S. 07527/14	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.9		0.9	13.3	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a mark incised on one side and on the same side several thin incised lines. Tree rings visible, cut from a large trunk.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/001	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.4		0.8	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a radial break which continues to the hole. On the surface there are dots of a thick whitish substance, perhaps stucco or paint.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/002	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.1		1x0.8	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl chipped laterally. Encrusted on one surface, the other shows traces of manufacture.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/003	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.7x0.8	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with several holes probably caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/004	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.4		0.7x0.9	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, covered by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/005	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.7		0.9x1.1	18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with several holes probably caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/006	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.5		1x1.1	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. One side show traces of a whitish substance. Warped hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/007	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.3		0.6	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with oval hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/008	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.4		0.9	13.7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with deep lateral break which continues to the central hole. Whitish efflorescence is present on both sides.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/009	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	6		0.9	18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, well preserved and well-shaped. One side is covered by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/010	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.3		0.7	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, badly preserved, with small lateral breaks.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/011	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5		0.9x1	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, well preserved with both surfaces slightly encrusted.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/012	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.4		1	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl broken in two parts, badly restored with glue.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07528/013	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	5.1	0.8	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete but slightly warped, one surface covered by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/014	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.9	1	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with several holes probably caused by insects; warped hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/015	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.9	0.9	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, well-polished on both sides. One surface show traces of brown encrustation, while the other may have yellowish paint.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/016	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1	0.7	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral crack. One surface is covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other one by patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/017	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	4	0.7x1	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral crack. One surface is covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/018	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.3	0.7x1.1	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral crack. One side is encrusted.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/019	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.8	0.5x0.7	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one surface covered by a thin layer of patina, the other one is encrusted and shows incised marks.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/020	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.9	1	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, chipped, with a lateral break which continues to the central hole and another smaller fracture. One side is covered by a thin patina, the other one is encrusted and shows thin incisions, but no precise pattern is visible.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/021	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.5		1	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep fracture which continues to the central hole, which is quite warped near this crack. One surface is slightly encrusted, the other one shows whitish efflorescence near the hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/022	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.6		0.7	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, well-shaped, but badly preserved and one surface highly worn. Clean and made of an unusual type of wood.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/023	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	6.1		0.7	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one surface highly encrusted, the other one with a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/024	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.8		0.7	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one side covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/025	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.2		0.7	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one side covered by encrustation and the other clean, with wood vases evident.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/026	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.9	4.9		0.9	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one side covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other one by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/027	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.6		1	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete and clean.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/028	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	6.2		0.8	18.7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with both sides covered with a thin patina and whitish encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/029	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		0.9	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with deep lateral crack. One side is encrusted and covered by a thick layer of whitish encrustation.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/030	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.8		1x1.2	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with one side covered by a thick layer of encrustation and the other one by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/031	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.9x0.7	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with two deep lateral cracks, which continue to the central hole. Worn surfaces and a yellowish spot on one side.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/032	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	5.4		0.9	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one surface clean and the other covered by a thin patina.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/033	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.2		0.9	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep lateral break. One side is covered by a thin patina and the other is clean.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/034	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.6		0.9	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, broken, with the two fragments now poorly attached with glue. Worn and badly preserved.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/035	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.5		0.7x0.9	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete. One surface and side are covered by brown encrustation, the other surface by greyish encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/036	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.8		0.9	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete but quite worn. Elliptical, warped hole on both sides and surface covered by traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/037	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.7		0.9x1.1	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with a warped polygonal hole, probably due to the insertion of several wedges.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/038	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.7		0.7	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, slightly warped. It does not show traces of encrustation but spots of patina on the surface. One side has a knot. It	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										was made from a longitudinal cut of a log.	
S. 07528/039	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	6	0.7	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with small lateral break. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other one by patina. On this side, traces of manufacture are visible as well as the wood vases.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/040	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.6	0.7	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, small and thick, completely preserved. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/041	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.6	1	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, one side covered by a thick layer of encrustation, the other one clean and with marks from its manufacture.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/042	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.8	0.6	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl very well preserved. One side is covered by a thin layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/043	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.7	0.8	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep lateral crack. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation and a break "stopped" by a wooden peg, perhaps an ancient attempt of restoration. Hole is warped, worn by usage and wedges.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/044	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.5	0.9	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep lateral break. Badly preserved with darkened spots and whitish efflorescence. Different wood from other spindle whorls. One side shows signs of manufacture.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07528/045	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5	0.9	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a small lateral fracture. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation and its hole is warped by ancient wedges.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/046	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.1	0.5x0.7	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with small hole. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation and whitish efflorescence. It also shows probable traces of yellowish paint.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/047	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.8	0.8x0.6	7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a lateral break and highly worn surfaces. One side is covered by a thin patina. Hole is warped by ancient wedges.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/048	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.1	0.8	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral crack and traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/050	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.7	1	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep lateral crack which continues to the hole. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/051	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.8	0.9	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with whitish encrustation on both surfaces. Traces of a yellowish paint (?) are visible on one surface and on side. On the same surface are present traces of burning.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/053	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.9	0.9x0.8	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/055	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	6.1	1	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete and with encrusted surfaces. Hole is highly warped on one side probably due to ancient wedges.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/056	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.4		1x0.8	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a thick layer of encrustation and traces of yellowish paint (?).	Turin - ME
S. 07528/057	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.4		0.7	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with small lateral crack which originates from the central hole. Highly worn surfaces with traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/058	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.2		0.9	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, broken on one side with traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/059	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	6		1.1x1.3	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral breaks and holes caused probably by insects. Central hole quite irregular. Both surfaces are covered by thick layer of encrustation and on one side there are spots of a whitish substance.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/060	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.1		0.6	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with small, warped and off-centre hole. Covered with encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/061	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.1		1	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl warped and badly preserved. Warped hole due to ancient wedges.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/062	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.8		0.6	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral breaks. One side is covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/063	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.3		0.9	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl completely ruined with a big central hole, and a smaller on the surface, probably caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/064	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0.9	3.8		0.5	4	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, small and ruined or worn, with an oval central hole.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/066	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.9		0.5	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with deep lateral break which continues to the central hole. One surface is covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/068	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	5.9			16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, unfinished. One side shows signs of the preparation for making the central hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/070	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	5.6		0.9	18	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral break. One side shows traces of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/073	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.4		1	7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Small cylindrical spindle whorl, badly preserved, with yellowish traces on both surfaces around its hole, and other holes likely caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/074	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.7		0.6	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well-preserved. Encrusted on both surfaces.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/075	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.3		0.7	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite worn but without encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/076	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.9		0.9	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, heavily encrusted.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/077	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.5		1	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with yellowish traces on the surface and other traces of encrustation. Oval hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/078	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.9		0.7	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, badly preserved, with lateral breaks and encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/079	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0.9	4		0.6	6.6	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Small spindle whorl, complete, with four radial lines painted with a pink colour.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/081	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5		1	16	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl broken and now composed of two fragments.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/082	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.2		1	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, slightly warped, with lateral breaks. Encrustations and whitish efflorescence on the surface.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/083	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.2		0.9	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl badly preserved and made of a dark wood.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/089	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.4	5.1		0.9x0.7	14	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with traces of encrustation on one side.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/092	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	4.2		0.5	8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with heavy encrustation on the surface.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/093	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	3.9		0.6	8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl decorated by four radial lines painted in black and another line decorates the external edge.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/096	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.9		0.7	15	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with a deep lateral fracture and a thick layer of encrustation.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/099	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.7		0.8	8.3	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl only partially preserved with side chipped. Warped hole likely due to ancient wedges. One hole on the surface. Both sides are covered by whitish efflorescence.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/103	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1	5.6		0.9	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with small lateral break and free of encrustation. Irregular central hole.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/104	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.1	5.5		0.7	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with warped central hole probably due to ancient wedges. Clean surfaces.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/105	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.1		0.7	11	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, with one surface covered by encrustation and an incised mark. Highly worn.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
S. 07528/106	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.8		0.9	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl with lateral breaks and encrusted on the surface. Two radial lines are painted in black.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/107	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.7	4.7		0.9	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, encrusted on the surface and with cross-shaped incisions.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/108	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.8		0.8x1	17	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, encrusted on the surface and with incised marks near the edge.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/109	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	5.1		0.7	12	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl warped and partially missing, likely due to insects. Central hole warped by ancient wedges. Different wood, more compact.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/110	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.6			5	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl completely lacking the central part, probably due to insects. Traces of encrustation are also present.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/111	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.9		0.9	10	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, encrusted on the surface and with small holes probably caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/112	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	5.4		0.8	8	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl only partially preserved probably due to insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/113	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.5	5.6		0.6	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete, encrusted and with a small perforation likely caused by insects.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/114	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.3	4.3		0.5	9	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Cylindrical spindle whorl, complete and well- preserved. Encrusted on the surface.	Turin - ME
S. 07528/115	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.6	4.2		0.x0.5	7	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Truncated cone spindle whorl, complete, with marks from its manufacture on the surface.	Turin - ME

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
S. 07528/116	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.2	4.4		3	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018		Small fragment of a cylindrical spindle whorl.	Turin - ME
S. 09978/3	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1.8	4.7		0.8	13	Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl, encrusted on the surface.	Turin - ME
S. 07587/09	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2.5	4				Spinazzi-Lucchesi 2018	Cylindrical spindle whorl, broken and only partially preserved.	Turin - ME
C5110_tissage_4.40	Spindle	Cylindrical	Wood	2	0,75		0,77	4.5+x		Small fragment of shaft inside the hole of the spindle whorl, which is completely worn, only a small part is preserved. Covered by a thick layer of encrustation.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.12	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,43	4,9		0.7x0.89; 0.9x0.8	7,8		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Hole quite irregular. All surfaces covered by a thin layer of patina. Transversal cut from a quite large branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.13	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,12	0,58		0,68	10,2		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Hole quite regular. One surface covered by a whitish efflorescence. Tangential cut.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.14	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,68	5,4		0,78	9,9		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Hole quite irregular on one surface. All surfaces covered by a quite thick patina. Transversal cut.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.15	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,55	5		0.4x0.5; 0.5x0.6	10,6		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Hole quite small and irregular on one surface. All surfaces covered by a quite thick patina. Black spot near the edge. Transversal cut.	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
C5110_tissage_4.16	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,51	4,8		0,89	7,2		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. All the surfaces are a little worn but still covered by a thick layer of patina and some encrustation. Transversal cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.18	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,67	5,3		0,87	8.6+x		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved, small part missing. One surface is covered by a thick incrustation on(?) which a mark is incised. The other surface has a thinner incrustation. Tangential cut (?).	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.19	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,09	4,88		0,82	5,2		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and quite well preserved. Very thin. All surfaces are covered by a thin layer of patina. Transversal cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.20	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,2	4,88		0.82x 0.92	6,6		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted but one surface is very worn and there is a very large fracture on one side. The other surface is covered by a thick layer of encrustation and a mark is barely visible. Transversal cut.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.21	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,18	4,9		0.91x 0.86	6		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and well preserved. Hole is a little bit warped on one side. All surfaces are covered with spots of a thin patina. Transversal cut.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.22	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,3	6		0.91x 0.98	12,6		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and quite well preserved except for a wide lateral fracture/hole. One side covered by a layer of incrustation and the	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										other by a thin patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	
C5110_tissage_4.23	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,8	5	0,8	10,3			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and quite well preserved except for a wide lateral fracture/hole. One side covered by a layer of incrustation and the other by a thin patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.24	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,7	5,3	0,8	11,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and quite well preserved except for a wide lateral fracture/hole. One side covered by a layer of incrustation and the other by a thin patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.25	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,16	5	0,9	4.0+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted but badly preserved. Part of the side missing. Both sides covered by a layer of encrustation. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.26	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,3	5,6	0,98	7.0+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted, only half preserved. One side covered by a thin layer of encrustation, the other by a patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.27	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,51	4,6	0.7x0.87	6.0+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted, wood quite worn and a small portion is missing. One lateral fracture. Covered by a thin patina on both sides. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.28	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,25	5,7		5.1+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted, only 2/3 preserved. Both sides are covered by a patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
C5110_tissage_4.29	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,08	4,59		0,7	4,2		Small, cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted, one large radial fracture. Wood quite worn. Both sides are covered by a patina. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.30	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,6	4,8+x		0,57	5+x		Cylindrical spindle whorl, highly worn, only a small part preserved. One side covered by a thick layer of encrustation/stucco. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.31	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,58	5,25		0.85x 0.68	11,4		Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite worn, almost all preserved but partially broken on the edge. One side covered by a layer of encrustation. Transversal cut. Cut from a larger branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.32	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,44	4,9		0.8x0. 98	8		Cylindrical spindle whorl, well crafted and almost complete. Very worn wood. All sides are partially covered by an incrustation. Transversal cut.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.33	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	2,14	4,4+x			7.2+x		Cylindrical spindle whorl, highly worn, only a small part preserved. One side covered by a thick layer of encrustation/stucco. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.34	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,35	4,94		0,83	4,3		Cylindrical spindle whorl, highly worn, only partially preserved. All sides covered by traces of encrustation, whitish substance also inside the hole Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
C5110_tissage_4.35	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,21	4,47		0,66	4,5			Small, cylindrical spindle whorl, almost complete. Large through hole next to the main one. One surface is worn. All surfaces are still covered by a thick layer of encrustation/stucco. Tangential cut?	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.36	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,37	4,5		0,8	4,9			Small, cylindrical spindle whorl, almost complete. Highly worn wood. Incised mark still visible. Some traces of encrustation are still visible on the other side. Transversal cut. Cut from a larger branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.38	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,5	4,8		1,04	5,8			Cylindrical spindle whorl, almost complete but with a large fracture on the side. All covered by a layer of encrustation, but on one side is thicker than on the other. Wood not clearly visible.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.39	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical		1,75	4,8		0,87	7,7			Cylindrical spindle whorl, almost complete but wood extremely worn. Covered by a thin layer of encrustation. Transversal cut. Cut from a small branch.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.41	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,7	4+x		0,69	3.1+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, almost completely worn.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.42	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	0,7	4,98		0.7x0.88	3.7+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, quite flattish. Well crafted but with a oval hole. One surface is covered by a thin layer of encrustation. Tangential cut. Wear traces near the hole?	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.43	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1+x	3.6+x			1.8+x			Cylindrical spindle whorl, almost completely worn.	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution	
C5110_tissage_4.44		Cylindrical	Wood	1,3	4,43		0.49x 0.58	5,4			Cylindrical object, well crafted but possibly something went wrong when piercing it. Second oval hole near the edge. Tangential cut?	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.45		Cylindrical	Wood	1,16	7,16		0.96x 1.43	8.3+x			Rounded and flattish object with a square hole. Transversal cut. Covered by a layer of encrustation.	IFAO
C5110_tissage_4.37	Spindle whorl	Cylindrical	Wood	1,9	0,83						Small fragment of shaft inside the hole of the spindle whorl, which is completely worn, only a small part is preserved.	IFAO

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
E 14535 3	Spatula	Bone		11,5	1,7	0,3				Bone spatula with one end missing and the other nearly rounded. The piece is well carved and highly polished. A rib was split lengthwise to expose the cancellous bone, which remains visible and slightly rough in the central area where the surface is concave and near the rounded end. The upper surface is highly polished, with fine striations visible near the end. The sides are completely smoothed, rounded, and polished through use. The cancellous bone is well smoothed near the tip, less so along the rest of the body, but a distinct shiny patina is clearly visible..	Louvre
E 14141	Spatula	Bone		7,9	1,8	0,3				Partially broken bone spatula, with the pointed end missing and the opposite end slightly rounded. The surface is not particularly polished and appears dirty. On the ventral side, the cancellous bone is exposed and remains quite rough. Both ends are filled with soil, while the central portion is cleaner but shows a reddish coloration.	Louvre
E 14435 5	Spatula	Bone		8	1,1	0,2				Small bone spatula, well carved and well polished, with one rounded end and an elongated, tapered point. The surface shows numerous fine striations, and a whitish rectangular area on the top has altered the bone's coloration. The cancellous bone is	Louvre

N.	Typology	Material	H	D	Th	Hole	W	Bibl.	Notes	Description	Museum/Institution
										partially visible on the ventral side. Both surfaces are covered with thin striations, likely from use or manufacturing.	
E 21564	Spatula	Wood		7,8	1	0,3				Small wooden spatula, very likely cosmetic) with one end carved in the shape of a clog and the other end rounded. The object has a knife-like form, with one side carved to resemble a blade and the opposite side left thicker and rounded. A thread is knotted at one end; it was originally much longer when found but is now mostly lost. The thread appears to be Z-cabled, Z-plyed, and S-spun.	Louvre
E 16575 B	Needle	Bronze		9	0,1					Long and thin bronze needle, eye missing. Not straight, many curves.	Louvre
E 16575 D	Needle	Bronze		6,8	0,1					Thin needle, point missing and bent. The eye has been done by piercing the shaft.	Louvre